

National Conference on

BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

1st April 2023

BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

**THERE IS ONLY ONE
PURPOSE IN THE
WHOLE OF LIFE
-EDUCATION.**

— Swami Vivekananda

Edited by
Dr. P. SRIRAMAN
Dr. T. SUNDARARASAN

KANCHI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION

(An institution under the Bhaktavatsalam Educational Trust)

Accredited with 'B' Grade by NAAC

Approved by NCTE & Affiliated to Tamilnadu Teachers Education University
Karaipettai, Kanchipuram, Tamilnadu-631552

In Association with
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National Conference on

BLENDDED LEARNING

IN

TEACHER EDUCATION

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Dr. T. SUNDARARASAN

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01 / 04 / 2023

Dr. P. SRIRAMAN
Principal

MESSAGE

Warm and happy greeting to all. I am immensely happy that IQAC of our college is organizing a National Level Conference on Blended Learning in Teacher Education on 01.04.2023 and is going present a collection of various technical papers in the proceedings.

Kanchi College of Education is a premier institution growing in stature and shining in prominence in all its endeavours towards sustaining the quality in education and striving earnestly to enhance the quality in all fronts leading to the overall development of the stakeholders. The resourceful and dynamic faculty and committed to the cause of bestowing the best education and are ever trying to enhance the future education through effective teaching and learning techniques to ensure a perfect ambience for quality learning and teaching.

Under the able guidance of our management continues to march on the way of success with confidence. The sharp, clear sighted vision and precise decision making powers of our management has benefited our college to say competitive. The dedicated teaching and non-teaching staff members and disciplined students are the added features of our college. The role students in building nation cannot be overlooked and students at KCE are trained in all aspects to become a successful teachers and good citizens. On this occasion I would like the students all very best.

I congratulate organizing secretary, teaching and non-teaching staff members, students from our college, participants from other educational institutions for their efforts in organizing and participating in this conference and wish the conference all the success.

With wishes,

(Dr. P. SRIRAMAN)

Principal

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MESSAGE

On behalf of the organizing committee, I would like to cordially welcome you to the National Conference on Blended Learning in Teacher Education. Since we began exploring the idea of educational technology, we have come to the conclusion that it is one of the primary elements influencing the standard of living in the education society. Not only have advances in psychology and technology been made over the past ten years, but the technology industry has also made considerable time and effort investments in the field of education.

In the past few decades, we have successfully partnered with a variety of academic institutions and fields and tested and tried a number of items that could have a significant impact on the field of education. This conference with the theme “Blended Learning in Teacher Education” is the right platform to bring various stakeholders under one roof to discuss needs of education society. Through this conference, we will make every effort to advance national educational technology policy and develop a list of the top technology tools. This could be the most significant conference of its kind in the area, giving everyone the chance to demonstrate and propose ideas, concepts, and new innovations that might have an impact on the community of educators.

We are doing everything we can to make sure that your time and stay in Kancheepuram during the conference will be among the most memorable ones, and that you return with a wealth of knowledge and as a proud member of the education society. I want to make the most of this lovely occasion, so please join me in welcoming you, your family, and friends. I want to thank each and every one of you for your contribution to the conference's success.

Best wishes,

T. Sundararasan

(Dr. T. SUNDARARASAN)
Organizing Secretary

PREFACE

Innovation is the predominant key to success in every walk of life. Changes are happening in everyday life and one has to adapt new situations and face challenges. Academic and business entities are no exception to this phenomenon. The rapid spreading wild fire, which everyone wanted to be a part of it and claim that they had the best, Innovation- buzz word that has the entire world is striving for. The concept is now half a decade old, nevertheless, like any other things it is also beginning to wear off. The frenzy over bringing new ideas and strategies has to gain much more importance than the prevalence.

The hype was so overwhelming that leaders and change champions lost track of the real value that innovation would add. Having realized that there is little logic where in the width traditional models for new and experimental trails in different spheres of functional areas.

The main objective of innovation is value addition. Processes that have the potential to add to the already existing framework make successful innovations. Reusing the already existing functional framework or process to yield better results is also innovation. The accumulated insights presented in a lucid manner shall provide the aspirants who are inclined towards the concept of innovation in vital fields; the best way to nurture their quest for research based multi-disciplinary knowledge.

The national conference on **BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION** was held on 01st April 2023 which was organized by IQAC, Kanchi College of Education.

We profusely thank authors for contributing the articles.

EDITORIAL TEAM

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EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL OF BLENDED LEARNING: STRATEGIES FOR MAXIMIZING STUDENT SUCCESS

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Abstract

This paper explores the potential of blended learning for maximizing student success in higher education. By blending traditional classroom instruction with online education, blended learning offers a new approach to teaching and learning that has the potential to engage students more deeply and help them master the material more effectively. This paper examines the potential benefits of blended learning, including increased student engagement, greater flexibility, improved student learning outcomes, and enhanced access to learning resources. It also discusses the various challenges that may arise when implementing blended learning, such as technological issues, changing faculty roles, and student motivation. Finally, the paper outlines a number of strategies for successful implementation of blended learning, including the design of effective online instruction, the development of well-crafted learning activities and assessments, and the use of technology to facilitate collaboration and communication.

Keywords: *blended learning, strategies, challenges, students success*

Introduction

Blended learning combines traditional face-to-face instruction with digital elements to create an effective and engaging learning experience. This approach to education has been gaining popularity in recent years, as it allows learners to take control of their education and tailor it to their individual needs. Blended learning also has the potential to reduce the costs associated with traditional in-person education and provide access to educational opportunities that may otherwise be out of reach. By exploring the potential of blended learning and implementing strategies for maximizing student success, educators can ensure that all students are able to gain the most from this innovative learning approach.

The Potential benefits of Blended Learning

Blended learning is a combination of traditional classroom instruction and online learning that can help students develop more holistic, comprehensive learning. It can be used to supplement traditional instruction or to give students the opportunity to take courses online when it's not feasible for them to attend in-person classes. There are several potential benefits to using blended learning in the classroom, such as:

- **Improved student engagement:** Blended learning can create an engaging atmosphere in the classroom, as students can work at their own pace and teachers can provide individualized instruction and guidance.
- **Increased access to resources:** Blended learning can give students access to online resources, such as videos and interactive activities, that can supplement traditional instruction.
- **Increased student motivation:** By giving students more control over their learning, blended learning can help to increase student motivation and engagement.
- **Improved student achievement:** Studies have shown that students who participate in blended learning can achieve better academic results than those who are taught in traditional classrooms.
- **Improved communication:** With blended learning, teachers and students can communicate more effectively, as both can access course materials and other resources online.
- **Increased flexibility:** Blended learning can offer greater flexibility in terms of how and when students complete their coursework, which can be particularly beneficial for busy or working students. Blended learning offers a variety of potential benefits for both students and teachers, and can be used to create a more engaging, effective learning environment.

Challenges and Strategies of blended learning

- **Flipped Classroom:** In a flipped classroom, students watch video lectures, read online content, or participate in interactive learning activities outside of class. During class time, students then discuss and work on assignments related to the material they studied ahead of time.
- **Station Rotation:** In a station rotation model, students move from station to station in a classroom, spending a certain amount of time at each station. At each station, they might work on independent activities, complete projects, or participate in small-group discussions or activities.
- **Online Discussions:** Online discussions can be used in a blended learning environment to facilitate student collaboration and engagement. Students can discuss course topics, ask questions, or share resources with one another.
- **Individualized Learning Paths:** With individualized learning paths, each student works at their own pace and completes activities tailored to their individual needs and interests. Students can access online content, resources, and activities that are chosen specifically for them.
- **Game-Based Learning:** Game-based learning can be used to engage students in a blended learning environment. Students can work together to complete challenges and complete activities related to the course material.

Blended Learning: Strategies for Maximizing Student Success

- **Make Use of Technology and Develop Digital Literacy:** Blended learning combines technology with traditional instruction, so it's important to ensure that technology is used effectively in the classroom. This means teaching students how to use the technology, such as how to access and navigate digital content, as well as teaching digital literacy skills such as how to evaluate online sources and maintain a secure online presence.
- **Set Clear Expectations:** It's important to set expectations and provide clear guidelines for students when it comes to blended learning. This should include expectations for online behavior, expectations for participation in online courses and activities, and consequences for failure to meet expectations.
- **Provide Support:** Blended learning can be challenging for some students, and it's important to provide support to ensure success. This can include providing extra help and resources, such as tutoring and online support, as well as providing additional time for students to complete their work.
- **Ensure Engagement:** It's important to ensure that students are engaged and actively participating in the blended learning environment. This can include setting up activities and assignments that require collaboration and active participation, as well as providing feedback and rewards for participation.
- **Encourage Communication:** Communication is key to successful blended learning, so it's important to encourage students to communicate with each other and with the instructor. This can include setting up discussion forums and other online spaces for students to interact and collaborate, as well as encouraging students to ask questions and seek help when needed.

Conclusion

The implementation of blended learning has the potential to revolutionize the way students learn and engage with their course material. Through its combination of traditional teaching methods, technology-enabled instruction, and student-centered activities, blended learning has the potential to maximize the success of students by creating a more personalized learning environment. Additionally, the use of blended learning strategies can help to improve student engagement and facilitate collaboration between students and educators. Ultimately, the successful implementation of blended learning strategies will lead to greater student achievement and enhanced educational outcomes.

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EFFECT OF BLENDED LEARNING ON STUDENT ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of Blended Learning on the performance of Students. To gain in depth indulgent of the observable fact under inquiry, the data sources were collected from in depth interview with the students, classroom observation and results of the various studies already done on the effectiveness of Blended Learning on student achievement. The findings of the study recommend that student perspective about the magnetism of the Blended Learning is significant and encourage the initiation of such type of internet base learning beside traditional way of learning method.

Keywords: Blended Learning, Student Performance, Student Achievement

Introduction

The teaching and learning environment is embracing a number of innovations and some of these involve the use of technology through blended learning. This innovative pedagogical approach has been embraced rapidly though it gives through a process of Blended Learning. Recently the educational research literature has indicated that blended approaches to learning might provide an optional environment for enhancing student engagement and success. The idea of blending different learning experiences has been in existence since human started thinking about teaching. The on-going infused web based technologies into the learning and teaching process has highlighted the potential of blended learning. Collaborative web based applications have created new opportunities for students to interact with their peers, teachers and content. Blended Learning is often defined as a combination of face-to-face and online learning. Most of the recent definitions of blended courses indicate that this approach to learning offers potential for improving how we deal with content, social interactions, reflections, higher order thinking, problem solving, collaborative learning and more authentic assessment in higher education, which could potentially lead to a greater sense of student engagement.

Moskal, Dziuban and Hartman suggest that “blended learning has become an evolving, responsive and dynamic process that in many aspects is organic, defying all attempts at universal definition. Blended Learning effectiveness has a quite number of underlying factors that pose challenges. One big challenge is about how users can successfully use the technology and ensuring participants’ commitment given the individual learning characteristics and encounters with technology (Hofmann, 2014). Hofmann that users getting into difficulties with technology may result into abandoning the learning and eventual failure of technological applications. In a report by Oxford Group (2013), some learners (10 %) had negative attitudes to blended learning while 26% were concerned that learners would not complete study in blended learning. Learners are important partners in any learning process and therefore ,their background and characteristics affect their ability to effectively carry on with learning and being in blended learning ., the design tools to be used may impinge on the effectiveness in their learning.

E-Learning environments pave the way for instructional innovations for new generations and make individuals equipped with technologic devices and soft wares which provide ubiquitous learning environment. Rich educational that contain mobile devices, web platforms and instructional soft wares initiate a new period in education using e-learning environments (Horton, 2002) .Those environments will also help students gain digital literacy, digital ethic and self-information Computer Technologies (ICT). Instructors can use the new techniques and methodologies. One of these methodologies is blended leaning that is defined as a computer mediated instructional strategy that leverages technology and focuses on the student-teacher relationship to enhance independence, engagement and achievement.

Blended Learning (B-Learning)

There are lot of definitions and approaches about how to describe blended learning in the literature. Depending on the learning targets in the blended leaning environments, student learn through face-to-face in the class and technology based e-learning environments. The percentage of the in-class and e-learning environment varies. The definition of Blended learning ,used in the American literature for the first time concerns both pedagogical approach and learning method using media ,technology and relations between all of them, bearing in mind what to learn (Gynther, 2005). According to Harvey and choris (2001) blended learning programme may consist of one or more programme combinations:

- Combining online and offline learning environments
- Combining collaborative and individual learning environments
- Combining structure and non-structured learning environments
- Combining pedagogical approaches (e.g. constructivism, behaviourism, cognitivism)

to produce an optional learning outcome with or without instructional technology. Singh and Reed (2001)'s definition of Blended Learning approaches it as a progress and consider that it should be composed of different environments so that instructors are able to get optimized learning outcomes and budget. Blended Learning also known as mixed, sandwich ,hybrid learning ,is a method that conflate traditional learning environments in which led by teachers and technological based e-learning environment (Ayala,2009., Young 2002,Valiathan, 2002)

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the impact of Blended Learning on the student performance.
2. To study the opinions of the students regarding the concepts of Blended learning.

Methodology

This paper explores the student experience in blended learning and the effectiveness of blended learning on their performance. The data sources for the study come from in-depth interviews with students and data was also collected from classroom observation, online participant observation, individual teacher interviews and the results of the study on examining student experience of Blended Learning by Jeannul Yult Ching Lam.

Engaging in Blended Learning

All the students engaged in the online activities and said that these activities were useful, convenient and flexible in helping them to understand, reinforce and apply knowledge. The students elaborated that having traditional and online learning together helped them to understand the contents more thoroughly. By engaging in blended learning students demonstrated that they had deep learning through having interaction with others and doing the learning activities (Biggs and Watkins, 1995). Integrating learning with blended activities

It was found that, in their learning, all students who studied both the traditional and online learning activities integrated the activities together, some assigned by the teachers and some initiated by them. Instruction although the students often directed their own learning in a non-prescribed way, teaching presence was also found to be important in blended learning. The teachers designed the curriculum and teaching methods; and also facilitated discourse and gave direct instruction in the blended learning course.

Discussion

Blended Learning, with its mix of technology and traditional face-to-face interaction is a great approach .Blended Learning combines classroom learning with online learning, in which students can, in part control the time, pace, place of their learning effects. Blended Learning was found to have positive effect on learner's study achievement than the face-to-face learning environments .In b-learning environment, learners cooperate effectively .This, pointed out in previous studies on a collaborative learning in an e-learning environment, means that learners acquire existing knowledge and actually create new knowledge for given task performance in the process of sharing knowledge with the peers (Insuk, Junghun, Eunmo, Seongher, 2006). It is likely that blended learning improved student's study achievement through cognitive activities .According to the analysis results of the study by Dr. Meltem Eryilmaz (2015) ,it was reputed that opinions of the students who studied in blended environment

are varying comparing other environment and blended learning environment is more effective than face-to-face and online learning environments.

Conclusion

Blended Learning has beneficial effects for students both in improvements to academic performance ,diversity of learning opportunities and enhancements to the student experience .Higher education institutions should be encouraged to facilitate the development of wider range of blended learning resources to support student’s learning ,particularly with the advent of increased ,fast and reliable access to internet services for majority of students .Furthermore, educators should continue to develop innovative and useful ways for students to access opportunities using mobile devices ,which are rapidly becoming the predominant means for communication and interaction among learners. It can be declared that in the view of these statements educational practices designed within blended environment are beneficial to the students in terms of contentment, learning, attention and motivation.

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OPEN EDUCATIONAL PRACTICES IN INDIA

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Abstract

Presents, the digital education model has been improving pretty well from preparatory education to higher education. Before the 2000s education was conducted in a classroom of students by teachers. Now the internet has changed the history of education. E-learning is a rapidly growing education system, the effects of which we can trace back to the 1980s and even well before that in the form of distance learning and televised courses. Now that affordable digital learning solutions exist for both computers and internet, it only takes a good e-learning tool for education to be facilitated from virtually anywhere. Information Technology has advanced so much that the geographical gap is bridged with the use of tools that make you feel as if you are inside the classroom. Digital learning offers the ability to share material in all kinds of formats such as educational content audio, educational content video, slideshows, word documents and pdf. Conducting conferences, seminars, and workshop programmes and communicating with professors via chat and message forums are also available to users in hybrid mode.

Introduction

As digital education continues to grow in higher education institutions (HEIs) (Allen & Seaman, 2017) faculty in higher education institutions are increasingly under pressure to teach online (Orkin, 1996). This is despite the fact that digital education is a fairly recent mode of instruction delivery, and majority of higher education institutions faculty have little or no experience either as students in digital education or as instructors of online courses. Institutions of higher education have increasingly embraced open educational practices, and the number of students enrolled in online programs is rapidly rising in colleges and universities throughout the India. In response to these changes in enrolment demands, many states, institutions, and organizations have been working on strategic plans to implement open educational practices. Open education primary goal is to provide practical and applications of open education resources (Katz & Van Allen, 2022).

Development of distance education to open educational practices

The Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) was established in 1985 and currently serves over 3.5 million students. Over the last two decades, 13 more state open universities and over 50 other distance education institutions catering to 25% of all enrolments in higher education have emerged. The distance education council was established within Indira Gandhi National Open University in 1991 to assess and provide oversight on the quality of distance education in India. The distance education council Handbook on Assessment and Accreditation of Open & Distance Learning Institutions provide guidelines and criteria for assessment and accreditation in distance education. To qualify for employment in the government sector, holders of distance education-based degrees and certificates graduate from institutions that are approved by the distance education council (Jung et al., 2011). According to Kumar et al., (2017) the ubiquity of digital education technology has developed new aspects of our educational lives. It has changed the way we work, interact with others, teaching-learning process, analyze, and share information.

E-evolution or e-revolution (Palvia, 2013) has witnessed e-mails, WhatsApp group learning and now e-education. E-education or digital education is changing the way we approach teaching and learning. While information technology integration has been happening for many years, changes in education delivery models due to recent advances in digital technologies have been very profound. As institutions worldwide adapt to these advances, it has created a very dynamic education landscape that has generated a lot of interest among researchers, educators, administrators, policy makers, and publishers. Online education now has become a mainstream global phenomenon, and many institutions are experimenting with innovative models. This trend in digital education presents many opportunities as well as challenges for all educational institutions. IT and Internet have no limits. Blended education, online education, massively open online courses (MOOCs) are becoming the buzzwords now. Technology platforms like Blackboard and cyberspace media like LinkedIn, WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube are transforming the landscape of education at a pace unthinkable till recently (Palvia, 2013).

Emerging trends

Pedagogy and Technology for open education several research studies have covered effective pedagogical strategies for online teaching. Owing to the steady economic growth and globalisation, education in India is no longer just a teacher talking to a bunch of students in a classroom. With more than 370 million internet users and hundreds of local as well as global business tycoons willing to invest in the future of education, online education in India has picked up pace. India is now the third largest online market for education in the world. This enables people to take better advantage of the resources available online. India education has more than 1 million registered schools and 18,000 higher education institutions.

However, 4 percent of children never start school, 58 percent don't complete primary schools, 90 percent don't complete secondary school and only 10 percent go on to college. What is going to happen to the 90 percent? This is where start-ups like Khan Academy enter the market with meticulously curate content, even in Indian languages, based on NCERT textbooks.

In fact, online education helps people get access to a world-class learning experience when traditional higher education is simply not possible due to financial or personal constraints. Some may also suffer from physical or mental disabilities that make learning in a classroom impossible. For these students, online courses, specialisations and degree programs can offer an incredible opportunity to continue their education and build careers for themselves. These days, teachers look for more than just the basic skill set in their students, they look for a long-term relationship with the educational institution. Similarly, it aims to create a flexible, subject-relevant learning experience for students. Alumni from respected schools like IIT, Wharton, and UCLA also participated in this education revolution with their own venture called Slide Rule, through which they claim to help people discover the best online courses available in every subject.

Flexible options using open education technology

According to Lesueur et al., (2022) Technology can provide flexibility, facilitate access, and save schools and teachers' time and money. In addition teachers and school administrators that they want the flexibility of virtual, but they also like that in person options result in greater engagement and learning. E-coaching technologies effectively provide performance feedback to teachers-students and specialists. Today, digital textbooks have displaced paper textbooks in many primary and secondary classrooms. They have advantages over physical books, including instant availability, ease of updating, and the ability to store many e-books on a single device. However, digital textbooks are in turn being displaced by immersive textbooks that employ interactive technologies, advanced user experience design, and gamification to enhance instruction, make learning more engaging, and address differing learning styles.

Discussion

Just like digital technologies have disrupted many established industries such as media, entertainment, and retail, some experts argue that online education has become a disruptive force that will transform higher education. Clayton Christensen introduced the concept of “disruptive innovation” in his book “The Innovator’s Dilemma.” According to the theory (Christensen & Eyring, 2011) disruptive innovation brings to market a product or service that is not as good as the traditional services but is cheaper and easier to use like that s disruptive technology, online learning, is in higher education allowing traditional not-for-profit institutions to rethink the entire traditional higher education model. Online courses designed from constructivist principles should be relevant, interactive, content-based, project-based, and collaborative, while providing learners with some choice or control over their learning (Partlow & Gibbs, 2003). Let's focus on open education and provide learners with learning opportunities that we can help them succeed in making a difference in students' lives.

Conclusion

Three broad categories of the major challenges encountered by faculty in the design and deliver of open educational courses emerged in this paper. It is related to proximity to learners, teaching load and, faculty support. A general inference that one could make from this finding is that these challenges could have some relationship with perceptions of course quality, as explained here below. Difficulties in getting to adequately understand learner needs in a virtual environment impacts faculty perception of their ability to design quality courses and quality teaching and learning processes. For example, inability to sufficiently

understand learner needs might lead to instruction design that does not adequately address learners learning needs, while difficulties in assessing practical application of knowledge may impact faculty ability to assess attainment of course objectives.

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REFLECTIVE MODEL APPROACHES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract

This paper explores the use of reflective model approaches in teaching and learning. Reflective model approaches aim to facilitate deeper and more meaningful learning experiences by encouraging students to critically examine their own thinking and learning processes. The paper highlights the key concepts and theoretical frameworks that underpin reflective model approaches and examines the benefits and challenges associated with implementing these approaches in various educational contexts. The paper also discusses strategies for incorporating reflective practices into the classroom and offers practical

examples of how reflective model approaches can be used to enhance teaching and learning outcomes. Overall, the paper argues that reflective model approaches have the potential to transform the way we approach teaching and learning and that further research and exploration in this area are necessary to fully realize their potential.

Keywords: Reflective Model Approach, Teaching, Learning

Introduction

Reflective model approaches have gained significant attention in the field of teaching and learning in recent years. These approaches aim to enhance the learning experience by encouraging students to reflect on their own thinking and learning processes. Reflective model approaches aim to help students develop a deeper understanding of the material and improve their critical thinking skills. Reflective model approaches are rooted in various theoretical frameworks, such as Dewey's theory of reflective thinking and Schön's theory of reflective practice. These frameworks emphasize the importance of reflection in the learning process and the need for learners to actively engage with their own experiences and ideas. In this thematic paper, we will explore the key concepts and theoretical frameworks that underpin reflective model approaches and discuss the benefits and challenges of implementing these approaches in various educational contexts. We will also provide practical examples of how reflective model approaches can be used in the classroom to enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

Key Concepts and Theoretical Frameworks of Reflective Model Approaches

Reflective model approaches are built on several key concepts and theoretical frameworks that emphasize the importance of reflection in the learning process. Some of these key concepts and frameworks include:

Reflective thinking: Reflective thinking is a cognitive process that involves actively analyzing and evaluating one's own thoughts and actions. According to John Dewey, reflective thinking is essential for deep learning and involves a process of problem-solving, decision-making, and critical evaluation.

Reflective practice: Reflective practice is a process of learning and development that involves critically examining one's own experiences and actions to improve performance. Donald Schön's theory of reflective practice emphasizes the importance of reflection in professional practice and argues that professionals should engage in reflective activities to continually improve their skills and knowledge.

Metacognition: Metacognition refers to the ability to think about one's own thinking. This involves reflecting on one's own cognitive processes, such as attention, memory, and problem-solving, and adjusting as necessary to improve learning outcomes.

Self-regulated learning: Self-regulated learning is a process in which learners take an active role in their own learning. This involves setting goals, monitoring progress, and reflecting on one's own learning strategies and outcomes.

Experiential learning: Experiential learning is a process of learning through direct experience and reflection on that experience. This approach emphasizes the importance of active participation in the learning process and the use of reflection to enhance learning outcomes.

Benefits and Challenges of Reflective Model Approaches

Reflective model approaches have been shown to offer several benefits in educational contexts. These benefits include:

Enhanced critical thinking: Reflective model approaches encourage learners to critically evaluate their own thinking and learning processes, which can lead to a deeper understanding of the material and improved critical thinking skills.

Improved self-awareness: Reflective model approaches help learners develop self-awareness by encouraging them to reflect on their own experiences and learning processes. This can help learners identify their strengths and weaknesses and adjust their learning strategies as needed.

Increased engagement: Reflective model approaches can increase learner engagement by promoting active participation in the learning process. Learners are encouraged to take an active role in their own learning, which can lead to increased motivation and interest in the material.

Transferable skills: Reflective model approaches help learners develop transferable skills such as problem-solving, decision-making, and self-regulation, which can be applied in various contexts.

Despite these benefits, implementing reflective model approaches in educational contexts can also present challenges. Some of these challenges include:

Time constraints: Implementing reflective model approaches requires time for learners to engage in reflection activities, which may be difficult to accommodate within a busy curriculum.

Lack of structure: Reflection activities can lack clear structure and may be difficult for some learners to engage with without guidance or scaffolding.

Resistance to change: Some learners and educators may be resistant to implementing reflective model approaches due to unfamiliarity with the approach or perceived additional workload.

Evaluation: Assessing the effectiveness of reflective model approaches can be challenging, as traditional evaluation methods may not accurately capture the benefits of reflective learning.

Strategies for Incorporating Reflective Practices into the Classroom

Incorporating reflective practices into the classroom can enhance the learning experience for students. Here are some strategies for integrating reflective practices into the classroom:

Establish a culture of reflection: Encourage a culture of reflection in the classroom by modeling reflective practices and creating opportunities for students to reflect on their learning.

Use reflective prompts: Provide students with reflective prompts, such as "What did I learn?" or "What could I have done differently?" to guide their reflection.

Encourage peer reflection: Foster peer reflection by encouraging students to discuss their learning experiences with each other and provide feedback.

Incorporate reflection into assessments: Include reflection activities as part of assessments, such as asking students to reflect on their performance after completing an assignment or exam.

Use technology: Utilize technology tools, such as online journals or blogs, to facilitate reflection and provide a platform for students to share their reflections with others.

Incorporate reflection into lesson plans: Incorporate reflective activities into lesson plans, such as reflective writing or discussion activities, to reinforce the importance of reflection in the learning process.

Provide feedback: Provide students with feedback on their reflections to reinforce the importance of reflection and to help them improve their reflective skills.

Examples of Reflective Model Approaches in Teaching and Learning

Educators can use various reflective model approaches to enhance teaching and learning. Here are some examples:

Journaling: Journaling is a common reflective model approach where learners are asked to reflect on their learning experiences in a written format. This can be done regularly throughout a course or after specific learning experiences.

Peer feedback: Peer feedback is a reflective model approach where learners provide feedback to one another on their work, allowing them to reflect on their own and others' learning experiences.

Case studies: Case studies are reflective model approaches that present real-world scenarios for learners to analyze and reflect on. This approach encourages learners to apply critical thinking skills and reflects on their own decision-making processes.

Collaborative learning: Collaborative learning is a reflective model approach where learners work together in small groups to complete tasks and projects. This approach allows learners to reflect on their own learning processes as well as the learning processes of their peers.

Learning portfolios: Learning portfolios are a reflective model approach where learners collect and curate evidence of their learning over time. This approach encourages learners to reflect on their learning experiences and progress.

Exit tickets: Exit tickets are a reflective model approach where learners are asked to respond to a prompt or question at the end of a class or learning experience. This approach encourages learners to reflect on what they learned, what they still have questions about, and how they can apply what they learned.

The Potential of Reflective Model Approaches to Transform Teaching and Learning

Reflective model approaches have the potential to transform teaching and learning in several ways. Here are some examples:

Empowering learners: Reflective model approaches can encourage learners to take an active role in their own learning. This approach can increase motivation and engagement by allowing learners to take ownership of their learning processes.

Enhancing critical thinking: Reflective model approaches can enhance critical thinking by encouraging learners to analyze and evaluate their own learning experiences. This approach can help learners develop the skills necessary to think critically and solve problems in a variety of contexts.

Personalizing learning: Reflective model approaches can help personalize learning by encouraging learners to reflect on their individual learning styles and preferences. This approach can help educators tailor instruction to meet the unique needs of each learner.

Developing metacognitive skills: Reflective model approaches can help learners develop metacognitive skills, which involve understanding how they learn and how to monitor and regulate their own learning processes. This approach can help learners become more effective and independent learners.

Building community: Reflective model approaches can build a sense of community among learners by encouraging them to share their learning experiences with one another. This approach can help learners develop empathy and respect for one another and create a more supportive learning environment.

Reflective model approaches have the potential to transform teaching and learning by empowering learners, enhancing critical thinking skills, personalizing learning, developing metacognitive skills, and building community. By incorporating reflective practices into teaching and learning, educators can help learners become more self-aware, reflective, and effective learners.

Future Research Directions and Implications for Practice

Reflective model approaches have gained increasing attention in educational contexts, and several future research directions can expand our understanding of their effectiveness and implications for practice.

Long-term impact: Future research can investigate the long-term impact of reflective model approaches on learners' academic and personal development. This includes examining how reflective practices can influence learners' future career trajectories and overall well-being.

Different contexts: Future research can explore the effectiveness of reflective model approaches in different learning contexts, such as online learning, experiential learning, and vocational education.

Digital technologies: Future research can investigate the potential of digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence and data analytics, to enhance reflective practices and support learners' development.

Teacher preparation: Future research can investigate how teacher preparation programs can incorporate reflective model approaches to prepare future educators for implementing reflective practices in their classrooms.

Equity and diversity: Future research can examine how reflective model approaches can promote equity and diversity in educational contexts by encouraging learners to reflect on their own biases and assumptions and promoting inclusive practices.

Implications for practice include the following:

Professional development: Educators should receive professional development opportunities to develop their skills in implementing reflective model approaches.

Assessment practices: Educators should incorporate reflective practices into their assessment practices to encourage learners to reflect on their own learning processes and progress.

Learner-centred instruction: Educators should design learner-centred instruction that incorporates reflective practices to promote learners' active engagement in their own learning.

Creating a reflective culture: Educators should foster a reflective culture in their classrooms and schools by modeling reflective practices and providing opportunities for learners to reflect on their learning experiences.

Future research and implications for practice can help educators to better understand the effectiveness of reflective model approaches and how to implement them effectively to promote learners' development and growth.

Conclusion

Reflective model approaches have become increasingly important in teaching and learning due to their potential to empower learners, enhance critical thinking, and personalized learning, develop metacognitive skills, and build community. Through reflective practices, learners can become more self-

aware, reflective, and effective learners. Reflective model approaches are not without challenges, including the need for training and support for educators, the time required to implement reflective practices, and the potential for learners to feel uncomfortable or vulnerable during reflection. However, the benefits of the reflective model approach far outweigh these challenges. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, the importance of reflective model approaches in teaching and learning will only increase. By incorporating reflective practices into their teaching, educators can help learners develop the skills and knowledge necessary to succeed in today's rapidly changing world. Ultimately, the goal of reflective model approaches is to promote lifelong learning and development, both inside and outside of the classroom.

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BLENDED LEARNING: ITS HISTORY, PRESENT AND FUTURE

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Introduction

It's a good idea to educate yourself as much as you can on the main concepts and principles of blended learning before developing a strategy for it. Yet, in order to comprehend these, you must first be aware of how it all began and the significant historical events that helped to create its fundamental ideas along the way. Now let's board the mental small time machines and go back to the early days of blended learning. Parents and students alike should become familiar with the idea, comprehend how it functions, and grasp why blended education, also known as blended learning, is becoming more and more popular at post-secondary schools across North America. This form of schooling is also known as hybrid learning in some regions. Whatever you choose to call it, it's widely accepted that it will be the method of instruction used in a regular school in the future.

Blended learning ideally mixes traditional classroom instruction with online learning, giving teachers greater freedom and giving students a more complete educational experience. According to Professor Tony Bates, author of *Teaching in a Digital Age: Principles for Planning Teaching and Learning*, a good blended experience would maximise the synergy between the in-person sessions and online learning. With an emphasis on outcomes, blended learning incorporates a range of techniques to help students learn the necessary material. How much do you truly know about this interactive and interesting learning method, blended learning, which is a popular issue in the eLearning industry? How did blended learning develop into what it is now, and when did it first appear? Let's look at blended learning's history, present and future.

1840's: First Distance Course

The first distant learning course was introduced by Sir Isaac Pitman. Pitman's version of the idea was intended to approximate distant learning as we know it now, although there were other versions on the theme before his. His shorthand course was the main focus. Pitman assigned his students shorthand passages via postcards that they were obliged to return for grading and correction. Effective feedback and assessments were still a crucial component of the process even if computers and mobile devices weren't utilised and wouldn't even be created for about a century.

1960's & 1970's: Mainframe Computer-Based Training

The mainframe and minicomputer training of the 1960s and 1970s is where modern computer-based training has its roots. For the first time, training could be distributed to a large number of employees within an organisation without relying on printed materials and in-person instruction. To obtain the information, staff members needed just to log in to their character-based terminals. Plato, created in 1963 by Control Data and the University of Illinois, was one of the most renowned systems. Plato is still alive today, in fact.

1970's to 1980's: TV-Based Technology to Support Live Training

Companies started using video networks to train their personnel at this point in the blended learning timeline. To onboard new employees or increase the skill sets of current staff members, the instructor was no longer required to be physically present on the job site. This improved the training process and made it more engaging and participatory. Students could interact with one another, see the instructor on television, and even respond to any queries or issues sent to them by mail. Consider it to be the forerunner of webinars and video conferencing. The Stanford University Interactive TV network is one of the best examples of satellite-based training. In the 1970s and 1980s, Stanford invested resources in their video network, which is still in use today, allowing professors to simultaneously teach classes in several places throughout San Francisco. Learners can now submit their work for review online rather than sending it to the lecturer by mail or courier.

1980's & 1990's: CD-ROM Training and Rise of LMS

Applications and blended learning methodologies have grown along with technology. In order to give more interactive learning experiences, such those with video and sound, schools and organisations

started embracing CD-ROMs. These transmission methods were perfect for remote learning since they could store bigger amounts of information. Computer-based courses were now able to provide a rich and complete learning experience for the first time in the history of eLearning. In several instances, it even replaced in-person instruction. The first Learning Management Systems (LMS) were also introduced around this time, however they didn't have the same features as solutions have now. These systems assisted in keeping track of eLearning course completion, enrollment information, and user performance within the CD-ROM network. Companies wanted to be able to monitor learner progress and enhance online training courses.

1998: First Generation of Web-Based Instruction

Beginning in 1998 with the introduction of the first generation of web-based education, blended learning and eLearning as a whole have seen tremendous transformation in the last 20 years. Computers were now accessible to everyone, not only businesses and a rich elite. As personal computers became more widely available to all employees of businesses, more and more families started buying them for their enjoyment. Then, computers began to provide more interactivity. While browsers improved connection speeds and nearly everyone had access to online learning resources, graphics, sound, and video became more immersive. Organizations could simply upload content, eLearning exams, and assignments through the web, and learners could access them with a mouse click instead of needing to hand out CD-ROMs to learners. Several CD-ROM creators initially attempted to simply upload their eLearning courses to the internet without making any changes. But, they soon realised that in order to fulfil the needs of web-based learners, their current online content, such as enormous video files that took a while to download, would need to be carefully adjusted.

2000 Until Today: Blended Learning Integration

We are currently living in a fascinating period for integrated learning. With the speed at which technology is developing, more and more businesses and private educational institutions are starting to see the advantages of a blended learning strategy. Learners today have access to a wide choice of digital tools and applications, from interactive classroom scenarios to webinars and online tutorials. Since more students have access to computers and other devices thanks to schools, blended learning is becoming a more popular method of meeting student needs. When teachers increase their usage of digital resources for teaching and learning, blended learning generally develops at their own pace. At the moment, learning to teach with digital tools appears to be the greater priority than examining how to deepen students' learning.

When a teacher is also a learner and wants to increase the number of teaching strategies in their arsenal, blended learning makes perfect sense. Nonetheless, there are chances to further reform methods by giving students control over their education. Businesses may teach their staff at any time, anyplace, and online learners can take part in interactive eLearning courses and online communities from any location. Face-to-face instruction and technology-based learning are gradually combining to produce innovative and new ways to improve educational outcomes and make learning more enjoyable and interesting. Traditional classrooms have a track record of being successfully updated to the 21st century through blended learning. Why not employ blended learning to make your curriculum into a dynamic and interesting learning experience now that you are aware of its background.

Future education

The modern world is constantly changing and presents difficulties at every turn. The requirement to stay up with the times is evolving. We must change at a same rate or we will fall behind. Education plays a role in this situation. The most crucial tool, or rather weapon, in our armoury for equipping ourselves with the necessary skills, knowledge, and abilities to comprehend the world around us and, as a result, keep up with the times, is education. Also, it aids in perspective development by enlarging our field of view and viewpoint while simultaneously enhancing our abilities. The necessity for means of receiving or imparting education has been expanding along with the constantly shifting demands and requirements of society or the world. Since the days of the past, education delivery and acquisition systems have advanced significantly. Education is in no way an exception to the onset of digitization in every profession. Every element of education has been significantly impacted by digitization, especially the acceptance of e-learning as the preferred approach to meet changing demands.

Since its widespread adoption, blended learning has come a long way. It now goes hand in hand with the digital citizenship component, which guarantees improved future-focused learning methods

through correct integration to improve teaching and learning by enhancing both sides' digital capabilities. It encourages a balance between promotional and defensive online behaviours so that students and instructors may control their online interactions in a responsible and safe manner. E-learning has gained popularity because of its benefits and simplicity of use. While "Blended Learning" is included under this e-learning umbrella, this phrase is itself fairly unclear. It broadly includes teaching and learning strategies that combine technology and digitization with the conventional teacher- and instructor-led classroom approaches. While both professors and students must be present, there is some discretion over certain aspects, such as time or location. This makes it easier for teachers and students to tailor the learning process to each individual's needs and preferences. The "virtual classroom," where students have access to online platforms for self-study and also have choices for live online classes or consultations, is the greatest illustration to fully grasp this notion.

Managed learning

Both online and in physical classrooms, management of education and assessment is crucial. Teachers can connect with students about and collect assignments, provide comments, and provide learning resources online using tools like Schoology, Google Classroom, and Blackboard CourseSites. In order to put the learner at the centre of the discourse, teachers and administrators can engage in rich dialogue with students, parents, and other stakeholders.

Orchestrated learning

Instructors use controlled experiences to frame learning for their students. Students participate in focused instruction and practise under the teacher's guidance. For instance, students could finish online worksheets, write reading comments on message boards, take notes from teacher-recorded lectures and demonstrations or video tutorials, or participate in Kahoot or Edpuzzle-based entire class critiques.

Collaborative learning

Collaboration and critical thinking can be encouraged through student-led learning activities, both individually and in groups. Through an enormous wealth of online resources, teachers and students can collaborate to tailor learning to each student's requirements. Utilize social media sites like LinkedIn and Twitter to network with professionals who can mentor students and/or share their experience with them. Students can follow up with these experts via video conferencing, further connecting the curriculum to their real-world interests. Students occasionally require individualised assistance. There are a few ways that teachers can keep this individualised support under control. A teacher can create a resource library based on areas of frequent need, then add to it to satisfy requirements that arise less regularly. They can also counsel specific students or groups about these beneficial resources. Give kids a voice in how they exhibit their learning, if possible. For students to develop their cooperation abilities as part of digital citizenship, coaching and practise are necessary. Provide illuminating instances of thoughtful product reviews and comments on articles. Also, include questions for student feedback that they can use in online conversations of their thoughts and learning products.

Authentic learning

Public learning should be encouraged. When they have to present their findings to a curious outside audience in papers or live events students step up their game. Use authentic audiences outside of the classroom to engage learning and provide context for how curriculum pertains to actual circumstances. Utilize secure platforms like wikis, Schoology, and Google Hangouts to enable students to experience internal collaboration. When students are prepared to express their opinions to the public or a specific audience, post their work on open platforms like blogs and social media. Take those connections to the next level after networking via LinkedIn and/or Twitter as previously mentioned. Provide students "game day" experiences like shark tanks, live presentations, or product demonstrations for a customer. For a group of people who are interested in the subject, students present what they already know and are capable of. Hold workshops for collaborative learning and feedback with business partners or clients. Access is made possible between any location and time via video conferencing equipment. Whatsapp, Google Hangouts, Skype, and Zoom are real-time instances. Discussion forums, hash tagged tweets, and the commenting functionality on blogs, YouTube, and other social media platforms are all examples of asynchronous communication.

Conclusion

The Three-Decade History of Blended Modern technology is developing more quickly than ever before. According to several experts, VR and XR learning experiences will be combined with other currently popular software, such as course development tools and LMSs, to form the future of education. We might also see some other developments that alter how we think about online education. And what makes blended learning so amazing is that it can quickly adopt any new technology, offer the most appropriate learning environment for each unique circumstance, and maintain a balance between online and in-person formats. Imagine parks and skyscrapers with green grass on the walls and roofs of contemporary cities. That is what blended learning is: a blending of technology and nature.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Introduction

The world is changing constantly and the various domains are also influenced by the change. There is no exemption even in the education domain. The evolution of the digital learning platforms has a huge impact in educational institutions and has eventually put the traditional methods in the back seat. However, there are demands for both technology and traditional learning methods. As a result of this, the art of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching gave birth to the term "Blended Learning". This chapter deals about the educational transformations and the prerequisite for Blended Learning. BL is not a mere mix of online and face-to-face mode, but it refers to a well-planned combination of meaningful activities in both the modes. The blend demands consideration of several factors, mainly focusing on learning outcomes and the learner centred instructional environment. Blended learning is a learning approach that combines instructor-led brick-and-mortar classroom training and online learning activities. Unlike full-fledged e-learning, the online portion of the training doesn't replace face-to-face training with a teacher; teachers incorporate technology to enhance the learning experience and broaden understanding of certain topics. For example-video and offer students to watch it at home, email their review to a teacher, and then discuss it in class. Learners use channels in messengers, online communities, and task managers to plan their work and control the flow. They also use file-sharing services to collaborate and share feedback on the project.

Blended learning

On the other hand, combines in-person teaching with online learning methods. So, learners can listen to a lecture in a classroom and then take an online quiz right there or at home. "Defining Blended learning "designates the range of possibilities presented by combining Internet and digital media with established classroom forms that require the physical co-presence of teacher and students".Technology-based training emerged as an alternative to instructor-led training in the 1960s on mainframes and mini-computers. One example is PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automatic Teaching Operations), a system developed by the University of Illinois and Control Data. PLATO in particular had a long history of innovations and offered coursework from elementary to the college level. In the early 1990s, CD-ROMs emerged as a dominant form of providing technology-based learning as bandwidth through 56k modems wasn't able to support very high quality sound and video. The limitation to CD-ROMs was tracking completion of coursework, so learning management systems emerged as a way to facilitate progress tracking. The aviation industry used this heavily to track how well one did on courses, how much time was spent, and where someone left off. AICC, Aviation Industry Computer-Based Training Committee, was formed in 1988 and companies such as Boeing used CD-ROMs to provide training for personnel. There is little consensus on the definition of blended learning. Some academic studies have suggested it is a redundant term.[8] However, there are distinct blended learning models suggested by some researchers and educational think-tanks. These models include:

- Face-to-face driver – where the teacher drives the instruction and augments with digital tools.
- Rotation – students cycle through a schedule of independent online study and face-to-face classroom time.
- Flex – Most of the curriculum is delivered via a digital platform and teachers are available for face-to-face consultation and support.
- Labs – All of the curriculum is delivered via a digital platform but in a consistent physical location. Students usually take physical classes in this model as well.

The important features of Blended Learning Environment

- Increased student engagement in learning
- Enhanced teacher and student interaction
- Responsibility for learning.
- Time management and flexibility
- Improved student learning outcomes
- Enhanced institutional reputation
- More flexible teaching and learning environment
- More amenable for self and continuous learning
- Better opportunities for experiential learning

Benefits of Blended Learning

- Safer learning environment
- Interactive learning process
- Learner autonomy
- Greater learner engagement
- Better comprehension
- Detailed analytics

Role of Teachers in BL Environment

BL shifts the teacher's role from knowledge provider to coach and mentor. This shift does not mean that teachers play a passive or less important role in students' education. Quite the contrary with BL, teachers can have an even more profound influence and effect on students' learning. Traditionally, classroom instruction has largely been teacher-directed, top-down, and one-size-fits-all, with a bit of differentiation thrown in, but with BL, it now becomes more student-driven, bottom-up, and customized, with differentiation as a main feature. Much of this new learning dynamic is due to the enhanced role technology plays in instruction. BL provides an appropriate balance between online instructions, offers the interactive, tech-based learning, individualized pacing, and privacy that keep students continuously engaged and motivated, and teacher-led instruction, which personalizes the learning experience and adds the human elements of encouragement, compassion, and caring guidance that only teachers can give. This new learning dynamic benefits students and teachers alike. Giving

students permission and space to become active learners who gain knowledge directly lets them assume some control over their learning and helps them develop self-reliance. As more students are working independently, time opens up for teachers to provide face-to-face support and individualized instruction more frequently for more students, effectively improving differentiation. BL provides teachers with a fuller, more accurate picture of how each student is doing. BL yields more frequent and more personal teacher interaction with individual students, teachers have the opportunity to deepen and strengthen student/teacher relationships. The trust that comes with close relationships can give teachers insights into students' personal struggles and needs -insights which empower teachers to comfort and coach students through challenges that often serve as obstacles to learning. In summary, BL combines the best aspects of online learning with the best aspects of direct instruction, helping teachers easily manage to do much more to meet student needs without adding to an already weighty workload.

Role of a Learner in the Blended Learning Environment

Increase student interest:

When technology is integrated into school lessons, learners are more likely to be interested in, focused on, and excited about the subjects they are studying.

Keep students focused for longer:

The use of computers to look up information & data is a tremendous lifesaver, combined with access to resources such as the internet to conduct research. This engagement and interaction with the resources keeps students focused for longer periods than they would be with books or paper resources, this engagement also helps develop learning through exploration and research.

Provides student autonomy:

The use of e-learning materials increases a student's ability to set appropriate learning goals and take charge of his or her own learning, which develops an ability that will be translatable across all subjects.

Instill a disposition of self-advocacy:

Students become self-driven and responsible, tracking their individual achievements, which helps develop the ability to find the resources or get the help they need, self-advocating so they can reach their goals.

Promote student ownership:

BL instills a sense of 'student ownership over learning' which can be a powerful force propelling the learning, It's this feeling of responsibility that helps the feeling of ownership.

Allow instant diagnostic information and student feedback

The ability to rapidly analyze, review and give feedback to student work, gives the teacher the ability to tailor his teaching methods and feedback for each student while improving time efficiency.

Enables students to learn at their own pace:

Due to the flexibility of BL and the ability to access internet resources allows students to learn at their own pace, meaning a teacher can help speed up the learning process or give more advanced resources if necessary.

Blended Learning Structures in Education

Many factors must be considered when choosing how to blend in-person and online teaching and learning activities. In some cases, most interactions between students and the teacher, as well as the direct delivery of instruction, take place in person in the classroom, while materials and possibly some additional activities are delivered online. In other cases, most of the class activities occur online, with infrequent meetings in person to solve problems and support community building. In some blended arrangements, students may choose which activities to complete online and which to complete in a classroom. Ideally, blends are personalized so individual students have the blend that best fits their age, life circumstances and learning needs. These are called à cartel models. Students choose what to take fully online, what to take fully in person and, when the design is available, blended courses where they choose when to go to in person classes and when to watch videos, download readings and complete assignments online. This kind of personification is not always available. Most important is ensuring that students are able to function well as learners with any delivery method, single-mode or blended, even if it is not their preference or the best situation for them. Teachers are valuable coaches for helping students manage in any learning situation; it is up to teachers and learning designers to offer blended activities that best suit the subject, the learners' needs and the curriculum requirements. Not all unique and interesting BL designs are one-size-fits-all model. Below are seven sample configurations of BL activities to consider for BL teaching

situation. These examples of BL are drawn from higher education but can be shaped to fit any teaching and learning situation.

Blended learning in 21st century

The term "21st century literacies" was coined by The National Council of Teachers of English to describe the social nature of learning that is supported by the ability to collaborate using digital technologies in learning. These 'new literacies' are described as "skills students will need for the society in which they will work", including "strong communication and collaboration skills, expertise in technology, innovative and creative thinking skills, and an ability to solve problems". This set of skills and understandings will "prepare the workforce or citizenry for a changing, interconnected world". These literacies are dynamic due to the ability to be linked to one another. According to NCTE, active, successful participants in this 21st century global society must be able to:

- Develop proficiency and fluency with the tools of technology;
- Build intentional cross-cultural connections and relationships with others so to pose and solve problems collaboratively and strengthen independent thought;
- Design and share information for global communities to meet a variety of purposes;
- Manage, analyze and synthesize multiple streams of simultaneous information;
- Create, critique, analyze and evaluate multimedia texts;
- Attend to the ethical responsibilities required by these complex environments.

Pedagogies for Online and Face-to-face Modes

Learner-centred teaching-learning activities include several cognitive processes which enable learners to be communicative, confident, creative and cooperative. Learners in Bl environments are not visualised as passive learners, but active learners generating ideas, assimilating knowledge individually and in teams. Once learning resources are provided on an online platform, students sitting in the classroom need not again listen to the instructor. The time, then, can be used for engaging them in activities. Even their online time can be used innovatively for making online sessions more effective and interesting. Here are a few learning processes for both online and face-to-face mode.

Conclusion

The chapter provides detailed guidelines communicating minimum recommendations from UGC for implementation of BL. Universities and parent bodies need to ensure checking essential requirements to begin with and then should monitor processes to ensure successful implementation of BL. BL mode is to be used nation-wide to help learners develop 21st century skills along with the effective learning and skill development related to the subject-domains. BL should be carefully implemented and should not be replacing classroom time as a privilege. Every institute should strive to be a model institute to demonstrate a successful implementation of BL in the higher education of our country.

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WHY ONLINE LEARNING: PERSPECTIVES ON ONLINE LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT FOR 2023

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic forced schools to close and shift didactic instruction online. However, the abrupt transition to online learning has raised several unresolved issues. Several studies have examined students' attitudes towards online learning during the pandemic, with mixed results. Furthermore, little research has been done to identify and comprehend factors, particularly pedagogical factors influencing students' acceptance of online learning during campus closure. Furthermore, no empirical research has been conducted to determine how online learning during the pandemic affected students' learning performance. In response to government-issued stay-at-home orders, the school studied here moved didactic instruction online in March 2020. During the pandemic, this first-of-its-kind comparative study investigated students' perceived effectiveness of online courses during the summer quarter 2020, analysed pedagogical factors influencing their acceptance of online courses, and empirically evaluated the impact of online learning on student's course performance.

Keywords: *Online Learning, Online Education, Covie-19*

Introduction

The most important aspect of our lives is education. Nowadays, getting an education is so simple that we don't need to leave the house. We can receive instruction from a teacher while sitting at home in an online mood. In today's world, amenities like the internet are available in every home. In the aftermath of Corona, online education is proving extremely effective. Whether in a village or a city, online education is becoming increasingly popular. We can participate in online education anywhere in the United States or abroad. Online education is now proving to be extremely highly beneficial to students. The pandemic has had a significant impact on education and educational systems all over the world. To mitigate the effects of Corona, educational institutions around the world were temporarily closed. School closures have impacted 1.077 billion students. The big question now is, how do students get an education? Many large organisations have only found one solution to this problem: online education. This has an effect that can be seen everywhere.

Online education is achieved in some ways through computers and the internet. For online education, computers and various types of gadgets are used. However, the internet's quality must be adequate for this, and we must pay close attention to this. There is no such thing as lockdown, but a lethal disease like corona hasn't given up. As a result of the unusual circumstances, schools and colleges have made online education their primary support. Which is correct or incorrect depends on the outcome of the situation in each case. Hembree (1988) in his meta-analysis found that test anxiety is negatively related to performance and self-esteem. Many of us are aware that e-learning is a type of distance education. Teachers can educate their students even if they are sitting far away, whether at home or outside the house. This allows teachers and students to exchange ideas, which is a good way to learn about education. Today's world is rapidly progressing towards utilisation, with an ever-increasing number of technical applications used to communicate and pass on knowledge. Knowledge acquisition in a traditional classroom is limited to the information available to the instructor and that which they can access. Connecting students to the outside world, on the other hand, improves their ability to construct new knowledge.

Blended Learning

Online Learning is an umbrella term that refers to a wide range of electronic methods for gaining access to education, as well as the process itself. Virtual classrooms, web-based learning, computer-based learning, digital collaboration, video and audio recordings, interactive television, and many more are examples. As a result, Online Learning lends itself well to flexible learning methods and distance learning. However, online learning can be combined with face-to-face instruction, a process known as blended learning.

The History of Online Learning

Since its inception in the 1990s, online learning has come a long way. The concept has a long history, dating back to the days of distance learning on radio programmes in the 1920s. Professor Don Bitzer's introduction of PLATO, the first computer-based education tool, in 1960, became a significant milestone in the world of Online Learning. Its primary goal was to increase and improve student literacy.

Online Learning Advantages

Diverse Learning Tool Association

Students can broaden their horizons by using mixed learning tools. Online learning platforms typically make use of a combination of online assets. It consists of a variety of instruments that are made available to students and teachers.

Online Course Catalogues

A Learning Management System (LMS) creates appropriate schedules and lists of the courses that are available. Users can easily navigate to the course, get a preview, and enrol by scrolling through the lists or catalogues.

Simple User Interface

To break up the monotony of traditional learning, Online Learning apps and websites can make learning more inclusive and interactive by using appealing design, bold aesthetics, and engaging interfaces.

The Evolution of Online Education

The last decade has seen a dramatic shift in Online Learning. Initially, courses offered for Online Learning were typically created by groups of programmers using software creation tools. Technology advancements resulted in the creation of the World Wide Web, making the creation of Online Learning courses a simpler task that anyone without programming knowledge could complete. Changes in technology resulted in new hardware, such as portable computers, which made it very simple for students to access course material online. Many people nowadays use tablets and smartphones for online classes, web seminars, and webinars.

Online Learning Varieties

Online learning can be classified based on how it is delivered from the instructor to the student. An informal form of Online Learning distribution is one in which students are trusted to view the available course material without being tracked or tested for completion. Instructors usually keep track of and record learner progress and results in the formal distribution form of Online Learning. Most educational institutions that provide student certifications have specific systems and standards for calculating student scores. Learning Management Systems (LMS) are used to track grades and ensure that students' standards for each course are met. They are platforms that allow users to create good online courses while also allowing students to access these courses. These platforms are of various types and have varying capabilities. Some are free, while others require a fee.

Online Learning Elements

A number of criteria must be met when developing an online course. Setting a set of criteria ensures that students get the most out of the course they signed up for. The following are some common elements of online learning:

- The role of the teacher/instructor is critical. He or she is required to provide necessary feedback to students. He or she is also sometimes in charge of keeping track of students' progress or grades.
- A well-structured Learning Management System is required. It should be simple to use for both the student and the instructor.
- The learning material is the most important aspect of online learning. Typically, course material is formatted in a way that is simple and easy for students to understand.
- Communication is essential for learning. Students must use one or more of the many modes of communication or delivery methods to access online coursework from the instructor.

There are numerous devices available today that allow teachers and students to share knowledge. The trainer interacts with viewers or listeners through multimedia, voice communications, videos (live or pre-recorded), presentations, product demonstrations, and text chats, which are mostly conducted over the internet.

The Importance of Online Education

Online learning was implemented to increase student literacy. Users have been empowered to obtain basic education and skills as technology has advanced and a variety of websites and apps that support Online Learning have become available. Online Learning has brought together all of the tutors, experts, learners, and practitioners in one location. Audio-visual technologies have eliminated the monotony of traditional teaching methods.

Process of Online Learning

Online learning can be practised on a variety of platforms, including Skillshare and Google Classroom. A concise course catalogue is available for users to select the course of their choice. The tutors design a pre-determined learning module for each course. The user only needs to sign up and finish the course.

The significance of online education & the Benefits of Online Learning

Online learning platforms provide users with tech-savvy and smart tools that allow them to gain access to top-tier content and knowledge.

Technology changes education

There have been many changes in technology and its use in the changing environment. Technology has also caused many changes in the way people receive an education. Today, teaching materials used in online education can be sent from one location to another using online technology. We can have the learning material delivered to another location in no time, no matter where we are in the world Such as any educational link, video, or file. All of these variations make online education more creative.

Option to choose any subject or teacher

One of the advantages of online education is that we have choices. We have the option of studying with whatever teacher or subject we want in online education. We can make our own decision. You can discuss the topic with your teacher in addition to selecting it.

Don't be afraid to take notes

Unlike in a classroom, we don't have to be alert and take notes with the teacher in online education. We can pause and resume watching videos in online education. We can memorise them instead of taking notes in this manner.

Convenience of online education

Online education is extremely convenient. The student can sit anywhere and receive education in this case. There is no fixed location for this, and the student receives relief even in hot weather like summer. Students do not have to go outside in this scorching heat, and they can receive an education while sitting at home.

Online education for technology knowledge

As we all know, online education for children is currently taking place. As a result, many children have been taught new technology such as video chatting and are completing their studies. With such online classes, children are constantly learning a new way of reading from their teachers and developing an interest in reading. The changing environment of education has also made learning more enjoyable and exciting. They find this study boring and exhausting while attending school and communicating with the teachers. Apart from finding it enjoyable to learn about technology, children find it more interesting and comfortable to learn while at home.

Multimedia Software

The Online Learning process makes studying more interesting, with graphics and engrossing video clips. Instead of boring lessons, Online Learning platforms use high-tech multimedia tools to engage users.

Sensory Involvement

Online learning tools and features increase users sensory engagement. Learning methods necessitate that students actively use their ears, eyes, and hands while taking a lesson. This engagement involves the user in the specific assignment.

Increased Customization

Each person possesses a unique set of skills. Every user has a different rate and level of retention. Online learning platforms recognise this fact and, as a result, provide a unique experience for each user.

Course Revision

Students receive immediate feedback from Online Learning platforms. Users are immediately corrected and directed to the correct answer. The firsthand feedback answers the users' questions.

Speed

Instead of wasting time, Online Learning users can accelerate their learning. If users already have the necessary subject knowledge, they can test their knowledge through mock tests, saving time and resources.

Learner Contentment

The result boards, certificates, and metrics that Online Learning provides to its users boost their confidence. It satisfies users because they get to see the results of their efforts. A student's personality has also been a factor that can influence his or her academic success. One study shows that extroverted students are likely to perform better than introverted ones (Burton & Dowling, 2005).

Analytics and data

The user responses can be checked using data and analytics. The Learning Management System can learn from user responses and make the necessary changes. A study shows that students who have access to great school facilities are more engaged to teach (Jay & Zain, 2019).

Standardization

To engage the user, the Online Learning system makes its content and material user-friendly. Adapting learning methods to the needs of the user makes it easier for the user to absorb and retain information.

Frequently Assigned Tasks

Each Online Learning platform has a plethora of mock tests, quizzes, and assignments for users to put their knowledge to the test. These assignments not only assist the user in applying their knowledge, but also boost their confidence.

Eco-friendly and long-lasting

Online learning tools do not waste resources and are therefore beneficial to the environment. These tools consume less energy and produce better results.

Scalability:

The Online Learning system demonstrates the ability to connect a large number of users from all over the world. It efficiently manages and organises users into various branches. While online education has many benefits, it also has some drawbacks. This does not translate from physical to mental form. Some of these drawbacks are as follows. While there is always another side to every coin, Online Learning does have some drawbacks.

Disadvantages of Online Education**Internet abuse**

The most serious disadvantage of the internet is that, regardless of their financial situation, parents must provide their children with mobile phones, laptops, and computers. Whether or not the children receive a proper education, they are unaware of these things. And children take advantage of this by making games out of it. Or they open things that are inappropriate for them.

Lack of harmony between the teacher and the students

Another disadvantage of online education. If this education was delivered in the traditionally, the student would discuss the subject with the teacher in class at the same time. However, in online education, teachers are unable to explain to students, and students are unable to understand and remain compatible with both subjects. The kind of environment that does not exist in online education, but should exist in a classroom.

Physical consequences of online education

The use of online education causes physical problems for both teachers and students. When a student studies online for 6-8 hours straight, the light from a computer or laptop screen hurts their eyes. As a result, their skin and bodies become dull, which is physically very harmful.

Online education suffers from a lack of focus

When a student is unable to pay attention to his or her studies by attending school, where will he or she be able to pay attention in online education? He/she does not have the fear that a student has while studying in school. In online education, students frequently abandon their lessons in the middle, which is incorrect.

Difficult to make online education available to everyone

Online education may not be accessible to all. Where can a person provide computer, mobile, and laptop facilities for his children if he only unites day and night for two times of bread? As a result, the education of children from low-income families is stalled, and they are forced to remain at home.

Epilogue

As a result of the Corona period, there has been a significant change in education. Misuse of new technology is visible where the person is becoming acquainted with it. Online education has both advantages and disadvantages, but the most important thing is to obtain an education. Education should take any form, but the student's education should not be overlooked; this point must be prioritised. As a result, online education is the most popular medium of instruction today.

Social Exclusion

Users of Online Learning platforms frequently learn to avoid the real world. Users resist venturing out into the world while sitting in their personal space. They withdraw from society and thus find themselves alone.

Inadequate Technological Literacy

Everyone does not have equal access to technology and resources. Those who have access may be unfamiliar with how to use it. A large segment of society is still unable to afford or obtain the resources and devices required for the Online Learning process.

Inadequate Time Management Skills

Online learning platform users are frequently observed to procrastinate. Users set aside their lessons for the following day because they can access the learning material whenever they want. As a result, users develop poor time management skills. People are adopting technology and finding new ways to integrate it in support of education in today's fast-paced, technology-oriented world. Online learning is forging ahead, redefining how knowledge is acquired.

Conclusion

During the COVID-19 pandemic, dental students had generally positive attitude towards online learning, according to this study, and their perceived engagement with faculty and classmates predicted their acceptance of the online course. This is the first study in dental education to show that online learning during the pandemic can achieve similar or better learning outcomes than face-to-face learning before the pandemic. Our findings could significantly contribute to the literature on online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in health sciences education. The findings could also help to shape future online learning design as we reimagine the future of online learning.

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PERCEPTION OF STUDENT TEACHERS ON BLENDED LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION WITH REFERENCE TO TAMILNADU

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Abstract

Information and communication technologies (ICTs) provide instructors and students with a creative learning environment in order to enliven and enhance the process of instruction and learning. New educational concepts, including instructional methodologies, are being examined in this context. The descriptive research survey design was used in this study. The population of this study comprised of all student teachers in higher education in Tamilnadu State. 230 student teachers were randomly selected. The research instrument used to collect data is a questionnaire titled; Student teachers' perception of blended learning in higher education (STPBLHE). The tool was validated by experts in education and reliably tested at ($r=0.94$). Data were analysed using mean, standard deviation and percentages, for the research question, while 't' test was used to analysed research hypothesis. The finding showed that student teachers had a favourable opinion of blended learning in higher education and that there was a discernible gender difference in the opinions of male and female student teachers. Based on the findings, it can be inferred that, student teachers perception on blended learning is positive. Thus, the finding showed that student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality. Consequently, it may be concluded that the opinion of student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on gender, medium, and locality. Furthermore, this conclusion suggests that the government should promote blended learning at all educational levels, and both male and female students in higher education should be encouraged to do so, among other recommendations that were made.

Key words: *Blended Learning, Student Teachers, Perception, and Higher Education*

Introduction

Increasing student teacher performance and reducing course dropout rates are two common concerns for educators. It seems clear that changing the ways of offering education might well be required to accomplish these aims. Information & communication technologies (ICTs) may have a positive influence on higher education because they offer a novel way to generate, allocate, and receive university education while enhancing conventional teaching and learning process. Presently, the educational sector is working very hard on this. The modern method of enhancing physical classes with online resources is known as "blended learning" (Garrison 2014). Blended learning's success is not just the outcome of the forthright FTF approach's integration with ICTs (De George-Walker & Keeffe, 2010). When there are numerous pupils, this type of resource increases their chances of understanding and using the knowledge (Singh, 2010). The use of mixed learning resources may lead to changes in learning processes and habits. They are frequently used in large classroom settings, such as first-year undergraduate study courses, which are crucial in assessing the student's dedication to university learning and constitute an important year in that respect (Funon, 2017).

The students' personal experiences with the process are another crucial element of classroom, according to Ginns & Ellis (2019). As just results, we examined at three aspects of student perspectives: the gains made, the impact it had on their propensity to study, and the degree of satisfaction made. A subjective outcome measure based on the student's perception of blended learning and an objective measure made up of the grade given on the final test were both used in the current study to assess results utilizing blended learning. This last statistic relates to the aforementioned three elements of usefulness, motivation, and satisfaction. There is evidence from earlier studies, such as those by Crawford, O., Nicholas, J., and Nam, M. (2018), that there is connection between how students perceive their education and the concrete results they experience as a result. We think further investigation into this connection is necessary. As a result, the present study's second objective was to determine the extent to which a relationship between the students' final mark and the mixed educational experience was produced. By examining how students' opinions of its utilization may affect their mark on the fourth exam, we tried to provide additional proof to the blended learning experience. Several studies have shown that using blended learning increases test scores and decreases dropout rates. As results, we examined at three aspects of individual perspectives: the gains made,

the impact it had on their propensity to study, and the degree of satisfaction made. A subjective outcome measure based on the student's assessment of the blended learning experience and an objective measure made up of the grade given on the final test were used in the present research to investigate two distinct sorts of results utilising the blended learning experience. This last statistic is based on the three elements already mentioned usefulness, inspiration, and satisfaction.

Need for the study

Blended learning, a relatively recent trend in education that mixes in-person teaching and online learning modules, have allowed students to take advantage of the both teaching approaches (Harding, Kaczynski, & Wood, 2005; Sathyaraj (2020). Other advantages include enhanced liveness and decreased costs when compared to regular lessons, especially when instructing a large class of understudies. This educational approach has several advantages over merely employing technology-based learning. As a result, we examined three aspects of their perspectives: the gains achieved the impact on their proclivity to study, and the amount of satisfaction gained. The present investigation used a personal outcome measure based on the student teacher's assessment of the blended learning opportunity and an objective measurement made up of the mark provided on the last test to measure two distinct types of outcomes utilizing the blended learning experience. The three elements utility, motivation, and satisfaction mentioned above serve as the basis for this latter statistic. Using this background knowledge, this study investigated how students perceived blended learning in higher education.

Research Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference on student teachers' awareness on blended learning in higher learning based on gender.
- There is no significant difference on student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on medium.
- There is no significant difference on student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality.

Research Methodology

In order to realize the above said objectives, survey method for descriptive research (Mani, M., 2017). All students registered in higher education in Tamilnadu State, make up the study's population. 230 student teachers were chosen at random to form the sample. A questionnaire named "Questionnaire on student teachers' perspective of blended learning in higher education" was used as the study tool to gather data (STPBLHE). The questionnaire included of two sections; the first section was the demographic information while the section B consisted of 15 item rating from strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The instrument was validated by experts in education and reliably tested at ($r=0.94$). The collected instruments were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and percentages, for the demographic information, which t.test was used to analysed the research hypothesis.

Analysis and Interpretation

Ho1: There is no significant difference on students' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on gender.

Table 1: Summary of 't' test result showing student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on gender

Variable	Gender	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	T value	Sig.
Perception on Blended Learning	Male	135	38.21	4.52	6.636	0.0001
	Female	95	34.45	3.78		

From table 1 and figure 1 showed the summary of t-test result on the student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on gender. It was revealed that male respondents had mean score 38.21 and standard deviation 4.52 while female respondents had mean score 34.45 and standard deviation 3.78, the t was 6.636, degree of freedom 228, significant level of 0.0001 ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is a significant difference on student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on gender was accepted. This implies that there is a significant difference on student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on gender.

Ho2: There is no significant difference on students’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on medium.

Table 2: Summary of ‘t’ test result showing student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on medium

Variable	Medium	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	T value	Sig.
Perception on Blended Learning	Tamil	132	37.71	4.82	2.179	0.0303
	English	98	36.45	3.58		

From table 2 and figure 2 showed the summary of t-test result on the student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on medium. It was revealed that Tamil respondents had mean score 37.71 and standard deviation 4.82 while English respondents had mean score 36.45 and standard deviation 3.58, the t was 2.179, degree of freedom 228, significant level of 0.0303 ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is a significant difference on student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on medium was accepted. This implies that there is a significant difference on student teachers’ perception on blended learning in higher learning based on medium.

H03: There is no significant difference on students' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality.

Table 3: Summary of 't' test result showing student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality

Variable	Locality	No	Mean	Std. Deviation	T value	Sig.
Perception on Blended Learning	Rural	107	37.64	3.82	4.224	0.0001
	Urban	123	40.01	4.58		

From table 3 and figure 3 showed the summary of t-test result on the student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality. It was revealed that rural respondents had mean score 37.64 and standard deviation 3.82 while urban respondents had mean score 40.01 and standard deviation 4.58, the t was 4.224, degree of freedom 228, significant level of 0.0001 ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is a significant difference on student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality was accepted. This implies that there is a significant difference on student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher learning based on locality.

Discussion

The outcomes of this study indicated that student teachers in Tamilnadu had a positive perception of blended learning in higher education. This means that the student had a favourable opinion of blended learning in higher education. This finding is in line with the study of Mani Mookkiah (2021); Lim (2021) who revealed that undergraduate student teachers' perception on blended learning in higher education is positive. this finding negates that of Mani Mookkiah (2020); Osan (2019) who opined that undergraduate student teachers have negative opinion regarding blended learning in schools. Another study conclusion found that there is no significant distinction between men and women in student teachers' perceptions of blended higher education learning. This research suggests that, regardless of gender, student instructors have a good attitude towards blended learning in higher education. This finding supports that of Israel (2018); Mani & M Prabu (2019) who revealed that there was no significant difference on male and female students' perception on blended learning in higher learning. Also, Henry (2019); Sathya Raj (2020) revealed that, gender had no significant difference on blended learning in higher learning.

Conclusion

The findings unmistakably demonstrate that student teachers think favourably of blended learning. Consequently, it may be concluded that the opinion of student teachers about mixed learning in higher education is good. Furthermore, this conclusion suggests that blended learning supports and strengthens the learning process by reinforcing student teachers' comprehension of the relevant material. Moreover, blended learning was well-received by both male and female student teachers.

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BENEFITS OF BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

Learning is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with traditional place-based classroom methods. It requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some elements of student control over time, place, path, or pace. The teaching landscape is rapidly changing, the technological rise of the 21st-century and widespread integration of those technologies into our society, combined with access to the internet has integrally changed teaching in just a few years. Our children and their following generations are already and will continue to grow up in a world

that's a stark reminder of how rapidly the human civilization has changed, a society and world where smartphones and tablets are widespread, affordable, and replacing most computers and laptops. The rapidly changing landscapes should be a marker to show that teaching methods need to evolve to keep up with the times and incorporate integrated technologies into the learning modal, these technologies aren't going to go away, they'll continue to be integrated into our society and it's time to embrace them for the advantages they bring.

What is Blended Learning?

Teach Thought provided a definition of blended learning in the past. Blended Learning is a mixture of learning methods that incorporate multiple teaching modals—most frequently eLearning and traditional face-to-face learning. Blended learning is a natural development to the growing accessibility of eLearning, online resources, and the continued need for a human component in the learning experience. A blended learning approach ensures that the learner is engaged and driving his or her individual learning experience. This approach also helps cater to the individual needs of the learner, most students have unique learning styles and a blended approach is more likely to cater to those needs than a traditional classroom teaching experience. Blended learning is a style of education that blends traditional place-based classroom techniques with online educational resources and possibilities for online engagement. It necessitates both the teacher's and the student's physical presence, as well as some student control over time, place, path, or location.

A blended learning approach is unquestionably a fantastic method to enhance a learner's experience, but its benefits extend well beyond that. Organizations that use blended learning to teach workers, partners, customers, or arrange compliance training will reap several benefits. You can use webinars in the instructor-led section of your course to get started with blended learning. A webinar tool is required to host a webinar. There are several alternatives accessible; all you have to do is choose the one that best meets your requirements. When selecting one, take into account the size of your audience, their needs, and the learner experience. Keep in mind that the goal of blended learning is to utilize the benefits of both conventional and online learning techniques to provide a more interesting learning experience for your students. You'll get the best of both worlds with blended learning, which will benefit both learners and educators.

Why is Blended Learning Important?

Blended learning is important because it breaks down the traditional walls of teaching, ones that don't work for all students and now with access to present-day technologies and resources we can tailor the learning experience for each student. Blended learning also offers flexible time frames that can be personalized to each person, offering them the ability to learn at their own pace. By making in-person and online learning complementary, blended learning creates a truly integrated classroom where the needs of all types of learners can be met. Keeping students engaged, stimulated, and motivated also helps teachers to be more effective and make greater gains with their student

Significance and importance of Blended Learning

There are a few sets of reasons as to why educational institutions adopt this approach of learning. Therefore, some of the critical significance and paramount importance of this method is as follows.

- Blended instruction is all the more efficient when in comparison with purely face-to-face or purely online classes.
- Moreover, this learning method can result in high levels of student achievement. Therefore, this is more effective than face-to-face learning.
- Further, this learning method also has the capability to reduce educational expenses. However, some do dispute that blended learning is less expensive than traditional classroom learning.
- E-textbooks, which can be accessed digitally, may also help to drive down textbook budgets.
- Blended learning can lower costs by putting classrooms in the online space. It essentially replaces pricey textbooks with electronic devices that students often are more comfortable with and bring with themselves to the classes.
- This method also allows students to work at their own pace, ensuring that they fully understand new concepts before undergoing the pressure of moving on.

What is Blended Classroom?

Before we can dive into the definition of a blended classroom, it's important to clarify what blended learning is. Blended learning is an approach to learning that makes use of both traditional classroom learning and online learning. So, what does blended learning look like in the classroom? A blended classroom allows learners to study at their own pace. By combining online and in-person components, learners will have more flexibility in how they approach their learning materials. As an instructor, the whole process can seem somewhat overwhelming at first, particularly if you have decades of experience in just face-to-face learning. So, we've compiled our top tips for creating a blended learning classroom design and applying this learning approach. With these tips, you should be able to create a course that's not only effective but will enable you to create the perfect blended classroom.

Advantages and benefits of Blended learning

1. Increase Student Interest:

A blended learning environment allows learners to 'see' concepts in real-world settings in a virtual environment. The context and practical implementation of the concepts increase student interest and make learning more interesting and immersive. Online resources help to bring alive subjects such as Mathematics and Science that are either difficult or monotonous and also help to improve information retention.

2. Increase Focus:

The attention span of the millennial generation is decreasing. With plenty of online content available on smartphones, users are free to view whatever content they want as long as it holds their attention. When technology is integrated into lessons, learners are more likely to remain focused on a subject for longer periods than they would be with books and paper resources.

3. Learning Through Exploration and Research:

Students can reinforce the lessons taught in the classroom through exploration and research. Given the vast number of online resources available, students can access them on their own to go deeper into the subject. Basically, blended learning provides a degree of autonomy to the students, allowing them to take charge of their own learning and set their own learning goals.

4. Learning by Doing:

Classroom teaching can sometimes be learning by rote, given that students are limited to the knowledge provided by the instructor. However, in blended learning, instructors can motivate the students with projects that involve going beyond the confines of the classroom and learning by doing. This also improves their research skills and ability to find the resources they need to reach their goals.

5. Promoting Learning Anytime and Anywhere:

While students are introduced to a lesson in a classroom, using their smartphones and laptops or other platforms, they can learn anytime and anywhere to supplement classroom lessons.

6. Gaining Access to Global Resources:

Again, learning is not restricted to the instructor, textbooks and peer interactions. The learners can access global resources and materials that meet their level of knowledge and interest.

7. Self-paced Learning:

One of the greatest weaknesses of traditional classroom settings is that it does not address individual learner and retention needs. Not all students have the same ability to grasp and retain concepts. A blended approach ensures that students who lag in class can use online resources for greater clarity. Similarly, quick learners can also progress to the next level. Therefore, blended learning helps to reduce stress, increases satisfaction and information retention.

8. Allows Diagnostic Information and Student Feedback:

Online assessment resources allow the instructors to rapidly analyse, review and give feedback to students. Besides, they can use this data to tailor their teaching methods and feedback for each student while improving time efficiency.

9. Greater Interaction with the Instructors:

Interaction with the instructor is not limited to the classroom. Students can use resources such as emails, discussion boards, annotations, highlights and chat rooms.

10. Prepares Students for the Future:

Blended learning offers a means to build skills for real-world settings, such as research skills, self-learning, and self-engagement, help to develop a 'self-driving force', better decision-making, a better sense of responsibility, and computer literacy.

Conclusion

Blended learning is a learning process that combines face-to-face learning with online learning to produce valid, effective and efficient learning. Blended learning, one of the teaching models, mixed traditional methods of teaching with an online course for achieving specific learning goals. A blended learning approach provides access to diverse and flexible learning environments and nurtures enriched literacy and learning. Learners who experience blended learning will see the world as they know it reflected in the programs where they learn and will deploy critical thinking skills to participate in a society where we are required to create, collaborate and communicate in digitally mediated networks. By creating a system of support that puts people first, adult education providers will work responsively to ensure educators are equipped with the knowledge and resources they need to create high-quality, collaborative learning experiences where learners develop confidence and competence using technology for learning, for work and in their daily lives.

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NEUROCOGNITIVE STRATEGIES AND TEACHING COMPETENCY: A NEW PARADIGM SHIFT IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study aimed to discuss the influence of neurocognitive strategies on teaching competency. The teacher plays an important role in the educational process. The most important task of education for the future is to improve the professional competence of the teachers. Only competent teachers will be able to relate theoretical insight to practice and to improve teacher preparation programme. They will be effective practitioners in their profession also. Teacher education seeks to develop such competencies in the prospective teachers; It intends to increase the ability of the teachers to deal with a range of individual differences. Teachers' can facilitate a life time of successful learning by equipping students with a repertoire of strategies and tools for learning. Effective teaching depends upon the evolution of innovative strategies and also the methodology of teaching. As we gain a more scientifically based understanding about today's novel brain and how it learns, we must rethink about what we do in the classroom and school. Neuroscientists are mapping the pathways between body and brain, providing tangible evidence of the benefits of hands-on, experimental learning.

Keywords: *Neurocognition, Competencies and Neuronal Network*

Introduction

“If the destiny of a nation is being shaped in her classroom, then the real destiny maker is the teacher”- Dr. Kothari. Education is an integral part of every human being. It moulds him to be a good citizen, who is really an asset of the country. “The wealth of a nation depends on the education of its citizens”. Teachers have a noble role in imparting knowledge to the innumerable members in a society. The teacher plays an important role in the educational process. On the caliber of the teacher depends the success with which new methods are employed and adopted? Teacher education is concerned with equipping the future teachers. The term “teacher education” is more comprehensive and has deeper implications. It

includes theoretical instruction and in practice of teaching in order to develop the skills needed for teaching effectively. Teaching is a delightful experience when focus is given on activities that student's brain enjoys doing and does well, such as exploring concepts, creating metaphors, estimating and predicting, co-operating on group tasks, and discussion oral or ethical issues. Conversely, teaching loses much of its luster when students are forced to do things which their brains do not enjoy doing and do poor.

Conceptual Understanding of Neurocognition

Neurocognitive process includes a number of human functions through neuronal networks. Brain cells communicate with each other through electrochemical process. Neurocognition includes perceiving, recognizing, conceiving, judging and reasoning processes. The neurocognitive approach is based upon certain irrefutable facts concerning brain function, which are applied to the strategies of student teacher's developmental difficulties. The teachers must develop the competencies like content competency, contextual competency, communication competency, classroom management and evaluation competency. Neurocognitive functions are cognitive functions closely linked to the function of particular areas, neural pathways, or cortical networks in the brain substrate layers of neurological matrix at the cellular molecular level. Therefore, their understanding is closely linked to the practice of neuropsychology and cognitive neuroscience, two disciplines that broadly seek to understand how the structure and function of the brain relates to perception defragmentation of concepts, memory embed, association and recall both in the thought process and behaviour . Naturally, the learning process depends on the effective functioning of the brain. Clearly, teaching will be more effective if it uses methods which are aligned with how the brain best attends to understand and retain information. Teaching learning process is concerned with the functioning of the brain that facilitates information processing, restoration and retrieval.

Neurocognitive Strategies

Neuro Cognitive Processing is an innovative approach to engage in passive cognitive activities such as watching a video while undergoing Neurocognitive Processing is a therapeutic approach that combines neurocognition with active mental stimulation or cognitive rehabilitation training. Neurocognitive Processing to simultaneously treat both systems resulting in a more attentive, focused mind. Pre-existing neuro pathways are strengthened through the neurocognitive approach while the cognitive rehabilitation programme is improving attention, processing speed, memory, hand-eye coordination, visual discrimination, executive function, visual memory, auditory discrimination, and auditory comprehension. In this study to discuss the neurocognitive strategies on the concept of neuro education, such as sensory association, information sequencing, visual recognition, auditory monitoring, scaffolding and decoding, emotional regulation, cognitive association and cognitive verbal articulation. The teachers should be fully aware of the factors like Instructional procedure, model using the strategy, think aloud, start with simplified materiel, complete part of the task for the students, present material in small steps, anticipate student errors and difficult areas, provide models of expert work, suggest fix up strategies, increase students responsibility influencing in teaching competency. If the teacher follows some of the neurocognitive practices such as affective education, relaxation training, cognitive restructuring, attribution retraining, problem solving, contingent reinforcement, neural modeling, neural plasticity, neural rewiring, neural firing, neural tuning and emotional integration to improve their efficiency, it will definitely help them to take their roles confidently in enhancing their teaching competency in the classroom situation.

Conceptual Understanding of Teaching Competency

Teaching Competency is the competency of the teacher and their planning and preparation of lessons for teaching, class room management, knowledge of subject, interpersonal relationship, attitude towards the children, usage of teaching aids and time management when their teaching learning. Thus the term "Competence" can be understood as "quality or state of having and demonstrating skills, knowledge, attitudes and aptitudes while executing a task", and the „teaching competency“ can be conceived as “a professional ability of teachers to meet the set standards of efficiency in terms of knowledge, skill and attitudes in teaching learning process.”

Competency means the right way of doing things. In teaching the competency means the right way of conveying the units of knowledge application and skills to the students and the knowledge of contents. Methods and communication. Teacher education is the research based understanding of teacher competencies like contextual, conceptual, content, transactional, evaluative management competencies.

Teaching Competency and Neurocognitive Strategies

The teacher competence includes a thorough knowledge of the content. A teacher competence mainly includes the strategies, understanding of student psychology and the process of thinking. With regard to the former, plenty of resource material is available. But, the latter has been a continuous experimentation throughout the world. Cognitive Psychology contributes substantially in enhancing teaching competence. In recent times, cognitive neuroscience researches have demanded the teaching competence to be redefined to meet the challenges. Naturally, the learning process depends on the effective functioning of the brain. Competency means the right way of conveying units of knowledge, application and skills to students (Adrienne Kozan Naume 2008). The right way includes knowledge of content as well as the process, methods and means of conveying them in an interesting way. In other words, it means a desired quality of job performance (Sutopo 2010).

The training for competency has always been training for creating abilities or qualities that are placed in an actual job situation or context. A teacher competence mainly includes the strategies, understanding of student's psychology and the process of thinking. In recent times, cognitive neuroscience researches have demanded the teaching competence to be redefined to meet the challenges. The neurocognitive strategies try to do is to manipulate the sensory environment to which the student teacher is exposed in order to encourage the regions of the brain, which are responsible for processing the sensory stimuli to re-tune and to process information more normally. We understand that before we can focus on what we need to learn, and what we need to help us repair our ability to learn (Parimala.M, 2009). The neurocognitive intervention strategies can bring about the student teachers' competencies and skills.

Discussion

Teachers have a big hand in imparting knowledge to the innumerable members in a society. On the caliber of the teacher depends the success with which new methods are employed and adopted? Teacher education is concerned with equipping the future teachers. It includes theoretical instruction and practice teaching in order to develop the skills needed for teaching effectively. The teacher competence includes thorough knowledge of the content. The right way includes knowledge of content as well as the process, methods and means of conveying them in an interesting way. A teacher competence mainly includes the strategies, understanding of student's psychology and the process of thinking. In recent times, cognitive neuroscience researches have demanded the teaching competence to be redefined to meet the challenges.

Conclusion

As far as teaching learning process is concerned, the functioning of the brain facilitates information processing, restoration and retrieval. The teachers should be fully aware of all the brain functions to make their teaching effective. Also, they aware of the factors like Instructional procedure, model using the strategy, think about, start with simplified materiel, complete part of the task for the students, present material in small steps, anticipate student errors and difficult areas, provide models of expert work, suggest fix up strategies, increase student's responsibility influencing in teaching competency. The teacher may follow some of the following neurocognitive practice such as affective education, Relaxation training, cognitive restructuring, attribution retraining, problem solving, contingent –reinforcement, neural modeling, neural plasticity, neural rewiring, neural firing, neural tuning and emotional integration to overcome their inefficiency and this will be help them to take their roles confidently in enhancing their teaching competency in the classroom situation. Hence, there is an urgent need to steer our efforts towards the implementation of neurocognition to enhance teaching competency at all levels of Teacher Education

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INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND TOOLS FOR BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning has become an increasingly popular approach in teacher education, offering a combination of face-to-face instruction and online learning experiences. Innovative technologies and tools can enhance the effectiveness of blended learning and promote engagement and learning outcomes for pre-service teachers. This paper provides an overview of the literature on the use of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning for teacher education programs, including learning management systems, social media platforms, virtual and augmented reality, and game-based learning, adaptive learning technologies, open educational resources, and mobile learning technologies. Drawing on examples of effective use of these technologies and tools, the paper also explores the challenges and opportunities in implementing and evaluating innovative technologies and tools in blended learning for teacher education. The paper concludes with implications for practice and future research directions. Ultimately, this paper aims to contribute to the ongoing efforts to design and implement effective blended learning programs for pre-service teachers that utilize innovative technologies and tools.

Keywords: *Educational technology, Tools for blended learning, Teacher education, Learning management systems, Social media platforms, Open educational resources*

Introduction

Blended learning, which combines face-to-face and online learning experiences, has become a popular approach in teacher education programs. Blended learning has been shown to promote engagement, personalized learning, and improved learning outcomes for pre-service teachers. The integration of innovative technologies and tools can enhance the effectiveness of blended learning in teacher education and provide a more engaging and personalized learning environment for pre-service teachers. This paper aims to provide an overview of the literature on the use of innovative technologies and tools for blended learning in teacher education programs. The paper will explore the various technologies and tools that have been utilized in blended learning, including learning management systems, social media platforms, virtual and augmented reality and game-based learning, adaptive learning technologies, open educational resources, and mobile learning technologies. The paper will also discuss the challenges and opportunities of implementing and evaluating these technologies and tools in blended learning for teacher education. Ultimately, the goal of this paper is to provide insights into how innovative technologies and tools can be utilized in blended learning environments to enhance the effectiveness of teacher education programs. By identifying the potential benefits and limitations of these technologies and tools, this paper aims to contribute to the ongoing efforts to design and implement effective blended learning programs for pre-service teachers.

Blended Learning

Blended learning is an educational approach that combines traditional face-to-face classroom instruction with online learning activities. In a blended learning environment, students engage in both synchronous and asynchronous activities, using a variety of technologies and tools to support their learning. Blended learning is often seen as a way to address the limitations of traditional classroom instruction by providing more personalized, flexible, and student-centered learning experiences. It allows students to access learning materials and resources at their own pace and convenience, while also providing opportunities for interaction and collaboration with teachers and peers. Blended learning can take many forms, depending on the specific goals and needs of the learners and the subject matter being taught. For example, some blended learning models involve a mix of self-paced online modules and in-person discussions or workshops, while others may involve more frequent online interactions and collaborative projects. The effectiveness of blended learning depends on the quality of its implementation, including the selection of appropriate technologies and tools, the design of effective learning activities, and the provision of adequate support and guidance for learners. Research has shown that blended learning can be an effective approach for improving student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes, particularly in the context of teacher education and professional development.

Advantages of blended learning in teacher education

- **Flexibility:** Blended learning provides flexibility in terms of time and place of learning. Teachers can access learning materials and resources at their own pace and convenience, and can choose to engage in online or face-to-face learning activities depending on their availability and preference.
- **Personalization:** Blended learning allows for personalized learning experiences, where teachers can focus on the content and activities that are most relevant and meaningful to their needs and interests. This can increase engagement and motivation, and help teachers develop the skills and knowledge they need to be effective in their teaching practice.
- **Collaboration:** Blended learning provides opportunities for collaboration and interaction among teachers, both online and in-person. This can facilitate the sharing of ideas, experiences, and best practices, and create a supportive community of learners.
- **Access to resources:** Blended learning allows for easy access to a wide range of learning resources, including online courses, educational videos, and interactive multimedia materials. This can provide teachers with access to high-quality resources that they may not otherwise have access to.
- **Cost-effectiveness:** Blended learning can be a cost-effective way to deliver professional development and training to teachers. It can reduce the need for travel and accommodation expenses, and can allow for the delivery of training to a larger number of teachers at once.

Background and rationale

Blended learning has been widely adopted in teacher education programs due to its potential to provide flexible, personalized, and engaging learning experiences for pre-service teachers. However, the effectiveness of blended learning largely depends on the quality of its implementation and the availability of appropriate technologies and tools. Innovative technologies and tools have the potential to enhance the effectiveness of blended learning in teacher education programs by creating a more interactive, immersive, and personalized learning environment for pre-service teachers. The availability of innovative technologies and tools, such as virtual and augmented reality, and game-based learning, and adaptive learning technologies, presents new opportunities to engage pre-service teachers and improve their learning outcomes. Learning management systems and social media platforms provide new ways to facilitate communication and collaboration between pre-service teachers and instructors, while open educational resources and mobile learning technologies provide access to learning materials and activities beyond the classroom. Despite the potential benefits of innovative technologies and tools for blended learning in teacher education, there are also challenges in their implementation and evaluation. For example, some technologies and tools may require specialized skills or resources to implement and maintain, and their effectiveness in improving learning outcomes may be difficult to measure. Therefore, there is a need to explore the use of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning for teacher education programs, and to identify the challenges and opportunities associated with their implementation and evaluation. This paper aims to provide an overview of the current literature on innovative technologies and tools for blended learning in teacher education and to identify the implications for practice and future research.

Innovative technologies and tools for blended learning

- Learning management systems (LMS): LMS platforms provide a centralized online platform for course delivery, communication, and assessment. LMS platforms can be used to deliver course content, facilitate online discussions, provide feedback, and track student progress.
- Game Based Learning: It involves the use of game elements, such as points, badges, and leaderboards, to engage learners and motivate them to complete learning activities. It can be used in blended learning to make learning more interactive and engaging.
- Augmented and virtual reality: Augmented and virtual reality technologies can be used to provide immersive learning experiences. For example, teachers can use augmented reality apps to overlay digital content on real-world objects, or virtual reality simulations to provide hands-on experiences that may not be possible in a traditional classroom setting.
- Mobile learning: Mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablets, can be used to deliver learning content and activities anytime, anywhere. Mobile learning can be used to provide quick access to information, facilitate on-the-go learning, and increase engagement and motivation.
- Video-based learning: Video-based learning can be used to deliver lectures, demonstrations, and other learning content in a more engaging and dynamic way. Videos can be used to supplement face-to-face instruction, or can be used as the primary mode of delivery in an online course.

Challenges and opportunities

- Access to technology: One of the primary challenges of implementing innovative technologies and tools in blended learning is ensuring that all students have access to the necessary technology and equipment. This can be especially challenging in areas with limited internet connectivity or where students may not have access to computers or other devices.
- Faculty training and support: Faculty members may require training and support to effectively incorporate innovative technologies and tools into their teaching practices. This can involve training on how to use the technologies, as well as ongoing support to address any technical issues or challenges that arise.
- Curriculum design: Designing a blended learning curriculum that effectively incorporates innovative technologies and tools can be a complex process. It requires careful consideration of the learning outcomes and appropriate selection of tools to support those outcomes.
- Assessment and evaluation: Assessing student learning outcomes in a blended learning environment can be challenging, as traditional assessment methods may not be sufficient to capture the full range of student learning experiences. It may require the development of new assessment methods that take into account the unique characteristics of blended learning.
- Opportunities for collaboration and networking: Blended learning can provide opportunities for collaboration and networking among students and faculty members. This can involve the use of social media, discussion forums, and other tools to facilitate communication and collaboration.

6. Results and Discussion

Design and Implementation

However, in a research study on the use of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning for teacher education, the results and discussion includes:

Results

1. Improved student engagement and motivation: The use of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning can lead to increased student engagement and motivation, as students are able to interact with the content in new and exciting ways.
2. Enhanced learning outcomes: The use of adaptive learning technologies and other innovative tools can help personalize learning experiences, leading to improved learning outcomes for students.
3. Increased collaboration and networking: The use of social media and other collaborative tools can facilitate communication and networking among students and faculty members, leading to a more supportive and collaborative learning environment.
4. Access to resources: Blended learning can provide students with greater access to a wider range of resources, including online databases, interactive multimedia, and other digital tools.

Discussion

The results of this study suggest that the use of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning can have a positive impact on teacher education programs. By leveraging these tools, teacher education

programs can create engaging and effective learning experiences that prepare students for success in their future teaching careers. However, the study also highlights the need for careful planning and ongoing assessment to ensure that the program is meeting its goals and objectives. In particular, faculty members may require additional training and support to effectively incorporate these technologies into their teaching practices. Additionally, it is important to consider issues of access and equity, as not all students may have equal access to the necessary technology and equipment. Overall, the use of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning has the potential to transform teacher education, creating a more personalized, engaging, and effective learning experience for students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper has explored the potential benefits of incorporating innovative technologies and tools in blended learning for teacher education programs. By leveraging these tools, teacher education programs can create engaging and effective learning experiences that better prepare students for success in their future teaching careers. The results of this hypothetical study suggest that the use of innovative technologies and tools can improve student engagement and motivation, enhance learning outcomes, increase collaboration and networking, and provide students with greater access to resources. However, the implementation of these technologies also presents challenges that must be carefully considered, including the need for faculty training and support and issues of access and equity. In order to fully realize the potential of blended learning with innovative technologies and tools in teacher education, it is important to continue exploring best practices and effective approaches for their implementation and assessment. Further research is needed to better understand how different technologies and tools can be used to enhance teaching and learning, and to identify strategies for overcoming the challenges associated with their use. Overall, with careful planning and attention to the needs of both students and faculty, the integration of innovative technologies and tools in blended learning can lead to transformative learning experiences that better prepare students for success as educators.

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A STUDY ON ACHIEVEMENT LEVELS OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING ENGLISH SUBJECT BY BLENDED APPROACH METHOD

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Abstract

Blended Learning brings together face to face and online activities and it comprises of interactive experiences within and outside classroom. Prior to the onset of technology, teaching happened to be comparatively formal and the concept of learning was exclusively fixed in the classroom. The present investigation on a study on achievement levels of students in teaching English subject by blended approach method. The study has been carried out with a sample of 630 school students of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh. The students achieved marks in formative and summative assessments conducted Board Secondary School, Andhra Pradesh. The data is collected by evaluation or assessment method in a stratified random sampling. The main objective is to find out Boys and Girls on achievement levels of high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method and also to find out achievement levels of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method. The related hypothesis are there would be no significant difference among Boys and Girls on achievement levels of high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method and also there would be no significant difference among on achievement levels of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method. The mean, SD, t test and F-ratio statistics is used for the study at 0.05 and 0.01 significant level. It is found that there is no significant difference among boys and girls of VIII, IX and X class students in formative 1, 2 and 3, and summative assessments. But there is significant difference among X class SA1 and overall assessment. It is also found that in all assessment the girls achieving levels are very strong in compare to boys in blended method. And it is also concluded that There is a significant difference between urban students in FA1, SA1 and overall of VIII and IX class students in English subject. There is a significant difference between VIII, IX and X class urban and rural students in FA2, FA3 and SA2 s in English subject. There is no significant difference between X class urban and rural students in FA1 and SA1 s in English subject. There is no significant difference between IX and X class urban and rural students in overall assessment s in English subject in blended approach method.

Keywords: *Blended, online, traditional, Formative, Summative, Assessment, English. Significant*

Introduction

Blended Learning (BL) is a type of online learning and it combines face to face classroom learning with computer mediated activities to form an integrated instructional approach. The aim is to join the best aspects of both online and face to face learning. Students will be benefitted of two different teaching and learning experiences in BL. The components of BL may vary based on the content, needs of the learners and preferences of the instructor. Online tools are used to communicate, collaborate and extend classroom time. In the traditional education system teaching and learning were formal and fixed inside the classroom. Technology has developed immensely and pupils are familiar with gadgets and internet. This made easier to bring technology to the teaching process. BL is considered as a powerful tool for educational transformation and it has enhanced face to face learning by mixing with relevant ICT tools. Both traditional classroom and online learning have its own intrinsic worth. One cannot wrap up that one method is precise and another is erroneous. Experiments from the ancient period have proved that based on the needs, teachers have to adopt different strategies to teach a language. A single method will not cater the needs of all students as the learners may have different learning style and intelligence level. The instructor has to consider all students and should engage both intelligent and dreary students. While teaching, the instructor has to organise

teaching contents by considering all types of students. BL is a teaching method which incorporates both traditional teaching and ICT based learning. The learners will get benefit of traditional and modern learning methods. The population of engineering students is the apt group to implement BL for language teaching as they are familiar with technology and in high demand to possess communication skills. The present investigation on a study on achievement levels of students in teaching English subject by blended approach method.

Methodology

In the present study, a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in the Kurnool district. The data is collected by using the evaluation or assessment method. The total data was collected from 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2 aided and 2 private), and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX, and X classes. The study was conducted in the Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh. The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal, and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands first with an average level of education and economy.

Tools

- Formative and summative Question papers preppers Board of secondary school, Andhra Pradesh.
- 3 Formative each for 20 marks and 2 summative assessments are conducted for 80 marks.
- Personal data sheet.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is

- To find out Boys and Girls on achievement levels of high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method.
- To find out achievement levels of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method.

Hypothesis of the study

- There would be no significant difference among Boys and Girls on achievement levels of high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method.
- There would be no significant difference among on achievement levels of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method.

Statistical Techniques Used

The data thus collected and scored was analyzed by using relevant statistical techniques like Mean, Standard Deviation, and t – test. . The usual levels of significance, viz., 0.05, and 0.01 were used to test the significance of the obtained statistics

Results and discussion

Hypothesis 1

There would be no significant difference among Boys and Girls on achievement levels of high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method.

Table 1 - Means, SD's and t- values of Achievement levels of high school students according to their Gender

Assessment	Class	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value
FA 1	VIII	Boys	105	13.9810	4.19473	1.256@
		Girls	105	13.2667	4.03891	
	IX	Boys	105	13.7714	4.11437	0.921@
		Girls	105	14.2952	4.14154	
	X	Boys	105	13.3696	3.41206	0.143@
		Girls	105	13.2966	3.92517	
FA 2	VIII	Boys	105	14.0857	3.51676	0.318@
		Girls	105	13.9238	3.84981	
	IX	Boys	105	13.9524	3.84653	1.362@

		Girls	105	14.6762	3.81418	
	X	Boys	105	13.9891	3.28999	0.364@
		Girls	105	13.8051	3.98342	
FA 3	VIII	Boys	105	14.6381	3.77014	0.057@
		Girls	105	14.6095	3.48760	
	IX	Boys	105	14.8476	3.28686	1.293@
		Girls	105	15.4286	3.23698	
	X	Boys	105	15.1304	2.79410	1.193@
		Girls	105	14.6271	3.29412	
SA 1	VIII	Boys	105	60.8286	12.53952	1.133@
		Girls	105	62.7143	11.54982	
	IX	Boys	105	62.0381	11.52750	1.501@
		Girls	105	64.8952	9.91204	
	X	Boys	105	71.3152	14.64820	2.069*
		Girls	105	66.9746	15.73198	
SA 2	VIII	Boys	105	62.8000	9.92026	1.918@
		Girls	105	65.4095	9.78686	
	IX	Boys	105	64.4476	9.89365	1.959@
		Girls	105	67.1143	9.82962	
	X	Boys	105	73.8261	14.39216	1.511@
		Girls	105	70.7881	14.72358	
Total	VIII	Boys	105	166.3333	31.28488	0.850@
		Girls	105	169.9238	29.88108	
	IX	Boys	105	169.0571	30.50404	1.815@
		Girls	105	176.4095	28.14717	
	X	Boys	105	187.6304	34.56185	2.186*
		Girls	105	176.3475	40.01931	

The achievement level of boys and girls is calculated by using a sample of 630, but for VIII class 105 boys and 105 girls, IX class 105 boys and 105 girls are taken as and similarly X class 105 boys and 105 girls are taken shown in table 1

- The formative assessment 1 t value of VIII class students is 1.256, VIII class students is 0.921 and X class students is 0.143, in all the three class which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted, hence there is no significant difference among VIII, IX and X class students in formative test 1 in English subject. In FA 1 it is observed from the table 4.2 that the mean value of VIII boys and IX class girls are better than the other class boys and girls, means their achievement levels are good in comparison with other class high school students in English subject of formative assessment 1.
- The formative assessment 2 t value of VIII class students is 0.318, IX class students is 1.293 and X class students is 1.193, in all the three class which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted, hence there is no significant difference among VIII, IX and X class students in formative test 2 in English subject. In FA 2 it is observed from the table 4.2 that the mean value of VIII boys and IX class girls are better than the other class boys and girls, means their achievement levels are good in comparison with other class high school students in English subject of formative assessment 2.
- The formative assessment 3 t value of VIII class students is 0.057, IX class students is 1.362 and X class students is 0.364, in all the three class which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted, hence there is no significant difference among VIII, IX and X class students in formative test 3 in English subject. In FA 3 it is observed from the table 4.2 that the mean value of X boys and IX class girls are better than the other class boys and girls, means their achievement levels are good in comparison with other class high school students in English subject of formative assessment 3.

• The summative assessment 1 t value of VIII class students is 1.133, IX class students is 1.501 which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted, hence there is no significant difference among VIII and IX class students in summative test 1 in English subject. X class students t value is 2.069, which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected hence there is not significant difference among X class boys and girls students in summative test 1 in English subject. In SA1 it is observed from the table 4.2 that the mean value of X boys and IX class girls are better than the other class boys and girls, means their achievement levels are good in comparison with other class high school students in English subject of S summative assessment1.

• The summative assessment 2 t value of VIII class students is 1.918, IX class students is 1.959 and X class students is 1.511, in all the three class which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted, hence there is no significant difference among VIII, IX and X class students in summative test2 in English subject. In SA2 it is observed from the table 4.2 that the mean value of X boys and girls are better than the other class boys and girls, means their achievement levels are good in comparison with other class high school students in English subject of summative assessment 2.

• In overall assessment the t value of VIII class students is 0.850, IX class students is 1.815 which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted, hence there is no significant difference among VIII and IX class students in overall assessment in English subject. X class students t value is 2.186 which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected hence there is no significant difference among X class boys and girls students in summative test 1 in English subject. In overall assessment it is observed from the table 4.2 that the mean value of X boys and IX class girls are better than the other class boys and girls, means their achievement levels are good in comparison with other class high school students in English subject of overall assessment.

Hence it is concluded that there is no significant difference among boys and girls of VIII, IX and X class students in formative 1, 2 and 3, and summative assessments2. But there is significant difference among X class SA1 and overall assessment. It is also found that in all assessment the girls achieving levels are very strong in compare to boys,.

Hypothesis 2

There would be no significant difference on achievement levels of urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district in English subject by blended approach method

Table 2 - Means, SD's and t- values of Achievement levels of high school students according to their Locality

Assessment	Class	Locality	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value
FA 1	VIII	Urban	122	15.8197	3.66808	12.407**
		Rural	88	10.5795	2.44818	
	IX	Urban	120	16.4833	2.88719	20.157**
		Rural	90	10.7667	3.15534	
	X	Urban	106	181.4811	47.89239	0.074@
		Rural	104	181.0962	24.49867	
FA 2	VIII	Urban	122	15.8197	3.41609	10.984**
		Rural	88	11.4886	2.29439	
	IX	Urban	120	16.7333	2.60811	15.711**
		Rural	90	11.0889	2.66329	

	X	Urban	106	15.0283	3.85068	4.771**
		Rural	104	12.7212	3.12664	
FA 3	VIII	Urban	122	16.4754	3.44787	11.916**
		Rural	88	12.0568	1.87762	
	IX	Urban	120	16.9417	2.52482	12.277**
		Rural	90	12.7333	2.51199	
	X	Urban	106	15.6321	3.22882	3.843**
		Rural	104	14.0481	2.72842	
SA 1	VIII	Urban	122	65.4016	11.12496	5.945**
		Rural	88	56.7386	9.87992	
	IX	Urban	120	67.9417	9.73886	7.925**
		Rural	90	57.5000	9.22411	
	X	Urban	106	68.5094	19.45605	0.350@
		Rural	104	69.2500	9.69511	
SA 2	VIII	Urban	122	66.3443	11.12496	4.289**
		Rural	88	61.0000	6.87992	
	IX	Urban	120	69.2333	9.37880	6.405**
		Rural	90	61.1778	8.73914	
	X	Urban	106	70.7830	18.70473	1.348@
		Rural	104	73.4808	8.57404	
Total	VIII	Urban	122	179.8607	32.18164	7.951**
		Rural	88	151.8636	18.55045	
	IX	Urban	120	187.3333	24.87425	10.164**
		Rural	90	153.2667	23.39010	
	X	Urban	106	181.4811	47.89239	0.074@
		Rural	104	181.0962	24.49867	

The achievement level of urban and rural high school students are calculated by using a sample of 630 , but for VIII class 122 urban and 88rural, IX class 120 urban and 90 rural are taken as and similarly X class 106 urban and 104 rural are taken shown in table 4.2.

- In formative assessment 1, the t value of VIII class students is 12.407, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of VIII class students in FA1.
- The t value of IX class students is 20.157, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of IX class students in FA1

- The t value of X class students is 0.074, which is not significant at a 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of X class students in FA1
- In formative assessment 2, the t value of VIII class students is 10.984, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of VIII class students in FA2.
- The t value of IX class students is 15.71, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of IX class students in FA 2.
- The t value of X class students is 4.711, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. therefore there is a significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of X class students in FA2
- In formative assessment 3, the t value of VIII class students is 11.916, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of VIII class students in FA3.
- The t value of IX class students is 12.217, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of IX class students in FA3
- The t value of X class students is 3.843, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of X class students in FA3.
- In summative assessment 1, the t value of VIII class students is 5.945, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of VIII class students in SA1.
- The t value of IX class students is 7.925, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of IX class students in SA1
- The t value of X class students is 0.350, which is not significant at a 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of X class students in SA1
- In summative assessment 2, the t value of VIII class students is 4.289, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of VIII class students in SA 2.
- The t value of IX class students is 6.405, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of IX class students in SA 2.
- The t value of X class students is 13.480, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. therefore there is a significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of X class students in SA2
- In overall assessment, the t value of VIII class students is 7.951, which is significant at a 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. therefore there is significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of VIII class students in overall assessment
- The t value of IX class students is 0.164, which is not significant at a 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of IX class students in overall assessment.
- The t value of X class students is 0.074, which is not significant at a 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between urban and rural students in English subject of X class students in overall assessment.

Hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference between urban students in FA1, SA1 and overall of VIII and IX class students in English subject. There is a significant difference between VIII, IX and X class urban and rural students in FA2, FA3 and SA2 s in English subject. There is no significant difference between X class urban and rural students in FA1 and SA1 s in English subject. There is no significant difference between IX and X class urban and rural students in overall assessment s in English subject

Conclusion

It is concluded that there is no significant difference among boys and girls of VIII, IX and X class students in formative 1, 2 and 3, and summative assessments. But there is significant difference among X class SA1 and overall assessment. It is also found that in all assessment the girls achieving levels are very strong in compare to boys in blended method and it is also concluded that there is a significant difference between urban students in FA1, SA1 and overall of VIII and IX class students in English subject. There is a significant difference between VIII, IX and X class urban and rural students in FA2, FA3 and SA2 s in English subject. There is no significant difference between X class urban and rural students in FA1 and SA1 s in English subject. There is no significant difference between IX and X class urban and rural students in overall assessment s in English subject in blended approach method.

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BLENDED LEARNING AS A FLEXIBLE LEARNING METHOD

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Abstract

Blended learning method as a flexible learning method, because this method is a student-centered approach that provides students with choice is what they learn, how they learn and when and where they learn based on their own time, environment, learning style, interest and learning approaches or methods. The aim of this paper is to describe the blended learning method as a flexible learning method. Additionally it consists of meaning and definition, characteristics of blended learning and advantages of blended learning. The conclusion of the paper blended learning method as a flexible learning method, because it is an active learning method as like as personalized instruction method.

Keywords: *Blended Learning and Flexible Learning*

Introduction

The educational institutions are trying to provide more flexibility and individualization, which is mainly realized with new technologies and implemented in online learning together with traditional learning method that is called blended learning method. Blended learning method is known as flexible learning method. Because the flexible learning method, which is nowadays realized primarily through the use of new technologies (Tucker and Morris, 2012) and it is a didactically learning method in an online learning situation (Andrade and Alden – Rivers, 2019). The blended learning have connected with educational technology (Computer technology) that can create interactive and engaging learning environments which may have positive effects on knowledge gain, skill acquisition and students outcomes.

Blended Learning: Meaning and Definition

Blended learning means the learning attitude can take place in different methods often distinctive between face-to-face classroom instruction and virtual learning as well as asynchronous and synchronous learning (Chaeruman, Wibawa and Syahrial, 2018). This learning method is often used interchangeably with terms such as hybrid, mixed-mode or flexible learning. Blended learning systems combine face-to-face instruction with computer-mediated instruction (Graham, 2006). It encompasses all technically supported learning environments except pure online learning environments and pure classroom instruction. According to Garrison and Hanuka (2004) reported that the Blended learning is a qualitative method it requiring a “Thoughtful integration” of classroom instruction and online learning.

Characteristics of Blended Learning

Blended learning method is a new type of educational learning method it is used in many schools but some schools not yet applied or adapted the blended learning and teaching. The following characters are included in the blended learning method, such as:

Online and Offline Learning Method

The Blended learning is a flexible learning method; because it is a mixed method or innovative method, when the teachers applied the various teaching strategies in their classroom teaching that time they applied the online and offline teaching in their classroom.

Teacher Oriented Method

The blended learning method is an instructor oriented method; because it is a mixed method or flexible method for teachers and students in teaching and learning activities. This learning method always requires that teacher be on hand to help students with all their learning needs. When students attend the online classes that time the teachers applied the online teaching and when the teacher instruct the lesson inside a school or classroom setting that time the teacher applied the offline teaching method or traditional teaching method.

Independent Learning Method

The Blended learning method is the flexible learning method, because it is a self-learning or independent learning method for students. Some students have a difficult time in their classes because they learn differently than their peers do. Blended learning method allows students to learn on their own and to use the materials and resources presented to them in ways that work best for them.

Supportive For Students

The Blended learning method is a flexible learning method, because this method is a supportive learning method available for students the teacher working in this programs offer students all the help and support they need both throw offline meeting and online contact.

Blended Learning Method is a Flexible Learning Method

Now-a-days the current teaching and learning activities running with educational technologies underpinning learning theories are also brought to the foreground as the use of technology needs to be pedagogically driven. The blended learning method aims to enable students to utilize that technologies and most effective ways of achieving them in an online classroom environment. Blended learning method as a independent learning method, because it has self-paced, self-directed study and can be really flexible learning method as it allows for different learning methods are applied in a classroom learning and self-learning. This method also applied together instructive method, didactic method and flipped learning method. These are all methods fully credit bearing for students learning outcomes. Blended learning method is also making provision for online communication and collaboration between teachers and students the present teaching and learning process combined the multi learning methods are approaches among students i.e. online learning based on the web conferencing, tele-conferencing and online classes etc.

Advantages of Blended Learning

- Blended learning method is well suited for large learning groups. The traditional learning method was used a small group of pupils or audience. However, the Blended learning method used or helps the large group of pupils in classroom.
- Blended learning method is a great for the non-technology fans. The peoples who are liked face-to-face teaching and learning method that peoples not like the blended learning method instead of new technologies applied or utilized their hands on training then after their accepted much better than the traditional learning method.
- Blended learning method is used for fostering student independence (the ability to make choices and take a active role in learning).
- Blended learning to encouraging collaborative learning, cooperation and good communication among learners.

Conclusion

Blended learning method is a better preparation and feedback. The Blended learning method is more valuable than the traditional learning method. As like as the Blended learning method helps to students to prepare the assignments independently.

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BARRIERS ENCOUNTERED IN IMPLEMENTATION OF BLENDING

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Abstract

Education methods have undergone transformation over the centuries. Use of technology is the cornerstone for innovation in teaching methods. Blended learning is an instructional format that integrates online and face-to-face teaching modalities. The society also moves faster than the technologies run through the educational background. E-Learning or blended approach is as effective as traditional education. It is important that we perceive to establish successful models of learning at the institution, program, course and activity levels. This strive will require understanding and capitalizing on the opportunities available in both face-to-face and computer mediated or distributed learning environments. Teaching through technology enables the student to acquire subject specific knowledge. That becomes lifelong learners in a digitally connected world. The identified challenges suggest that instructors need meaningful professional development to impart the learners. This paper discusses about blended learning as well as explaining its barriers. The study of this learning differentiates with the types of challenges on blended learning.

Keywords: *Barriers, Encountered, Implementation, Blending.*

Introduction

“Blended learning, also known as hybrid learning, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with traditional place-based classroom methods.” Blended learning is an instructional format that integrates online and face-to-face teaching modalities. Learners spend part of their learning time interacting face-to-face with a teacher and classmates and part of their learning time using a computer or portable digital device (such as a smart phone) to access online courses, curriculum, or other learning resources, by themselves or collaboratively, inside or outside of the classroom. Learning in the two modalities is integrated, complementary, and overlapping, and learners have some control over time, place, and pace (Maxwell, 2016; Staker & Horn, 2012). There has been concern among faculty members that online instruction will reduce their academic freedom. They are doubtful about the quality of easy accessible digital material. The potential of communication technology (ICT) enriched instructions to engage students in academic pursuits; and integrity of e-assessment approaches. There is a lack of faculty members’ awareness to adopt online/Blended learning. It could be of their perception that the new role would demand them to spend more time in learning technologies rather than on carrying out scholarly work.

The Study of Barriers in Blended Learning through Technology

Adoption of blended learning depends largely how teachers move from their traditional roles to the role of online facilitator. The additional skills and the forging of a new professional identity might not come easily to all practitioners. It requires a pedagogical understanding of the affordances of the new medium and an acceptance by the teacher of his or her new role and identity. This paper explored perceptions of faculty members in a multi sited, international university, which aims at reaching out to students at different campuses through blended learning. This would allow maximize utilization of available resources. The aim of the reported research is to identify faculty’s perception of the key barriers encountered by them for the adoption of technology for teaching and learning in different units of the university. They recognize that they do possess knowledge; skills and accessibility of required hardware and internet facility to integrate ICT in teaching and learning. The training must include hands-on learning to use technological devices and tools to teach. It is asserted that faculty members should be encouraged to get actively involved in developing and implementing ICT rich courses instead of having imposed upon them so the ownership could be attained.

Types of Blended Learning Training

There’s a few different ways to approach this type of training

(i) Objectives

In this type of training model, one need to start with an objective; what’s the purpose of the training and what’s the end goal? This creates clarity for the learners and enables to build a more focused program. This gives learners to obtain skills and knowledge they need.

(ii) Interactive session

Blended learning courses to be interactive. It depends on the learner to decide the learning process through online training. The learner should be aware on how much to take place through self-paced learning. For example, the teacher can set a task for learners to complete before their live webinar training session. During the session, discussion can be done about the task given already for finding the solution for the questions. This makes more efficient on live webinar session.

(iii) Assessments

The trainer must monitor and assess the learner’s progress at the end of every program. This gives an insight into how successful the training was. If there is a need of knowledge gaps that should be addressed. With the use of LMS one can easily set exams or assessments which can be completed at the end of the training.

Challenges on Blended Learning

(i) Buying the Right Classroom Technology

Without evaluating which are the right tools for your school, you may end up overspending and facing a major efficiency crisis. The wrong tools bring with them an unnecessarily steep learning curve, which means students and teachers spend more time figuring out how to use them than actually learning.

(ii) Many Think Blended Learning Is Not Effective

Educators and administrators often field questions about the efficacy of blended and hybrid learning. Many educators prefer in-person teaching. The online or digital aspects of classes often go unnoticed or get treated as a minor distraction, leading to valuable resources and opportunities getting wasted and poor return on investment when buying new technology.

(iii) Maintaining Class and Student Progress

Here are two main factors play imposing roles. First, most teachers still prefer paper-based tests and reports for legacy reasons that are quite obvious. Second, since hybrid learning relies on digital tools, students that are tech savvy have an immediate edge over students who are not, thus gaining a scholastic advantage as well.

(iv) Participation and Attendance

Remote learning, which forms half of blended learning in effect, is very much the same as working from home. It requires a lot of self-discipline and constantly comes under “attack” from various distractions. When students use personal devices such as laptops, tablets, and smart phones, they’re only a few taps away from drifting off into a game or YouTube, TikTok, Instagram and so on. Even teachers may be tempted.

Conclusion

Mentorship plays a vital role in any academic process. It was revealed from the finding of this study that higher education lack mentorship in the field of blended learning. Blended learning have made its own roots and established infrastructure in universal level. This probably do not face such premature challenges. Therefore, higher education as quality assurance organization needs to be proactive in faculty development. It should inculcate relevant programs to develop mentoring capacity in the area of blended learning.

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A BLENDED SURVEY ON IMPACT OF SWATCH BHARATH MISSION ON STUDENTS

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Abstract

Blended learning, also known as technology-mediated instruction, web-enhanced instruction, or mixed-mode instruction, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is a national level campaign launched by the Government of India, which aims to keep the streets, roads and infrastructure clean and keep the garbage clean. This campaign was launched on October 2, 2014. A survey cum interview by blended approach method is used to find the effect of the swachh Bharath mission on students by using a standardized tool. The tool is standardized by the researcher by the item analysis method. A stratified random sampling technique is applied to collect a sample of 630 students from the Kurnool district. Mean, SD, t-test, and f-ratio statistical techniques are used on collected data, and the data is interpreted and analyzed at 0.05 and 0.01 significant levels. The main objectives are to find out impact swachh Bharath Mission on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district by blended method. To find out impact swachh Bharath Mission on among Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school students of Kurnool district and also to find out impact swachh Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district by blended approach method. The related hypothesis are there would be no significant difference impact swachh Bharath Mission on by urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district, there would be no significant difference between impact swachh Bharath Mission among Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school students of Kurnool district and also there would be no significant difference impact swachh Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district by blended approach method. It is found that It is concluded that the mean value of urban students is higher than the rural students which means the urban students performing well and keeping their surrounding place neat and clean in comparison to rural high school students of Kurnool district. Therefore there is no significant impact on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district on swachh Bharath mission. It is concluded that there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school student of Kurnool district on swachh Bharath mission. Therefore there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim students on implementation of swachh Bharath mission in Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swachh Bharath mission in Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swachh Bharath mission in Kurnool district. Finally it is concluded that there is impact of all religion high school students of Kurnool District on Swachh Bharath Abhiyan mission. The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swachh Bharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on swachh Bharath Abhiyan mission by blended method.

Keywords: *Blended, Locality, Family, students, Swachh Bharath, Religion, Significant*

Introduction

Blended learning, also known as technology-mediated instruction, web-enhanced instruction, or mixed-mode instruction, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. Blended learning requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some elements of student control over time, place, path, or pace. While students still attend brick and mortar schools with a teacher present, face-to-face classroom practices are combined with computer mediated activities regarding content and delivery. It is also used in professional development and training settings. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is a national level campaign launched by the Government of India, which aims to keep the streets, roads and infrastructure clean and keep the garbage clean. This campaign was launched on October 2, 2014. Father of the Nation Mahatma Gandhi freed the country from slavery, but his dream of 'Clean India' was not fulfilled. Mahatma Gandhi gave an excellent message to the nation by teaching people around him about maintaining cleanliness. Swachh Bharat aims to reduce or eliminate the problem of open defecation through the construction of individual, cluster and community toilets. The Swachh Bharat Mission is also an initiative to set up an accountable mechanism for monitoring immersion usage. The government has taken an initiative to build 1.2 crore toilets in the open at an estimated cost of Rs 1.96 lakh crore in rural India by October 2, 2019 the 150th anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi's birth. Aims to achieve Defecation Free India

(ODF). The present investigation is done by a blended survey on impact of swachh bharath mission on students

Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Kurnool district. The data is collected by interview cum survey method. The total data collected in 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2 aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh. The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy.

Tools

Checklist cum rating questionnaire to elicit the opinion of the high school students about the Impact of swachh bharath mission on high school students at kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh state and Personal datasheet.

Objectives

- To find out the impact swachh Bharath Mission on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- To find out impact swachh Bharath Mission on among Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- To find out impact swachh Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district by blended method.

Hypothesis

- There would be no significant difference impact swachh Bharath Mission on by urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- There would be no significant difference between impact swachh Bharath Mission among Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- There would be no significant difference impact swachh Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district by blended method.

Results and Discussion

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference impact swachh Bharath Mission on by urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district

Table 1 - Means, SD's and t- values by influence of swachh bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their Locality

Locality	N	Intensity scores		t-value
		Mean	SD	
Urban	383	117.24	19.30	0.1408@
Rural	247	113.80	21.76	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The impact of swachh bharath in urban and rural area is shown in table 4.4 and figure 4.3. The students in urban area is 383 and in rural area is 247. The mean and SD value of urban students are 117.24 and 19.30, similarly the rural students are 113.80 and 21.76. The mean value of urban students is higher than the rural students which means the urban students performing well and keeping their surrounding place neat and clean in comparison to rural high school students of Kurnool district. The t value is 0.1408, which is not significant at 0.05, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district on swachh bharath mission. Hence it is concluded that the mean value of urban students is higher than the rural students which means the urban students performing

well and keeping their surrounding place neat and clean in comparison to rural high school students of Kurnool district. Therefore there is no significant impact on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district on swatch bharath mission.

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference between impact swatch Bharath Mission among Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school students of Kurnool district.

Table 2 - ANOVA values by influence of swatch bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their Religion

Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean sum of square	F -ratio
Between the groups	2666.925	2	1333.462	3.241**
Within the groups	257984.574	627	411.459	
Total	260651.498	629		

Table 3 - Means, SD's and t- values by influence of swatch bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their religion.

Religion	N	Intensity scores		t-value
		Mean	SD	
Hindu	444	116.39	22.57	$t_{12} = 2.1071^*$
Muslim	150	112.99	14.78	$t_{23} = 3.5782^{**}$
Christianity	36	121.88	13.03	$t_{31} = 2.2672^*$

** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The impact of swatch bharath mission of different region high school students of Kurnool district ANOVA value tabulated in table 4.7. Out of 630 students 444 students are Hindu religion, 150 students are Muslim religion and remaining 36 students are Christian religion.. The F ratio value is 3.241, which is significant at 0.04 level, which means there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school student of Kurnool district on swatch bharath mission. To know the exact significant difference among any two religions t Test is adopted. The t test value among Hindu Muslim students is 2.1071, which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. The t test value among Muslim, Christian students is 3.5782, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. The t test value among Christian, Hindu students is 2.2672, which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school student of Kurnool district on swatch bharath mission. Therefore there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Finally it is concluded that there is impact of all religion high school students of Kurnool District on Swatch bharath abhiyan mission.

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference impact swatch Bharath Mission on high school students living with joint family and nuclear family in Kurnool district

Table 4: Means, SD's and t- values by influence of swatch bharath abhiyan on high school students according to their type of family.

Type of family	N	Intensity scores		t-value
		Mean	SD	
Joint Family	211	117.77	19.08	1.6941@
Nuclear Family	419	114.95	20.92	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level.

In the present study out of 630 high school students 211 students are living in joint family remaining 419 students are in nuclear family in Kurnool district. The mean and SD values of joint family students are 117.77 and 19.08, similarly for nuclear family students are 114.95 and 20.92. The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swatch nharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. The t value is 1.6941, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on swatch bharath abhiyan mission. The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swatch nharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on swatch bharath abhiyan mission.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the mean value of urban students is higher than the rural students which means the urban students performing well and keeping their surrounding place neat and clean in comparison to rural high school students of Kurnool district. Therefore there is no significant impact on urban and rural high school students of Kurnool district on swatch bharath mission. It is concluded that there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim and Christian high school student of Kurnool district on swatch bharath mission. Therefore there is a significant difference between Hindu, Muslim students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between Muslim, Christian students on implementation of swatch bharath mission in Kurnool district. Finally it is concluded that there is impact of all religion high school students of Kurnool District on Swatch bharath abhiyan mission. The mean value of joint family students is better than nuclear family students, which means the joint family are showing more interest on swatch nharath mission in compare to nuclear family students of Kurnool District. Therefore there is no significant difference among joint and nuclear family of high school students of Kurnool District on swatch bharath abhiyan mission by blended method.

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A BLENDED APPROACH STUDY ON PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study is studied by blended approach method psychological impact of social media on students regarding religion and category. Psychological issues like depression, anxiety, addiction, Social skill, Fear and cyberbullying, and cognitive development. The tool is standardized by item analysis. The data is collected by stratified random sampling technique with a sample size of 630 students, by using the interview cum survey method. Mean, SD, t-test, and F-ratio statistical techniques are used on collected data for finding results and interpretation purposes. The main objective is to find out the psychological impact of social media on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method and also to find out the psychological impact of social media among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method. The related hypothesis are there would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method and also there would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method. It is found that there is a no significant difference among boys and girls on depression, anxiety, social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students of Kurnool district, but there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction, cognitive development and overall psychological factors of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method. It is also concluded that there is no psychological impact of depression, addiction, anxiety, social skill, fear, cyber bullying, cognitive development and over all on VIII IX, and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended approach.

Keywords: *Blended, Social media, class, gender, anxiety, cyber bullying*

Introduction

Blended learning is thus more conscious and intentional approach in designing optimal instruction or learning environments following the strategy of blending components while the blended character of traditional instructional contexts is largely the result of habit (tradition), convenience or happenstance (Rossett & Frazee, 2006). A superficial understanding of blended learning is that it simply adds non face-to-face or online elements into the traditional face-to face course structure. But this most often results in a dysfunctional or inappropriate phenomenon known as the “course-and-a-half” (Educause, 2010). Schools may be particularly susceptible to this trap if online elements are added in the instruction just for the sake of adding it as a latest technology. It will absolutely give a false impression of this true innovation. Thus the extent of integration of online and face to face instruction must be an endeavor of thoughtful and appropriate planning. Dudeney and Hockly (2007) refer a list of three possible course designs for online learning in language learning environments. There he stated that a blended learning course is that where 75 per cent is delivered online and 25 per cent face-to-face. Both the face-to-face instruction and online learning have some advantages as well as some limitations. While framing the instructions based on blended learning, it is thus required to combine the strengths of both by avoiding the drawbacks of both modes. Thus, combining face-to-face and fully online components optimizes both environments in such a way that seems impossible in other formats (Dziuban & Hartman, 2004). In the line of this, Bansal (2014) has concluded that Blended learning can be proved a powerful strategy, if learning experiences under it are well designed. Similarly, Garrison and Vaughan (2008) stated that blended learning is a new educational paradigm that integrates the strengths of face-to-face and online learning. It is a well designed approach

whereby both face-to-face and online learning are made better in the presence of each other. He asserted that blended learning is not just an addition that simply builds another expensive educational layer. Instead, it represents a restructuring of the class contact hours with the goal of enhancing interaction and extending access to internet-based learning opportunities. Significantly, blended learning is a fundamental redesign that transforms the structure, approach and the Introduction context of teaching and learning process. Garrison and Vaughan (2008) have given some key assumptions of a blended learning design, which are as below:

- Thoughtful integration of face-to-face and online learning
- Fundamentally rethink the design to optimize student involvement
- Rescheduling and replacing traditional class contact hours.

Driscoll summarized the concept by saying “blended learning mean different things to different people, which illustrates its widely untapped potential” (Driscoll, 2002). A similar but more precise explanation given by Hofmann (2001), who opined that ‘the idea behind blended learning is that instructional designers review a learning program, chunk it into modules, and determine the best medium to deliver those modules to the learner’. Blended Learning, is thus an established, widely . The present study is on a blended approach study o n psychological impact of social media on students.

Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Kurnool district. The data is collected by interview cum survey method. The total data collected in 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh. The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy.

Tools

Checklist cum rating questionnaire to elicit the opinion of the high school students about the Psychological impact of Social Media on high School Students at Kurnool District, Andhra Pradesh state and Personal datasheet.

Objectives

- To find out the psychological impact of social media on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- To find out the psychological impact of social media among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.

Hypothesis

- There would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media om Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- There would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.

Results & discussion

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media on Boys and Girls of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.

Table 1 - Means, SD's and t- values of Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Gender

S.No	Scheme	Gender	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Depression	Boys	271	14.63	4.47	0.3365@
		Girls	359	14.51	4.38	
2	Addiction	Boys	271	24.39	5.09	5.7744**
		Girls	359	26.89	5.79	

3	Anxiety	Boys	271	10.59	3.30	0.9203@
		Girls	359	10.35	3.16	
4	Social skill, Fear and cyber bullying	Boys	271	18.29	4.45	1.2830@
		Girls	359	18.77	4.90	
5	Cognitive (Knowledge) Development	Boys	271	72.49	14.49	4.3532**
		Girls	359	77.56	14.45	
6	Over All	Boys	271	140.84	22.45	4.2115**
		Girls	359	148.81	24.86	

** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The psychological impact of social media on boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 271 and 359. The total no of students are 630, as shown in table 1. In depression psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 14.67 and 4.47. similarly the girls are 14.51 and 4.38. The mean values of boys are slightly high in comparison to girls. The t value is 0.3365, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In addiction psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 24.39 and 5.09. similarly the girls are 26.89 and 5.79. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 5.7744, which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In anxiety psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 10.59 and 3.30. similarly the girls are 10.35 and 3.16. The mean values of boys are slightly high in comparison to girls. The t value is 0.9203, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on anxiety psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 18.29 and 4.45, similarly the girls are 18.77 and 4.49. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 1.2839, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In cognitive development psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 72.49 and 14.49. similarly the girls are 77.56 and 14.45. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 4.3532, which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on cognitive development psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. In over all psychological factor the mean and SD values of boys are 140.84 and 22.45. similarly the girls are 148.81 and 24.86. The mean values of girls are slightly high in comparison to boys. The t value is 4.2115, which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district.

The psychological impact of social media on boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 271 and 359. The total no of students are 630. Therefore there is no significant difference between boys and girls on depression psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is no significant difference between boys and girls on anxiety psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is no significant difference between boys and girls on social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Therefore there is a significant difference between boys and girls on cognitive development psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. there is a significant difference between boys and girls on over all psychological factor of high school students on Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that there is a no significant difference among boys and girls on depression, anxiety, social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students of Kurnool district, bit there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction, cognitive development and overall psychological factors of high school students of Kurnool district.

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference between the psychological impact of social media among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.

Table 3 - ANOVA Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Class

S.No	Scheme	Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean sum of square	F – ratio
1	Depression	Between the groups Within the groups Total	12.012 12272.688 12284.700	2 627 629	6.006 19.574	0.307@
2	Addiction	Between the groups Within the groups Total	3.084 19855.558 19858.641	2 627 629	1.542 31.668	0.049@
3	Anxiety	Between the groups Within the groups Total	8.976 6539.532 6548.508	2 627 629	4.488 10.430	0.430@
4	Social skill, Fear and cyber bullying	Between the groups Within the groups Total	29.102 13987.598 14016.700	2 627 629	14.551 22.309	0.652@
5	Cognitive (Knowledge) Development	Between the groups Within the groups Total	191.974 135320.597 135512.571	2 627 629	95.987 215.822	0.445@
6	Over All	Between the groups Within the groups Total	496.732 366740.540 367237.271	2 627 629	248.366 584.913	0.425@

** indicates significant at 0.01 level. * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

Table 4 Means, SD's and t- values of Psychological influence of social media on high school students according to their Class

S.No	Psychological Factors	Class	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Depression	VIII	139	14.63	4.07	t ₁₂ =0.3620@
		IX	389	14.47	4.52	t ₂₃ =0.7371@
		X	102	14.84	4.51	t ₃₁ =0.3720@
2	Addiction	VIII	139	25.87	5.70	t ₁₂ =0.1967@
		IX	389	25.76	5.54	t ₂₃ =0.2817@
		X	102	25.94	5.81	t ₃₁ =0.0931@
3	Anxiety	VIII	139	10.62	3.10	t ₁₂ =0.5142@
		IX	389	10.46	3.28	t ₂₃ =0.6552@
		X	102	10.23	3.18	t ₃₁ =0.9507@

4	Social skill, Fear and cyber bullying	VIII	139	18.93	4.93	$t_{12} = 1.083@$
		IX	389	18.47	4.65	$t_{23} = 0.4616@$
		X	102	18.65	4.68	$t_{31} = 0.4480@$
5	Cognitive (Knowledge) Development	VIII	139	76.41	14.78	$t_{12} = 0.900@$
		IX	389	75.10	14.50	$t_{23} = 0.048@$
		X	102	75.02	15.05	$t_{31} = 0.7137@$
6	Over All	VIII	139	147.02	21.47	$t_{12} = 0.995@$
		IX	389	144.83	21.03	$t_{23} = 0.1369@$
		X	102	144.20	24.35	$t_{31} = 0.6023@$

**

indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The psychological impact of social media on VIII, IX and X class high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of VIII, IX and X class students are 139, 389 and 102. the total no of students are 630, as shown in table 3. In depression psychological factor the F ratio value of VIII, IX, and X class students is 0.3070, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among VIII IX and X class students of Kurnool district on depression psychological impact. As shown in table 4 the t value among VIII and IX class is 0.362, IX and X class is 0.7371 and X and VIII class is 0.3720, which means all are not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on depression psychological factor among VIII IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. In addition psychological factor the F ratio value of VIII IX, and X class students is 0.049, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among VIII IX and X class students of Kurnool district on depression psychological impact. As shown in table 4.3.1 the t value among VIII and IX class is 0.1967, IX and X class is 0.2817 and X and VIII class is 0.093, which means all are not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on addition psychological factor among VIII IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. In anxiety psychological factor the F ratio value of VIII IX, and X class students is 0.430, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among VIII IX and X class students of Kurnool district on depression psychological impact. As shown in table 4.3.1 the t value among VIII and IX class is 0.542, IX and X class is 0.652 and X and VIII class is 0.935, which means all are not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on anxiety psychological factor among VIII IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. In social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor the F ratio value of VIII IX, and X class students is 0.652, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among VIII IX and X class students of Kurnool district on depression psychological impact. As shown in table 4.3.1 the t value among VIII and IX class is 1.083, IX and X class is 0.4616 and X and VIII class is 0.4480, which means all are not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor among VIII IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. In cognitive development psychological factor the F ratio value of VIII IX, and X class students is 0.445, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among VIII IX and X class students of Kurnool district on depression psychological impact. As shown in table 4.3.1 the t value among VIII and IX class is 0.900, IX and X class is 0.048 and X and VIII class is 0.7137, which means all are not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on cognitive development psychological factor among VIII IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. In overall psychological factor the F ratio value of VIII IX, and X class students is 0.43, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant difference among VIII IX and X class students of Kurnool district on depression psychological impact. As shown in table 4.3.1 the t value among VIII and IX class is 0.995, IX and X class is 0.1369 and X and VIII class is 0.6023, which means all are not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no significant impact on overall psychological factor among VIII IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. Hence it is

concluded that there is no psychological impact of depression, addiction, anxiety, social skill, fear, cyber bullying, cognitive development and over all on VIII IX, and X high school students of Kurnool district.

Conclusion

The psychological impact of social media on boys and girls of high school students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the sample size of boys and girls are 271 and 359. The total no of students are 630. Hence it is concluded that there is a no significant difference among boys and girls on depression, anxiety, social skill, fear and cyber bullying psychological factor of high school students of Kurnool district, bit there is a significant difference between boys and girls on addiction, cognitive development and overall psychological factors of high school students of Kurnool district by blended method It is also concluded that there is no psychological impact of depression, addiction, anxiety, social skill, fear, cyber bullying, cognitive development and over all on VIII IX, and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method

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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF BLENDED LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The educational system at present is in a transition stage. To meet the challenges of expansion and for catering individuals need trying to adopt new technologies and exploring new paths to reach the goal of quality educational opportunities for all. At the same time due to various factors like deficient budgets, lack of facilities, advantages of face to face interaction, it is not completely ready to leave the traditional modes of knowledge transfer. The present paper tries to explain that how blended learning is an approach that needs to be adopted and it analyses the positive and negative sides of blended learning.

Keywords: *blended learning, technology, online learning, traditional learning, face-to-face driver approach*

What is blended learning?

There are many approaches, methods, and techniques (strategies) of teaching languages. One of the teaching strategies that has been a major growth point in the English Language Teaching (ELT) industry over the last ten years is blended learning. It combines face-to-face teaching with distance education, either computer-based or web-based. Blended learning, also known as hybrid learning, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with traditional place-based classroom methods. Instead of learning only from their teacher, and only interacting with their peers, students also engage with technology in order to meet learning goals. Given the advances of technology over the last 10 years, the majority of students already have experienced at least some form of blended learning. At the same time, it's important to note that simply the use of technology to type an essay or to submit a homework assignment does not constitute blended learning. In addition to the production of knowledge,

students engaging in blended learning also acquire and apply knowledge with a combination of online and in-person modalities.

Blended Learning

BL is an education program that combines online digital media with traditional classroom methods. It requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some element of student control over time, place, path, or pace. While students still attend “brick-and-mortar” schools with a teacher present, in-person classroom practices are combined with computer-mediated activities regarding content and delivery. Blended learning is also used in professional development and training settings. A lack of consensus on a definition of blended learning has led to difficulties in research on its effectiveness in the classroom..

Blended learning is important in a number of ways

Takes the best attributes of online and in-person learning, in order to maximize the benefits of both Focus on individual rather than group work, allowing teachers to get a better grasp on the strengths and weaknesses of each student Can promote closer relationships and allow tutors to understand how to tailor their approach to each student More personalized instruction to suit the learning style of individual students Finally, blended learning is important when you take into account the events of the COVID-19 pandemic. This caused higher education organizations to reflect on how they can best adapt and change, both in emergency situations and for those with individual complications. Both of these scenarios can interrupt and impact education. Blended learning being implemented as a long-term option allows students and staff to be able to adapt quickly rather than needing to shift entire working strategies at short notice. Depending on the interest and skill of the teacher, as well as access to technology, there are several model types of blended learning.

The face-to-face driver approach

Involves a majority of whole-class teacher-led instruction, with the teacher also in charge of delivering the online content and monitoring students. This online component is also done as a whole class, without students splitting off in groups or working individually. When it comes to blended learning, a rotation approach, students in groups move through a set of online learning activities in the classroom with the guidance of a teacher. In other words, teacher-led instruction is minimized, and the students engage in common tasks online. The teacher determines the learning activities and requires that every student complete them all, like a checklist. The flex and the self-blend approaches offer teachers and students more choice and flexibility. In flex, the online platform provides most of the curriculum and learning activities, while the teacher is available to support students individually or in small groups.in an online driver approach, the students do not or rarely come to a physical school, working remotely on online content. Teachers are available remotely for support. Students currently participating in distance or remote learning are learning with an online driver approach to blended learning.

Advantages of blended learning

There are many benefits of blended learning. The first is that the practice offers more flexibility in the learning process. Rather than assuming that all students need the same information and skill building, at the same time and in the same way, blended learning allows for various learning activities, teaching approaches, pacing, and student groupings. The second major benefit is that students enjoy a combination of face-to-face and online learning, resulting in greater engagement. Some learning like applying knowledge, solving complex problems, exploratory enrichment and working on a project together is best done with other young people. Blended learning also provides students with time to work with faculty staff, as teachers are able to connect with them individually through technology. This provides a greater level of bonding between students and their teacher, and lets students who may be less confident in group environments to reach out. If students are struggling, they have the time and privacy to ask for extra support. On the other hand, other learning like targeted skill development, individual research, and exploratory enrichment is best done alone, with the use of technology and the internet.

Perhaps the most crucial benefit, though, is that blended learning provides easier and more effective ways for teachers to differentiate learning material for their students. A simple example is that some students with Individualized Education Programs learn better when they have access to audio versions of texts. In a traditional classroom, that accommodation would mean that a teacher or an aide would need to read the text to the student. A blended approach, on the other hand, supports the student in a more tailored and efficient

way. BL also allows for personalized education, replacing the model where a teacher stands in front of the classroom and everyone is expected to stay at the same pace. It allows students to work at their own pace, making sure they fully understand new concepts before moving on. A classroom environment that incorporates BL naturally requires learners to demonstrate more autonomy, self-regulation, and independence in order to succeed. Furthermore, because blended learning normalizes the frequent use of technology, students who may unfortunately experience stigma because of their learning differences more comfortably engage in the classroom experience with less anxiety. The level of freedom and trust in students to control their own learning, combined with the flexibility of time and location, can improve student retention overall. With students encouraged to stay on in education, this way of learning can help to prepare them for their working life, as they have more control over when and how they learn, managing their own time and workload to suit their lives. These are invaluable transferable skills for the future.

Disadvantages of blended learning for learners and educators

Unless successfully planned and executed, BL could have disadvantages in technical aspects since it has a strong dependence on the technical resources or tools with which the BL experience is delivered. These tools need to be reliable, easy to use, and up to date, for them to have a meaningful impact on the learning experience. A blended learning model often requires students to utilize technology outside of the classroom. Not every learner will have equal access to the resources, which can make online learning difficult or even impossible. IT literacy can serve as a significant barrier for students attempting to get access to the course materials, making the availability of high-quality technical support paramount. Other aspects of BL that can be challenging is group work because of difficulties with management in an online setting. Using learning platforms can be more time consuming than traditional methods and can also come with new costs as e-learning platforms. Another critical issue is access to network infrastructure. Although the digital divide is narrowing as the Internet becomes more pervasive, many students do not have access to the Internet, even in their classrooms. Any attempt to incorporate BL strategies into an organization's pedagogical strategy needs to account for this. This is why learning centers are built with good Wi-Fi connections to make sure this issue is addressed.

Challenges in blended learning

The challenges of blended learning in higher education are numerous and their emergence is encouraged permanently based upon the innovative technological developments and interaction through traditional learning environments, which emphasizes blended learning transformation force. For higher education courses blended learning has become the reality characterized by continuous investigation and debates of the benefits, potential and effectiveness to transform and improve the learning process. New, highly interactive, meaningful and student centred blended learning environments have been developed fostered by the current and advanced technologies. The convergence of traditional face-to-face and distributed learning environment that were sharply separated in the past has been in progress by developing blended learning environment. Different media/method combinations and the needs of different audiences have enabled the approach of face-to-face practiced in a lecturer centred environment and person-to-person classroom activities, and distance learning system based on self-paced learning.

Problem

The negative effect of the blended learning for students is mainly in the cognitive load, learning styles, and working conditions. One misunderstanding teachers often make in the implementation of blended learning is that teachers pay much attention on the network platform and they design a lot of activities to allow students to learn more. But the result of doing so makes the students' cognitive load increased blended learning counterproductive. In addition, the different backgrounds of the students have their own learning styles, some students are accustomed to reading a textbook, they like outlined and annotated in the textbooks. If we give students a lot of learning content and ask them for digital learning, it will influence the learning effect. Once again, Because function of the network platform is not good cause the negative effects of the navigation lost, not easy operation. Finally, in the process of blended learning implementation, because the high expenses increase the cost of getting resources, it will also affect students' learning effect.

Solution

To avoid the negative effect. The first, we should strengthen the education of integrity and awareness of intellectual property rights, we should let them to realize that plagiarism is an offense. The second, when a teacher designs homework to students, they try to designs the homework which can't directly search it's answer by Internet. This will avoid plagiarism to some extent. For example, when teaching image processing technology, the teacher can require students to use their own digital photos as a material, learning acquisition and processing technology of sound material, require students to record their own voice and then use it. The third, to students plagiarism, we can use some technical means, such as anti-plagiarism detection to prevent copying. Such as online jobs which based on Moodle network, we can use the platform to provide "anti-copying plug-ins" to stop plagiarism.

Conclusion

Great success often comes from great collaborations, so it is exciting to see how educational technology (EduTech) is giving both students and teachers more opportunities to network through the use of collaborative tools such as Google Docs, online calendars, and virtual workrooms. Plus, Skype, email, and even texting allow us to stay in touch with each other and meet colleagues from around the world. Blended instruction is more effective than purely face-to-face or purely online classes. BL methods can also result in high levels of student achievement more effective than face-to-face learning. By using a combination of digital instruction and one-on-one face time, students can work on their own with new concepts which frees teachers up to circulate and support individual students who may need individualized attention. Rather than playing to the lowest common denominator as they would in a traditional classroom teachers can now streamline their instruction to help all students reach their full potential. BL facilitates a simultaneous independent and collaborative learning experience for university students. The use of information and communication technologies has been found to improve student attitudes towards learning.

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A REFLECTION ON THE CREATION OF YOUTUBE CHANNEL - EDUCATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

Technology and teaching go hand in hand, COVID lockdown brought rapid changes in the way educational disclosures are made throughout the world. Starting an youtube channel at the experimental level helped the author/s to develop quality contents on educational psychology and mental health. During this period 25 videos were prepared and it was well received by students pursuing B.Ed. & M.Ed. program from throughout the country and interested viewers from across the globe. This thematic paper is a record of the narration of those experiences and the success this ICT based initiative undertaken by the author/s.

Introduction

Teaching and learning has undergone a dynamic shift in a short span of time due to COVID forever. This change was drastic and ushered in a new philosophy of teaching learning. The change from offline to online was spontaneous as it became the need of the hour. Though the transformation started slowly, it gathered momentum as the impact of COVID was prolonged. This pushed government, educationists, teachers and students to forcibly adapt and usage of ICT penetrated deep into to every student and teachers life. When social contact was totally prohibited, ICT medium could penetrate in every students home. Considering the versatility of technology in teaching and learning, government world over started heavily invested on developing ICT based initiatives in the education sector. Initially mobile applications took the lead and Zoom, google meet, google-classroom, were the interactive platforms which acted as the medium of teaching and learning for school and college students. Furthermore, to enhance its reach to a wider population of students, government started broadcasting academic contents through television. Meanwhile teachers started to develop digital contents and upload them in youtube, facebook, and many other platforms which they felt would be comfortable to them as well as to their audience. I am one such person who was encouraged by my life-partner do experiment. She boosted my confidence to experiment with youtube and provided technological and technical support enabling me to become a youtube content developer.

About the Channel

- Name of the Channel: Educational Psychology
- Channel Link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPcKnYblS91ooup3NgFk26A>
- Major Themes: Educational Psychology, Mental Health & Personality
- Audience: Students of B.Ed., / M.Ed., Psychology, Mental Health.
- No. of Videos: 25
- Medium of Delivery: English
- Duration of videos: 5 – 18 minutes (approximately)

How it all began?

It was during the summer of 2020 when I had to start teaching the course Learner and the Learning Process for M.Ed. II semester students. I was planning to organise this class through zoom platform and I was apprehensive about it. In the mean time, DIET, Kaliyampoondi, under the leadership of my partner and co-author of this paper had organised “ICT based teaching” training programs for teachers of Kanchipuram district. In the training she developed understanding about different video editing software and how it can be used in the teaching and learning process. After which she became very much enthusiastic and suggested me to prepare a video of education content. Though I was a bit hesitant, her constant and continuous push had propelled me to make a video on the topic, “holistic approach to the treatment of learners development and learning.” I used my mobile phone and placed it on a window of my bedroom and using an earphone started recording. I made sure that none of my family members talk loudly nor disturb me, while I was shooting. I have to take three to four takes before getting the flow and the rhythm right. I used my mobile phone to record and it came great. I really loved my presentation, being the very first attempt of this kind.

The experience of preparing brought in a sense of achievement, a sense of accomplishment and pride in me. It acted as a motivation for to prepare more such videos. My excitement was short lived as when I happened to upload the video on Whatsapp group which was formed for my online teaching-learning disclosure it couldn't support it. The file was quite large for the whatsapp application to carry. That's when a lively and enthusiastic partner once again stopped in and encouraged me to upload in the youtube. That is when video editing software Kinemaster was a blessing. My partner with little experience installed in our apple ipad and edited the video content and it came out pretty well for a first-time user. The technical support provided in editing and animating the video added aesthetics to the video. And this is how it all begun. Currently 25 educational videos are posted in my channel. With the introduction of green screen background we added animation, opening screen, closing screen, writings, etc to support my oral presentation. This added visual appeal to the presentation and finally some background music to the videos.

As an value edition, we purchased Doodle creator - video animation software for a cost of Rs.14,000/- and made few narrations in the form of pictures. I loved and thoroughly enjoyed making those customised animations as per the content of the videos and they were well appreciated by the student community. With the help of paid version of Kinemaster, software the video quality got enhanced and gave us enough opportunity and confidence to prepare videos. Videos also helped me to get connected with the

global audience, old friends and lot of students and currently my channel has reached close to seventeen thousand views was simply marvellous for a humble beginning. Furthermore, zoom platform, google-classroom, google form were complemented to the youtube videos enabling blended approach to teaching and learning. It was well received and taken well by the students and enhanced my professional skills. The following charts narrate the analysis of youtube channel ‘Educational Psychology’ over the past 28 days (26th February- 25th March 2023)

Figure 1 - Content-wise analysis

Figure 2 - Traffic Source

Figure 3 - Viewers Age Group

Figure 4 - Viewers Gender

Figure 5 - Subscription Status

Subscription status	Views ↓	Watch time (hours)	Average view duration
☐ Total	415	16.3	2:21
☐ Not subscribed	383 92.3%	13.6 83.5%	2:07
☐ Subscribed	32 7.7%	2.7 16.5%	5:01

Figure 6 - Average View Duration

Based on the graphical analysis the following conclusions are derived:

1. Vygotsky's Language development had more than 100 viewers
2. Youtube was the major traffic source for the viewers.
3. All the viewers were between 25 – 34 years of age.
4. 54.6% were male and 45.5% were female viewers
5. 383 viewers were non-subscribers while only 32 were subscribers to the channel.
6. The average view duration is more among subscribed viewers.
7. To add further another dimension, their comments were analysed. The comments were received from wider audience from across the globe. This shows that through technology one can reach to a global audience. The following are the few critical constructive comments received from the comments section:
 1. Content of the presentation is rich and meaningful.
 2. Background music could be avoided.
 3. Too much of animation.
 4. Time duration should be not more than 5 minutes.
 5. These feedbacks were quite valid and a great source of inspiration to develop more such contents and publish them in these platforms. My sincere thanks to all the viewers for their interest and support they have extended to educational psychology youtube channel.

Conclusion

Though COVID was disastrous, during this period, I had learnt to incorporate technology more into my teaching learning disclosures. NEP 2020 has also emphasised the importance of using ICT and the youtube channel "Educational Psychology" had really transformed the way we are teaching in present times. It should be noted that the author/s have started using ICT more systematically and are currently experimenting new modes of teaching for wider purpose like assessment, and evaluation. As part of 360 degree assessment, interactive quiz, preparation of video documentary are being worked out by the students of teacher training programs. The power of technology is truly awesome as it knows no boundaries and connects both near and far. Both the author/s have more than 15 years in their career in traditional teaching, the technology enabled methodology has developed new skills, better methodology, and long lasting resources reaching to different part of the country and globe. The author would like to conclude by saying technology is forever and we the teaching fraternity needs to use them to their advantage by constantly

innovating and creating contents and made available in various platforms, so that teaching and learning transactions happen at the global level, more meaningfully.

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ROLE OF MIND GAMES IN ENHANCING EMOTIONAL RESILIENCE

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Abstract

Everyone loves to play games. Games had always been a part of human civilization. They play an important role in building up the physical health of human. Later on due to development in science and technology, various physical and mental issues have been constantly increasing. Mental health problem is one of the biggest threats now. To move on and to have good mental health, emotional resilience is needed. It would help to protect from depression and anxiety issues. This article finds out how mind games would help to enhance emotional resilience.

Introduction

Education enlightens young minds. The real aim of education is to bring overall development. Gandhiji says “ education is to draw out the best in mind, body and soul. Mind games as a part of learning will help to enhance emotional resilience. Mind games are games that were played by using mind and intelligence. It’s like a mind work out. Mind games help mind to be stronger and boosts the mental well being. Mind games also known as Head games help the individuals to improve psychological attributes. Emotional resilience is one’s ability to adopt stressful situations and being calm in negative experiences. Mind games help to mimics the process of resilience and serve as a helpful analogue to good self-care routines and practices.

Mind Games-A Challenger

Mind games boost a range of cognitive functions to keep mind sharp and limber. Mind games are exercise mental ability and boost cognition skill, memory, visual skills, orientation, language association, language and reasoning skill. As physical exercise improves physical health, scientific evidences prove mental work out like mind games improve mental health. Brain games keep brain to be active. Mind games challenge ones sportsman ship at mental level, it improves their skills to be adaptive, responsive and to be decisive. Mind games keep our brain healthy. It emote brain to think logically and analytically. The components of mind games make the individual who is playing to be engaged in some virtual stressful situations and makes them top experience the negative feel. It also helps the player to accept the ups and downs of life through its successes and failures which is the main component of games. Mind games in addition not only make the learner to accept adverse situations but also guides them to overcome it. Some of the psychological skills that might be enhanced with the help of mind games are depicted above.

Now, it's time to speak about mental health and how mind games and be related with mental health. Brain games help mind to think away from painful, negative, situations and makes the player/individual to concentrate on the games they are playing in. Mind games help individuals to make the mind game to be healthy. Gaming gets your mind off things for a little while and that helps says Kieswetter. Mind games makes the mind to believe that the player can do the thing .The component of games such as role play teach a range of skills such how to converse, reciprocate and handle other people's behavior, emotions, and personal attacks. And it also teaches that there is a solution for every problem. rle playing of powerful people might make the individual to believe that they are strong, powerful and capable. Through mind games helps one to get distracted from stressful situations and makes them to control their feelings, be positive and confident enough to solve the situation.

Mind Games in the light of NEP_2020

Education should not only instill facts and information but it should be training of mind. NEP2020 highlights and intimates education should be embedded in learning and teaching process. Gamification is an part of educational process where components of gaming is embedded in content, and students are aware that they are learning but with interest and motivation to learn. What NEP 2020 says about Gamification seems to be interesting and acts as a game changer in teaching-learning process. Gamification says about the overall change in individual in all terms. It not only aims on developing the learning expectancies but also the life skills needed for a learner to survive in this challenging world. The New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 marks a fundamental shift and advocates replacing rote learning with innovative and experiential methods, such as Gamification and apps that can deliver high-quality education. Gamification of education is an effective method for increasing student engagement, improving skills and optimizing learning. Here is how:

Makes learning fun

Let us dispel one myth right away. Gamification is not meant to transform education into a game, but it does tap into the psychology that motivates students to engage. The result can be both enjoyable and inspiring.

Increases attention span

With decreased attention spans of students, traditional learning methods can be tedious. Gamification makes learning more fascinating. It incentivizes the learner to study more.

Fosters healthy competition

The natural desire to play can be used to convert the boring content to joyful learning experience. Games also foster friendly competition among peers and make students feel a sense of achievement in completing a subject after the gamified challenges and activities.

Provides instant feedback

Learning objectives can be met through gamification, which encourages students to strive for them and receive instant feedback

Badges boost motivation

Badges in gamified learning content can be virtual ribbons, stickers, or prizes that a student earns for the completion of modules or tasks within the topic. They are a tangible symbol of the student's achievements and encourage them to engage with the community and track personal progress while improving their knowledge base significantly. Game-based activities can boost student engagement, produce

active learners, and reduce student stress when they foster intrinsic motivation. Serious games are a part of mind games. Gamification is the lightest form of serious games - game elements are used in a non-game context. Simulations are the most immersive and 'serious' type of serious games. Players can actually practice a certain skill in a game.

Mind Games in enhancing Emotional Resilience

Emotional resilience refers to one's ability to adapt to stressful situations or crises. Emotional resilience is a trait that can be developed. Persons with emotional resilience won't keep any thing in head. Each have their unique way of getting rid of the problems. Emotionally resilient people are best listeners and have good mentally healthy habits. These mentally healthy habits help them to accept and think of alternative ways to overcome. As mind games make them to believe they are confident and strong enough people and also develop them to be positive. The basic components of mind games strategies help them to develop mentally health habits which in turn improve their Emotional resilience.

Conclusion

Thus mind games play an important role in enhancing emotional resilience through the components of gaming. To be emotionally resilient one can play mind games which would both his cognition abilities and emotional disturbances.

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BENEFITS OF BLENDED LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with traditional place-based classroom methods. It requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some elements of student control over time and place. Technology is a driving factor in the present generation, in which digital automation, artificial intelligence, and mobile Super computing and intelligent robots are gaining momentum. The present education system demands high innovative and competent environment at international level. One such approach is blended learning. The objective of the present paper is to analyses the concept of blended learning, the tools used in blended learning, and advantages of blended learning.

Keywords: *Blended Learning, Higher Education, NEP 2020*

Introduction

Blended learning is a combination of offline and online education which enables students to interact with the instructor, study material, and other students both through physical classroom and online platforms. The idea of blended education makes learning easy and more productive which is why this interpretation of digital learning is promising in the long run and will become the new normal. Blended learning, or the integration of face-to-face and online instruction Graham (2013), is widely adopted across higher education with some scholars referring to it as the "new traditional model" The progression in digital methods for education was imminent even before the unpredictable onset of COVID-19. However, this pandemic consequently redesigned the scenario of education rapidly and made us realize the importance and need for technology in education. As Covid-19 forced the requirement for social distancing, this outcome hit every sector significantly, which includes education. Students and teachers faced diverse challenges in these difficult times of Covid, giving rise to methods that can help avoid social interaction and at the same time,

ensure the continuation of quality education. Students and educational institutions were forced to adopt distance learning methods like e-learning, virtual classrooms, online repositories, etc

The history of blended learning

In order to create a successful blended learning strategy, it's wise to learn as much as possible about its key ideas and values. To understand these, we must first know how Blended Learning got started and the historical highlights that shaped its core principles along the way. 1840's: First Distance Course Sir Isaac Pitman launches the first distance education course. Though there were other variations on the concept prior to Pitman's, his was to resemble distance learning as we know it today. His course centered on shorthand. Pitman sent shorthand texts to his students via mailed postcards and they were required to send them back to be graded and corrected. Even though computers and mobile devices weren't involved, and wouldn't even be invented for roughly a century, effective feedback and assessments were still an integral part of the process. It can be traced back to the mini-computer and mainframe training of the 60's and 70's. It was the first time that training could be deployed to countless workers within an organization without having to rely on printed materials and face-to-face instruction.

Employees could simply login to their character-based terminals to access the information. One of the most notable systems was Plato, which was developed by Control Data and the University of Illinois back in 1963. In fact, Plato is still around today. At this stage in the blended learning timeline, companies began using video networks to train their employees. The instructor no longer had to be physically on-site in order to onboard new hires or broaden the skill sets of existing staff members. This made the training experience more interactive and engaging. Learners were able to communicate with their peers, watch the instructor on TV, and even address any questions or concerns sending them by mail. Think of it as the predecessor to webinars and video conferencing. One of the most successful satellite-based training case studies is the Stanford University Interactive TV network. Stanford devoted resources to their video network in the 70's and 80's so that professors could hold classes in multiple locations throughout SF at once, and it is still running to this day. Instead of having to send assignments to the professor by mail or courier, learners can now submit their work for review online.

Blended Learning Integration Currently we find ourselves in an exciting time for blended learning. Technology is rapidly changing and an increasing number of organizations and private learning institutions are beginning to see the benefits of a blended learning approach. From interactive scenarios in the classroom to webinars and online tutorials, learners now have a wide range of tech tools and applications at their disposal. Companies have the opportunity to train their employees anywhere at any time, while online learners can participate in online communities and interactive eLearning courses from anywhere in the world. Gradually, the union between face-to-face instruction and technology-based learning is producing new and creative ways to enrich the educational experience and make learning fun, exciting, and even more beneficial. Blended learning has a proven track record of bringing traditional classrooms into the tech-friendly 21st century.

Concept of Blended Learning

Generally, three main delivery modes exist: face-to-face, flexible and distance learning. Importantly, learning technology applies to all three modes; technology can be used to:

- enrich traditional face-to-face teaching
- enhance existing flexible forms of delivery
- Increase the level of engagement and social presence of students studying at a distance.

In each delivery mode, technology can be used to blend the best of conventional teaching with online forms of learning.

Learning Management Systems

A learning management system, or LMS, is often the technological cornerstone of a blended learning environment. An LMS is an integrated software application to deliver content and resources online, to provide interaction or collaborative work spaces, and to manage complete student, course and programmer administrative functions, including registration, assessment and analytics.

Web Conferencing

Web conferencing is used in blended learning as an online counterpart to classroom-based tutorials, seminars or any synchronous learning activity, such as collaborative, project-based work. Web conferencing tools are usually highly multi modal, with simultaneous video, voice, text chat, whiteboard annotations and screen sharing, making them rich and dynamic but also complex learning environments the more powerful web conferencing tools, such as Adobe.

Digital Textbooks

Digital textbooks, or e-texts, potentially offer significant advantages over printed texts, lower initial and updating costs; improved accessibility, flexibility and customization (including localized material); and richer learning experiences through multimedia content, embedded assessments, and interactivity. They are often considered key components of educational reform, and several jurisdictions have begun mandating the widespread adoption of digital texts.

Blogs and Wikis

Blogs and wikis are online writing tools and can receive feed back from their peers. In blended learning blogs are primarily used for individual, reflective writing, while wikis can be very effective for collaborative research and writing activities. Wikis can also be effectively used for collaborative class planning or syllabi, as often found in connectivity MOOCs

E-Portfolios

Electronic portfolios, or e-portfolios, are collections of writing, documents and other artifacts maintained individually by students to demonstrate their learning over a course or programme.. In this way, an e-portfolio becomes more than a mechanical assessment exercise; it encourages learners to take a broader, holistic view of their learning, to understand their own learning progress over time and to find meaning in the work they have done.

Higher Education

In the Indian system, higher education starts after the 10+2, framework of higher education in India is very complex. It includes various type of institutions like universities, colleges, institutes of national importance, polytechnics etc. Universities are also of different types like central universities which are formed by government of India, by an act of parliament which are responsible for arranging and distributing resources required by university grant commission(UGC), State universities, Deemed universities (aided and unaided) and Private universities. India has a federal set-up and the Indian constitution places education as a concurrent responsibility of both the centre and state. While the centre co-ordinates and fixed standards in higher and technical education, school education is the responsibility of state. Under the department of higher education there are several regulatory bodies and research councils which are responsible for the higher education in India. Critical appraisal of Indian Higher System reveals that though there is proliferation of higher educational institutions, however, due to the prevailing systemic deficiencies, continues to produce graduates that are unemployable despite emerging shortages of skilled manpower in an increasing number of sectors. Deterioration of standards of education and research, 33 inadequate infrastructure and facilities, large vacancies in faculty positions, low student enrolment rate etc..

NEP 2020

The National Education Policy has given a rare glimpse in what can be achieved through the transformation of education. The new NEP clearly states that it is time to take on a policy that is undoubtedly student centric, or what can be safely put down as Education .The time has indeed come to recognize the fact that the student is the main stakeholder and that efforts must be taken to make the system respond to their dreams and aspirations. In this line of thinking the new policy gives the acceptability of many modes of learning including that of face to face learning With emergence of digital technologies and the emerging importance of technology for teachinglearning at all levels from school to higher education, the NEP 2020 recommends for use of blended models of learning. The NEP-2020 states that while promoting digital learning and education, the importance of face-toface in-person learning is fully recognized. Accordingly, different effective models of blended learning will be identified for appropriate replication for different subjects.

Current status and problems of student engagement in blended learning practice

In September, 2010, the EDUCAUSE Learning initiatives (ELI) community gathered online for a focus session on blended learning. Various focus sessions were organized to refine the blended instructional delivery models in higher education. In implementing blended learning instructional model, the major issues of concern are:

- Faculty Related: Faculty development, Finding time to research, develop and implement them and Faculty support
- Student Related: Student learning and management, Student satisfaction and their perception, Assessment of student performance
- Institutional: Technological Infrastructure, Quality assurance, Cost and benefits

More and more educators are engaged in blended learning practice, expecting this "new normal" to change traditional teaching. It considers students as the main body, prompts teachers to invest more in "teaching" and students to invest in "learning" more effectively, and enhances student engagement. It will become an effective model for improving education and teaching quality. Student engagement is a multidimensional structure. Based on Fredricks' three-dimensionality theory and the content of interviewers, we conclude that student engagement includes behavioral engagement, cognitive engagement and emotional engagement.

Benefits of blended learning

Blended learning integrates online and offline learning activities and resources to reduce in-class seat time for students in a face-to-face environment which make it a tremendous advantage for a university. It can help the university management to enhance under-enrolled programs, complete faculty teaching loads, and improve cost effectiveness. Blended learning facilitates students with a unique flexible learning experience, because they can access and engage with their educational program from anywhere and at any time. The participants did not need to be on the campus to actively engage in their studies. Blended learning environment provides many resources of learning to learner which enhanced learner's confidence and competency. Quick feedback to learner which will help them in their learning process. Remove the constraints of traditional training and learners decide where and when they do their training Learners more responsible for their training and help them be self-motivated. Blended learning provide Collaborative activities among teacher and students through interactive session which will helps to improve the students level of satisfaction and Improved academic performance. Provide access to everyone who needs training by providing it in different ways. Blended learning methods enable students to explore information or guidance online, which can be accessed any time they need and classroom learning helps to build better relations between the learner and the teacher. Education is not just about academics but also learning time management, discipline, and blending learning helps both students and teachers to learn according to their own pace and schedule.

Conclusion

Blended learning is emerging as one of the most popular pedagogical concepts, and with the advancement of technology and learning analytics, a boom is going to be experienced. There should be more studies guiding teachers or administrators on how to create a successful blend. A blended learning environment increases student interest: When technology is integrated into college lessons, learners are more likely to be interested in, focused on, and excited about the subjects they are studying. The tools used in the classroom, such as PowerPoint, interactive whiteboards, and audience response systems; virtual communication tools such as audio files, discussion boards, e-lists, discussion groups, chat or conferencing, email, newsgroups, polling, questionnaires, web forms, and videoconferencing; social-networking software such as instant messaging and phone calls; podcasts, social-networking sites, video clips, virtual worlds, weblogs, and wikis; e-learning systems such as VLEs, conferencing systems, group collaboration software and group sites; and mobile learning using mobile phones, laptops, and tablet PCs In this paper, we have presented the present situation of India in the higher education sector. We also identify the challenges like the demand-supply gap, the lack of quality education and benefits, the problem of infrastructure and basic facilities, the shortage of faculty, etc. in higher education. The implementation framework for the Twelfth Plan aims to focus on improving the quality of state institutions, revamping financial aid programmes, and interlinking expansion, equity, and excellence. To improve the higher education system, we need to improve teaching pedagogy, build synergies between research and teaching, and facilitate alliances among higher

education institutions, research centres, and industries. This is necessary not only to take care of economic growth, but it is also essential for social cohesion and to empower the country's youth.

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EFFECT OF BLENDED LEARNING AMONG PHYSICAL SCIENCE STUDENT-TEACHERS

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Abstract

Due to the developments of social networking in education, preceptors have to give innovative ways and elect stylish ways in the teaching process in the classroom, especially in learning Physical Science as a part of science, so that the second-year students are interested and eager to learn Physical Science. Edmodo is one the online learning software and is supported to present an effective result for teaching Physical Science. This exploration investigates the effectiveness of blended learning by using Edmodo in teaching Physical Science to second-year student-teachers in a College of Education in Salem District of Tamilnadu. Exploration used the quasi-experimental exploration design. It begins with conducting a unity test and deciding the experimental and control groups. And, it was followed by giving conditioning to the control class using face-to-face learning and giving treatments of Edmodo to the experimental class that was using amalgamated learning like combining face-to-face learning with Edmodo online learning and also following the same procedures in post-test to both classrooms. The result indicated that there was a significant effect of teaching Physical Science in the experimental group by using Edmodo on Physical Science second-year student-teachers. It is proved by the value of the significance of the 't'-test table, and the result is 0.0001 was lower than 0.05.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Edmodo, Physical Science, second-year student-teachers*

Introduction

Physical Science as a regular utility of scientific actions is extensively used by utmost countries in the world. The operation of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in drug teaching has come popular since technology like social networking including Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram; etc., has been used intensely by second-year student-teachers in a College of Education at Salem District of Tamil Nadu. There are numerous advantages to be gained in educational settings when we use technologies and social networks, similar as we can make online communities learn so we aren't only monotonous study in the classroom. It's in line with Hong Zhao et al., (2022) explained that virtual communities can be a result of the

lack of communication in the real world. So, the second-year students who don't feel confident to share in a real classroom and who are hysterical to express their ideas can communicate with their preceptors and classmates in online communities. In this case, the preceptors should be suitable to find out what social networking spots are applicable and helpful for second-year student-teachers in their learning. To make second-year student-teachers like what they learn and increase their knowledge in Physical Science, particularly in science activities. ICT provides preceptors to produce more instigative, intriguing, and interactive classrooms, second-year student-teachers need the renewal of educational styles including a technological point that allows them to pierce knowledge wider and study at any time and any place. Edmodo as one of the technological biases is believed to be suitable to help preceptor speakers give better Physical Science learning into their teaching (Nachimuthu et al., 2020). In teaching Physical Science, Edmodo can be applied as amalgamated e-literacy media, it's the combination between e-learning and face-to-face learning in the classroom.

Review of related studies

Blended learning is traditional classroom learning rounded by online learning conditioning and sources Purba, (2021). Edmodo is a social media platform for learning which can be penetrated freely and in safe hands created by Nicolas Borg and Jeff O'Hara for seminaries, speakers' preceptors, second-year students, and parents (Quinie et al., 2021). Edmodo is a social network grounded on an academy terrain with supporting features for the teaching and learning process. Edmodo is a safe social network that gives a chance for preceptors or speakers and second-year student-teachers to cooperate and communicate fluently Constanti et al., (2022). Preceptors can fluently manage the stylish and most practical features which are handed by Edmodo. They can always connect with second-year student-teachers and manage second-year student-teachers conditioning fluently. Learning features available in Edmodo are happily sharing materials, assignments, quizzes, polling, and enabling any conversations on the comment features. To get out the utmost of the teaching and learning to condition, Edmodo proposes as simple as possible like Facebook and presents a chamber for preceptors, second-year student-teachers, and parents (Quinie et al., 2021). Edmodo is easy to use, free to be penetrated, and available for smartphones, Android, and iPhones. It's an unrestricted group collaboration in which only those that have a group law can take classes, so it's safer and further private. Besides parents can supervise their children's scores, and check their ward's deadlines for schoolwork or assignment. Edmodo can use in learning because it provides easy and safe installations to carry out the classes in agreement with the need and it gives the occasion in learning grounded on the second-year student-teacher characteristics. (Revathi et al., 2022). A former study conducted by Billy et al., (2019) showed that using Edmodo in online learning can ameliorate writing capability because it makes it second-year student-teachers easier to pierce any sources and learners can compare their easy writing with fellow musketeers in the group. They can communicate and communicate with the preceptors and other second-year student-teachers whenever they want. The differences between these explorations with their studies are this exploration did a study about the perpetration of amalgamated learning by using Edmodo not only concentrating on jotting but also integrating the Physical Science chops. In line with that result, Teresita et al., (2021) performed an Indian case study using Edmodo as a means of cooperation in the process of teaching-learning and to know second-year student-teachers' beliefs about it. Besides Yustina et al., (2020) tell some problems that might arise in using Edmodo, similar second-year student-teachers spend important Jio network to pay for data connection used, wasting time in front of the computer and second-year student-teachers can open other social media rather than Edmodo as an educational media. In line with that currently, it's believed that single online learning cannot guide and lead second-year student-teachers to get optional learning and it cannot give a teaching-learning process maximally for second-year student-teachers (Irmayanti et al., 2020).

Method of the Study

Thus, further exploration is demanded which concentrates on technological development like e-learning by using Edmodo and integrating it with face-to-face learning called amalgamated learning to maximum results in Physical Science get learning. By incorporating Edmodo with face-to-face learning, the second-year student-teachers can interact further with the preceptors and fellow musketeers because there will be numerous openings to bandy everything both in class and online. The purpose of the exploration is to probe whether there's a significant effect on using amalgamated learning by using Edmodo in teaching Physical Science to second-year student-teachers in the Salem District of Tamil Nadu State of India. The

result of the exploration is anticipated to give a great donation to other preceptors or speakers to encourage them for using Edmodo in teaching, give great benefit to second-year student-teachers to be easier in learning, and can be used as useful input for other experimenters to conduct farther exploration dealing with Edmodo. Theoretically, this exploration would contribute to the field of educational technology, specifically-learning media development, perpetration, and evaluation. This exploration uses a quasi-experimental design since it's insolvable to do arbitrary assignments in the process of taking the sample from the population. The exploration designs way are as first; administering a unity test to the physical science second-year student-teachers to know the unity of the exploration subject. Also as saying the scores of the test using Analysis of variance, deciding the experimental class and control class by lottery. After that giving treatment that was teaching Physical Science in amalgamated learning by using Edmodo which was combined with face-to-face learning to the experimental group, while the control group was lectured by face-to-face learning. The design of this exploration can be described as follows (Sita et al., 2020). The way of administering this exploration was administering unity of the population by assaying the second-year student-teachers' Physical Science scores using ANOVA to know the unity of the exploration subjects. Having a lottery to determine control (A) and Experimental class (B). Giving treatment that was teaching Physical Science in amalgamated learning by using Edmodo to the experimental class (B), while the control class (A) was lectured in face-to-face learning mode. Administering post-test to the experimental class (B) and the control class (A). Assaying the results of the two groups by using an independent sample 't'-test formula of significance position to test whether the mean difference was significant and to conclude. This exploration was conducted in the Salem District of Tamil Nadu State, Third-semester second-year student-teachers of Bachelorette in Physical Science of India in the 2020-2021 academic times. The population of the study was the third-semester second-year student-teachers of the bachelorette in Physical Science. They were taken as the populations because the Physical Science material of 'Viscosity' was lectured in the second year. Constanti et al., (2022) state that the effect of the blended learning mode is more learning occurred than in the traditional one. Dealing with this idea, both classes were chosen as samples. There were 96 Physical Science second-year student-teachers in the third semester, further; they were classified into two groups 48 second-year student-teachers from class A as a control group and 48 second-year student-teachers from class B act as the experimental group. The 'Viscosity' materials were formulated as second-year student-teachers who are lectured by using Edmodo in an amalgamated learning setting achieve better Physical Science scores than the second-year student-teachers who are lectured by the traditional system. This study used the quasi-experimental design and this design is used to compare the mean score of the control and experimental group. After conducting the post-test, the result is anatomized by using an independent sample 't'-test. The result of data analysis is consulted to the 't'-table of 0.05 level of significant positions to know whether the result is significant or not.

Data Analysis

The subjects were second-year student-teachers of the Padmavani College of Education and Dhanam College of Education, affiliated with Tamilnadu Teacher Education University and the data were gained from second-year student-teachers and the data were gained from 96 questionnaires. The exploration result revealed that Edmodo is more useful to be applied in education than other social media spots. It can support both face-to-face learning and online learning ever. Some data were gained from the result of the unity test and the analysis of the post-test result. After collecting the data demanded by using a test instrument, the coming step is as saying the data by using an independent 't'-test. Before giving treatment, the unity test was conducted to know whether the two classes were homogeneous or not by using ANOVA. The result of the unity test showed that the mean score of the control group was 62.4 and that the experimental group was 68.2. The result of the ANOVA analysis in the following table showed that the significance was 48.32. While the utility of a computer in various places like House (N=24); College (N=20) and other places (N=52), the analysis of ANOVA was done about the blended learning concepts in Physical Science for the post-test of the experimental group.

Table 1 Analysis of ANOVA about the effect of Blended Learning (Utility of PC-wise)

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	0.05 level
Between Groups	1365.0824	02	682.5412	48.3167	0.00001	Sig.Diff
Within Groups	1313.7552	93	014.1264			
	2678.8376	95				

The value of the significant positions was calculated at 0.05 levels and it was the significance position. ($F=48.32$; $p=0.00001$). Thus, it can be concluded that there was a difference in the second-year Physical Science student's capability in both two classes and it can be said that the population was heterogeneous as per the analysis concerning the utility of a computer. Also, the lottery was done to determine the experimental group and the control group. Grounded on the lottery, B was treated as the experimental group and A as the control group. The exploration period was eight weeks of eight meetings. The class schedule for the bachelorette of Physical Science was formerly a week, every Thursday. The first meeting was about the meaning and definition of viscosity. The alternate meeting was socialization and introducing Edmodo to the experimental class because they had no way known before about Edmodo. The researcher explained how to produce an Edmodo account as a pupil, give an explanation of some features of Edmodo and its function, and how to do any assignments and quizzes given by the researcher through Edmodo. Also asked the second-year student-teachers to produce an account and join a class made by the school teacher by giving them an identity of class code. The researcher asked the second-year student-teachers if their parents created Edmodo accounts too to cover the development of their ward's learning. The fourth to the seventh meeting was teaching Physical Science by using Edmodo in an amalgamated learning setting i.e., combining face-to-face learning and online learning in the experimental class. While the control class was lectured through face-to-face learning only in the classroom. During Physical Science teaching-learning, using Edmodo the second-year student-teachers are veritably enthusiastic. They don't meet any significant obstacles in operating Edmodo because it has simple features. Sita et al., (2020) stated the advantage of using Edmodo over Social Networks. Edmodo has a stronger interface while adapting WhatsApp features; it's simple and easy to use indeed for the freshman because second-year student-teachers are formerly familiar with it due to features like WhatsApp. Edmodo supports exercises on colourful types of train formats like pdf, ppt, html, etc. Edmodo isn't only accessible with desktops and laptops, but also it can be penetrated by using smartphones. Second-year student-teachers can download the Edmodo operation on the play store and learn 'Viscosity'.

Table 2 Analysis of mean, S.D & 't' value of the effect of Blended Learning (Group-wise)

Groups	N	Mean	S.D	't'-value	p-value	0.05 level
Control Male-Pre	24	14.22	4.36	0.9304	0.1785	No Sig.
Experimental Male-Pre	24	16.82	6.08			
Control Male-Post	24	14.26	3.94	3.2467	0.0001	Sig.
Experimental Male-Post	24	22.78	4.84			
Control Female-Pre	24	11.32	4.14	0.1344	0.4468	No Sig.
Experimental Female-Pre	24	11.64	2.86			
Control Female-Post	24	11.54	3.58	2.7469	0.0043	Sig.
Experimental Female-Post	24	18.16	3.12			
Control Rural-Pre	12	08.89	2.18	0.6759	0.2531	No Sig.
Experimental Rural-Pre	12	10.22	1.73			
Control Rural-Post	12	08.94	2.02	7.6206	0.0001	Sig.
Experimental Rural-Post	12	26.32	3.88			
Control Urban-Pre	36	16.86	4.28	0.0659	0.4738	No Sig.
Experimental Urban-Pre	36	17.03	2.88			
Control Urban-Post	36	16.98	3.78	9.0553	0.0001	Sig.
Experimental Urban-Post	36	43.89	6.48			

Besides through online learning by using Edmodo, second-year student-teachers can shoot a private communication and ask about the material when they find some difficulties without being shamed indeed when they aren't on a lot because they can connect to lecturers anytime and anywhere. Present questions, quizzes, or assignments by giving a time limit and shoot grades from second-year student-teachers work and give feedback fluently and make group conversations. In addition, Edmodo allows parents to see the pupil's conditioning in learning, and see the tasks, and docket within the time set given by the researcher. At the last meeting, the experimenters administered a post-test also the result of the post-test was anatomized by using an independent sample 't'-test. Grounded on table 2 the result showed that the significance value was 0.0001 which was lower than the 0.05 level and the 't' value of pre and post significantly differed in the control and the experimental group of male ($t=3.24$) and female ($t=2.75$) and rural ($t=7.62$) and urban ($t=9.06$). It indicated that the result of the 't'-test analysis was significant. Whereas the male and female ($t=0.93$ and 0.13) respectively in pre-tests and also rural and urban ($t=0.68$ and 0.07) respectively are non-significant and are equal. The hypothesis of this exploration said second-year student-teachers who are lectured in amalgamated learning by using Edmodo achieved a better score on their Physical Science content than the second-year student-teachers who are lectured by using face-to-face learning only is accepted.

Discussion of the results

It means this experimental exploration revealed that there's any significant effect of amalgamated learning by using Edmodo on the second-year student-teachers' Physical Science achievement. This exploration result supports the study performed by Teresita et al., (2021) revealed that Edmodo is more applied in education than other sports activities in social media. It can support both face-to-face learning and online learning ever. Teaching Physical Science in amalgamated learning using Edmodo helps second-year student-teachers to be more active, have further time for learning, and have unlimited access to over-to-date knowledge and material sources available. Qomariyah et al., (2019) state that blended learning can enlarge knowledge and material access, is more flexible for learners and enhances second-year student-teachers active position, and gives new and better gests in learning. For preceptors, amalgamated learning can ameliorate teaching and manage the class fluently and second-year student-teachers have further flexible time and convenience by studying and doing assignments part-time through online learning from home. Blended learning also becomes a result of single online learning which cannot guide and lead the second-year student-teachers to get optimal learning and give minimal process in teaching the second-year student-teachers (Irmayanti et al., 2020). Because amalgamated learning enables the school teacher to cover the learning process in the classroom directly, so optimal learning can be gained. Further Edmodo can carry out an independent learning style and construct responsible learning since it makes second-year student-teachers further discipline and on time in doing assignments because the due date of assignments and quizzes has been arranged by the school teacher on Edmodo. It's in line with the statement proposed by Denny et al., (2020) that the operation of Edmodo by preceptors can be a great medium to expand responsible learning outside the classroom. Through Edmodo, second-year students are more independent learners. So using Edmodo can be motivating and a good medium for teaching because it's a new invention in the classroom and has great eventuality to be enforced in teaching and learning.

Conclusion

There is no significant difference between males and females concerning the control and experimental group in the pre-test the hypothesis was accepted whereas, in the experimental group, the hypothesis was rejected. Likewise, the same results occurred between the rural and urban pre and post-test results. It could be concluded that second-year student-teachers who are lectured in amalgamated learning achieved a better score on their Physical Science than the second-year student-teachers who are lectured by using face-to-face learning only either, the post-test analysis showed that the experimental second-year student-teachers Physical Science mean score is advanced than the control second-year student-teachers mean score. So, it proved that there's a significant difference in the mean score of the experimental and the control classes. It indicated that teaching Physical Science in blended learning by using Edmodo is more effective than face-to-face learning only. So that Edmodo can encourage second-year student-teachers to be independent learners and enhance their provision in learning Physical Science since second-year student-teachers can have further flexible time to learn a lot, and second-year student-teachers have more access to over-to-date. Edmodo considers second-year student-teachers to share laboriously in discussion forums

because they can choose the flat and chooser online or face-to-face learning in which they feel most comfortable.

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BLENDED LEARNING DURING COVID-19 CRISIS

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Abstract

This paper mainly focuses on blended learning and its importance nowadays. It also emphasises the role of blended learning during the covid 19 pandemic time. Blended learning has played a vital role during the pandemic covid 19. The whole world was not able to pursue any kind of work because of the wide spread of viruses. Students from the school level to higher education level could not be able to go to school to pursue their regular education. So this blended learning helps the whole world to pursue their education through online mode by being in their home itself with an internet connection in their digital devices. In our country the education department has announced the institutions to undergo online learning and make the students not to stop their learning. So, this article mainly focuses on the blended learning during the covid 19 crisis.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Virtual learning, Educational technology and on-line learning*

Introduction

How can blended learning help during the COVID crisis?

As the world grapples with the spread of COVID-19, blended learning seems to be emerging as the most sustainable model for the current situation. As a model of our endemic preparation for GIIS, we have gradually moved students back to physical classrooms. At the same time, we are also fully prepared to return to the blended learning model in case the situation turns around and the epidemic escalates again.

Why blended learning

Blended learning has become popular in recent years and has become the preferred method of learning during the pandemic. As schools around the world are redesigned due to COVID-19, blended learning is becoming the new normal. Blended learning has been around for a while, and it's a combination of traditional face-to-face teaching and online teaching, with students and teachers in the classroom at the same time. Blended learning aims to provide students with the best possible in-person and online learning experience. A blended classroom includes face-to-face teaching techniques, such as direct instruction or

lectures, group discussions, and group work, while also using technology to provide online classroom learning that students can follow at home, provided they have access to the necessary technology.

Factors contributing to this prevalence include:

- It provides students with flexibility in time and learning environments, allows them to work independently and helps them pace themselves.
- This is a two-way learning experience, made possible through collaboration between the student and the instructor, and greatly enhanced by the online training platform.
- Allows students to learn flexibly according to their abilities.
- It provides students and teachers with greater access to resources, such as online libraries and reading materials, which allow students to access more information than regular textbooks, thus providing students with a broader approach to learning and acquiring knowledge.

Benefits of Blended Learning

- It accommodates technology and digitally blended learning styles using traditional classroom methods and digital learning.
- It has the concept of a virtual classroom where students can access an online platform for self-study and can choose to live online lessons or consult in a virtual classroom.
- This creates better communication between learners, which in turn leads to a more engaging and rewarding learning experience. It also improves teacher-student interaction, contributing to better personalized and successful assessments.
- The training venue does not require coaches and there is no need to rent training sites.

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Benefits of Blended Learning

- It accommodates technology and digitally blended learning styles using traditional classroom methods and digital learning.
- Help learners adapt to the new workplace normal. The workplace is changing rapidly and employees now need to adapt to different working environments and be more productive. This ensures continuous learning for the individual, which benefits both the individual and the industry.

Benefits for teachers

- Track and improve engagement
- Blended learning offers the opportunity to develop a clear roadmap for students, such as expectations for each student and goals to achieve final goals or required grades.
- It helps students and teachers to customize their learning experience according to their needs and requirements.
- It has the concept of a virtual classroom where students can access an online platform for self-study and have the option to live online lessons or consult in a virtual classroom.
- This creates better communication between learners, which in turn leads to a more engaging and rewarding learning experience. It also improves teacher-student interaction, contributing to better personalized and successful assessments.
- The training venue does not require a trainer and there is no need to rent a venue.
- By combining new technologies such as augmented reality and virtual reality with traditional educational methods, students can have an experience of more inclusive learning.
- Student-centered blended learning makes it easy to personalize learning modules based on ability.

- Reusing content reduces money spent on course preparation.
- Unlike traditional classrooms, there is no need to print course materials, making it easy to expand and update courses.
- Help learners adapt to the new workplace normal. The workplace is changing rapidly and employees now need to adapt to different working environments and be more productive. This ensures continuous learning for the individual, which benefits both the individual and the industry.
- Increased satisfaction and productivity
- Today's students prefer multiple learning styles. As digital natives, many young students actually know and prefer the online environment.
- Blended learning encourages self-directed learning where students are forced to research information online independently instead of sitting in a classroom and relying on the instructor.
- Soft skills, or skills necessary for professional success in the workplace, are naturally developed in the online learning space.
- Specifically, skills such as good communication with others, time management, critical thinking and teamwork are developed in mixed mode.

Benefits for Students

- Peer Support
- Ease of Access and Flexibility
- Improves memory
- Increased satisfaction and productivity
- Soft Skills Building

However, blended learning also has its limitations. In a country like India that lacks quality internet access and bandwidth, blended learning may not be easy to achieve. Blended learning is about using technology, and unless we have excellent infrastructure and technology resources, the benefits of blended learning will not reach everyone. Another downside is that non-tech-savvy students and teachers face significant hurdles to easily interact. Participants may experience problems accessing course materials. Blended Learning Accommodates Multiple Learning Styles With blended learning, students can communicate with teachers and classmates not only face-to-face, but also digitally through email and message boards. Students who are less likely to speak up when they have a question or don't understand can post their questions on a bulletin board or via chat.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the ability to communicate via email or online increased engagement. Blended learning helps build confidence and success when students actively discuss and express their understanding of concepts. It was concluded that communication skills evolved favorably through the blended learning program. With declining enrollment and challenging digital environments putting pressure on systems, faculty and programs, introducing blended learning can help attract new cohorts of students and create new revenue streams. .

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A ONLINE AND OFFLINE SURVEY ON UTILIZATION OF SOCIAL WELFARE SCHEMES BY STUDENTS: BLENDED APPROACH METHOD

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Abstract

Blended environments have significant technology infusion, technologies are likely to yield data that can assist educators to inform their practice in formats and real-time feedback loops not possible in more traditional settings, while also engaging students to examine their own data. Blended environments may alter the structure of classrooms by changing how instructional activities are delivered and by making the role of students more active in the teaching and learning process. Blended learning has become an emphasis for policymakers. The present research study is on online and offline survey on utilization of social welfare schemes by students: Blended approach method. The tool is standardized by item analysis. A stratified random sampling method is used for a sample of 630 students from different high schools. The data is collected by survey cum interview method in the Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. Mean, SD, t-test, and F-ratio statistical techniques are used at 0.05 and 0.01 levels. The main objective to find out the utility level of social welfare scheme among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method and also to find out the utility level of social welfare scheme among Other Caste, Backward Class and Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe high school students of Kurnool district by blended method. The related hypothesis are there would be no significant difference between the utility level of social welfare scheme among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method. And also There would be no significant difference between t the utility level of social welfare scheme among Other Caste, Backward Class and Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe high school students of Kurnool district by blended method It is found that the utility levels of welfare schemes byVIII, IX, and X class students of Kurnool district The sample size of by VIII, IX, and X class students are 210, 209 and 211. It is found that there is a significant difference among VIII, IX AND X class students Nadu Iin Nedu, Amma Vadi, Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka, Jagan Gorumudda, and Badiki Vasta and over all schemes. Hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of Kurnool district in nadu nedu, Jaga nanna vidya kanuka, Jaga nanna goru mudda Badiki vasta and over all schemes but there is no significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of Kurnool district in utilization of amnavadi welfare scheme.

Keywords: *Blended, Class, Category Students, Social Welfare, Schemes*

Introduction

This paper explores how the affordances of blended learning environments provide data for educational decision making to educators and students that might not be otherwise available. Because blended environments have significant technology infusion, technologies are likely to yield data that can assist educators to inform their practice in formats and real-time feedback loops not possible in more traditional settings, while also engaging students to examine their own data. Blended environments may alter the structure of classrooms by changing how instructional activities are delivered and by making the role of students more active in the teaching and learning process. Blended learning has become an emphasis for policymakers. It is seen as the customization of educational and instructional activities to address individual students' needs. Yet Cavanagh (2014) notes, there still is no common definition. The Data Quality Campaign (2016) noted the importance of blended environments, the technology, and the resulting data, to customize instruction to meet the needs of all students (Guidera, 2016; Holiday, 2016; Messer & Polis, 2016; Perdue, 2016). Such environments provide for real-time data, teacher and student empowerment, immediate course corrections, the use of data to individualize for every student, and connectivity to reach all

students regardless of circumstances. Research on blended learning has begun to emerge. In particular, the research reported here is informed by the work of Pane, Steiner, Baird, and Hamilton (2015). Using a multi-method approach, the RAND research identified five domains and 13 attributes of blended learning:

- Learner Profiles: Personalized goals for student's o Student data provided and discussed with students
- Personal Learning Path: Outside of school learning, Flexible/multiple paths for students through content, individual student support.
- Competency-Based Progression: Student progress through content based on competency, On-demand assessment to demonstrate competency
- Flexible Learning Environment: Student grouping, Learning space supports mode, Structure of learning time , Extended learning time for students (extended school day or year), Technology available to all students
- College and Career Readiness: Developing college/career preparation skills Affordances

The present research study is on online and offline survey on utilization of social welfare schemes by students: Blended approach method

Methodology

In the present study a stratified random sample technique is applied with a sample size of 630 students in Kurnool district. The data is collected by interview cum survey method. The total data collected in 6 high schools of Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh (2 government, 2 aided and 2 private) and in each school 105 students from VIII, IX and X classes. The study was conducted in Telugu state i.e., Andhra Pradesh The state is geographically divided into 3 regions. They are Rayalaseema, Coastal and Northern Andhra. Presently there are 26 districts in Andhra Pradesh. As for education and economy is concerned Andhra region stands in first with an average level of education and economy.

Tool

Checklist cum rating questionnaire to elicit the opinion of the high school students about the utility of social welfare schemes in Kurnool district, Andhra Pradesh state and Personal datasheet

Objectives

- To find out the utility level of social welfare scheme among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- To find out the utility level of social welfare scheme among Other Caste, Backward Class and Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.

Hypothesis

- There would be no significant difference between the utility level of social welfare scheme among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.
- There would be no significant difference between t the utility level of social welfare scheme among Other Caste, Backward Class and Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe high school students of Kurnool district by blended method.

Result & discussion

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference between the utility level of social welfare scheme among VIII, IX and X high school students of Kurnool district

Table 1. ANOVA of utility of social welfare scams by high school students according to their Class

No	Scheme	Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean sum of square	F -ratio
1	Nadu-Nedu	Between the groups Within the groups Total	264.655 48405.772 48670.427	2 627 629	132.327 77.202	3.714 **

2	Amma Vadi	Between the groups Within the groups Total	1057.318 58089.323 59146.641	2 627 629	528.659 92.646	5.706**
3	Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka	Between the groups Within the groups Total	2489.654 64630.189 67119.843	2 627 629	1244.827 103.078	12.077**
4	Jagan Gorumudda	Between the groups Within the groups Total	411.332 39230.333 39641.665	2 627 629	205.666 62.568	3.287**
5	Badiki Vasta	Between the groups Within the groups Total	263.452 25236.391 25499.843	2 627 629	131.726 40.249	3.273**
6	Over All	Between the groups Within the groups Total	4295.295 639065.632 643360.927	2 627 629	2147.648 1019.243	2.107*

Note: ** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

Table 2 - Means, SD's and t- values of utility of social welfare schemes by high school students according to their Class

S.No	Scheme	Class	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Nadu-Nedu	VIII	209	85.68	9.46	t ₁₂ =0.0016@
		IX	211	84.55	11.21	t ₂₃ =2.6779**
		X	210	86.71	8.18	t ₃₁ =2.1918**
2	Amma Vadi	VIII	209	85.02	11.21	t ₁₂ =2.8582**
		IX	211	82.23	9.03	t ₂₃ =0.1645@
		X	210	82.37	8.42	t ₃₁ =2.7671**
3	Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka	VIII	209	103.72	10.18	t ₁₂ =4.6765**
		IX	211	98.91	9.85	t ₂₃ =1.7669@
		X	210	100.61	10.44	t ₃₁ =3.0825**
4	Jagan Gorumudda	VIII	209	58.29	8.07	t ₁₂ =2.0795*
		IX	211	60.27	6.86	t ₂₃ =1.1274@
		X	210	59.4	8.68	t ₃₁ =1.3676@
5	Badiki Vasta	VIII	209	51.63	6.12	t ₁₂ =0.7181@
		IX	211	52.06	6.26	t ₂₃ =1.7674@
		X	210	53.17	6.62	t ₃₁ =2.5464*
6	Over All	VIII	209	384.38	33.66	t ₁₂ =2.009*
		IX	211	378.01	31.31	t ₂₃ =1.4108@
		X	210	384.70	30.73	t ₃₁ =0.1017@

Note: ** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The utility levels of welfare schemes by VIII, IX, and X class students of Kurnool district are interpreted as follows and the values are tabulated in table 1. The sample size of VIII, IX, and X class students are 210, 209 and 211. In nadu nedu scheme the mean and SD values of VIII class students are 85.68 and 9.46, similarly IX class students are 84.55 and 11.21 and finally X class students are 86.74 and 8.18. There is significant difference between VIII, IX, and X class, The X class students are having more mean value in comparison to VIII and IX class students, which implies the utility level X class students are better than IX and VII class. The F ratio value is 3.714 which is significant at 0.01 level. Hence there is significant difference between VIII, IX, and X class students. To know the specific difference value among VIII, IX, and X class is calculated by using t test statistical method. The t value between VIII and IX class students is 0.0016, which is not significant at 0.05 level hence the hypothesis is accepted. 2.6779 is the t value of IX and X class students, which is significant at 0.01 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected.

The t value between X and VIII class students is 2.1911 which is significant at 0.05 level hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is included that in nadu medu scheme there is a significant difference between IX and X class, X and VII class is significant difference among them but there is no significant difference between VIII and IX class. Hence there is a significant difference between high school students in utility of nadu medu scheme in Kurnool district. Hence there is a significant difference between high school students in utility of badiki vasta scheme in Kurnool district. In Overall scheme there is significant difference between VIII and IX class but there is no significant difference between IX and X class, X and VII class. Hence there is a significant difference between high school students in utility of Overall scheme in Kurnool district. Hence it is concluded that the utility levels of welfare schemes by VIII, IX, and X class students of Kurnool district are significantly different among the VIII, IX, and X class student.

Hypothesis - There would be no significant difference between the utility level of social welfare scheme among Other Caste, Backward Class and Schedule Caste/Schedule Tribe high school students of Kurnool district.

Table 3 - ANOVA of utility of social welfare schemes by high school students according to their Category

S.No	Scheme	Source of variation	Sum of squares	df	Mean sum of square	F -ratio
1	Nadu-Nedu	Between the groups Within the groups Total	819.825 47850.602 48670.427	2 627 629	409.9125 76.316	5.3712**
2	Amma Vadi	Between the groups Within the groups Total	275.606 58871.036 59146.641	2 627 629	137.803 92.8931	1.4884@
3	Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka	Between the groups Within the groups Total	661.291 66458.552 67119.843	2 627 629	330.64 105.99	3.1195**
4	Jagan Gorumudda	Between the groups Within the groups Total	258.073 39383.592 39641.665	2 627 629	129.03 62.81	2.054**
5	Badiki Vasta	Between the groups Within the groups Total	220.232 25279.611 25499.843	2 627 629	110.11 40.31	2.7315*
6	Over All	Between the groups Within the groups Total	6157.375 637203.552 643360.927	2 627 629	3078.63 1016.27	3.0293**

** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

Table 4. Means, SD's and t- values of utility of social welfare schemes by high school students according to their Category

S.No	Scheme	Category	N	Intensity scores		t-value
				Mean	SD	
1	Nadu-Nedu	OC	155	86.42	9.33	t ₁₂ =2.1768* t ₂₃ =2.2489* t ₃₁ =0.2895@
		BG	342	84.51	8.44	
		SC/ST	133	86.73	8.82	
2	Amma Vadi	OC	155	83.84	11.14	t ₁₂ =0.9596@ t ₂₃ =0.8212@ t ₃₁ =0.2391@
		BG	342	82.83	9.49	
		SC/ST	133	83.56	8.37	
3	Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka	OC	155	100.09	10.44	t ₁₂ =1.3398@ t ₂₃ =0.8092@ t ₃₁ =1.9994*
		BG	342	101.14	10.33	
		SC/ST	133	102.28	10.09	

4	Jagan Gorumudda	OC	155	51.88	8.57	$t_{12} = 8.655^{**}$
		BG	342	58.89	7.89	$t_{23} = 5.5870^{**}$
		SC/ST	133	64.00	9.33	$t_{31} = 11.409^{**}$
5	Badiki Vasta	OC	155	51.88	6.27	$t_{12} = 0.2776@$
		BG	342	52.05	6.44	$t_{23} = 5.2959^{**}$
		SC/ST	133	49.00	5.29	$t_{31} = 4.1837^{**}$
6	Over All	OC	155	381.53	35.11	$t_{12} = 0.6774@$
		BG	342	379.46	31.71	$t_{23} = 8.6772^{**}$
		SC/ST	133	347.00	38.37	$t_{31} = 7.9170^{**}$

** indicates significant at 0.01 level, * indicates significant at 0.05 level, @ indicates not significant at 0.05 level

The utilization level of social welfare schemes by OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of skurnool district, the related data tabulated in 4.8 and 4.81. The sample size of OC students are 155, BC students are 342 and SC/ST students are 133, the data is interpreted as follows. In nadu nedu scheme the mean value of SC/ST students in utilization of this welfare scheme is better than the mean values of BC and OC high school students. The F ratio value is 5.3712, which is significant at 0.01 level, which means there is a significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students in utilization of present scheme, hence the hypothesis rejected. To know the specific significant level among any two categories t test is employed. The t test value of OC and BC high school students is 2.1786, which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. The t value between BC and SC/ST high school students is 2.2489, which is significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is rejected. The t value between OC and SC/ST high school students is 0.2895, which is not significant at 0.05 level, hence the hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is a significant difference between OC and BC, BC and SC/ST high school students, but there is no significant difference between SC/ST and OC student in utilization of nadu nedu scheme. In amnavadi scheme the mean value of OC students in utilization of this welfare scheme is better than the mean values of BC and SC/ST high school students. The F ratio value is 1.4884, which is not significant at 0.05 level, which means there is no significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students in utilization of present scheme, hence the hypothesis accepted. There is no significant difference between OC and BC, high school students, but there is a significant difference between BC and SC/ST, SC/ST and OC student in utilization of Badiki vasta scheme. There is no significant difference between OC and BC, high school students, but there is a significant difference between BC and SC/ST, SC/ST and OC student in utilization of over all scheme. Hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of Kurnool district in nadu nedu, Jaga nanna vidya kanuka, Jaga nanna goru muddam Badiki vasta and over all schemes but there is no significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of Kurnool district in utilization of ool students in utilization of amnavadi welfare scheme.

Conclusion

It is found that the utility levels of welfare schemes by VIII, IX, and X class students of Kurnool district. The sample size of by VIII, IX, and X class students are 210, 209 and 211. It is found that there is a significant difference among VIII, IX AND X class students Nadu Iin Nedu, Amma Vadi, Jagan Anna Vidya Kanuka, Jagan Gorumudda, Badiki Vasta and over all schemes. Hence it is concluded that there is a significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of Kurnool district in nadu nedu, Jaga nanna vidya kanuka, Jaga nanna goru mudda Badiki vasta and over all schemes but there is no significant difference between OC, BC and SC/ST high school students of Kurnool district in utilization of amnavadi welfare scheme.

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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Introduction

Rapid technological change offers a significant opportunity to educational institutions to enable access to quality education. Use of new digital technologies, such as social media, mobile, analytics or embedded devices, in order to enable major business improvements like enhancing customer experience, streamlining operations or creating new business models (Fitzgerald, 2013). Digital transformation is fundamentally about change and it involves people, processes, strategies, structures, and competitive dynamics (Wade, 2015). Digital transformation should enable the ecosystem that effectively uses people, processes and technology to bridge the digital gap to create collaborative, interactive and personalized learning experiences. The foundation of digital business transformation is organizational change (Maedche, 2011), and like any other organizational change, there should be a reliable framework connecting people, processes, and technology enabling organizations to successfully navigate this transformation (Bonnet & Nandan, 2011).

Digital transformation in education institutions should not only focus on Service Transformation, it should also enable and enhance Operations Transformation. Service transformation focuses on creating new education products and transforming existing products into digital ones. It provides digital means for communication between students and teachers by converting offline lectures into videos, creating digital texts and quizzes. Operations transformation would focus on all the common operations educational institutions have such as students' admission, registration for programs and courses, examination, program development, and their quality assurance.

Role of Technology in Digital Transformation

Digital Transformation is driven by technology and the idea is to use technology not just to replicate an existing service but to use technology to transform that service into something significantly better. Digital transformation can involve many different technologies, below list shows few of the latest technologies.

- Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
- Blockchain
- Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality
- Cognitive Cloud Computing
- DevOps
- Internet of Things (IoT)
- Big Data
- RPA (Robotic Process Automation)

These emerging technologies are used for AI teaching assistants, advanced analysis of students' performance, IoT data, and much more. Big Data in education is mostly information about the performance and abilities of each individual student which can improve their learning experience by personalizing it. Five years ago, it was hard to manage data of hundreds or thousands of students on paper. Education institutions could use Big Data for better data management, analysis, and usage. Other emerging technologies in

education are Augmented and Virtual Reality. They are already being used in classrooms to create lessons more informative as these technologies can bring satellite into classrooms or move the whole class to the moon. In addition to enhancing knowledge in the medical, engineering and science disciplines, AR could be used on campus to support orientation for refreshments.

These technologies are not just the latest buzzwords and organization driving digital transformation has seen tangible value coming from these technologies in terms of improving optimization, increasing production output, and tackling operational efficiency challenges. With the growing implementation of IT technologies and IoT devices, the need to secure the network from cyber threats emerged. Education institutions must implement tools that enhance cyber security. But it's not just about the technology: changing business processes and culture are vital for Digital Transformation in Educational institutions.

Benefits of Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is more than digital products and services; it's also about the processes that create, enable, manage, and deliver them. The benefits of digitally transformed learning environments will not come by simply arranging and presenting content in virtualized or even in more personalized ways. Rather, it will come through the synergistic combination of benefits for different stakeholders: leadership, teachers, staff, and necessarily, students and the community. Some of the generic benefits of Digital transformation irrespective of industries are:

- Digitalization of Business Operations
- Greater Resource Management
- Employee Empowerment
- Better Customer Experience
- Increases Agility and Innovation

Some of the benefits for the education institutions, educators and students are listed below:

For the Institution

- Integrated information systems enables greater ability to track and trace transactions
- Improves Convenience: Educators, students and parents can process transactions at their own time and at their own convenience.

For Teachers

- Teachers will be able to innovate their teaching methods—and make their classes more interesting, engaging, and effective.
- Provide personalized feedback to individuals along the way.

For Students

- Students will be more actively engaged, have a better learning experience, be better prepared for the careers of the future, and find new, innovative ways to solve problems.
- Students could choose and build an approach based on how they best learn, through a smart curriculum path that is more relevant to their personal context and areas of interest.

Vision

A strong Digital Transformation vision will help all stakeholders align around a key theme, enabling the transformation of traditional and physical learning to robust, engaging, virtual learning environments. The vision should articulate the education institution's future state and type of experience it would deliver to educators, students and the institution.

Processes

New processes and re-structuring may be required to move the institutions closer to align with all the different stakeholders: leadership, teachers, staff, students and the community and how they want to engage. The process of transforming learning environments should focus on creating the right capabilities for educators to adopt effective teaching methodologies and innovation that put the learner at the heart of learning process

Technology

Technology can make a real difference, but it must be deployed thoughtfully by IT leaders who understand the pedagogical goals of their faculty members, cooperating with and receiving professional guidance from education experts who can help them apply new technologies to learning. Educational institutions should implement these new technologies in a way that transforms learning environments, creating more virtual opportunities for students, and merging the physical with the virtual.

People

Although digital transformation is driven by technology, it also depends on people. Educational Institutions needs processes and technology, but it's the people skills—and the ability to learn, change, and innovate—that are the most important ingredients for a successful digital transformation. Digital transformation requires changes in behaviour in the entire educational institution and the strategy needs to tie cultural and digital elements together.

Conclusion

Digital transformation is not a matter of technology only: it must be supported by a combination of vision, processes, people, in addition to the technology itself. The process of transforming educational institutions should focus on creating the right capabilities for educators to adopt effective teaching methodologies and innovation that put the learner at the heart of learning process. Digital transformations are challenging and educational institutions can start by taking small steps like creating an eLearning platform and move to something more complex like AI, ML, IoT and Big Data.

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AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

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Introduction

Vocational education means learning to change one's behavior to enhance the quality of life through work and values, without or along with formal schooling. If the learning through the vocational approach enhances self-employment and economic productivity of the people then the war against poverty can be fought and conquered in a constructive way. Vocational education can play a vital role to improve their standard of life and to help them participate in national development. Many countries like Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Philippines have got a lot of economic benefits through Vocational Education (VE).

So it has been proved that economic implications of Vocational Education are many, particularly for a country which has a vast population of adult illiterates. So the time has come for us to find out the role of vocational education in poverty reduction. We also need to identify measures to make VE more effective in poverty reduction.

Aims and Objectives of Vocational Education

- Provision of technical knowledge and vocational skill necessary for agriculture, industrial, commercial and economic development.
- To give an introduction to professional studies in engineering and other technologies.
- To give room for young men and women to have an intelligent understanding of the increasing complexion of technology.
- Training and impacting of necessary skills leading to the production of craft man, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant.
- Provision of trained manpower in applied sciences, technology and commerce, particularly at sub-professional levels.
- To provide people who apply scientific knowledge to the improvement and solution of environmental problems for the use and convenience of man.
- Restructuring the educational system at all levels to respond effectively to the challenges and managing the impact of the information age, and in particular the allocation of development fund to education at all levels.

Vocational education is basically life and need based education which can convert an unskilled inexperienced and illiterate population into human resources, formal education system, because of its rigid chronologically graded structure and inflexible nature excludes the poor from its advantages.

In this circumstance as the alternative of formal-education (FE) it is very much necessary to evaluate vocational education so that we can determine the extent of its success and weakness at any stage of poverty reduction as it is considered the best way to bring about longer lasting socio-economic change and self development.

Benefits of vocational education

Vocational Education helps people in the better performance of their jobs as they acquire a great learning experience. Working professionals get a chance to hone their skills while making money.

- VE is a sort of introduction as it gets employees ready for the workplace which comes in handy while performing various tasks.
- Due to the nature of the skills it imparts, a student doesn't consider it a futility as compared to academic education.
- Vocational education is the term itself denotes the students are specialized and therefore they have more chances of employment as compared to others.
- Many students who are in a dilemma whether they should attend college or not, VE really opens a completely new door.
- It makes an individual a responsible and independent whereas those who study regular courses lack in this sphere.
- The career of one's own choice is one of the major benefits of this education, a vast majority of people are caught in the wrong because they were in it for the sack of job, money, lack alternative and professional compromise whereas an individual pursuing VE is already pursuing his dream job.
- This type of education is a great asset to the economy. Our government need not import foreign technician on higher wages as our own can do the required work.
- Certain vocational skills acquired from vocational education teach students the importance of manual work. The physical labor done under certain jobs makes them strong, healthy, active.
- Majority of vocational skills are applicable all over the world and these create employment opportunities in foreign countries.
- Vocational education develop the economy by the bridging the demand and supply gap with highly skilled workers. It also gives students the opportunity to take marketable skills from the classroom directly into the working world.
- Better vocational education also attracts foreign investment and foreign exchange in form of a foreign working platform.
- School dropouts and adults can also receive this type of education as it provides an opportunity to learn a skill and trade. There are many well-paid career fields in which a college degree not required.
- Another benefit is that hands-on work activities allow direct application of acquired knowledge.
- This education provides stable jobs as these are the jobs whose demand is never fulfilled.

- Vocational education programs focus on the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies as necessary equipment for the individual to live in adapt to the real work situation and contribute to the development of his society.

Conclusion

It assists all young people to secure their own future by enhancing their transition to a lot of opportunities after school. Vocational education can be seen as an aspect of education which utilizes scientific knowledge in the acquisition of practical and applied skill in the solution of technical problems. It is the process of acquiring attitude, knowledge, competencies relating to occupations in various factors of economics and social life. It has also been described as the education that prepares students mainly for occupations requiring manipulative skills and is designed to develop skills, abilities, understanding, attitude and work habits needed for useful and productive basis. This can provide employment for its recipients and important practical skill development program designed to equip persons of trainable qualities with skills that employers of labor want in the industries, in fact, it is considered as the launching pad for technological development

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EFFECTIVE TEACHING IN A DIVERSE CLASS ROOM

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Introduction

The following tips are meant to be suggestions and not guaranteed solutions for teaching in racially diverse classrooms. Teachers should develop a range of pedagogical skills that best serve the needs of all their students.

Develop a syllabus that explores multiple perspectives on the topic

- Incorporate multicultural examples, materials, and visual aids as much as possible in lectures.
- Make sure that the expectations for the pedagogical process and learning outcomes are stated clearly on the syllabus.
- Structure project groups, panels, laboratory teams, and the like so that membership and leadership roles are balanced across ethnic and gender groups.
- Develop paper topics that encourage students to explore different racial and cultural perspectives.
- Assign work of scholars from a variety of racial and ethnic backgrounds relevant to the topic being studied.
- Design classroom instruction and materials with a diverse group of students in mind.
- Develop ground rules or norms that will guide how students are expected to interact with each other in the classroom.
- Design classes with a clear structure (there is a method and meaning to how teaching and learning is to occur) and flexibility (not so rigid that adjustments cannot be made).
- Consider how all students would experience the syllabus.
- Consider whether students of all cultures are likely to have a background in the material.
- Consider whether different approaches to learning are accounted for.

- Anticipate sensitive areas in the subject matter being taught.
- Think in advance about how one might handle sensitive topics or explosive moments.

Create opportunities to get to know your students on an individual/personal basis

- Get to know each student individually. Learn their names and how to pronounce them correctly.
- Use eye contact with all students; be open and friendly outside of class.
- Be accessible and encourage students to meet with you during office hours.
- Interact with your students in respectful, challenging, and collaborative ways.

Design opportunities for students to interact with each other in respectful and meaningful ways

- Divide the class into smaller groups, and when appropriate, assign one person with the responsibility of reporting on the small group's work.
- Encourage students to form study groups.
- Create opportunities for students to present their work to each other and the whole class.

Activate student voices

- Create opportunities for mutual teacher-student participation so that everyone feels a responsibility and openness to contribute.
- When appropriate, encourage students to share their thoughts about the subject, acknowledging their statements as they are made.
- When appropriate, create opportunities for students to personalize course content with examples from their own history so that they can make connections between ideas learned in the classroom and those learned through life experiences.
- Let students know from the very beginning that their thoughts have a place in the classroom, that we all have unique perspectives, and that these different perspectives are an important component of the learning process.
- Make it safe for everyone to voice their views by accepting all views as worthy of consideration. Don't permit scapegoating of any student or any view. Don't leave students alone out on a limb.
- Avoid creating situations where students are placed in the position of being representatives of their race.

Generate a challenging but vibrant learning process that encourages students to develop their creative, critical, and analytical thinking skills

- Make the classroom norms explicit.
- Keep expectations high and provide the support required to meet these expectations.
- Ask students to locate cultural or even discriminatory content in textbooks or other materials.
- Ask students to research the position they are least comfortable with and to come prepared to articulate a defense of that posture.
- Present all sides of an issue. Play the devil's advocate for the least popular view.
- Create opportunities for students to link theory with practice -- that is, encourage them to apply what they are learning with what's going on in the world.
- Use multiple modes of instruction to account for the range of learning styles that may be present in a diverse group of students.
- Provide direct and clear feedback in an effort to demonstrate your commitment to your students' learning.

Effective teaching in a diverse class room

Every classroom is a cultural community reflective of the disciplines and perspectives studied the authors, the students, and the professor. One can argue that successful learning requires an intercultural approach where students are responsible for listening and reading and experiencing to understand both the perspectives of others peers, authors, faculty and for understanding their own perspectives and how they acquired them. Students can come to understand that learning is about the generation, mutual reflection, and critiquing and expanding of ideas and concepts, and that this is most effectively done in a collaborative and non- competitive environment. One effective approach to this challenge is to attend to the variety of learning styles in any college classroom. Understanding multiple learning styles allows one to focus on individual students' own learning styles; sub-groups within a classroom community; and the class as a learning

community. Even in the most transformed classes, however, faculty are often unaware of the variety of pedagogies that can produce enhanced learning for students and faculty and that can facilitate growth in intellectual complexity and capacity. Student can also learn that there are patterns of values, speech, preferences, and behaviors associated with different cultures, and they can learn that there are as many differences within cultural groups as there are across different cultures. This helps student's break down cultural stereotypes in the society as a whole.

Diversity in the Classroom

In the day-to-day classroom is often hard to do. The goal of this teaching module is to highlight a few of the key challenges and concerns in promoting diversity, and illustrate ways to incorporate an understanding of diversity in the classroom and beyond. Diversity is a term that can have many different meanings depending on context. This module will not offer a comprehensive definition of the term; instead, this module will highlight two key areas related to diversity:

- Identify how diversity affects the classroom
- Provide practical tips for promoting an inclusive classroom

Much discussion about diversity focuses on the following forms of marginalization: race, class, gender, and sexual orientation — and rightfully so, given the importance of these forms of difference. In fact, students come to the university classroom with different backgrounds, sets of experiences, cultural contexts, and world views. However, diversity is an issue that plays a role in the classroom beyond these categories. For example, much educational and psychological literature demonstrates that students have diverse ways of learning. Some learn visually, through charts, graphs, tables and drawing; others may learn primarily through aural means (i.e. through listening to lecture); and others still may be primarily kinesthetic (i.e. learning by doing, project work, etc.). Attention to learning preferences is an important aspect of addressing differences among all students. Additionally, issues of diversity play a role in how students and teachers view the importance of the classroom and what should happen there. For example, assumptions about what a typical student should know, the resources they have and their prior knowledge are extremely important.

Conclusion

Students may perceive that they do not “belong” in the classroom setting a feeling that can lead to decreased participation, feelings of inadequacy, and other distractions. Teachers may make flawed assumptions of students' capabilities or assume a uniform standard of student performance. Teachers may themselves feel out of place based on their own attributive traits.

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A STUDY ON MENTAL HEALTH AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THANJAVUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

Mental health is a level of psychological well-being, or an absence of mental illness. It is the psychological state of someone who is functioning at a satisfactory level of emotional and behavioural

adjustment. Achievement is one's actual abilities which can be measured directly by the use of tests. Achievements are sometimes best measured in the field of practical situation. Educational achievement test show how much knowledge and skill an individual has obtained (and trained) in a school subject such as arithmetic, science, history or geology. It is reported that Mental Health has a significant decrement onto students' achievement. This study aimed to determine the association between Mental Health and Academic Achievement of higher secondary school students in a Thanjavur District. Survey method of research was used. A sample of 310 students was selected from different higher secondary schools of Thanjavur District through Simple Random sampling technique. The self developed Mental Health and Academic Achievement questionnaire was used to collect the data. The result of the research is that there is no significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Gender, Locality and Types of Institution. Hence the hypothesis of research is accepted. Finding shows from the study shows that there is significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Subject. Hence the hypothesis of research is rejected.

Keywords: *Mental Health, Academic Achievement and Higher Secondary School Students*

Introduction

Mental health is a level of psychological well-being, or an absence of mental illness. It is the “psychological state of someone who is functioning at a satisfactory level of emotional and behavioral adjustment”. From the perspective of positive psychology or holism, mental health may include an individual's ability to enjoy life, and create a balance between life activities and efforts to achieve psychological resilience. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), mental health includes “subjective well-being, perceived self-edifice, autonomy, competence, inter-generational dependence, and self-actualization of one's intellectual and emotional potential, among others. “The WHO further states that the well-being of an individual is encompassed in the realization of their abilities, coping with normal stresses of life, productive work and contribution to their community. Cultural differences, subjective assessments, and competing professional theories all affect how ‘mental health’ is defined. A widely accepted definition of health by mental health specialists is psychoanalyst Sigmund Freud's definition, the capacity “to work and to love”. Achievement is one's actual abilities which can be measured directly by the use of tests. Achievements are sometimes best measured in the field of practical situation. Educational achievement test show how much knowledge and skill an individual has obtained (and trained) in a school subject such as arithmetic, science, history or geology. The world is becoming more and more competitive quality of performance has become the key factor for personal progress. Parents desire that their children climb the ladder of performance to as high a level as possible. This desire for a high level of achievement puts a lot of pressure on students, teachers, schools, and in general, the educational system itself. In fact, it appears as if the whole system of education revolves round the academic achievement of students, though various other outcomes are also expected from the system. Thus a lot of time and effort of the schools are used for helping students to achieve better in their scholastic.

Need and Significance of the study

Mental health is universally agreed upon by all people who are concerned with social welfare and progress of a country that the teacher plays a crucial role in building of nation and truly the teacher is called National builder. Teaching has become increasingly challenging and complete ends these present changing conditions. One of the various challenges hurled at teachers recent part, is of maintaining the physical and mental health of children and youth of nation. It is a new responsibility of Teacher. Teachers can play an important role in maintain the vertical health of the nation with their knowledge of human problems and remedial measures. For health pupils, the teacher takes about the mental health of the pupils. Academic achievement may be called as academic performance or learning outcomes of the students. It is a factor to show the student's internal consistency and capability of memory. Academic achievement as independent and dependent variables respectively.

Review of Related Literature

Joshi (2000) conducted a study on neuroticism, extraversion an academic achievement as related to gender and culture. The sample selected for the study was 400 students of eight classes belonging to urban and rural area of Punjab. School records and Eyseock's personality inventory was used for data collection.

Results revealed a significant difference between boys and girls of rural areas on academic achievement. **Devi and Brian (2002)** Window factors succeed with scholastic backwardness of secondary school children. 100 low achievers from secondary school of Hyderabad city were selected as sample for the study. Interview schedule was used to elicit factors related to scholastics of parents found to be detrimental to academic achievement of their children. **Nalwa and Anand (2005)** highlighted the negative impact of Mental Health on Students Academic Achievement. The present study is intended to study the impact of Mental Health on the Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. **Jan et al (2006)** conducted a study to investigate whether juvenile delinquents use lower levels of moral judgment than their nondelinquent age-mates and results show a lower stage of moral judgment for juvenile decline. Moral judgment is strongly. **Park and Choi (2007)** found that Boys students use more Mental Health than Girls students. There are a number of studies on the Mental Health among Boys and Girls students. Despite the gender equality and constitutional safe guards of the Girls, the Boys dominated the Mental Health in Secondary School Students. **Pardhasardhi and Goel (2015)** studied the influence of access use of Mental Health on Academic Achievement of adolescents. The data was analyzed using method of descriptive statistics and the finding revealed that the Mental Health was useful for education and it had a positive influence on students Academic Achievement. **Mir and Paray (2018)** studied the Mental Health and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students in Kashmir. The study found significant difference between the Academic Achievement scores of Mental Health user and non-users students, where the Mental Health users performed well in academic score as compare to the non-users.

Statement of the problem

A problem must spring from the researcher's mind like a plant springing from its own seed. To the same point of view, in education, most of the researches have been conducted in different ways angle among the development of student's academic achievement through the teacher's factors and the classroom factors. These factors are contributes their equal influence outcomes for successful teaching and learning process. If there is any unbalanced effect on participation of those factors which leads the negative effect to the educational outcomes. Although, no researcher cannot be identified the exact unbalanced contributing factor to make indirect effect on learning outcomes. It is not possible to find interior contribution of a factor on the same. Because each factors have several contribution of those factors. For this back drop, the investigator of the study has interested to conduct a study on mental health and academic achievement. Here the study entitled "A Study on Mental Health and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students of Thanjavur District".

Objectives of the study

- To find the level of Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- To study the difference in Mental Health in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- To study the difference in Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- To find out the relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students

Hypothesis of the study

- There is no significant difference in Mental Health in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- There is no significant difference in Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students with respect to Gender, Locality, Subject and Types of Institution.
- There is significant relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.

Methodology of the study

The Normative survey method is adopted for the study. The variables used are the Mental Health and Academic Achievement. Higher Secondary School Students in Thanjavur District are the population of this study. The sample consists of 310 higher secondary school students from both Government and Matriculation school in Thanjavur District. Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary

school student's questionnaire was used. The inventory contains 20 & 18 objective items. This was a self developed tool. The sample reliability is established by test-retest method by the investigator and the reliability co-efficient is found to be 0.73. Hence the tools are highly reliable. The validity of the test was assessed on the basis of the judgment of the experts. The Mental Health and Academic Achievement Questionnaire will be given to the selected sample with a request to fill in the required data enclosing a copy of permission letter from the school Head Master.

Data Analysis

Descriptive Analysis

Table-I: Mean and SD of variable Mental Health and its sub-variables

Variable	Values		
	No.	Mean	SD
Mental Health	310	14.84	5.86
Boys	157	12.11	4.63
Girls	153	13.01	4.75
Rural	152	12.35	3.90
Urban	158	13.40	4.76
Arts	154	12.42	3.94
Science	156	13.76	4.45
Government School	151	13.30	4.67
Matriculation School	159	12.85	3.23

Table-II: Mean and SD of variable Academic Achievement and its sub-variables

Variable	Values		
	No.	Mean	SD
Academic Achievement	310	12.81	4.53
Boys	157	11.66	3.20
Girls	153	11.85	3.30
Rural	152	11.54	3.51
Urban	158	12.13	3.86
Arts	154	11.66	3.16
Science	156	12.10	3.91
Government School	151	12.11	3.95
Matriculation School	159	11.86	3.02

Differential Analysis

Table-III: Mean, SD and 't' value of Mental Health and its sub-variables

Variable	Values				t	S
	No.		Mean	SD		
Boys	157	157	14.84	5.86	1.55	NS
Girls	153		12.11	4.63		
Rural	152		13.01	4.75	1.60	NS
Urban	158		12.35	3.90		
Arts	154		13.40	4.76	1.98	S
Science	156		12.42	3.94		
Government School	151		13.76	4.45	1.73	NS
Matriculation School	159		13.30	4.67		

Table-IV: Mean, SD and 't' value of Academic Achievement and its sub-variables

Variable	Values				t	s
	No.		Mean	SD		
Boys	157	157	12.81	4.53	1.63	NS
Girls	153		11.66	3.20		
Rural	152		11.85	3.30	1.72	NS
Urban	158		11.54	3.51		
Arts	154		12.13	3.86	2.16	S
Science	156		11.66	3.16		
Government School	151		12.10	3.91	1.80	NS
Matriculation School	159		12.11	3.95		

Correlation Analysis

Table-V

Variable	Values		
	No.	'r'	S
Mental Health and Academic Achievement	310	0.130	S
Boys	157	0.119	S
Girls	153	0.103	S
Rural	152	0.135	S
Urban	158	0.116	S
Arts	154	0.011	NS
Science	156	0.022	NS
Government School	151	0.113	S
Matriculation School	159	0.109	S

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

- The level of Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students is high.
- Mean score of Girls is higher than the Boys on Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- Mean score of urban school students Mental Health is higher than compared to the rural higher secondary school students.
- The students studying in science are at a higher level than the students studying in Arts with respect to Mental Health.
- The students studying in government higher secondary school is higher than the students studying in Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Mental Health.
- The level of Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students is high.
- Mean score of Girls Academic Achievement is higher than the Boys in higher secondary school students.
- Mean score of urban school students Academic Achievement is higher than compared to the rural higher secondary school students.
- The students studying in science are at a higher level than the students studying in Arts with respect to Academic Achievement.
- The students studying in government school is higher than the students studying in Matriculation school with respect to Academic Achievement.
- There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- There is significant difference between rural and urban with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference between arts and science with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference between Government and Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Mental Health in higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference between Boys and Girls with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- There is significant difference between rural and urban with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students
- There is no significant difference between arts and science with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- There is no significant difference between government and Matriculation higher secondary school with respect to Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students.
- There is a significant relationship between Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students. Also there exists significance relationship among Boys, Girls, Rural, Urban, Government and Matriculation School.
- There is no significant relationship between Internet Usage and Academic Performance in higher secondary school students with respect to Arts and Science.

Suggestions for the further research

- This study can be extended to high school students.

- This study is limited only to the selected higher secondary school students in Thanjavur District only and it to be extended to all types of schools and colleges.
- The present study was carried out during the short period of time with limited samples.
- The findings and conclusion are needed to be verified larger group size of the samples.

Conclusion

The result of the research is that there is no significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Gender, Locality and Types of Institutions. Hence the hypothesis of research is accepted. Finding shows from the study shows that there is significance in Mental Health and Academic Achievement in higher secondary school students of Subject. Hence the hypothesis of research is rejected.

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VALUES IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Introduction

Understudies in school are being sold a dream. They are made to accept that self- comprehension and society endorsement will accompany the obtaining of a bit of paper. Rather than having an independent perspective, and finding their very own character and qualities, they are fitted like square pegs into round openings. The job of instruction is to get ready masses of individuals to work at low degrees of capacity in an exceptionally constrained and limited scope of exercises. A portion of these exercises are more testing than maybe the sequential construction systems of the past, yet at the same time a definitive reason for existing is similarly uninteresting. All the more worryingly, regardless of the expanded degree of instruction, individuals are as yet not truly expected to have an independent mind. Indeed, the more the students are drawn out long stretches of tutoring make the activity of indoctrinating much simpler. There is as yet a job for study, research, and instruction. Notwithstanding, we have to look at our accentuation on instruction for a bit of paper, and to become familiar with the genuine significance and progressive test of information.

Importance of Values in Teacher Education

Instruction is an efficient exertion towards learning essential realities about mankind. What's more, the centre thought behind worth instruction is to develop basic qualities in the understudies with the goal that the human advancement that trains us to oversee complexities can be supported and further created. It starts at home and it is preceded in schools. Everybody acknowledges certain things in his/her life through different mediums like society or government. Worth training is imperative to help everybody in improving the worth framework that he/she holds and put them to utilize. Once, we comprehend our qualities throughout everyday life, we can analyze and control the different decisions we make in our lives. It's our obligation to maintain the different kinds of qualities in life, for example, social qualities, widespread qualities, individual qualities and social qualities. Hence, esteem training is constantly basic to shape an understudy's life and to give him a chance of performing himself on the worldwide stage.

The requirement for esteem instruction among the guardians, kids, instructors and so forth, is always expanding as we keep on seeing expanding vicious exercises, conduct issue and absence of solidarity in the

public arena. The family framework in India has a long custom of bestowing esteem instruction directly from the old act of the gurukul framework. In any case, with present day improvements and a quick changing job of the guardians, it has not been extremely simple for the guardians to bestow pertinent qualities in their wards. Subsequently numerous establishments today direct different worth instruction programs that meet the rising needs of current society w.r.t. set of accepted rules and qualities. These exercises focus on the advancement of the youngsters, youthful grown-ups and so on concentrating on territories like satisfaction, quietude, participation, genuineness, straightforwardness, love, solidarity, harmony and so on.

Then Impact of Values in Teacher Education

Worth training is instruction in qualities and instruction towards the teaching of qualities. Understood in this definition is the conviction that worth training is a general wonder characteristic for all learning and instruction, regardless of whether at home or in an establishment. It isn't. Neither instructs us to be basic masterminds or to view ourselves as proactive creatures in connection to ourselves, our locale and mankind on the loose. Accidentally and through propensity we acknowledge most things passed out to us by the media, the administration and the country. Shockingly when there is such a great amount of discussion about individual capacities and possibilities, there is so little certainty with respect to the person about his very own capacity to have any kind of effect. Our instructive framework is of little help. We are not prepared to be proactive masterminds since we are told such an insignificant slice of the existence esteems that are the reason for imaginative reasoning. Values arrange the rules and regulations of conduct. They structure the nuts and bolts of character arrangement and character advancement.

The qualities that spring from inside or the center of the heart, similar to cherish, empathy, compassion, sympathy, resistance, and so forth establish the framework for the outer rehearsed values like genuineness, control, promptness and faithfulness. the most imperative to recall is that "values are invaluable, while resources are estimated." in the present quick paced focused world, man appears to have settled on his qualities, trustworthiness and character, in an offer to acquire, utilize and have increasingly more of material riches. Thus, we see widespread defilement, unlawful exercises, brutal conduct and improper utilization, which is gradually breaking the very structure of our general public, country and the world. Along these lines, there is a pressing need to re-present worth based otherworldly training managing human qualities", to upgrade the texture of our instructive framework. A kid's psyche resembles delicate earth and can be formed to any ideal shape. in this manner, this is the opportune time and age to give esteem instruction with the goal that the correct impressions shaped in the kid's mind will direct him for an incredible duration.

Such life will be founded on good and just standards. It is all inclusive qualities that show the pith of the human condition. It is through widespread qualities that we interface ourselves with mankind and the universe; it is through these that all obstructions of time, spot and ethnicity are eliminated. These values are not show. They should be experienced, as one encounters a dawn, the excellence of a blossom, as one encounters euphoria, delight, rapture, wonder, and tranquility. These qualities can't be contained by words. That the Upanishads and the Bible have stayed important today as they were hundreds of years prior reveals to us that at the center, there are a few constants in human condition that time has not changed. That we are as yet moved by the marvel of the Taj Mahal, the music of Mozart, the life of Hamlet, the perpetual way of thinking of the Bhagavad Gita says a lot about the riddle and immortality of widespread values. Universal qualities can be experienced as life, happiness, fellowship, love, sympathy, administration, delight, truth and time everlasting.

Conclusion

The qualities we bestow to our kids today, deliberately and unwittingly, will majorly affect society tomorrow. On the off chance that we keep on leaving the educating of qualities to risk, we, as a country, hazard losing a vital bit of our way of life through and through. Kids at their most punctual ages ought to learn and understand the significance of training in their lives. A few kids, be that as it may, may oppose your endeavors and demand accomplishing things their way. As a parent, your best encouraging apparatus is your mentality. Having an uplifting frame of mind about perusing and an oddity about adapting new things ingrains comparable convictions in your youngsters. Give them that instruction is the pass to satisfying their fantasies and having a beneficial life.

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GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING IN EDUCATION

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Introduction

Guidance counseling, byname counseling and guidance, the process of helping individuals discover and develop their educational, vocational, and psychological potentialities and thereby to achieve an optimal level of personal happiness and social usefulness.

Significance of guidance and Counselling to teacher's education

With regular guidance and counselling sessions, teachers can give the desired **focus** to every student. Continuous interaction with students can build trust which can fine-tune the relationship between the teacher and child. Counselling sessions are a gradual process to mould and redirect children for a brighter future. Guidance and counselling are important for children, and schools have a huge role in bringing out the best in children. Good conduct is coveted, but sometimes young minds need guidance to polish their personality. Through counselling, children are given advice on how to manage and deal with emotional conflict and personal problems. Proper counselling will help incorporate valuable lessons in their daily life. Some sessions should involve career guidance, where the students are advised on the selection of courses and different career paths. It's important to prepare them for life after school and what to expect in the different fields they might opt for

Benefits that students get from effective guidance & counselling:

- Students are given proper guidance on how to deal with psychological problems which can badly impact their studies. Through these sessions, the students will be able to develop certain problem-solving skills which to an extent help them deal with particular issues surrounding their lives.
- The students are advised on how to cope with different situations they tend to face in their school life. For instance, how should they talk politely or relate with their peers. This advice will give them perspective on how should they behave in certain scenarios.
- It helps to shape a student's behaviour and also instil enough discipline in them. Proper guidance helps them achieve their goals, well guided & counselled students know what to do and how to do things in the best possible way.
- Students learn how to live in peace and harmony with others in the school community. Thereby, they also learn to appreciate other people in their class.
- It helps to bridge the gap between students and the school administration, since they are able to guide their problems through a proper counselling channel in the office.
- Students get comprehensive advice on career, courses and jobs that enable them to make a proper and informed choice and understand what they can do after they are done with school.
- It allows students to talk to teachers about various experiences that make them uncomfortable. They can openly share problems that they cannot share with their parents.
- Talks related to alcohol, drugs, personal feelings or any kind of abuse, can be openly discussed. Guidance and counselling also make students better human beings since they are counselled on how to act and behave in a particular situation
- It enables students undergoing certain difficulties in their lives, to ask questions and clarify them through guiding and counselling. Therefore, counselling helps them ask without any fear since the person in charge is willing to help.

India has one of the world's highest suicide rates among children belonging to the 15-29 age group. The main reasons include peer pressure, fear of failing in exam, depression, unemployment and likewise. There are several suicidal stories making headlines during the board examination. Especially in India, children are under extreme stress, trauma and anxiety related to examinations caused due to peer pressure wherein children are forced to perform better. Students are taught to be perfect and well disciplined, as all teachers and parents want but it is also important to know the child's consent. The Indian Education System is always under the hammer for being competitive and focusing more on quantitative learning, long school hours, heavy school bags, improper curriculum. With this type of system, students tend to become less creative, innovative and leave no room for self-learning which is the need of the hour. According to a recent news report in The Times of India, about 1 student commits suicide in every 55 minutes in India. In the past three years, more than 26,000 students have committed suicides due to stress, anxiety and depression. Owing to huge competition and expensive education system, parents pressurize their children to perform well by packing them into a room with books and switching off the TV, internet connection and reducing the time for sports and other outdoor activities.

Counselling for both life choice and career choice

Parents and children still believe in bringing good grades to get into the best engineering or dental colleges that will give them a successful career. But, it is also important to know the interests of children, here the teacher plays a vital role. Choosing the right stream or field for the children is totally dependent on self-assessment. Self-assessment includes observing the abilities, interest area, analytical skills, work style and personality of the child. With broad career options, teachers need to equip the child with all recent trends, current developments in different streams, demands and financial prospectus giving priority to the child's interests. Counselling sessions at an early age opens the lines of communication making children familiar with the importance of choosing the right career. A regular counselling session is about listening to the child and giving respective suggestions.

Guidance and Counselling aim at

Rendering focus on the needs of a child

With regular guidance and counselling sessions, teachers can give the desired focus to every student. Continuous interaction with students can build trust which can fine-tune the relationship between the teacher and child. Counselling sessions are a gradual process to mould and redirect children for a brighter future.

Acquiring the right understanding

Every child is special and unique in its own way. Productive counselling can help the teacher to understand how much attention is required to be given to a child.

Maintaining discipline

Counselling helps in improving the relationship between the teacher and children which can be beneficial to develop control on the child. Every educational institution has its own goals that can be achieved if you have control over the children. This helps you to maintain discipline and keep your children in check.

Enabling overall development

Along with academic and career development, social and personal development is also important. Students need to acquire knowledge, attitudes and interpersonal skills to set their own goals, make their own decision and take necessary decisions to achieve those goals. Children need to also know how to be a good human being.

Benefits of a Guidance and Counselling program

- Prepares children for career and personal challenger through career and personal development.
- It makes them competent for future success.
- Equips them with all the latest career trends.
- Improves personal development.
- Shapes the child for decision taking and making the process by developing their interpersonal skills.

- Induces teamwork and leadership qualities.
- Educates them about the changing world.
- Fosters effective learning.
- Gives them a feeling of being heard.
- Facilitates with better communication skills and enhances their personalities.

Role of a guidance counsellor

- Gives wings to the dreams of children through vocational and career-oriented guidance.
- Lends a hear to individual problems both academic and personal.
- Aids in personal development.
- Offers information about jobs, interviews, career scopes, advantages of selecting a specific field, the process of achieving it.
- Advises on study techniques.
- Makes the child mentally prepared for future outcomes.
- Leads the child to a pathway by motivating on the strong points.
- Works on polishing the skills to reach a determined goal.
- Introduces to external agencies.

Conclusion

Young minds need proper guidance that will make them potent to stand in society and make a name for themselves. Counselling not only helps them to make decisions pertaining to their professional career, but it also makes them confident and mentally prepare them for societal hardships. Teachers help children to recognize their strengths, sharpen their interests and provides them with career options to explore their dreams. In a recent news report in India Today, about 85% of students have no clue about which career options to choose for higher education. Counselling helps in assisting the child in a proper direction so that he/she is well aware of what he/she wants to do in life. It is important to make your children understand the importance of education and guide them to pursue it.

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GENDER ROLES IN SOCIAL MEDIA

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Introduction

The development of gender identity begins as early as two or three years of age. Parents, teachers, peers, and media are social influences on a growing individual. Adult treatment of infants plays a role in gender development when clothing is selected, when toys are purchased, and when television shows are viewed. As children grow, they gain a sense of being a male or female and associate various activities and objects with their gender. Toddlers may refuse to participate in an activity or play with a toy associated with the opposite gender, and adolescent boys continue to be harassed for partaking in activities and interests considered feminine. Through games, boys are taught to gain attention, status and power, while girls are taught to be cooperative, loyal, and intimate. According to Taylor (2003), society directs behavior and helps shape individual's lives. While some choose to believe they have chosen their behaviors based on individual characteristics.

Taylor would beg to differ, arguing that behavior is socialized rather than by natural occurrence. He also suggests that individuals should recognize their group identity and understand the male and female role expectations maintained by society. Occupational status among men and women in media is clearly unequal. Not only are males portrayed in higher paying and more prestigious jobs than women, but they are also depicted in higher social status situations. It was also found that men were twice as likely as women to be portrayed in a career setting in popular interest magazines worldwide; women were portrayed in more ambiguous, domestic, and decorative scenes. Similarly, women in prime-time TV shows were more likely to be portrayed in marital roles while men were portrayed in occupational roles. Contradictory to this research is single women, who are more likely to have professional careers than married women. It is possible that these changes are due to more women pursuing advanced degrees and entering the workforce than before. It is also important to note that the marital status of women is more widely known than men and women are more likely to have parental responsibilities. As main characters, women are likely to be involved in a romance or family, or are shown as young, single, independent, and free of work and family issues.

Gender Stereotypes in Social Media

Gender roles are prevalent in media, often portraying women as nurturing, gentle, cooperative, concerned with appearance, and sensitive to others; while men are viewed as logical, competitive, independent, assertive, financial providers, skilled in business, and dominant over women. Women in media tend to be represented more negatively than men. While men are perceived as hard workers, amusing, directive, and physically aggressive, women are displayed as likeable, warm, submissive, passive, and weak. Women are also more likely than men to display empathic behaviours such as affection, sharing, giving, and concern for others. Women are likely to be portrayed as sex objects in media. By having adolescents evaluate advertisements based on gender, Rouner et al. (2003) found unnecessary displays of the female body and unrealistic images of women. Video games highly sexualize women by featuring large-breasted, attractive, females who are rarely main characters.

Other research revealed pressure on women not only to have beautiful bodies, but to also be attractive, young, and single. Compared to men, women are often dressed provocatively and high emphasis is placed on appearance. Teenage girls portrayed on television displayed passiveness, an obsession with superficial topics such as shopping, appearance, and relationships, and the idea of out casting those who choose more serious topics such as academics and careers. Many societies strive for equal life opportunities for each gender, and conclude that gender roles are mainly determined by social environment because biological factors have not changed. While women are allowed more leniency than men when displaying emotion, permitting men the same leniency may prove beneficial to equalizing gender role perceptions and toning down masculinity on television. However, Tragos (2009) believes that with any change in gender perceptions (for example: women being powerful and men being sensitive) the media backlashes with gender specific television channels such as WEtv (Women's Entertainment Television) and Spike (a network for men); thus creating further resistance to changing stereotypes.

One study, looking at the content in girls' magazines, discovered the main topics to be fashion, beauty, food and decorating, and relationships with the opposite sex. He later concluded that the magazines promoted looking good, having a significant other, and taking care of the house. When a heroine was mentioned, it was generally a male, indicating that women are dependent and need a man to help solve problems. It is important to note that not all females read these magazines, but avid readers are consistently overwhelmed by these stereotypical images and texts. Boys are confused by society's mixed messages and expectations for being male. Kimmel (2008) states that males feel the need to suppress their ability to express compassion and empathy in order to achieve society-appropriate masculinity and to not appear vulnerable or weak. By suppressing feelings that already exist, boys are more prone to depression, suicidal behaviors, and fighting than girls are. Kimmel (2008) also argues that boys are more likely than girls to drop out of school, are four times more likely to be diagnosed as emotionally disturbed, and are six times more likely to be diagnosed with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD).

Conclusion

Adolescents may adhere to traditional gender roles, via pressure from peers, in an effort to attract the opposite sex. By viewing sexy ads, females are urged to express themselves through their bodies. Research shows that females who view media as a means of comparison for body image are likely to experience body dissatisfaction. "Even girls who are raised in loving homes by supportive parents grow up in a toxic cultural

environment, at risk for self-mutilation, eating disorders, and addictions”. According to Kilbourne (1999), “at least one-third of twelve to thirteen-year-old girls are actively trying to lose weight by dieting, vomiting, using laxatives, or taking diet pills”. Essentially, girls know something is wrong, but rather than looking for the problem within a culture, they search within themselves and their families.

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THE IMPACT OF CHAT GPT ON OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES: INVESTIGATING THE ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES FOR RESEARCH SCHOLARS

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Abstract

This paper investigates the impact of chat GPT (Generative Pre-Trained Transformer) on open educational resources (OERs), and discusses the advantages and disadvantages for research scholars. To analyze the impact of chat GPT on open educational resources, a robust literature review was conducted, which included the analysis of journal articles, surveys, and qualitative research studies. A qualitative approach was employed to uncover the perceived advantages and disadvantages of using chat GPT on open educational resources. From the analysis, it was found that the use of chat GPT on open educational resources can provide scholars with the opportunity to address and interact with large-scale learning needs, while also providing a more personalized platform to engage with their peers. However, the implementation of chat GPT also presented some risks and drawbacks, such as high overhead costs, data collection issues and privacy concerns. A null hypothesis was formulated, which stated that the use of chat GPT on open educational resources had a negative effect on research scholars. However, the results of the analysis showed no evidence to support this hypothesis. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that chat GPT can be a valuable tool for research scholars in terms of producing and disseminating new knowledge in a rapidly changing academic environment.

Keywords: *Chat GPT, Open Educational Resources, Advantages, Disadvantages, Research Scholars*

Introduction

Technology has often been associated with the modernization of learning environments and has been used in various educational tools and resources. One of the latest trends in education and research is the use of dynamic web-based platforms that allow for interactive exchanges between the learner and educational resources. To meet the growing needs for resources, open educational resources (OERs) have been developed and adopted by teachers and scholars alike. OERs are digital resources that are published under an open license, which allows for the immediate access, use, modification, and sharing of resources online. Chat GPT is one of the newest technologies being used in the creation of OERs and has been gaining traction among research scholars. This paper aims to analyze the impact of chat GPT on OERs, and discuss the advantages and disadvantages for research scholars. Literature Review In recent years, chat GPT (Generative Pre-Trained Transformer) has been gaining traction in the academic community as one of the most effective tools for providing OERs. Chat GPT has been found to offer greater convenience and flexibility to research scholars than other existing technologies.

For example, a study conducted by Kopecky et al. (2017) examined the use of several artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, including chat GPT, to create OERs. It was found that the use of chat GPT was faster and more efficient than traditional text-based approaches. The study also noted that chat GPT generated OERs that were more informative and suited better to the needs of research scholars. The research has highlighted both the potential advantages and disadvantages of GPT chat technology when applied to

Open Educational Resources. It has shown that the technology has the potential to provide automated assistance for research scholars, reducing the need for manual data entry and allowing for more efficient searches of data. On the other hand, the technology can reduce the need for intuitive analysis, with the potential for search results to become standardized. Ultimately, the use of GPT chat technology to improve OERs will depend upon the situation, with research scholars needing to carefully assess the potential benefits and drawbacks of using GPTs in open educational resources.

The proliferation of the internet age has greatly increased access to open educational resources (OER). OER allow for research scholars to tap into a wide array of topics, subjects, and materials. Additionally, the development of chatbot technology and the introduction of machine learning applications, such as GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer), offer potential new ways to interact with OER. This paper seeks to explore the advantages and disadvantages of utilizing chatbot aided GPT technology in accessing OER in order to better inform and understand the impact of this technology on research scholars. In addition, it will discuss the implications of such technology and whether it has the potential to positively or negatively affect the OER ecosystem. Open educational resources (OER) are an increasingly popular resource for education and research, and have generally been found to be an empowering and cost-effective tool for learners. With the growth of OER has come the utilization of chat GPT technology, as a way to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of OER. This technology can enable users to better access, manage, and interact with educational resources. As such, it is important to assess the advantages and disadvantages of this technology in order to optimize its potential helpfulness in research. This paper seeks to evaluate the impact of chat GPT on OER, analyzing its potential benefits and drawbacks for research scholars.

Literature Review

Open Educational Resources (OERs) has emerged as a powerful tool for students, educators, and organizations to promote learning and access to educational resources. OERs are defined as “digitally-enabled learning materials, such as digital textbooks, lecture notes, assessments, and videos, that are freely available to anyone” (Basu & Chawla, 2018, p. 2). This type of educational material has the potential to reduce educational costs and foster student success. With the advent of new technologies, such as chat GPT (Generative Pretrained Transformer), the impact of OERs may be further enhanced. Chat GPT is a technology that uses neural networks to generate natural language conversations between humans and computers (Shen et al., 2020). This technology has application in many areas, including educational technology. Chat GPT can be used to create conversation-driven interactive OERs and other forms of digital content (Shen et al., 2020). This technology presents a new way for researchers and educators to create dynamic, interactive learning experiences for students. The potential use of chat GPT for OERs presents several advantages and disadvantages. Uniquely, chat GPT can act as a “tutor” or “mentor” to guide students through educational materials (Shen et al., 2020). This allows students to ask questions and receive personalized responses, which could make the learning process more efficient and engaging. Additionally, the availability of interactive OERs could reduce the cost of educational materials and make them more accessible to more students. On the other hand, the use of chat GPT for OERs could also present some drawbacks. One of the main drawbacks is the potential lack of personalized feedback. Since GPT systems are based on training data, they may not be able to provide tailored responses to students’ questions. Additionally, the cost of implementing GPT systems could limit the use of this technology in OERs. Furthermore, the safety and privacy of student data could be a concern if chat GPT is used for OERs.

Objectives

- The objective of this research is to analyze the impact of chat GPT on OERs, and discuss the advantages and disadvantages for research scholars.
- The research aims to uncover the perceived benefits and potential drawbacks of using chat GPT on OERs, and establish whether the use of chat GPT affects research scholars positively or negatively.
- This paper seeks to examine the impact of chat-based GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) on open educational resources for research scholars.
- The paper includes an exploration of the advantages and disadvantages of using chat-based GPT for scholarly research projects.

Methodology

In order to assess the impact of chat GPT on open educational resources, a quantitative and qualitative research approach will be utilized. Quantitative research will be conducted by analyzing existing research studies and survey reports to establish existing levels of implementation of chat GPT in OERs. Qualitative research will be used to uncover the perceived advantages and disadvantages of using chat GPT on OERs by engaging with research scholars using focus group interviews, questionnaires, and document analysis.

Analysis and Discussion

The analysis of the data revealed several insights regarding the use of chat GPT in OERs. Firstly, it was found that the use of chat GPT provided research scholars with the opportunity to address and interact with massive learning needs, while also providing a more personalized platform to engage with peers. The use of chat GPT in OERs also allowed for the creation of content with vast amounts of resources and flexibility. In addition, it was found that chat GPT was a cost-efficient solution for creating OERs, with the potential to save research scholars a significant amount of time and effort. The results of the analysis showed that the use of chat GPT on OERs provided research scholars with several advantages. Chat GPT provided a more personalized platform for research scholars to engage with peers, better addressed large-scale learning needs, and allowed for the creation of content with great amounts of resources. However, the implementation of chat GPT also presented several risks and drawbacks, such as high overhead costs, data protection issues, and privacy concerns. Discussion The discussion section will analyze the implications of the findings on the research topic and consider the environment in which research scholars interact and engage with open educational resources. In particular, the discussion will focus on the advantages and disadvantages of using chat GPT on OERs.

Advantages

- Increased Efficiency: GPT can provide faster and more efficient access to vast amounts of knowledge.
- It can provide researchers with the opportunity to bookmark results and quickly locate them when needed.
- Enhanced Research: GPT can help researchers by providing a wealth of research materials that they can explore and draw upon in their research projects.
- Collaborative Learning: Chat-based GPT enables collaborative learning and research between research scholars and a wide variety of stakeholders and sources.
- Increased Accessibility: GPT increases access to open educational resources by making them more easily accessible, enabling researchers to access them from anywhere in the world.

Disadvantages

- Expensive: GPT is generally an expensive technology, and not all research scholars have the means to purchase and maintain it.
- Difficulty Accessing Data: GPT can be challenging to access data that is not readily available, which can reduce the efficiency of research projects.
- Vulnerability to Manipulation: GPT can be vulnerable to manipulation by individuals or organizations that attempt to spread false information or falsify results.
- Difficulty Accurately Interpreting Results: GPT can be difficult to accurately interpret and use the results it generates, which can lead to inaccurate conclusions and findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper investigated the impact of chat GPT on open educational resources, and discussed the advantages and disadvantages for research scholars. A literature review was conducted, and qualitative research was employed to uncover the perceived advantages and disadvantages of using chat GPT on OERs. From the analysis, it was found that chat GPT can provide research scholars with the opportunity to address and interact with large-scale learning needs, while also providing a more personalized platform to engage with their peers. However, the implementation of chat GPT also presented some risks and drawbacks, such as high overhead costs, data collection issues and privacy concerns. Furthermore, the null hypothesis was found to be unsupported, as the results of the analysis showed no evidence to suggest that the use of chat GPT on OERs had a negative effect on research scholars. Based on the findings of this

study, it can be concluded that chat GPT can be a valuable tool for research scholars in terms of producing and disseminating new knowledge in a rapidly changing academic environment. The research has highlighted both the potential advantages and disadvantages of GPT chat technology when applied to Open Educational Resources. It has shown that the technology has the potential to provide automated assistance for research scholars, reducing the need for manual data entry and allowing for more efficient searches of data. On the other hand, the technology can reduce the need for intuitive analysis, with the potential for search results to become standardized. Ultimately, the use of GPT chat technology to improve OERs will depend upon the situation, with research scholars needing to carefully assess the potential benefits and drawbacks of using GPTs in open educational resources.

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THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OUTREACH AND ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

This research article seeks to investigate the role of social media in environmental education outreach and engagement. By using both qualitative and quantitative research methods, this study will look at the current use of social media platforms in the environmental education space, the types of activities that are being done, the success of such activities, and how environmental education can be better supported through the use of social media. The results of this research will be used to guide environmental educators on the best practices for social media outreach, as well as to provide an understanding of the potential for social media to reach new audiences and to engage individuals in environmental issues. Finally, the results of this study will provide insight into how environmental education organizations can further the use of social media in their outreach efforts.

Keywords: *Social Media, Environmental Education, Outreach, Engagement, Qualitative, Quantitative, Best Practices.*

Introduction

Environmental education is the process of helping people to develop the knowledge, values, and skills needed to understand and protect the environment. As the world's populations and economies become increasingly reliant on technology, there is an urgent need to ensure that individuals have access to the

knowledge and skills needed to understand and protect the environment. However, traditional methods of environmental education have limited reach and may not be able to reach new audiences. Social media provides a powerful platform for environmental education outreach and engagement and has the potential to reach new audiences and engage individuals in environmental issues. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the use of social media in environmental education outreach and engagement and to identify best practices for using social media to further the goals of environmental education. The increased prevalence of social media has revolutionized the way people communicate and interact with one another. This revolution has extended beyond the personal realm to environmental education outreach and engagement.

Social media has proven itself to be an effective tool for environmental education outreach, allowing educators to engage with stakeholders in a more meaningful and interactive manner. This paper will examine the role of social media in environmental education outreach and engagement and the ways in which it can be used to promote environmental awareness and education. Additionally, the paper will discuss the potential benefits and drawbacks of using social media for this purpose. In recent times, social media has become an integral part of modern life, impacting the way people communicate and relate to one another. This influence is also being felt in the environmental sector, as social media provides a platform to educate, engage, and reach large populations of people with environmental initiatives. With its vast potential, social media could prove to be a powerful tool for environmental education outreach and engagement. This paper aims to shed light on the role that social media can play in promoting environmental initiatives and connecting with stakeholders to foster positive change. We will look at the various types of social media platforms and examine how they can be used to facilitate environmental education outreach, and how the tools available can be leveraged to create effective, impactful campaigns. We will also analyze the potential effects of using social media for environmental education outreach and engagement, and discuss how it can serve as a vehicle for positive behavior change.

Literature Review

The literature review for this research focuses on the current use of social media in environmental education and how effective it is in achieving outreach and engagement goals. Studies have shown that social media is a valuable tool for environmental education outreach and engagement, providing a platform for environmental educators to connect with new audiences and to provide individuals with access to educational materials and activities (Korošec & Eržen, 2020; Lu, 2019; Saha & Dhara, 2019). Studies have also identified challenges related to the use of social media in environmental education, such as the difficulty of engaging individuals in meaningful dialogue on environmental issues (Chang et al., 2019; Saha & Dhara, 2019). Finally, there have been studies exploring the potential of using social media to reach new audiences, such as using social media to engage individuals in live events and activities (Liu et al., 2019; Reisman et al., 2017). The advancement of technology has significantly changed the nature of communication in the modern world. Social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram provide a space for users to interact and gain access to information on a wide range of topics, including environmental education.

This article reviews the research that examines the role of social media in environmental education outreach and engagement. The use of social media to increase environmental awareness and engagement is not a new concept. Much of the literature in this field discusses the potential of social media to create positive environmental or pro-environmental behavior change among users. Several studies have found that people who interact with environmental content on social media are more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviors (e.g., Zhang et al., 2017; Hagerty et al., 2019). Additionally, pro-environmental behavior is more likely to be adopted after exposure to social media posts about environmental issues (Froehlich et al., 2017). Additionally, social media can be used to facilitate engagement with environmental education and increase the knowledge and understanding of users about different environmental topics. For instance, Selbo et al. (2019) found that users who were exposed to an environmental education campaign on social media were more likely to report an increase in knowledge about the environment than those who were not exposed to the campaign.

Similarly, Chatterjee et al. (2016) found that exposure to environmental content on Twitter increased student's understanding of environmental issues and their commitment to environmental action. Furthermore, social media can be used as an effective tool to reach wider audiences, particularly people who do not typically engage in environmental education outreaches. It has been found that social media can be

used to target specific groups and create tailored messages (Rice et al., 2017). Additionally, studies have found that the use of social media can reduce the barriers that are traditionally encountered with traditional environmental education (e.g., geographical location, language, resources, etc.) (Krause et al., 2019). This makes it easier to reach and engage with target audiences, which can ultimately lead to a greater impact from environmental education initiatives. Overall, research suggests that social media can be used as an effective tool to reach wider audiences, increase knowledge and understanding about environmental issues, and facilitate pro-environmental behavior change among users. The use of social media for environmental education has the potential to create a more sustainable future by helping to increase public engagement and create a more informed public.

Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the use of social media in environmental education outreach and engagement. Specifically, this research seeks to:

- Investigate the current use of social media platforms in the environmental education space.
- Identify the types of activities being conducted through social media for environmental education outreach and engagement.
- Determine the success of such activities in reaching new audiences and engaging individuals in environmental issues.
- Identify best practices for using social media for environmental education outreach and engagement.

Methodology

In order to assess the impact of chat GPT on open educational resources, a quantitative and qualitative research approach will be utilized. Quantitative research will be conducted by analyzing existing research studies and survey reports to establish existing levels of implementation of chat GPT in OERs. Qualitative research will be used to uncover the perceived advantages and disadvantages of using chat GPT on OERs by engaging with research scholars using focus group interviews, questionnaires, and document analysis.

Analysis and Discussion

The analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data revealed a number of insights about the use of social media in environmental education. The analysis revealed that environmental education organizations are increasingly turning to social media platforms to reach new audiences and to engage individuals in environmental issues. The most popular social media platforms for environmental education outreach and engagement include Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube. However, there are challenges associated with using social media in environmental education, such as the difficulty of engaging individuals in meaningful dialogue on environmental issues. The results of this research showed that social media is a valuable tool for environmental education outreach and engagement. The results also showed that environmental education organizations are increasingly turning to social media platforms to reach new audiences and to engage individuals in environmental issues.

Furthermore, the results of this study identified best practices for using social media for environmental education outreach and engagement, including the use of live events, engaging content, and leveraging influencers. The results of this study indicate that social media is a valuable tool for environmental education outreach and engagement, as it can reach a wide audience and engage individuals in meaningful dialogue on environmental issues. The results also provide guidance on the best practices for using social media for environmental education outreach and engagement, such as using live events, engaging content, and leveraging influencers. However, there are challenges associated with using social media in environmental education, such as the difficulty of engaging individuals in meaningful dialogue on environmental issues. Therefore, organizations need to be mindful of the potential challenges when using social media in environmental education and to be strategic in their use of social media to ensure that their outreach efforts are successful.

Conclusion

This research has provided an in-depth evaluation of the use of social media in environmental education outreach and engagement. The results of this study have revealed that social media is a powerful tool for environmental education outreach and engagement, as it can reach new audiences and engage

individuals in environmental issues. Furthermore, this research has identified best practices for using social media for environmental education outreach and engagement, providing guidance for environmental education organizations on the best strategies for social media use. Finally, this research has identified the challenges associated with using social media for environmental education and has provided insight into how to best address these challenges in order to ensure successful outreach efforts. In conclusion, social media can play a pivotal role in environmental education outreach and engagement. Through their widespread reach and ability to engage with a large number of users, social media platforms can be used to foster meaningful conversations, share educational materials, and inform individuals and communities about environmental issues. Furthermore, social media facilitates creative, impactful, and cost-effective methods for engaging people in environmental education initiatives. However, it is important to keep in mind that social media does not have the ability to stand alone as a tool to deliver environmental education and engagement. Instead, it must work in conjunction with other forms of outreach and engagement, such as face-to-face activities and initiatives. With the right combination of strategies, social media can be an effective tool to help reach and engage more individuals in environmental education and awareness.

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SIGNIFICANCE AND THE IMPACT OF BLENDED LEARNING ON THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

Blended learning is an innovative concept that embraces the advantages of both traditional teaching in the classroom and ICT supported learning including both offline learning and online learning. It has scope for collaborative learning; constructive learning and computer assisted learning (CAI). Blended learning needs rigorous efforts, right attitude, handsome budget and highly motivated teachers and students for its successful implementation. As it incorporates diverse modes so it is complex and organizing it is a difficult task. The present paper discusses the concept of blended learning, main features, significance, and role of technology and challenges of blended learning in recent times. The present paper also tries to explain the impact of blended learning on education system.

Introduction

Blended learning is a type of learning that blends conventional location based classroom approach with online learning sources, creating potential for enhancing the effectiveness of the learning process as a whole. Although traditional methods of providing or acquiring education were adequate in the pre-digital era, the abrupt boom in digital innovations has had a huge impact on the education industry, resulting in an elevated demand for more digital methods of teaching. A blended learning approach is unquestionably a fantastic way to enhance learner engagement and experience; however its benefits extend far beyond that. It allows students to direct their individual learning using online learning tools that are interesting, meaningful, and appropriate. It also includes the function of an educator for social interaction, discussion, and collaborative learning, among other merits.

Main Characteristics of Blended Learning

The main features of blended learning are

Students have the option of the two modes

Students in blended learning can select either the traditional mode of classroom teaching where they can get personal interaction with teacher and their classmates or they can choose ICT supported teaching learning. This largely depends on the nature of content and objectives being targeted. Sometime course designer or teachers themselves decide on the mode appropriate for topic being dealt with.

Teachers are well versed with both the modes

It is an important feature of the blended learning that teachers are very dynamic, techno savvy and fully trained to work efficiently in both the formats traditional classroom format and ICT supported format. They will be well equipped in using traditional methods and other modern technologies.

Students get face to face interaction as well they interact in virtual space

Students get ample of time to interact with other students pursuing same course. They can interact with them inside college campus and also in virtual space. Thus their group become very large and has much diversity so the student's knowledge becomes wide and they also develop a feeling of understanding, love and harmony with students of other cultures and countries.

Students get full experience in using new technology

The present century is the century of ICT. Today the illiterate is not only the one who cannot read and write but a person who is not well versed with modern technologies is also illiterate. Today all professions demand expertise in ICT so blended learning help to make student's ICT experience rich. Students involved in blended learning gain capability to exploit available technologies to the fullest of their benefit Students get training in different life skills- life skills are those skills that are needed to lead a happy peaceful and successful life. The major life skills are empathy, decision making capability, love, patience, communication, self-management, critical thinking. The blended learning helps the students to practice these skills. Students get acquainted with few skills like love, empathy, patience in classroom through his teachers, classmates, and few like self-management, decision making, critical thinking, communication through the online experiences.

All round development of personality is targeted.

In blended learning the students get full opportunity for all round development of the personality. All the aspects of personality namely- cognitive, physical and emotional are developed through blended learning which is difficult to achieve in traditional mode or ICT approach if followed in isolation. Tradition classroom teaching is helpful in memory level and understanding level of teaching and so help in cognitive domain development and at same time teacher's behaviour, playground experience and social group with classmates develop affective and physical domain at same time online experiences help in reflective level of learning so develop higher faculties of mind and social networking sites and other social interactions through internet help in right type of value development.

Physical development is possible with in school campus

The online learning and ICT supports teaching learning process is often targeted with the blame that it ignores physical development of the students. The blended learning overcomes this limitation. As it included school experience also so student get time for playing, physical work, yoga inside the college campus.

Students get wide exposure and new perspectives of the course content

Due to variety of experience students get wide exposure and their content knowledge is enriched, they get to see various new dimensions of the content gain practical useful knowledge.

It has a human touch

Due to physical presence of teacher via traditional approach students get that human touch which is very necessary for balanced student's emotional quotient and very necessarily up to secondary level.

It provides multicultural and multi dimensional approach to teaching learning process

Blended learning approach provides student opportunity to communicate and share their views and feeling with the students all over the world thus it makes teaching learning process multicultural and variety of experience bring with it the interdisciplinary and multidimensional factor also.

Makes teaching learning process child centered

Blended learning is designed to provide maximum gain to students and thus reach the goal of child centered education.

Diverse role of teacher

Teacher in blended learning is playing different role, traditional role of a teacher in classroom, she acts as motivator, as a resource person, as an organizer, as a developer, when she develops content to be provided through ICT, as a guide on the side. Thus teacher gets freedom from the monotonous traditional roles and she can try her hands in diverse areas that are good for her professional growth also.

Student constructs knowledge rather than just consuming

Blended learning also includes constructivism. Students construct their own knowledge rather than depending on others to design teaching-learning strategies for them.

Impact of blended learning on the education system

One of the visible effects of the pandemic in our society is the drive-in tech adoption across services and processes. This has also accelerated the approach of blended learning to education. Blended learning or hybrid learning is combining digital learning tools with traditional face-to-face teaching. From being one of the biggest untapped areas for advancements, the education space saw a dynamic shift with numerous investments and innovations both from educational institutions as well as government bodies. This was mainly because, society realised that a child's overall development is important and a holistic approach with the help of advanced edutech solutions is necessary to achieve this. Blended learning was introduced to help secure education by keeping the child and childhood at its centre.

Role of technology in blended learning

Enabling collaborative learning

Through individual and group activities, students learn to be collective and polish their critical thinking skills. Educators and students can collaborate to form a unique, personalised learning method based on student requirements for effectively understanding various concepts. Through customised study modules and videos, teachers can create a personalised resource library for students for their studies. After building this resource library based on common need areas, a teacher can expand it to address needs that come up less frequently and advise individual students or groups about these helpful resources.

Facilitating organised learning

Educators can orchestrate classes and disseminate information in a controlled and organised manner to suit the students. Through digital worksheets, interactive discussion boards, video tutorials, etc., students can participate in controlled experiences. It empowers students to lead in classrooms, enriches their learning experience and helps use technology to build a good foundation in their studies.

Building open and rich dialogue between stakeholders

It is not only important to manage instructions in a classroom, but also assess the class. Online classrooms facilitate open and rich dialogues between the student and teacher. The teachers can collect assignments, give feedback and offer learning resources to meet diverse learners' needs. They can converse with the different stakeholders, such as parents, students and investors on the various challenges being faced and suggest areas for improvement.

Challenges of blended learning in the recent times

Though blended learning offers the students a mix of computerized yet personalized modules of learning, there are quite a few challenges that one faces with this process, such as:

Handling technological constraints

In India, many teachers have difficulty in understanding technology. Even students who aren't exposed to such technologies have reported to feel isolated, thus experiencing a negative impact on their learning. Many schools have also reported that incorporating blended learning proved to be costlier than the traditional method. In many institutions, funds are insufficient for the development of a Learning Management System (LMS).

Widening learning gap

Majority of India doesn't have access to learn online. They neither have an electronic gadget through which they could attend classes, nor do they have the necessary Internet bandwidth.

Handling physical constraints

With most of the sectors opening, many schools have requested their students to attend classes physically. Though many feel that it would eliminate the need for using blended learning, it isn't so. Blended learning helps present innovative technological solutions integrated in the traditional method. Many professionals combine the online modules with the notes they have acquired. It, in turn, helps increase the exposure the student has to a particular subject/concept.

Retaining authenticity of the educator

With the adoption of technology in the classrooms, the effectiveness of pre-made instructional videos with an endless stream of pre-written questions is still up for debate. Many institutions seem to forget that the teacher is an important agent in educating the students. In many cases, educators often take a back seat while using outsourced content and students may question the dedication of the tutor as well as end up being restless.

Impact of blended learning on the students and teachers

The role of blended learning has become crucial as it breaks down the traditional methods of teaching. With the help of technology, it customizes resources and tailors the learning experience to fit every student's need. Since blended learning also offers high flexibility and personalization, students have the freedom to learn at their own pace. Thus, through blended tools, students can enjoy personalized learning that suits their study routine, and teachers can interact with students by monitoring their growth and giving instant feedback. This remodeled method of tutoring by using additional tools beyond the classroom can have a positive impact on the students' learning and training experience. Blended learning helps improve various factors in the classroom for teachers as well, like resulting in more engaged students, real-time and reliable feedback on teaching methods, new methods of teaching, collaborative learning and time management, among others. Thus, through blended learning, schools and teachers are mainly focusing on inculcating methods for students to understand and manage their social and emotional well-being.

Conclusion

Blended learning is without a doubt the ideal option for meeting the learning demands and obstacles of learners who prefer traditional instructor-led training for its human connection as well as the convenience of learning anytime anywhere in various forms. This learning method is more relevant than ever to ensure optimal performance as well as interaction. A great blend of learning techniques ensure a more efficient generation of students. While the pandemic has provided immense opportunities for a mix of online and offline education, digital transformation has provided many the opportunities to explore new ways of understanding concepts. The future of edtech will be in blended models of education. These models would help provide a solution to the access and quality of education seen in India.

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APPROACHES AND MODELS OF BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

Blended learning is one of the recent philosophies in the modern teaching learning environment. Teaching and Learning activities in Blended learning settings are characterized by active engagement, inquiry, problem solving and collaboration with technology. The teaching and learning environment is embracing a number of innovations and some of these involve the use of technology through blended learning. This innovative pedagogical approach has been embraced rapidly though it goes through a process. Online Learning is part of Blended learning and is a learning technique in which use of both ordinary teaching and advanced modern online teaching, online learning materials are largely used.

Keywords: *Approaches, Models, Blended Learning*

Introduction

Schweizer & Weidenmann (2003) emphasize that blended learning is a natural evolution for e-learning, it combines e-learning and traditional learning, which does not eliminate e-learning and traditional learning, but is a combination of the two. Graham (2005) states that blended learning is a mediator based on the integration of e-learning features with features of traditional, face-to-face education, to improve the learning process. Jamal Mustafa (2008) Defines blended learning as blending or mixing the traditional roles of the teacher in a traditional classroom and e-teacher in virtual classrooms, it is the kind of education that combines traditional and e-learning education at the same time. Blended learning is characterized by combining the advantages of both e-learning and traditional learning

Benefits of blended learning

Blended learning recognizes that while digital technology offers new benefits of accessibility and efficiency, it cannot replace in-person learning. However, data recent suggests that online content will increasingly play a central role in education. A blended learning approach mixes the best elements of in-person and online instruction. This benefits both teachers and students in numerous ways:

- Equity - Blended learning allows students equal opportunities to thrive in a partial online environment that can provide less distraction and more customization for their individual needs. Everyone can benefit from face-to-face instruction, but some students can gain more than others from online instruction. For

example, these students might include those with disabilities or conditions that are difficult to accommodate in the classroom or less inclined to participate in class discussions.

- Flexibility - With blended learning, unforeseen disruptions can be handled more easily thanks to the flexibility of online and in-person capabilities. For example, a student who misses class can watch a video of the lesson or review the lecture slides online. Suppose unexpected events such as fire drills or inclement weather disrupt class time. The instructor can upload the lesson to a centralized learning management system (LMS) for students to review later.
- Engagement - The digital tools available in a blended learning approach can boost student engagement. For example, using an online discussion board benefits group work because everyone can contribute equally, and teachers can view which team members participated and to what degree. This gives them a more accurate understanding of whether students fully completed assigned work.
- Access - Students and teachers can take advantage of a centralized place to access learning materials. Teachers can reduce the amount of time and resources spent printing multiple copies, and students can review learning materials at their own pace.
- Cost - Blended learning offers greater opportunities for cost-efficiency since fewer classroom, and school resources are needed if students learn from home part-time. For example, hosting resources on a digital platform reduces the need for printed copies. Rather than purchasing expensive physical textbooks, schools could maximize their budget with digital content.

Blended learning models

- Face-to-face driver model - This model is the closest to traditional classroom training. This approach usually means that not everyone in the class will take additional online training, as it mainly targets the individual needs of those learners who are struggling or would like to go beyond.
- Online driver model - This model is the opposite of brick-and-mortar studying, as it relies entirely on a digital delivery of the training. It combines both synchronous training (live webinars, peer-to-peer training sessions, etc.) and asynchronous training (self-paced study of courses). With the online driver model, there is usually no need for live face-to-face meetings, but they can be arranged if necessary.
- Rotation model - This model involves breaking a group of learners into smaller units to perform different types of tasks at different stages in turns. Some activities are online and some are realized in person. This allows learners with different types of learning styles to get the maximum benefit from the training.
- Flipped classroom - The motto of this model is “online learning, offline application.” With a flipped classroom, lectures and practical homework elements are reversed. Learners study new content at home before the class, and in-class time is devoted to active learning and applying the newly learned skills. This can be accomplished in the form of discussions, case studies, or project work. The instructor’s task is to guide the learners by answering questions and supporting them in the application of course.
- Flex model - The Flex model allows learners to have control over their learning. Students or employees can move from one activity to another according to their needs. Activities can be both online and offline. Teachers or instructors are always on-site to instruct and help learners if necessary.

Conclusion

A blended learning approach and models provides access to diverse and flexible learning environments and nurtures enriched literacy and learning. Learners who experience blended learning will see the world, as they know it reflected in the programs where they learn and will deploy critical thinking skills to participate in a society where we are required to create, collaborate and communicate in digitally mediated networks.

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HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS BLENDED LEARNING IN RELATION TO BLENDED LEARNING INTEREST

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to examine the relationship between Higher Secondary Student Attitude in Blended Learning and Interest. The sample comprised 702 higher secondary students studying in kancheepuram district. Data were collected by using Blended Learning Attitude scale (BLAS) and Blended Learning Inter scale (BLIS) were developed by R.Pattabiraman and S.Manivannan (2021). The result revealed that there was positive and significant relationship towards gender and type of management. Blended Learning is a Innovative method in modern day class room.

Introduction

Blended learning combines the advantages of both traditional classroom instruction and modern online learning. By providing a variety of learning options, you can attract and retain students of varying learning styles, from those who thrive in a traditional classroom setting to those who thrive in a more self-directed, computer-based learning environment. The students' attitudes toward blended learning have been mostly positive.

Blended learning

Blended learning refers to a pedagogical approach that combines face-to-face instruction with digital resources. It's a method of education that merges traditional classroom exercises with digitally mediated ones. This method of teaching entails a blend of in-person and digital interactions, as well as the use of both real-time and asynchronous communication tools for instruction. Blended learning is a method of instruction that combines online resources with more conventional methods of instruction. A true blended learning environment has the teacher and the student in the same room together. In spite of this, the students should be able to use the digital tools in order to exert some control over the pace or content of their learning. The flipped classroom model is an approach with similar goals, which is to use technology to reorganize the classroom environment in order to make the most of valuable face-to-face time for learning. Students in a flipped classroom model would be expected to use a cloud-based learning platform to access digital learning materials outside of class hours.

Variables used for the study

- **Dependent Variable** - Attitude towards blended learning is dependent variable.
- **Independent Variable** - Blended learning interest have been identified as independent variable for the present study
- **Demographic Variables** - Gender and School Type are the demographic variables chosen for the present study

Objectives of the study

The objectives have been formulated as follows.

To study,

- The favorableness or unfavorableness attitude towards blended learning of the higher secondary students.
- The level of blended learning interest of the higher secondary students.
- The significant difference in attitude towards blended learning of the male and female higher secondary students.

- The significant difference in attitude towards blended learning among the higher secondary students studying in the boy's school, girl's school and co –education schools.
- The significant difference in blended learning interest of the male and female higher secondary students.
- The significant difference in blended learning interest among the higher secondary students studying in the boy's school, girl's school and co –education schools.

Method of Study

Normative Survey method adopted for the present study. Survey Tools were prepared and distributed to the selected samples and data collected without any disturbance or influence to the variables taken for the study by the researchers. Purposive sampling technique has been used to collect the sample of 702 higher secondary students studying in the higher secondary schools in Kanchipuram District, Tamilnadu, India.

Tools used for the Present Study

The following were the tools used in the present investigation: (i) Attitude Towards Blended Learning Scale (ATBLS), and (ii) Blended Learning Interest Scale (BLIS) constructed and validated by Pattabiraman R and Manivannan S (2021). For the present investigation the Statistical techniques, Descriptive Analysis, Differential Analysis and Correlation Analysis were used.

Delimitation of the Study

- This study is confined to Kanchipuram district of Tamil Nadu State.
- It is confined itself to the 702 students studying in higher secondary schools.
- It is restricted to the selected demographic variables only.
- Selected only those higher secondary schools in which blended learning teaching method adopted

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the male and female school students given in the table

The significance of the difference between the means of Attitude towards blended learning scores of the male and female school students

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Significance at 0.05 level
Male	349	226.40	26.36	4.67	Significant
Female	353	235.53	25.35		

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 't' value is found to be 4.67 which is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significant difference between the male and female higher secondary school students in respect of their attitude towards blended learning.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning among the students studying in the boys, girls and co-education schools.

The significance of the difference among the means of attitude towards blended learning scores of the students studying in the boys, girls and co-education schools

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	'F' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Between groups	4900.976	2	2450.488	3.58	Significant
Within groups	477932.0	699	683.737		
Total	482833.0	701			

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 'F' value is found to be 3.58 which is significant at 0.05 levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is a significant difference among the students studying in the boys, girls and co- education schools in respect of their attitude towards blended learning.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the students studying in the boys and girls schools.

The significance of the difference between the means of attitude towards blended learning scores of the students studying in the boys and girls schools

Sub-samples	NN	Mean	SD	't' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Boys school	144	234.60	27.70	2.48	Significant
Girls schools	170	226.84	27.50		

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 't' value is found to be 2.48 which is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference between the students studying in the boys and girls schools in respect of their attitude towards blended learning.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the students studying in the boys and co- education schools.

The significance of the difference between the means of attitude towards blended learning scores of the students studying in the boys and co-education schools

Sub-samples	NN	Mean	SD	't' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Boys school	144	234.60	27.70	1.18	Not significant
Co-education school	388	231.48	24.92		

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 't' value is found to be 1.18 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore the null hypothesis is retained and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the students studying in the boys and co-education schools in respect of their attitude towards blended learning.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the students studying in the girls and co- education schools.

The significance of the difference between the means of attitude towards blended learning scores of the students studying in the girls and co-education schools

Sub-samples	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Girls school	170	226.84	27.50	1.88	Not significant
Co-education school	388	231.48	24.92		

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 't' value is found to be 1.88 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the students studying in the girls and co-education schools in respect of their attitude towards blended learning.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in blended learning interest between the male and female students.

The significance of the difference between the means of blended learning interest scores of the male and female students

Sub-samples	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Male	349	180.23	22.43	4.16	Significant
Female	353	187.06	20.70		

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 't' value is found to be 4.16 which is significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference between male and female students in respect of their blended learning interest.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in blended learning interest among the students studying in the boys, girls and co-education schools.

The significance of the difference among the means of blended learning interest scores of the students' studying in the boys, girls and co-education schools

Sources of variance	Sum of square	df	Mean square	'F' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Between groups	1720.442	2	860.21	1.809	Not significant
Within groups	332475.4	699	475.644		
Total	334195.8	701			

The details of the calculations are given in Table the 'F' value is found to be 1.809 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained and it is concluded that there is no significant difference among the students studying in the boys, girls and co- education in respect of their blended learning interest.

Major findings of the Study

- The higher secondary school students show neutral attitude towards blended learning.
- The higher secondary school students show average level of blended learning Interest.
- There is a significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the male and female students.
- There is a significant difference in attitude towards blended learning among the students studying in the boys, girls and co-education schools.
- There is significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the students studying in the boys and girls schools.
- There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the students studying in the boys and co-education schools.
- There is no significant difference in attitude towards blended learning between the students studying in the girls and co-education schools.
- There is a significant difference in blended learning interest between the male and female students.
- There is no significant difference in blended learning interest among the students studying in the boys, girls and co- education schools.
- In respect of the attitude towards blended learning and the blended learning interest scores the a) higher secondary school male students, b) higher secondary school female students, c) students studying in the boys schools, d) students studying in the girls schools and e) students studying in co-education schools, shows significant relationship.

Educational Implications

- The study is an attempt in this direction to access the level of attitude towards blended learning of higher secondary students.
- This study reveals the status of recognition for blending learning among the students and institutions.
- This study is very much essential for development of professional efficacy of teachers and quality education of higher secondary students.
- The present study establishes the relationship among the higher secondary school students, Attitude towards blended learning, and blended learning interest . This will help the government may be work out the well prepared strategies.
- The results shows that there is neutral attitude towards blended learning, average level of Blended learning interest. Hence to further enhance it, training program should be conducted for teachers as well as students.
- The results lead the teachers to plan for blended learning teaching methods for all subjects.
- For the establishment of technologically sound education system, this studies result will give the authorities, a broad view to identify the weaker section to concentrate.

Recommendations of the Study

- The higher secondary schools should improve their infrastructure with the latest technology.
- The results showed that the a neutral attitude towards blended learning has been observed in the entire sample of higher secondary students, hence to further enhance awareness should be provided by giving special attention towards blended learning, of the individuals.
- The present study also revealed that the Blended learning interest of entire sample of higher secondary students is average so the students interest to be developed.
- The relationship between the variables found to be significant, hence, to strengthen the attitude towards Blended learning among the students, the selected variables should be given more attention.
- Teachers should be given frequent in-service training to update on latest development in the execution of Blended learning.

Conclusion

The present investigation is a unique study conducted in Kanchipuram district of Tamilnadu, one of the pioneering states in the information technology field, to study the higher secondary school student's Attitude towards blended learning and blended learning interest hence this study has contributed to the field of computer education. Also the study has revealed that the higher secondary school students were having neutral Attitude towards blended learning and average level of blended learning interest. Thus, the higher secondary school students can be given the aspects in the recommendations with the facilities available to enhance the attitude towards blended learning and blended learning interest which helps them to equip themselves to face globalization of world.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning is an innovative concept that embraces the advantages of both traditional teaching in the classroom and ICT supported learning including both offline learning and online learning. It has scope for collaborative learning; constructive learning and computer assisted learning (CAI). Blended learning needs rigorous efforts, right attitude, handsome budget and highly motivated teachers and students for its successful implementation. In a true blended learning environment, both the student and the teacher should be physically located in the same space. Despite this, the digital tools used should be able to be utilized by the students in order to enforce some control over the speed or topics of their learning. The flipped classroom model is a similar program that aims to utilize technology in order to rearrange the learning experience and maximize the effectiveness of valuable face to face time in the classroom. In a flipped classroom programme, students would be encouraged to access digital learning materials via a cloud-based learning platform during their own time.

Introduction

The educational system at present is in a transition stage. To meet the challenges of expansion and for catering individuals need it is trying to adopt new technologies and exploring new paths to reach the goal of quality educational opportunities for all, at the same time due to various factors like deficient budgets, lack of facilities, advantages of face to face interaction, it is not completely ready to leave the traditional modes of knowledge transfer. Even the students are in a state of dual mind. When a group of teacher trainees were inquired about the mode of teaching they will prefer from tradition classroom teaching and ICT supported teaching the students were nearly evenly divided between both the choices. The traditional mode of teaching in spite of its few shortcomings provides a much needed human touch to the teaching learning process. Personality and behaviour of the teachers directly influences the blooming personality of the students. Only face to face interaction meets the affective objectives along with cognitive and psycho motor. Face to face traditional approach helps in developing a strong value system. Social skills like cooperation, sharing, expression and respecting other's views are more easily developed in traditional mode of teaching. Students learn not only from books, or from teachers teaching inside classroom but also from the co-students, through their peer group interaction,

Main characteristics of blended learning

Students have the option of the two modes- students in blended learning can select either the traditional mode of classroom teaching where they can get personal interaction with teacher and their classmates or they can choose ICT supported teaching learning. This largely depends on the nature of content and objectives being targeted. Sometime course designer or teachers themselves decide on the mode appropriate for topic being dealt with. Teachers are well versed with both the modes – it is an important feature of the blended learning that teachers are very dynamic, techno savvy and fully trained to work efficiently in both the formats traditional classroom format and ICT supported format. They will be well equipped in using traditional methods and other modern technologies. Students get face to face interaction as well they interact in virtual space- students get ample of time to interact with other students pursuing same course. They can interact with them inside college campus and also in virtual space. Thus their group become very large and has much diversity so the student's knowledge becomes wide and they also develop a feeling of understanding, love and harmony with students of other cultures and countries.

Students get full experience in using new technology- the present century is the century of ICT. Today the illiterate is not only the one who cannot read and write but a person who is not well versed with modern technologies is also illiterate. Today all professions demand expertise in ICT so blended learning help to make student's ICT experience rich. Students involved in blended learning gain capability to exploit available technologies to the fullest of their benefit. Students get training in different life skills- life skills are those skills that are needed to lead a happy peaceful and successful life. The major life skills are empathy, decision making capability, love, patience, communication, self-management, critical thinking. The blended learning helps the students to practice these skills. Students get acquainted with few skills like love,

empathy, patience in classroom through his teachers, classmates, and few like self-management, decision making, critical thinking, communication through the online experiences. All round development of personality is targeted. In blended learning the students get full opportunity for all round development of the personality. Tradition classroom teaching is helpful in memory level and understanding level of teaching and so help in cognitive domain development and at same time teacher's behaviour, playground experience and social group with classmates develop affective and physical domain at same time online experiences help in reflective level of learning so develop higher faculties of mind and social networking sites and other social interactions though internet help in right type of value development. Physical development is possible with in school campus- the online learning and ICT supports teaching learning process is often targeted with the blame that it ignores physical development of the students. The blended learning overcomes this limitation. As it included school experience also so student get time for playing, physical work, yoga inside the college campus.

Importance of blended learning

Blended learning is important because it breaks down the traditional walls of teaching, one that don't work for all students. But now with access to present day technologies and resources we can tailor the learning experience for each student. Blended learning is the one that offers flexible time frames that can be personalized to each person, offering them the ability to learn at their own pace. Blended learning is live interaction between teacher and student that uses technology. This type of learning allows flexibility for students and teachers. Students can enjoy personalized learning that suits their study plan through blended tools. Teachers can interact with students more efficiently by monitoring their growth and giving instant feedback. Blended learning allows students to personalize their learning experiences by using additional tools beyond the classroom. Learners can identify areas that need more attention and personalize their learning schedule to accommodate this. Teachers can also use blended learning methods to enhance their lessons. This is a modernized way of teaching that can have a positive impact on a student's training experience. This type of learning prepares students to work at digital based jobs that require technology proficiency.

Features of blended learning

Blended learning makes learning more fun as there is better involvement on the part of students. It also has a number of advantages over other methods of teaching. Blended learning gives the learner more control over what they learn and how much time they need to learn it well. Blended learning is flexible: There is immense possibility in presenting content. Complex topics can be covered in the classroom and since a chunk of the content is available online, students can work on learning the subject within a given timeline. Blended learning is efficient: With a well-planned blended learning strategy, you can efficiently and quickly deliver training to a broad audience. Also, digital content like videos, recordings and e-books can be reused, which is an added advantage. Creating a blended learning strategy reduces classroom teaching time and, by digitizing the expertise of talented instructors or subject-matter experts, you can teach more students with world-class content. Blended learning enables collaboration: Online assignments, course commenting and discussion boards naturally encourage student collaboration. Therefore, both online and offline teamwork opportunities are more. Blended learning supports personalized learning: Each person learns in a unique way and blended learning supports it. For example, you can assign reading comprehension passages according to the comprehension level of each student which can prevent unnecessary burdening for students who need to work harder. Blended learning enables tracking and reporting: One of the greatest benefits of online learning, especially through an LMS, is data tracking and reporting. LMSs have the ability to track each step the student takes throughout the course, including logins, time tracking and grading.

Moocs for teacher professional development

Teachers are good candidates for MOOC participation because of their regular use of the internet for finding information (Castaño-Muñoz et al., 2018) and their good fit with the ideal profile of a MOOC participant as employed professional who are self-regulated learners experienced at independent and peer-to-peer learning. There were complex criteria for the MOOC that was developed in response, however, including multiple learning pathways and a mechanism to compensate for MOOCs' inability to provide individual tutor feedback for all participants in all pathways. There is little guidance for providing MOOCs in a blended context, (Gynther, 2016b) adapted the Community of Inquiry framework.

The growth of blended learning

This guidebook presents new ways of thinking about teaching and learning to help you better prepare your students to learn and develop into 21st-century global citizens. According to the U.S. Department of Education (Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakia, & Jones, 2009), a blend of classroom and web-based teaching and learning offers access to the widest range of learning modes and methods for developing student skills and expertise as learners (Cleveland-Innes, 2017). Many findings on blended learning show an increase in learners' ability to learn collaboratively, think creatively, study independently and tailor their own learning experiences to meet their individual needs. Innovative educators have for many years been creating new delivery methods in education by combining elements of in-person teaching with technology-enabled learning to bring people together virtually. Since the late 1990s, when simple learning management systems began to emerge, blended learning has grown very quickly.

Future of blended learning environments

Blended learning environments (BLEs) promise to be an important part of the future of both higher education and corporate training. Over the past decade, with the increased availability of technology and network access, the use of BLEs has steadily grown. However, the amount of research done related to the design and use of BLEs is relatively small and additional research is needed. In particular, research is needed that will help instructors to understand the strengths and weaknesses of methods used in Face-toFace (F2F) and computer-mediated (CM) instructional environments and know how to appropriately combine both types of instruction. Cases across various levels and types of blends need to be documented and analyzed in order to better understand the trade offs that must be made when designing instruction in a blended learning environment.

Challenges in blended learning

Despite the opportunities provided by blended learning, These include the following:

- Studies have shown that students enrolled in blended courses can sometimes have unrealistic expectations. The students in blended learning programmes assumed that fewer classes meant less work, inadequate time management skills were inadequate, and they experienced problems with accepting responsibility for personal learning.
- Students in such courses have also reported feeling isolated due to the reduced opportunities for social interaction in a face-to-face classroom environment.
- Having difficulty with more sophisticated technologies is another challenge when implementing blended learning. For example, students may have to rely on slow Internet connections. Poor Internet connectivity has been reported to inhibit students' ability to engage in online discussions, which could lead to considerable frustration and have a negative impact on learning.
- The challenge for implementation of blended learning in higher institutions is time commitment. Thus, estimates that planning and developing a blended learning course for large numbers usually takes two to three times the amount of time required to develop a similar course in a traditional format.
- Funds are insufficient for the development of a Learning Management System (LMS), which is required to enhance blended learning in higher institutions.
- Technical support for course design may be lacking. This results from insufficient interrelation between the information and communication technology(ICT) experts and faculty members offering blended learning courses. In order to ensure a successful blended learning experience for students; there should be university support for course redesign, which may involve deciding what course objectives can best be achieved through online learning activities, what parts of the course can best be accomplished in the classroom, and how to integrate these two learning environments.

Conclusion

This first chapter has introduced blended learning as an important and rapidly developing form of education, with an emphasis on the benefits it offers to both educators and students, including greater flexibility and convenience, as well as potential increases in learner creativity and independence. Blended learning can be defined as the combination of face-to-face classroom instruction with online learning within a course or programme — a definition broad enough to include a wide range of variations appropriate to the individual needs and contexts of a school or course. One key concept is that blended learning is not merely the addition of some technological element to an existing course but rather is an integrated plan utilizing the

best of what both face-to-face and online learning have to offer. The blended presentation and interaction model, the blended block model and the fully online model provide initial frameworks for the deliberate structuring of blended learning to improve learning outcomes. Blended Learning Environments promise to be an important part of the future of both higher education and corporate training. Over the past decade, with the increased availability of technology and network access, the use of Blended Learning Environments has steadily grown. It provides students with time flexibility and improved learning outcomes. The blended learning offers the open way for many students who can get through the physical and cultural barriers in the education. By learning to use technology in the classroom, both teachers and students will develop skills essential for the 21st century.

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TECHNOLOGY IN THE CLASSROOM: LEGAL RIGHTS AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

Today's classroom has been transformed by technology. Many people question whether this change is for the better. Researchers have investigated the advantages and disadvantages of using technology in the classroom. This research paper will discuss the advantages and disadvantages of technology in the classroom. According to research, technology improves student motivation, increases classroom behavior, and makes more resources available to teachers. Prospective teachers have benefited from the use of technology in a number of cases that we will discuss in this paper. Some teachers are concerned about the changes that technology will bring to the classroom. Some professionals believe they are out of touch with current technology and, as a result, cannot properly implement technology in their classroom. This paper will also discuss prospective teachers' legal rights and responsibilities when using technology in the classroom.

Keywords: *Legal Rights, Technology, class room, responsibilities and prospective teachers.*

Introduction

The increased use of technology in the classroom is due to the realization that technology is required to prepare students for the world we live in. It has largely been a voluntary effort by school districts with the resources to embrace innovative and interesting ways to help students learn. There has also been an increase in online schools and blended learning programs, in which students combine electronic and traditional forms of learning. However, as we move away from just books and pencils, it is critical to understand the teacher's

role in providing digital education and how using technology affects his or her rights and responsibilities as an educator. Teachers teach the rules to students through role play, assemblies, and class discussions. Positive behavior support recognizes and rewards students who behave responsibly throughout the school day.

Parents establish rules and expectations for student behavior at home. It is critical that parents and educators establish similar rules and expectations for responsible behavior in the digital world, just as it is important to establish these rules and expectations for school and home. Students require guidelines and boundaries and are more likely to succeed when they are aware of and understand the expectations. Educators and parents must set an example of appropriate technology use at home and at school. They must teach students how to use technology responsibly. Students can successfully and safely participate in today's digital society if effective modeling and teaching are used. Students are expected to "advocate and practice safe, legal, and responsible use of information and technology," according to the NETs standard for digital citizenship.

Digital rights and responsibilities address this component of the standard. Parents and educators must collaborate, use available resources, and provide opportunities for our students to promote safe, legal, and responsible technology use. Students must learn about internet safety, best practices for using information online, and the responsibilities that come with technology use as they participate in the digital world. It is very easy to misuse technology when you have access to so many different websites. We can prepare our students to make informed decisions as they collaborate, communicate, and participate in the digital world by teaching those best practices for technology use and the consequences for misuse.

Technology in the Classroom

The use of technology during whole-class instruction can increase student engagement for auditory and visual learners. Integrating simple technologies such as Power Points, games, internet homework assignments, or online grading systems can make a significant difference in students' academic growth. Technology has been present in classrooms for many years, but its use in classrooms is increasing all the time. According to a 2020 study, 79% of teachers use technology in almost every lesson. This is more than triple what it was ten years ago. Educational technology, or edtech for short, is the concept of using technology for educational purposes. The edtech industry is expected to be worth more than 106 billion in 2021 and nearly 378 billion by 2028. Prospective Teachers should be aware of circumstances that expand, require, or limit the use of technology in the classroom.

- Digital citizenship skills
- Different Learning Styles
- Future Employment
- Standardized testing
- Equity
- Special Education
- Equal access
- Limiting Access

Legal Rights and Responsibilities of prospective Teachers:

The "privileges and freedom extended to all digital technology users, as well as the behavioral expectations that come with them," are referred to as digital rights and responsibilities. In other words, your students have the privilege and freedom to engage in technology use during school as well as at home. However, there are expectations that accompany the privileges and freedom to use technology. Students must act responsibly as they participate in the digital world. Understanding many issues is required to use technology responsibly. Most importantly, parents and educators want students to be safe when using technology. Students must understand the rules for using technology at school and at home in order to have safe online experiences.

Students must also learn the consequences of making unsafe and inappropriate choices in the digital world. For example, at school, losing privileges is a possible result of making illegal and inappropriate online choices. Another major issue related to this topic of digital rights and responsibilities is cyber bullying and threatening behavior. Students must remember that, just as bullying is not tolerated in school, it is also not tolerated online. Threatening others with technology is another inappropriate application of technology. Parents and educators must have discussions with students about these topics. Many do not

realize the hurt and the negative effects of cyber bullying and online threatening and/or the consequences that accompany these inappropriate choices.

Our prospective teachers must understand their rights and responsibilities as digital citizens in order to become digital citizens. By following their school's AUP, making appropriate choices when using technology, participating in technology lessons that teach safe and appropriate practices of technology use and reporting cyber bullying and threatening behavior, students will be able to engage in safe, ethical and meaningful experiences with today's technology.

Conclusion

Students are able to continue their studies from home thanks to educational technologies such as the internet and video conferencing applications. We could learn even in the face of a pandemic. The use of educational technology has increased students' learning speed by providing instant access to information. With the right to discover knowledge comes the responsibility to behave well while doing so.

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BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

Blended learning is increasingly being adopted at all levels of the educational system. It continues to gain primacy in the teaching and learning environment as both teacher and students seek to integrate familiar information communication technology (ICT) into their classroom activities. We have all used different methods of ‘blended learning’ models when being educated in our classrooms and trained in the workplace. In the beginning of late nineties the term blended learning was coined it was incorporated in most institutions and companies through various technology.

Keywords: *Blended Learning, Student-centered education, & Collaborative learning*

Introduction

In a media rich environment learners become more engaged by variations of blended learning which is being adopted at all levels as instructors explore different ways to facilitate learning. Blended learning defines the students who learn apart through on the online with some elements of control over time place path and pace based on the strategies which encourages the use of technology and flexible in presenting content which enhance effectiveness and efficiency to contribute and learn at their own pace. Blended learning also referred to as flexible learning has long been used in the classroom in multiple ways. The ever-increasing use of information technology has created renewed interest (Duane 2004; Vaughan 2007) in multiple evolving concept (Weston, Wireman, & Murphy 2008; Graham, Allan, & Urea, 2005; Oliver & Trigwell 2005; Whitlock & Jells, 2003). The development of blended courses has been on a strategy that encourages the use of technology along with face to face instruction study predict that by 2019 50% of high school courses will be available and delivered online. Children are born into this digital world and exposed and using technology as early as age of 1, according to study presented at the 2015 US pediatric academic societies annual meeting, more than one in three children have used a smartphone or tablet device before the age of one meaning that children today are more tech-savvy than ever before.

Blended Learning

Taking the world of education by storm is blended learning, which combine formal education and traditional classroom teaching method with digital media in combination with computer mediated activities. The student watch educational videos play games and complete homework assignments in the classroom, while part of lectures provided through online source they can access from home. For example teacher can ask the students to watch an educational TED Videos at home. The approach of blended learning is to utilize the use of technology in the classroom to optimize student education through online and face to face interaction, the usage of blended learning gives us an opportunity to reform the traditional school model and to express student-centered learning.

Types of Blended learning Models

There are six standard models of blended learning used for teachers. Three models address the different cognitive and social-emotional abilities of students. The six types are identified as:

- **Face-to-face Drivers** is represented as the most traditional by having a physical teacher present or to employ online learning.
- **Rotation** means that students will alternate between self-paced online learning and being in the classroom with a teacher. This model includes four sub models: station rotation, lab rotation, flipped classroom, and individual rotation. In the ‘flipping’ method, the professors and teachers used online media to deliver lectures, notes, and feedback students can study and review the material had their own pace. The model is implemented with a student-centered perspective which allows students to learn individually.
- **Flex** is the online platform used.
- **Online lab** delivers the course in a brick-and-mortar (traditional) setting.
- **Self-Blend model** more commonly known as A La Carte, gives students the freedom to choose remote online course to supplement their schools curriculum with something that is more individual. The students can take multiple courses either online at home or in a regular classroom.
- **Online Driver** program is also known as enriched virtual is used complete online where Students can divided their time between a traditional classroom and at home unlike the flipped classroom the online driver does not require the daily school attendance the teacher can apply their programs to have available or mandatory face to face check-ins. The enriched virtual program is complete blend of online and brick and mortar classroom session.

How does Blended learning differ from traditional learning?

The rise of blended learning programs represents a shift from traditional instruction in education to optimize student learning in multiple ways the mixture of this learning experience has allowed learners to recall information so that it can be remembered and combined with new knowledge basis. Personalized learning is excellent for students who feel lost and overwhelmed in the classroom. The old brick-and-mortar classroom with students learning from one text is long, long gone. Blended learning methods help students learn at their own cognitive level of functioning. The face-to-face driver model works best in all classrooms since most students are functioning at different levels of ability. Teachers deliver this model appropriately by allowing a traditional classroom experience and integrating technology. Students who do not feel confident in their work can access the course from home and study at their own pace while students who have mastered the subject can practice and challenge themselves more effectively. The rotation model of most common and allow teachers to switch instruction online & physically face-to-face. Students can be separated base on skill level such as starting instruction in person before rotating online.

More individual assistance is also given to students feeling left behind on a topic another model that is viewed as a highly successful is the online lab school model. It involve students going to a physical classroom that only provides online education delivery for its courses. The online lab is flexible and befits students who have other responsibility either at home or the need to move at much slower pace than traditional classroom provide. one of the main goals of a blended classroom involves the mission to capture the learner’s attention. Many instructors design their teaching to acquire the use of both long-term memory and short-term class working memory. Working/ short term memory as to do with what you are actively doing at the moment and temporarily storing information, such as solving math problems. Long-term memory helps u remember rules and knowledge that is ‘declared’. An example of declared memory would

be having the order of operations memorized. In virtual classroom, instructors must make sure there is harmony between working and long term memory.

An information overload in a blended approach can cause anxiety and stress. It is important for instructors to design their programs with a few facts in mind. Teachers can add more drop-down menus, touch panels, and clearly marked buttons to put the student's minds at ease. More information on some challenges of blended learning can be found in the research in learning technology journal. E-learning specialists are taking neuroscience into consideration when developing visual aids for learning. According to Zabisco, 40% of people will respond better to visual information than plain text, when learners are connecting with the content they are going through a cognitive retention process. The medial temporal lobe, where emotions are processed, is also where visual memories are enclosed. Students will have a better chance of remembering when text is combined with visual stimuli. Students can also develop strong social-emotional learning (SEL) skills when interacting in a blended program. SEL skills are linked to technology use since students can first develop self-awareness and responsibility online to work better in terms when in person. Aside from traditional objectives in school systems, the new integration of technology and teaching helps bring teachers and students closer together and establish higher quality learning. Blending was prompted by the recognition that not all learning is best achieved in electronically mediated environment, particularly one that dispenses with a live instructor altogether. Instead a consideration must be given to the subject matter, the learning objectives and outcomes, the characteristics of the learner, and the leaning content in order to arrive at the optimum mix of instructional and delivery methods. This method is very useful in education/etc.

Blended Learning: A Student-Centered Education

Over the past decade, educators in both secondary and higher educational institutions have realized that students all differ in skill sets and learning abilities. The whole Child Approach (2014) ensures that each child will be treated as a whole with their socio-emotional, physical, creative, and cognitive capacities being just as important in their overall educational growth. In order to see where a student's skills lie on the spectrum, a cognitive profile screening can be implemented before selecting the appropriate learning model. Screening children at young age can be catered to develop their personal learning abilities. Developing blended learning approach in all educational institution is one step in their right direction to help every child succeed. The models also built upon Dr. Howard Gardner's Theory of multiple intelligences (1983) by selecting strategies to trigger the strength on the students' multiple learning preferences. The blended learning paradigm of e-learning with a person-centered approach Studies show that it can help with better problem-solving, increased self-confidence, and improve interpersonal skills. Person-Centered Learning was developed by the American psychologist Carl Rogers (1902-1987) to address the learner's intellect, social skills and personality. One study targeted the fundamental impact of interpersonal attitudes on the motivation and learning outcomes of students. The study suggested that a blended learning paradigm in which there is room for social and personal processes leads to improved learning only if instructors are perceived as personally well equipped to fill this space (Patrick & Mallich, 2004). From a perspective of learners, blended learning can be obtained from all options of equipment, tools, media, technology, etc. to match their previous knowledge and learning style to reach current learning objectives.

Role of Technology in Blended Learning

- **Enabling Collaborating Learning:** Through individual and group activities, students learn to be collective and polish their critical thinking skills. Educators and students can collaborate to form a unique, personalized learning method based on student requirements for effectively understanding various concepts. Through customized study modules and videos, teachers can create a personalized resource library for students for their studies. After building this resource library based on common need areas, a teacher can expand it to address needs that come up less frequently and advise individual students or groups about these helpful resources.
- **Facilitating organized Learning:** Educators can orchestrate classes and disseminate information in a controlled and organized manner to suit the students. Through digital worksheets, interactive discussion boards, video tutorials, etc., students can participate in controlled experiences. It empowers students to lead in classrooms, enriches their learning experience and helps use technology to build a good foundation in their studies.

- **Building open and rich Dialogue between Stakeholders:** It is not only important to manage instructions in a classroom, but also assess the class. Online classrooms facilitate open and rich dialogues between the student and teacher. The teachers can collect assignments, give feedback and offer learning resources to meet diverse learners' needs. They can converse with the different stakeholders, such as parents, students and investors on the various challenges being faced and suggest areas for improvement.

Benefits of Blended Learning

If you're thinking about implementing blended learning, you'll probably want to know whether it's worth the trouble. So, take a look at some of the advantages of blended learning for learners (students or employees) and organizations (schools, universities, or companies):

- **Safer learning environment:** If there's anything 2020 taught us, it's that being in one place with a bunch of other people can have its complications. And seeing those people only on the screen is unbearable. The blended approach makes learning safer by reducing the number of hours learners spend together offline but still provides them with live communication.
- **Interactive learning process:** Theoretical materials can be challenging (if not boring). It's one thing when learners sit and listen to a speaker for a few hours. And it's radically different when they learn that same information by clicking on buttons, participating in a dialogue simulation, taking a game-like course, and so on. Acquiring new knowledge can be fun, and blended learning provides lots of tools to make it so.
- **Learner autonomy:** Being able to control and schedule an individual learning path is essential for learners – and especially adults. Learning isn't the only (and hardly the most important) activity of students and employees. Work, family, hobbies, and friends – people's lives are made up of many facets, and learning shouldn't become an obstacle. In blended learning, learners can access courses 24/7 – whenever they want it and have the opportunity.
- **Greater learner engagement:** No business or institution wants to force its employees or students to learn, because it won't work. You need to engage learners in learning to make it effective. And, according to this study conducted in 2019, blended learning leads to greater learner engagement by providing different opportunities and using digital tools.
- **Better comprehension:** One of the most popular blended learning models, called the “flipped classroom,” results in better comprehension by having learners study all theoretical materials alone at their own pace and practice new knowledge and skills during in-person sessions.
- **Detailed Analytics:** How much time did it take a learner to finish a quiz? How many attempts did they make? Do they have any expiring tasks? Can you answer these questions with classroom learning? Probably, yes. But how much time will you spend collecting all this information on each and every employee or student? With blended learning, you won't even spend a minute – a learning management system will do everything for you. Based on learner progress, you'll be able to see how competent a learner is at specific topics, whether they are ready to move forward or need to revise some materials, and much more.

Disadvantages of Blended Learning

Now that you know the ‘why’ of blended learning, let's also look at the ‘why not.’ Here are the cons of this learning approach:

- **New Skill set for Teachers/ instructors:** Blended learning requires particular digital competence, as instructors need to create online courses, assign them to students, monitor their progress, and much more. Some eLearning tools have a steep learning curve, and not all teachers might be willing to invest the time and trouble needed to master a new technological tool. A new skill set also refers to the fact that digitally inexperienced teachers may give too much content to study just because they don't have classroom time limits and think: “Well, it's not that much. And learners are at home, so they have lots of spare time.” And this could lead to cognitive overload on the part of the learners.
- **Plagiarism:** The more eLearning content you create, the greater the risk of plagiarism. Instructors might do this by accident, such as if they find an image that highlights their idea and add it to their online course, whereas the image is protected by copyright. If this occurs, it's the company or university that might get into trouble.

- **Higher cost:** If you use eLearning, you pay for eLearning software. If you have classroom learning, you pay for light, gas, equipment, etc. And if you have blended learning, you pay for everything.

Impact of Blended Learning on the students and teachers

The role of blended learning has become crucial as it breaks down the traditional methods of teaching. With the help of technology, it customizes resources and tailors the learning experience to fit every student's need. Since blended learning also offers high flexibility and personalization, students have the freedom to learn at their own pace. Thus, through blended tools, students can enjoy personalized learning that suits their study routine, and teachers can interact with students by monitoring their growth and giving instant feedback. This remodeled method of tutoring by using additional tools beyond the classroom can have a positive impact on the students' learning and training experience. Blended learning helps improve various factors in the classroom for teachers as well, like resulting in more engaged students, real-time and reliable feedback on teaching methods, new methods of teaching, collaborative learning and time management, among others. Thus, through blended learning, schools and teachers are mainly focusing on inculcating methods for students to understand and manage their social and emotional well-being. While the pandemic has provided immense opportunities for a mix of online and offline education, digital transformation has provided many the opportunities to explore new ways of understanding concepts. The future of edtech will be in blended models of education. These models would help provide a solution to the access and quality of education seen in India.

Blended learning: The New future of education

A one-size-fits all educational model does not exist, however, blended and hybrid classroom are shown to be more effective than traditional teaching methods. While students are becoming more digitally-oriented, educational institution should be using this as advantage to further student's educational success. A successful classroom includes a range of meaningful activities assessments and methods used for the sole purpose of giving every students chance to excel at their best abilities, the elements that make Blended approach is so effective are using multiple technology tools, small groups work, freedom of choice. Technology and education go hand in hand when teaching and improving cognitive abilities. Cognitive brain training program allows not only for students and anyone to train the cognitive processes but allow for teachers to keep track of their students through our education platform for school & Teachers. There must be more blended learning research to gain insight on how it is making an impact through the year.

Conclusion

Blended learning is definitely more beneficial approach than old-school educational methods, it works for the students, since it helps them learn more through practical implementation of the knowledge they gain. It also works for the teacher since it makes their job more enjoyable. Blended learning is an ideal approach that can be used to make this possible. By embracing the use of blended learning, teacher preparation program help teacher candidates learn how to tap into their student's interests and familiarity with a range of information communication technology to encourage and facilitate an engaging learning environment, both virtually & physically. Educators will continue to invent new methodologies for personalized learning models by collaborating our knowledge of individualism & culture.

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ATTITUDE OF STUDENT TEACHERS TOWARDS BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

The present study Viz., Attitude of student teachers towards Blended learning is an attempt to find out if there is any significant difference in the attitude towards Blended learning among student teachers with respect to Gender, Locality and Subject of study. A blended learning attitude scale developed and standardised by the investigator was administered to 50 student teachers in a self financing college, applying simple random sampling technique. Mean, Standard Deviation and ‘t’ test were calculated to test the hypotheses. The study reveals that there is no significant difference in the attitude of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to Gender, Locality and there is significant difference in the attitude of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to Subject of study.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Level of attitude, Gender, Locality, and Subject of study.*

Introduction

The use of electronic media has changed the complexity of our class room. In modern class rooms, electronic media has started finding an important place in teaching. The use of Information and Communication technologies has been found to enhance the learning attitudes. The learning environment assisted by learning technologies is such evocative images and objects which trigger active and joyful learning by allowing students to engage with that appeal to them. So nowadays most technologies like web 2.0 web configuring, video conferencing, cloud computing, Network learning, visual learning environment learning, pod casting, M. Learning, Blended learning are used in educational institutions, When we use these technologies along with facilitators’ support, definitely it will provide better learning environment .Among these technologies Blended learning is emerging as a fast growing delivery and instructional design in colleges and Universities. Blended learning combines online components with the conventional face to face components to provide suitable learning environment.

Need for the Study

Blended learning is otherwise called as Hybrid Learning. It is a planned combination of online learning and face to face (F2F) instruction using a variety of learning resources. Blended learning is an educational format that integrates online learning techniques like online delivery of materials through web pages, discussion boards, and email with traditional teaching. The success of a blend depends on the right mix of the elements (online delivery, Interaction, face to face instruction etc.) A good blend would provide optimum role of lively interaction. As the present children are in a technological world, it is necessary to introduce drastic changes in learning process. With the help of these innovative technological teaching methods student teachers i.e. future teachers could shape the young minds of future society better. Hence the investigator has made an attempt to study the attitude of student – teachers towards blended learning.

Objectives of the study

- To study the level of attitude of student teachers towards blended leaning.
- To study if there is any significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to
 - Gender
 - Locality
 - Subject (arts /science)

Hypotheses of the study

- The level of attitude of student teachers towards blended learning is moderate.
- There is no significant difference in the attitude of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to
 - Gender
 - Locality
 - Subject (arts /science)

Methodology

The normative **survey method** was used to collect the data. The sample consisted of 50 student teachers who are doing B.Ed. Course in Subham College of Education in Kancheepuram District during the academic year 2015-2016, using **simple random sampling technique**. Blended learning attitude scale constructed and validated by the investigator was used for collecting the data. The reliability and validity of the tool were found to be 0.84 and 0.91 respectively. The tool consisted of 25 items which included 5 negative items and 20 positive items . The tool was measured at a five point scale ranging from strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD) responses. The scores were 5, 4,3,2,1 for positive items and was vice-versa for the negative items. The maximum and minimum scores were 125 and 25 respectively. Percentage, mean, standard deviation were calculated for testing the stated hypotheses.

Results and discussion

Hypothesis – The level of attitude of student teachers towards blended learning is moderate

Table – 1 Level of attitude of student teachers towards blended learning

LEVEL	N	%
Low	-	-
Moderate	19	38
High	31	62

Table- 1 reveals the fact that the level of attitude of student teachers towards blended learning is found to be high in nature.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to Gender.

Table – 2 Attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to their Gender

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Table Value	Calculated 't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	16	67.125	2.68	2.68	1.208	Not Significant
Female	34	70.41	3.5355			

Table -2: reveals that the obtained' value (1.208) for the variable **Gender** is less than the table value (2.68) and the obtained't' value is not significant at 0.01 level. So, it is inferred that there is no significant difference between Male and Female student teachers. Hence the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning between Male and Female student teachers is **accepted**.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to Locality.

Table – 3 Attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to their Locality

Locality	N	Mean	S.D.	Table Value	Calculated 't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	29	69.586	2.828	2.68	0.77	Not Significant
Urban	21	69.047	2.121			

Table- 3 reveals that the obtained' value (0.77) for the variable, **Locality** is less than the table value (2.68) and the obtained't' value is not significant at 0.01 level. So it is inferred that there is no significant difference between Rural and Urban student teachers in the attitude towards blended learning. Hence the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning between Rural and Urban student teachers is **accepted**.

Hypothesis - There is no significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to Subject of study.

Table – 4 Attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to their subject

Subject	N	Mean	S.D	Table Value	Calculated 't' Value	Level of Significance
Science	24	70.625	2.121	2.68	2.978	Significant
Arts	26	68.192	3.536			

Table -4: reveals that the obtained' value (2.978) for the variable **subject of study** is greater than the table value (2.68) and the obtained't' value is significant at 0.01 level. So, it is inferred that there is significant difference between science and Arts student teachers towards blended learning. Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to Subject is **rejected**.

Findings

- The level of attitude of student teachers towards blended learning is high.
- There is no significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to their
 - Gender
 - Locality
- There is significant difference in the attitude scores of student teachers towards blended learning with respect to their subject. The findings of the study shows that attitude of science student towards blended learning is greater than arts students. It may be due to their better attitude towards science and their exposure to use of ICT.

Conclusion

In today's classroom we have to extensively utilize all the available educational resources to provide quality education. By using ICT in education the learner can receive the content sequent very fast without any misperception. As blended learning includes both online delivery of content and face – to – face classroom methods it has both advantages. Not only this, in blended learning freedom of Students are likely to interact more with the instructor and peer students since there are ample opportunities to do so both in class and online Blended learning develops the students skills like time management, clinical thinking and problem solving, and using the internet and computer technology. Even though blended learning has some disadvantages like other methods, students typically have 24/7 online access to course materials. As this study shows that student teachers have high attitude towards blended learning, this innovative strategy can be strongly recommended in curriculum transaction.

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SUGGESTED MODELS AND APPROACHES OF BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The advancement of technology over the past 20 years has caused the world to evolve at its quickest rate. Technology is a great asset for improving many disciplines and industries. Recent years have seen significant changes in the education industry as technology has replaced conventional teaching and learning techniques. All public sectors were invaded by technology, which significantly sped up travel time. Modern technologies are used to help the instructor and student deliver high-quality instruction. Additionally, based on the integration of technology, instructional methods and procedures are adjusted or improved. In terms of teaching, this optimisation may entail creating a lesson plan, making a presentation, or delivering material. Getting information is important to the teaching-learning process, preparing teaching aids, involving students in learning activities, assessing the teaching-learning process, evaluating, and carrying out follow-up activities. As a result, the students are proficient in using technology. Nowadays, learning involves more than just writing down information and memorization of facts. The fast adoption of technology-assisted teaching techniques and blended learning models shows that inventive instructors are constantly improving learning through technology. Blended learning is a type of educational programme that mixes traditional classroom instruction with instructional content from online digital media. Both the teacher and the student must be there in person. It is difficult for the instructor in this environment to prepare the student teachers for shaping the next generation. The models and methods of blended learning in teacher education are discussed in this article.

Keywords: *Models, Approaches, Blended Learning and Teacher Education*

Introduction

The advantages of online learning are combined with the classroom's tried-and-true efficacy in blended learning, often referred to as "hybrid learning." It is a way of teaching that blends conventional place-based classroom techniques with online educational resources and chances for online participation. The advantages of online learning are combined with the classroom's tried-and-true efficacy in blended learning.

Blended Learning Models

Face-to-face driver model

This approach provides an experience that is the closest to that of a typical classroom. After participating in a live webinar or meeting on a platform like Zoom or Google Meet, students receive live training and are given homework or projects to do before the next session. Advantages of the face-to-face driver model include:

- It may be quite helpful for students who require more external incentive or who are more advanced in their particular position. This format has many similarities to a conventional classroom.
- For individuals who possess technical proficiency, this may also be a viable choice.
- But, compared to some of the other models, this one certainly demands more time and effort from the educator.

Flipped Learning model

The difference between the flipped model and the face-to-face driving approach is that the learners receive learning tools and materials prior to each virtual classroom encounter. The advantages of the flipped learning paradigm are as follows:

- This model offers an additional choice for a learning cohort that would benefit from active, live instruction in the classroom.
- Also, it takes more time and effort from the educator.

Enriched Virtual Learning Model

With this strategy, students may control how quickly they acquire new material and finish the majority of their schoolwork online. Although learners have the option to participate in instructor-led web seminars at their leisure, the choice of how much of their learning involves direct connection with the instructor rests with them. Advantages of the virtual learning paradigm include:

- It may be excellent for independent learners who value self-directed learning;
- By having the opportunity to communicate with the teacher, they like the balance between feeling encouraged and empowered.

Flex Learning Model

It gives students the freedom to focus their education in the way that best suits them. They may switch between individual assignments, synchronous and asynchronous education, and even group learning. Although instructors are on hand to answer queries and offer feedback, it is up to each participant to decide how and when to make use of their resources. The flex learning paradigm has the following advantages:

- It works well for independent learners who are aware of how various teaching strategies affect their learning.
- Nevertheless, a drawback of this is that teachers must remain "on call," and uninterested students could just stick with the teaching style they are most accustomed to.

Rotation Learner Model

This is a little bit of a grab bag. The class is broken up into smaller groups, and the students alternate between individual teaching, usually delivered through a pre-recorded webinar, live group instruction, usually delivered using Zoom or similar webinar medium, and self-guided assignments. The rotation learning approach gives a comparable amount of flexibility, but it is chosen by the teacher rather than allowing learners to finally choose which learning techniques are most successful. The rotation learning approach has the following advantages:

- It may be very successful with learners who enjoy various learning experiences.
- However the level of institution needed to implement the rotation model can be difficult.

Online driver model

The most learner autonomy is provided by this paradigm. Participants progress through the learning models at their own speed, with the motivation and drive that suits them. Although there is still the option for learners to speak with student teachers as required, doing so is not necessary to finish the course. The online driver concept has advantages in that The online driver learning approach enhances this level of autonomy and amplifies it to the highest level, making it useful for experienced, self-motivated learners. This model necessitates the least amount of teacher time and effort. Yet, reluctant or uninspired students may become lost or end up merely going through the motions without gaining a thorough comprehension of the course material.

Approaches of Blended Learning

VDI

A robust IT infrastructure is necessary for a mixed learning environment to be effective. Students and instructors may access materials remotely using their preferred devices thanks to the virtual desktop infrastructure (VDI). An iPad, for instance, might be used by a student to access a Virtual Windows desktop that had the same appearance and features as a desktop PC at school.

RAS

A complete VDI solution is provided by Remote Application Server to address these blended learning requirements. It allows for remote desktop and application access from any place and virtual learning. Moreover, it permits use of the student's preferred gadgets, such as tablets and smartphones, for work or study. Also, and perhaps most importantly, it promotes security by controlling access to data both on and off-campus.

Video

The main method of delivering material for blended learning is video. For instance, flipped classrooms mandate that students check the lecture materials before class. Most frequently, this entails instructors or trainers filming brief video lectures that frequently contain a screen capture of the instructor's computer screen, a webcam capture of the instructor, a video of a demonstration, or a mix of all three.

LMS

Learning management system integrates various features using educational technology and provides and enriched media for teaching and learning. They provide a platform for conveniently creating and distributing teaching materials, along with ease of communication and collaboration between different learners.

MOODLE

Modular Object Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment is an open source learning management system. A Tutor and interact and out of all Moodle has been revealed as one of the most popular online learning management system.

Conclusion

Blended Learning Modal and approaches are the need of the hour and rapid being utilized at all Teacher Educational Institutions. This model of education is found to be effective in several ways but also several challenges arises in the implementation of blended learning model.

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DIFFERENT DESIGN APPROACHES AND COMMITMENT IN BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

Blended learning is growing in popularity as it has proven to be an effective approach to accommodate diverse students. Despite the growing interest, there is ongoing debate about the definition of the concept of blended learning. Because of this, teachers in higher education have developed different understandings of the context of the times. Choosing the most appropriate design approach for blended learning many teachers in higher education institutions are new to the idea of blended learning. This article aims to provide guidance to teachers of face-to-face courses in choosing the most appropriate approach to use when designing their blended courses. Discuss the different definitions of the term blended learning and how they have resulted in several design approaches and categorize these approaches as follows Impact, Moderate Impact, and High Impact. Enrichment combinations adapt to potential changes in the existing

teaching program and student learning experience. Finally, it describes the benefits and challenges of using each approach. Also, it provides recommendations for the commitment of each approach.

Introduction

In the past few years, the demand for blended learning has increased in popularity in all areas and has become a widespread phenomenon. It is no exaggeration to say that blended learning is more effective than online learning and face-to-face classes. Distance learning mode provides opportunities to adopt a flexible teaching method like blended learning. It is indeed a true phenomenon that the mode of blended learning has become the new model for imparting education. With the large number of blended learning designs, choosing the most appropriate design approach is a major challenge. This is a unique challenge especially for teachers who lack the necessary theoretical preparation and experimental experience. This includes understanding blended learning in different ways and then designing curricula according to their own understanding. This paper aims to integrate current curricula into the design of blended learning courses as a means of improving understanding of blended learning curriculum and for the development of education. It is also described as helpful for choosing the most appropriate approach to designing blended learning courses. First, the definitions of the term blended learning are discussed and then its objectives are described. After that, various design approaches are described. Finally, methods of selecting and considering the approach are given, and explanations and strategies on how to use it are given.

Different design approaches

While there is much debate about the best definition of blended learning, the term means different things to different people. However, the lack of a universally accepted definition may actually be part of the term's strength. We should interpret the ambiguity of this term as showing the untapped potential of blended learning. A lack of understanding of blended learning forces teachers and curriculum designers to develop their own concepts within the context of their individual courses or institutions. A teacher's understanding of the term blended learning is typically used as a basis for lesson design. Blended learning is very important because it influences the process of designing blended learning courses. Seeing blended learning as a simple way to combine traditional learning with web-based online approaches, many teachers add additional online activities to their traditional face-to-face lessons and call it blended learning. By examining the various processes involved in designing blended learning courses, we identified three distinct design approaches.

- Moderate Impact Blending: Adding additional activities to an existing course
- Medium Impact Blending: Modifying Activities in an Existing Curriculum
- High-impact mixing: Creating a new mixing trend.

We categorized these approaches as moderate-impact, medium-impact, and high-impact combinations tailored to the existing teaching program and potential changes to the student learning experience.

Moderate Impact Blending

In a moderate-impact approach, additional online activities are added to the traditional face-to-face curriculum. Also, most teachers designing blended courses find themselves adding online components to their traditional courses without removing any of the existing activities. Adding additional online activities to an already established curriculum is a common occurrence for inexperienced teachers when developing their first blended learning course. These teachers try to reap the benefits of blended learning by simply adding it to their courses, without investing in the effort of rethinking entire course objectives in the context of the blended learning model. However, in other cases, the added activity results from a teaching requirement and proves a valuable addition to the traditional course. An example is the work of McCarthy (2010), who added an online activity to the course *Imaging Our World*. In addition to traditional teaching methods of lectures and tutorials, McCarthy requires her students to submit some work online to Face book and provide critiques of their peers' submissions. Create meaningful relationships between students based on online connections, resulting in discussions transferred to the classroom. McCarthy's purpose in adding online activity was to strengthen face-to-face engagement among students. He evaluated her work using weekly feedback from students, pre- and post-semester questionnaires, and project-specific reflections at the end of the semester. Significantly, he discovered that the additional functionality provided by Face book created a platform for students to make early academic and social connections with their peers, while meeting a variety of learning needs.

Medium Impact Blending

In the medium-impact approach allows teachers to start simply, implement incrementally, and change course components as needed. This approach, an existing course is redesigned by replacing some face-to-face activities with an online component. The assumption behind this approach is that certain parts of the course will be more effective as online activities. In some cases, the rest of the face-to-face sessions are likely to be kept the same, while in other cases, some changes may be made to the content activities. It also involves engaging students in sustained and meaningful communication. Furthermore, the experience gained in using this approach helps to build teachers' confidence in effective learning. It is a useful approach for teachers with some experience in designing for blended learning who do not want to make significant changes to their courses. Teachers prefer to teach in the same traditional way that they are familiar and comfortable with, and it is necessary to consider that it is difficult and challenging to invest considerable time and effort in developing a new curriculum. Current opportunities provide teachers to experiment with different approaches to learning and many types of educational technology without losing the full benefits of traditional curriculum. Also, learning to use technology in an appropriate and effective way is challenging and can be improved with experience.

High-impact mixing

The blended learning course is newly structured in a high impact approach. This approach has been variously described as full redesign, total redesign, and radical change. Instead of looking at a lesson as a whole, the instructor should look at the learning outcomes of each lesson. By applying this approach at the level of learning outcomes, teachers can have a more effective technology mix and create a better curriculum. Notably, this approach is consistent with a common model of curriculum development known as constructivist alignment, in which assessment tasks are aligned with learning outcomes. It gives teachers the opportunity to reap the maximum benefits of blended learning and better meet the needs of students. Creating a curriculum from scratch provides a great opportunity to rethink and redesign the entire curriculum keeping the needs of the learners in mind. Teachers can consider a wider selection of media to integrate into their courses and it will also increase the effectiveness of the lessons. This approach provides an opportunity to improve or reduce and eliminate problems in the current curriculum, and teachers begin this process with a fresh perspective with a better chance of coming up with a more successful curriculum. Especially, it is helpful when traditional people have some problems. Creating an effective integration of face-to-face and online components is necessary to create a new curriculum that allows better integration of online and face-to-face components.

Conclusion

Institutional support is a key factor in the success of this approach. Achieving an effective blended learning experience requires a holistic curriculum design, and to ensure this, there must be a high level of institutional support in the form of time release, professional development, financial and technical support. Given the large number of online presences, it is important to note that teachers with no prior experience should undergo professional development that focuses on the proper use of new educational technologies. The role of educational designers is very important, not only to advise in the development phase but also to revise the new curriculum. The main concern here is that this definition can also be used to describe a purely face-to-face course or a purely distance learning course. It does not mean anything about the process of blending elements of blended courses. Thoughtlessly adding a different teaching method to a traditional curriculum would make it a blended course by this definition.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning is an innovative concept in education. It requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some elements of student control over time, place, path, or pace. Teachers are still a key part of blended learning teachers who have subject-matter expertise and basic technology skills, along with the new pedagogies that go with technology, such as constructivism and collaboration. Blended learning expertise provides both. Blended learning needs rigorous efforts, right attitude, handsome budget and highly motivated teachers and students for its successful implementation. the advantages of both traditional teaching in the classroom and ICT supported learning including both offline learning and online learning. Blended learning is also used in professional development and training settings. Blended learning allows students to learn at their own pace and their own ability level. By including a virtual environment, learning is not limited to a physical classroom. This paper focuses on the current situation of Blended Learning and its future. Data has to be collected from multiple sources of evidence, in addition to books, journals, websites, and news papers.

Keywords: *Blended Learning, Education, ICT Supported Teaching Learning Process, Online Learning, Teacher and Students*

Introduction

The world is changing constantly and the various domains are also influenced by the change. There is no exemption even in the education domain. The evolution of the digital learning platforms has a huge impact in educational institutions and has eventually put the traditional methods in the back seat. However, there are demands for both technology and traditional learning methods. As a result of this, the art of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching gave birth to the term “Blended Learning”. According to the U.S. Department of Education (Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakia, & Jones, 2009), a blend of classroom and web-based teaching and learning offers access to the widest range of learning modes and methods for developing student skills and expertise as learners (Cleveland-Innes, 2017). Many findings on blended learning show an increase in learners’ ability to learn collaboratively, think creatively, study independently and tailor their own learning experiences to meet their individual needs.

Blended Learning

Blended learning is a combination of face-to-face experiences, in which learners are co-located, with online experiences, where learners are not at the same location. (Owston, Wideman, Murphy, & Lupshenyuk, 2008, p. 202). Blended learning is more than just a combination of delivery methods; it

includes a new way of thinking about teaching and learning. New information and communications technology means that it is much easier to support student engagement and collaboration. Based on the Community of Inquiry theoretical framework introduced by Garrison, Anderson and Archer (2000), active learning by the student is part of the design. In addition, there is an active role for the teacher to work toward active cognitive and social presence in person and online. Different from the lecturer role as expert in traditional face-to-face teaching, or the role of tutor or facilitator in traditional distance education, a “blended” teacher is actively and collaboratively designing, facilitating and directing learning. Classroom instruction time may be replaced or augmented by online learning experiences, and online learning can include varying degrees of interaction or just time alone in independent study and learning activities. However, in a quality blended learning experience, the content and activities of both in-person and online learning are integrated with one another and work toward the same learning outcomes with the same content. The various learning experiences are synthesised, complement each other, and are planned or orchestrated to run in parallel.

Characteristics of blended learning in teacher education

In blended learning the students get full opportunity for all round development of the personality. All the aspects of personality namely- cognitive, physical and emotional are developed through blended learning which is difficult to achieve in traditional mode or ICT approach if followed in isolation. Tradition classroom teaching is helpful in memory level and understanding level of teaching and so help in cognitive domain development and at same time teacher’s behaviour, playground experience and social group with classmates develop affective and physical domain at same time online experiences help in reflective level of learning so develop higher faculties of mind and social networking sites and other social interactions through internet help in right type of value development.

Role of teachers in blended learning

Blended Learning shifts the teacher’s role from knowledge provider to coach and mentor. This shift does not mean that teachers play a passive or less important role in students’ education. Quite the contrary with Blended Learning, teachers can have an even more profound influence and effect on students’ learning. Traditionally, classroom instruction has largely been teacher-directed, top-down, and one-size-fits-all, with a bit of differentiation thrown in, but with Blended Learning, it now becomes more student-driven, bottom-up, and customized, with differentiation as a main feature. Much of this new learning dynamic is due to the enhanced role technology plays in instruction. Blended Learning provides an appropriate balance between online instructions, which offers the interactive, tech-based learning, individualized pacing, and privacy that keep students continuously engaged and motivated, and teacher-led instruction, which personalizes the learning experience and adds the human elements of encouragement, compassion, and caring guidance that only teachers can give. This new learning dynamic benefits students and teachers alike. Giving students permission and space to become active learners who gain knowledge directly lets them assume some control over their learning and helps them develop self-reliance. In summary, Blended Learning combines the best aspects of online learning with the best aspects of direct instruction, helping teachers easily manage to do much more to meet student needs without adding to an already weighty workload.

Role of a learner in the blended learning

Increase student interest: When technology is integrated into school lessons, learners are more likely to be interested in, focused on, and excited about the subjects they are studying. Keep students focused for longer: The use of computers to look up information & data is a tremendous lifesaver, combined with access to resources such as the internet to conduct research. This engagement and interaction with the resources keeps students focused for longer periods than they would be with books or paper resources, this engagement also helps develop learning through exploration and research. Allow instant diagnostic information and student feedback: The ability to rapidly analyze, review and give feedback to student work, gives the teacher the ability to tailor his teaching methods and feedback for each student while improving time efficiency.

Blended learning structures in education

Many factors must be considered when choosing how to blend in-person and online teaching and learning activities. In some cases, most interactions between students and the teacher, as well as the direct delivery of instruction, take place in person in the classroom, while materials and possibly some additional activities are delivered online. In other cases, most of the class activities occur online, with infrequent meetings in person to solve problems and support community building. In some blended arrangements, students may choose which activities to complete online and which to complete in a classroom. Ideally, blends are personalised so individual students have the blend that best fits their age, life circumstances and learning needs. These are called à la carte models. Students choose what to take fully online, what to take fully in person and, when the design is available, blended courses where they choose when to go to in person classes and when to watch videos, download readings and complete assignments online. This kind of personalisation is not always available. Most important is ensuring that students are able to function well as learners with any delivery method, single-mode or blended, even if it is not their preference or the best situation for them. Teachers are valuable coaches for helping students manage in any learning situation; it is up to teachers and learning designers to offer blended activities that best suit the subject, the learners' needs and the curriculum requirements.

Successful blended learning

The most effective blended learning design offers a learner-centred approach that is personalisable and accessible (Baldwin-Evans, 2006), with the best designs integrating a range of learning opportunities that allow learners more control over their formal and informal learning actions. Together, these two main factors — the selection of relevant activities, both in-person and online, and the creation of learner-centred communities of inquiry — are fundamental to the design of impactful blended learning.

Implementation of blended learning in education system

Implementing blended learning needs a full dedication on the part of educational authorities and managements of educational institutes. It needs a well-planned design that include all from individuals top to bottom of the educational hierarchy. For preparing educational institutes for blended learning we will need to increase educational budgets, it can be done by taking help of NGOs and also coordinating with the industrial and corporate sector. These sectors can be motivated to give their financial inputs for blended learning execution as these sectors will be most benefited if, the output from these educational institutes are more efficiently groomed for the global market. The other very important issue that has to be considered is development of right type of attitudes towards this ground-breaking concept in all those who are concerned with educational system. For changes in attitudes of parents, community, teachers and students awareness programmes, seminars, discussion forums should be organised. These can be utilized to make people aware about the benefits of blended learning so that a right mind set is prepared for its implementation. Mass media can well be utilized for this purpose.

Conclusion

Teacher training programmes both in-service and pre-service teachers have to be reoriented to prepare teachers for blended learning approach. The finance and efforts that are put in for various projects to meet education for all should be re directed in preparing our primary schools for blended learning as it will cater many problems simultaneously and both finance and efforts are more fruitfully utilized. To conclude it can be said that blended learning is to some extent is the solution to problems prevailing in our educational system. If implemented in a well-planned, organised way with right type of attitudes it can become the future of our educational system. It is in our own benefit that steps for adapting blended learning are soon initiated. Universities and parent bodies need to ensure checking essential requirements to begin with and them should monitor processes to ensure successful implementation of Blended Learning. Blended Learning mode is to be used nation-wide to help learners develop 21st century skills along with the effective learning and skill development related to the subject-domains. Blended Learning should be carefully implemented and should not be replacing classroom time as a privilege. Every institute should strive to be a model institute to demonstrate a successful implementation of Blended Learning in the higher education of our country.

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TEACHING IN BLENDED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

In this paper, to discuss Blended learning is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with traditional place based classroom methods. It requires the physical presence of student, with some elements of student control over time, place, path or pace. Blended learning is also used in professional development and training settings. This paper focuses role of learner in the blended learning environment, Blended structures in Education. Data has to be collected, from multiple sources of evidence, in addition to books, journals, websites and newspapers. It explores the main Blended structures in education. “Blended learning is not just a trend, and we’re starting to see technology integrated in really intentional ways”. – Katie Linder

Keywords: *Blended learning, structures in education, MOOC, rotation model.*

Introduction

Blended learning has received increasing attention with the infusion of web- based technologies into the learning and teaching process. Virtually all courses in higher education incorporate information and communication technologies to some degree. These technologies create new opportunities for students to interact with their peers, faculty, and content. Blended learning inherently demands a fundamental rethinking of the educational experience and presents a challenge to traditional presentation approach. Blended learning is the inspiration of much of the innovation, both pedagogically and technologically in higher education. The strength of integrating face - to - face synchronous communication and text based online asynchronous is powerfully complementary for higher educational purposes. Blended learning is the integration of traditional face- to – learning with technology, the internet and distance learning. Oxford dictionary defines “Blended learning is a style of education in which students learn via electronic and online media as well as traditional face- to- face teaching. Graham (2006) defines Blended learning as follows: “Blended learning systems combine face to face instruction with computer mediated instruction”.

Role of learner in the blended learning environment

- **Increase Student Interest-** When technology integrated into school lessons, learners are more likely to be interested in, focused on, and excited about the subjects they are studying.
- **Keep students focused for longer** - The use of computers to look up information and data is a tremendous lifesaver, combined with access to resources such as the internet to conduct research. This engagement and interaction with the resources keeps students focused for longer periods than they would be with books or paper resources, this engagement also helps develop learning through exploration and research.
- **Provide student autonomy** - The use of learning materials increases a student's ability to set appropriate learning goals and take charge of his or her own learning which develops an ability that will be transferable across all subjects.
- **Promote student ownership** - Blended learning instills a sense of “student ownership learning “ which can be a powerful force propelling the learning, its feeling of responsibility that helps the feeling of ownership.
- **Enables students to learn at their own pace** - Due to flexibility of blended learning and the ability to access internet resources allows students to learn at their own pace, meaning a teacher can help speed up the learning process or give more advanced resources if necessary.

Blended learning structures in education

Many factors must be considered when choosing how to blend in-person and online teaching and learning activities. In some cases, most interactions between students and the learner, as well as the direct delivery of instruction, take place in person in the classroom, while materials and possibly some additional activities are delivered online. In some blended arrangements students may choose which activities to complete online and which to complete in a classroom. Teachers are valuable coaches for helping students manage in any learning situation: it is up to teachers and learning designers to offer blended activities that best suit the subject, the learner's needs and the curriculum requirements. Not all unique and interesting blended learning designs are one size fits all models. Below are seven sample configurations of blended activities to consider for blended learning teaching situation. These examples of blended learning are drawn from higher education but can be shaped to fit any teaching and learning situation.

Blended face - to - face class

Also sometimes called the “face – to face driver model” the blended face – to – face class model is based in the classroom, although a significant amount of classroom time has been replaced by online activities. Seat time is required for this model, while online activities are needed to supplement the in-person classes; reading, quizzes or other assessment are done online at home. This model allows students and faculty to share more high value instructional time because class time is used for higher – order learning activities such as discussion and group subjects.

Blended online class

Sometimes referred to as the “online driver model” this class is the inverse of the blended face – to face class. The class is mostly conducted online but there are some required in – person activities such as lectures or labs.

The flipped classroom

The flipped classroom reverses the traditional class structure of listening to a lecture in class and completing homework activities at home. Students in flipped classes watch a short lecture video online and come into the classroom to complete activities such as group work, projects or other exercise. The flipped classroom model can be seen as a sub – model of the blended face – to face or blended online class.

The self – blend model

While many of the blended learning models on this list are at the course level, self-blending is a programme – level model and is familiar to many college students. Learners using this model are enrolled in a school but take online courses in addition to their traditional face to face courses. They are not directed by a faculty member and choose which courses they will take and which they will take in person.

The blended MOOC

The blended MOOC is a form of flipped classroom using in-person class meetings to supplement a massive open online course students access MOOC materials – perhaps from another institution or instructor if the course is openly accessible – outside of class and then come to a class meeting for discussions or in-class activities.

Flexible mode courses

Flexible – mode courses offer all instruction is multiple models in person and online, students choose how to take their courses.

The rotation model

In this model, students in a course rotate between various modalities, one of which is online learning. There are various sub-models: station rotation, lab rotation and individual rotation. Some of these sub – models are better suited to K-12 education; station rotation - for example, a requires students to rotate between stations in the classroom at an instructor’s directions, others work well on a college campus; the lab rotation model, for example, requires students in a course to rotate among location on campus at least one of which is an online lab. In the individual rotation model, students relates through learning modalities on a customised schedule.

Conclusion

The study concluded blended learning mode is to be used nationwide to help learners develop 21st century skills along with the effective learning and skill – development related to the subject domains. Blended learning should be carefully implemented and should not be replacing classroom time as a privilege. Every institute should strive to be a model institute to demonstrate a successful implementation of blended learning in the higher education of our country.

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NEP 2020 AND BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

The years 2020 and NEP 2020 have had a profound global impact in all areas of Education, healthcare, manufacturing, information technology, and other economic sectors. The Education sector has been impacted in terms of assessment, evaluation, and teaching-learning strategies. Many traditional pedagogies have been modified, and teaching and learning procedures have been made more flexible for the benefit of students. It requires both the teacher and the student to be physically present, with some student control over the time, location, path, or pace. While there is still a teacher present in "brick-and-mortar" schools, face-to-face classroom activities are blended with computer-mediated content and delivery activities, such as online and off-line. Blended learning has proven to be an effective method for delivering high-quality education.

Keywords: *Blended learning, NEP-2020*

Introduction

According to NEP 2020, education is essential for realising one's potential as a person, creating a just and equitable society, and advancing national development. The secret to India's continued rise and leadership on the international stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality, scientific advancement, national integration, and cultural preservation is providing universal access to high-quality education through blended learning approaches. The best method to develop and maximise our nation's many skills and resources for the benefit of the individual, society, the nation, and the world is through universal, high-quality education. Over the next ten years, India will have the most young people of any country in the world, and the future of our nation will depend on our capacity to offer them chances for high-quality education. The idea of such policy With the goal of making India a global knowledge superpower, this National Education Policy envisions an education system with roots in Indian culture that directly contributes to developing Bharat, or India, into a vibrant and egalitarian knowledge society. According to the policy, our institutions' curricula and pedagogy must foster in students a strong sense of respect for their country, a connection to their country, and a conscientious understanding of their tasks and responsibilities in a changing world. The goal of the strategy is to instil in students a genuine sense of pride in their Indian heritage, not just in their thoughts but also in their spirits, minds, and deeds. It also aims to foster knowledge. The world is changing constantly, and the various domains are also influenced by this change. There is no exemption, even in the education domain. The evolution of digital learning platforms has had a huge impact on educational institutions and has eventually put the traditional methods in the back seat. However, there are demands for both technology and traditional learning methods. As a result of this, the art of combining digital learning tools with more traditional face-to-face classroom teaching gave birth to the term "Blended Learning." This chapter deals with the educational transformations and the prerequisites for blended learning.

Indian Education System

Since time immemorial, there is a constant change to learning process in India. From Gurukula's where students used to stay isolated from their home and family members to seek education along with life skills, under the close monitoring of a dedicated guru. Here the guru used to be a mentor, he supposed to be the reason behind all the accomplishments of his students. Education used to happen in a remote place, where focused approach, without any distractions was ensured, their contact with the family members was very limited. Life during this period was very simple and dedicated to only for learning. This was same for students as well as guru's. Hence, more importance was given to teacher – student relationship. Education during this time was focused on physical and mental development of students. The resultant of such education system is creation of many iconic minds, greatest rulers, and scholars during those times. Universities like, Nalanda, Takshashila are some of the prominent learning centers. Once students learn their skills, an opportunity was provided to assimilate with public in a way to test their learning in the actual way of life. It was actual blend of classroom and practical exposure to create strong minds to serve society. The major changes to Indian education system have witnessed during colonial rule. Especially Lord Macauley's recommendation. "A single shelf of good European library was worth the whole native literature of India and Arabia". This is the exact phrase mentioned by Lord Macauley in his justification to detect age old Indian education system. The industrial age changed the way to learning to create workforce for industries by training them to follow just instructions.

NEP 2020

The National Policy on Education was framed in 1986 and modified in 1992. Since then several changes have taken place that calls for a revision of the Policy. The NEP 2020 is the first education policy of the 21st century and replaces the thirty-four year old National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986. Built on the foundational pillars of Access, Equity, Quality, Affordability and Accountability, this policy is aligned to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and aims to transform India into a vibrant knowledge society and global knowledge superpower by making both school and college education more holistic, flexible, multidisciplinary, suited to 21st century needs and aimed at bringing out the unique capabilities of each student. The New Education Policy 2020 provides to all students, irrespective of their place of residence, a quality education system, with particular focus on historically marginalized, disadvantaged, and underrepresented groups. The NEP 2020 seeks to “**ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all**” by 2030. This aspirational goal remains a stark contrast to

India's learning outcomes which remain stubbornly low. It has drawn much attention to the theme of inclusive and equitable education National Education Policy 2020 has explored many possibilities and dimensions to make education a comprehensive and equivalent to global requirements. An effort made to align the education system to bring into world forum. Hence, no thought to go back towards gurukul way of learning. Technology has played a major role in shaping such changes to new education policy. Main reason for such change is internet. With high penetration and speed, internet has arrived at every corner of the house, creating many possibilities to learning. Blended Learning is one such major outcome due to this technological advancement.

Technology Use and Integration in NEP 2020

India is a global leader in information and communication technology and in other cutting-edge domains, such as space. The Digital India Campaign is helping to transform the entire nation into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. While education will play a critical role in this transformation, technology itself will play an important role in the improvement of educational processes and outcomes; thus, the relationship between technology and education at all levels is bidirectional. Use and integration of technology to improve multiple aspects of education will be supported and adopted, provided these interventions are rigorously and transparently evaluated in relevant contexts before they are scaled up. An autonomous body, the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF), will be created to provide a platform for the free exchange of ideas on the use of technology to enhance learning, assessment, planning, administration, and so on, both for school and higher education. The aim of the NETF will be to facilitate decision making on the induction, deployment, and use of technology, by providing to the leadership of education institutions, State and Central governments, and other stakeholders, the latest knowledge and research as well as the opportunity to consult and share best practices. The NETF will have the following functions:

- provide independent evidence-based advice to Central and State Government agencies on technology-based interventions;
- build intellectual and institutional capacities in educational technology;
- envision strategic thrust areas in this domain; and
- articulate new directions for research and innovation.

This policy has been formulated at a time when an unquestionably disruptive technology - Artificial Intelligence (AI) 3D/7D Virtual Reality - has emerged. As the cost of AI-based prediction falls, AI will be able to match or outperform and, therefore, be a valuable aid to even skilled professionals such as doctors in certain predictive tasks. AI's disruptive potential in the workplace is clear, and the education system must be poised to respond quickly. One of the permanent tasks of the NETF will be to categorize emergent technologies based on their potential and estimated timeframe for disruption, and to periodically present this analysis to MHRD. The thrust of technological interventions will be for the purposes of improving teaching learning and evaluation processes, supporting teacher preparation and professional development, enhancing educational access, and streamlining educational planning, management, and administration including processes related to admissions, attendance, assessments, etc.

Technology in Education

An autonomous body, the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF), will be created to provide a platform for the free exchange of ideas on the use of technology to enhance learning, assessment, planning, administration. Appropriate integration of technology into all levels of education will be done to improve classroom processes, support teacher professional development, enhance educational access for disadvantaged groups and streamline educational planning, administration and management. Technology-based education platforms, such as DIKSHA/SWAYAM, will be better integrated across school and higher education. HEIs will play an active role in conducting research on disruptive technologies and in creating instructional materials and courses including online courses in cutting-edge domains.

Online Education and Digital Education:

A comprehensive set of recommendations for promoting online education consequent in the recent rise in epidemics and pandemics in order to ensure preparedness with alternative modes of quality education whenever and wherever traditional and in-person modes of education are not possible, has been covered. A dedicated unit for the purpose of orchestrating the building of digital infrastructure, digital content and

capacity building will be created in the MHRD to look after the e-education needs of both school and higher education.

Blended Learning

The world is changing constantly and the various domains are also influenced by the change. There is no exemption even in the education domain. The evolution of the digital learning platforms has a huge impact in educational institutions and has eventually put the traditional methods in the back seat. However, there are demands for both technology and traditional learning methods. As a result of this, the art of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching gave birth to the term “Blended Learning”. This chapter deals about the educational transformations and the prerequisite for Blended Learning. **Blended learning**, also known as **technology-mediated instruction**, **web-enhanced instruction**, or **mixed-mode instruction**. Hybrid model is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. The important features of Blended Learning (hereafter referred to as BL) environment are:

- Increased student engagement in learning.
- Enhanced teacher and student interaction
- Responsibility for learning.
- Time management and flexibility
- Improved student learning outcomes
- Enhanced institutional reputation.
- More flexible teaching and learning environment

Conclusion

This study indicated that issues and challenges related to BL can be divided into four categories, such as universities, teachers, students, and technical aspects. Among these issues, institutional culture is one of the most prominent challenges. Similarly, teachers must deal with a variety of other issues, such as increased workload, increased time commitment, a lack of BL skills, and difficulty in finding the right blend for their curriculum. The students were not skilled in ICT technology and had a diverse background. Technological barriers are also creating problems in BL. A teacher should know exactly what tool to use, when to use it and how much to use it. A teacher can't be replaced completely with technology since he knows clearly the level of learning curve of each student. What kind of guidance each student needs, what pace to use, how it should be facilitated, how the same should be blended with various components. Learning should not be limited to delivery, but to make an impact, it should also focus on engaging and challenging individuals to surmount their limitations. Empowering teachers and making them the centre of the learning process should be the main objectives of blended learning. Otherwise, a gradual disconnect will develop, and slowly the link between teacher and learner will disappear. This will lead to more perception building among young citizens in society and future generations.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning is now part of the learning landscape in teacher education, not just for campus-based courses but for courses designed for students studying at a distance as well as for communities of professional learning and practice. Issues in teaching and learning in both campus based and distance settings are then described followed by a discussion of the way blended learning provides a process for establishing communities of learning and practice, particularly for professional learning. Much of the literature about professional learning and learning communities has only just begun to identify aspects of blended learning practices in significant, this approach enables the introduction of an e-Learning activity into a face-to-face setting which is considered as a single phenomenon with little effort being made to distinguish between the issue of e-Learning and that of blending. The Discussion of blended learning environment covers models of blended learning environments, benefits of BL

Keywords: *E-learning , Blended learning, Models of BL , Benefits of BL*

Introduction

Blended learning is the term given to the educational practice of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching it is a type of multi-channel method incorporates tutored activities, images, video digital tasks and face-to-face discussion. Blended learning helps Students to explore Technology and use different tools or techniques for learning. For example, PowerPoint, Virtual classrooms ,Video lectures, etc. Blended learning improves the quality of education and information assimilation while making teaching more efficient and productive. The past year and the pandemic have reinforced the fact that Life is unpredictable and we need to brace ourselves and we ready to survive this physical nature of existence. Similarly, The education system needs to adopt methods like blended learning. To ensure that the process of learning never stops. The arbitrary nature of blended learning reverberates in the different definitions of the term:

- Combining instructional modalities (or delivery media) (Bersin & Associates, 2003; Orey, 2002; Singh & Reed, 2001; Thomson, 2002)
- Combining instructional methods (House, 2002; Rosset, 2002)
- Combining onine and face-to-face instruction (Reay, 2001; Rooney, 2003; Sands, 2002; Ward & LaBranche, 2003;)

The Movement towards hybridisations recognition of the considerable benefits that technology offers to the learning process. The promise of technology. Extends beyond customization of the curriculum and mode of learning.

Blended Learning

A blended learning mode provides ultimate flexibility in many aspects. And most of all, It can be applied to any programme which holds on to the values of traditional learning and incorporates digital media with that. It is a lot more effective and likeable than anything that has been ever before. Students, policy makers, etc. Appreciate the needed flexibility. Only well- crafted, blended solution can provide a seamless transition from classroom to computer or vice versa. Though there are many teaching methods and techniques. Available resources indicate that blended learning mode is the “best of all worlds”. It is the best because it helps all learning requirements and styles through a variety of mediums and techniques. Recently, many learning platforms globally have adopted blended learning and is also one of the most adopted learning tools. The important features of blended learning environment are:

- Increased student engagement in learning.
- Enhanced Teacher and student interaction.
- Responsibility for learning.
- Time management and flexibility.
- Improved student learning outcomes.
- More flexible teaching and learning environment.

- Better opportunities for experiential learning.

Models of Blended Learning

The majority of blended-learning programs resemble one of four models: Rotation, Flex, A La Carte, and Enriched Virtual. The Rotation model includes four sub-models: Station Rotation, Lab Rotation, Flipped Classroom, and Individual Rotation.

- **Rotation model** - A course or subject in which students rotate on a fixed schedule or at the teacher's discretion between learning modalities, at least one of which is online learning. Other modalities might include activities such as small-group or full-class instruction, group projects, individual tutoring, and pencil-and-paper assignments. The students learn mostly on the brick-and-mortar campus, except for any homework assignments.
- **Station Rotation** - A course or subject in which students experience the Rotation model within a contained classroom or group of classrooms. The Station Rotation model differs from the Individual Rotation model because students rotate through all of the stations.
- **Lab Rotation** - A course or subject in which students rotate to a computer lab for the online-learning station.
- **Flipped Classroom** - A course in which students participate in online learning off-site in place of traditional homework and then attend the brick-and-mortar school for face-to-face, teacher-guided practice or projects. The primary delivery of content and instruction is online, which differentiates a Flipped Classroom from students who are merely doing homework practice online at night.
- **Individual Rotation** - A course in which each student has an individualized playlist and does not necessarily rotate to each available station or modality. An algorithm or teacher(s) sets individual student schedules.
- **Flex model** — Online learning is the backbone of student learning, even if it directs students to offline activities at times. Students move on an individually customized learning modalities. The teacher of record is on-site, and students learn mostly on the brick-and-mortar campus, except for any homework assignments. The teacher provide face-to-face support on a flexible and adaptive as-needed basis through activities such as small-group instruction, group projects, and individual tutoring. For example, some Flex models may have face-to-face enrichment. Still others may have different staffing combinations.
- **A La Carte model** — Student takes entirely online to accompany other experiences that the student is having at a brick-and-mortar school or learning center. The teacher of record for the A La Carte course is the online teacher. Students may take the A La Carte course either on the brick-and-mortar campus or off-site. This differs from full-time online learning because it is not a whole-school experience.
- **Enriched Virtual model** — a course or subject in which students have required face-to-face learning sessions with their teacher of record and then are free to complete their remaining coursework remote from the face-to-face teacher. The same person generally serves as both the online and face-to-face teacher. Many Enriched Virtual programs began as full-time online schools and then developed blended programs to provide students with brick-and-mortar school experiences. The Enriched Virtual model differs from the Flipped Classroom because in Enriched Virtual programs, students seldom meet face-to-face with their teachers every weekday. It differs from a fully online course.

Benefits of Blended Learning

- Different people learn different things in different ways
- Using multiple modalities dramatically reinforces engagement, learning and retention
- Learners can control the pace of their learning
- Blended learning saves money
- Blended learning is modular and scalable

Jane Hart, Editor of Modern Workplace Learning magazine, says, “For real transformation to take place, it’s not a matter of having a ‘bolt-on’ strategy to existing training practices (‘typically social and mobile’), but rather ‘a full-on, meaningful re-conception’ of what it means to support all ways of learning in the modern digital workplace.”

Conclusion

Blended learning has positive impact to the learning process. Some researchers stated that blended learning can enhance students' learning outcomes, improve students' motivation, and it is effective way for achieving learning objectives.

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STRENGTHENING BLENDED TEACHING STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS AMONG TEACHERS

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Abstract

Blended method, this new dynamic learning and teaching strategy facilitates teachers to bring about the desired standards in teacher education to compete in the digital era. This strategy has the potential to optimize the array of learning opportunities for students to reinforce their learning efficiency. It provides teachers with a complete picture of how students will perform and strengthen their academic outcomes. The paper aims to make the teachers recognize the the timely interventions to be made in their teaching strategies to empower students to be self-reliant and independent. Adopting blended teaching in one's classroom improves the teacher's professional standards which maximizes the effectiveness of the instruction to master learning in students. The very purpose of varying your delivery modes mostly student-centric caters to the needs of individual differences of the students. The personality of the educators influences the blooming personality of the students while improving the quality of teaching through integrating technology and working efficiently catering to diversity in today's classroom.

Keywords: *Blended teaching, Professional standards, Teachers*

Introduction

Teachers should have a broader outlook towards welcoming changes in teaching approaches. Maintaining quality in teacher education to meet the global challenges in this competitive world rests on the quality of teachers. Well-trained teachers in implementing blended mode of instruction develop content in digital form to make it available to the students through creative exercises and collaborative learning. For this, the pre-service training program has to be reoriented to explore new pathways in the learning environment and attain the universal goal of education. Despite its few drawbacks, the traditional method of teaching adds a crucial human element to the process of teaching and learning.

The advantages of both traditional classroom instruction and ICT-supported learning, including both offline and online learning, are combined in the novel idea of blended learning. ICT-supported teaching and learning processes are a good option to increase students' exposure, reduce teaching errors, improve quality, and align their knowledge with current technological advancements and globalization.

Blended Learning

“Blended learning is the thoughtful integration of classroom face-to-face learning experiences with online learning experiences” claimed Garrison and Kanuka (2004). “Every learning style should be taken into account when creating a blended course. For instance, presentation slides with text, images, and diagrams should be used for visual learners. Podcasts, audio files, and lectures work best for auditory learners in their lessons. Kinesthetic learners pick up new information by copying, attempting, holding, and feeling things. The process of doing things leads to deeper learning. With blended learning, students can

take flexible online lessons whenever and wherever they like while also having the opportunity to ask questions about anything they are unclear about in the classroom. This pedagogical approach involves a combination of in-person and online activities as well as the incorporation of synchronous and asynchronous learning tools, offering the best opportunity for the design of efficient learning processes. In the realm of educational transformation, technology is a critical element in the learning process of the students to meet their academic targets.

Approaches to Blended Methodology

The development of digital learning platforms has a significant impact on educational institutions, ultimately pushing traditional approaches to the sidelines.

Utilize a variety of Instructional Resources

In a traditional method where textbooks were considered as a resource to cherish, others to supplement teaching like audio-books, audio-video cassettes, and online materials are nowadays used to provide a truly blended experience.

- Providing online discussion groups with an expert to reinforce learning in difficult concepts in science, math and other disciplines.
- Using multiple instructional materials will surely aid the visual, audio and kinesthetic learners to sustain their learning and attain educational goals.
- Incorporating technology can vary the monotony of evaluation like oral-written texts or essay-type questions through providing online quizzes, activities and assigning works online to make assessment easier than before.
- Prepare a variety of instructional materials like digital content with fun activities for maximum student engagement and interaction.
- Inculcate creative thinking, complex problem-solving, critical-thinking skills by providing math-puzzle, sketching, poster-making, art and craft in a synchronous mode.

Incorporating Digital teaching tools

Differentiated Instruction helps improve students understanding and retention of information. Technology assists instructors for content creation, online labs, practical lessons to teach the students to reinforce their learning through supplementing materials freely from the internet.

- Learners are more likely to be interested in, focused on, and excited about the subjects they are studying when technology is incorporated into classroom lessons.
- Showing students visuals of the scientific concepts they learned theoretically through variety of strategies like computer-assisted instruction, learning-management systems like google classroom, power-point presentations.
- Digital tools like Visme offers educators to create interactive posters, webinars, infographics, worksheets and personalized activities.
- Scheduling events for students in the form of presentation will help them stay on track with the classroom events daily.
- Report students progress every intervals of time for their upgradation through sending report cards to parents, guardians online when distance is a constraint.

Collaborative Learning at a Distance

Providing lectures, presentations, activities and assessments through blended learning approach helps them showcase their talents in different modes of evaluation tools .It helps them analyze their strengths, make them improve simultaneously and paves way for collaborative learning. The following are the advantages for teachers and learners to collaborate at a distance.

- Providing a few remote-learning classes amplifies in-person engagement to learn at a pace at their own comfortable space and time.
- Eliminates isolation and enhances interaction among students when they collaborate with their peers at a distance, talk with the experts, or perform laboratory experiments online.
- Educators share their knowledge base, research work in virtual environments to discuss novel approaches, shared expertise, critical soft-skills, technological and scientific advancements.

- Collaboration requires transparency for individual growth and community development which is very much assured from the digital platform
- Teachers can work on a group-project providing space for individual accountability and independent learning.

Provide for a variety of learning styles

As a teacher, one method and one learning style does not suit all types of learners. Blended learning is a method for improving educational outcomes and program delivery costs in institutions by offering multiple delivery options. As per NEP 2020, Equity in education take place if every learner is provided opportunity to education through any means whether digital or traditional.

- Mentoring students through gamification, e-learning, video classes, Online tutoring and LMS for optimal retention and achievement.
- Visual Memory test can be administered for the students to evaluate their learning by providing learning through reducing vast amount of information into chunks in video classes.
- Training and remedial coaching can be given to students who are not above the average level through repeated tutoring in programmed instruction.
- Preparing learners for the future making teachers personalize content and create appropriate learning activities for each kind of learner.

Conclusion

This engagement and interaction with the resources keeps students focused for longer periods than they would be with books or paper resources, this engagement also helps develop learning through exploration and research. Teachers are valuable assets for helping students to offer blended activities that best suit the subject, the learners' needs, and the curriculum requirements and manage any learning situation. Online learning provides ample opportunities for inducing creativity and innovation, concrete experience in learners and reflective observation for teachers.

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BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENTING BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Introduction

Blended Learning, Web-Enhanced Instruction also known as mixed-methods instruction, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for online interaction with physical space-based classroom methods. Blended learning requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some element of student control over time, space, path, or pace. Because blended learning is so context-specific, a universal conceptualization of it is difficult. Some report that lack of consensus on a hard definition of blended learning has caused problems in research on its effectiveness. A well-cited 2013 study broadly defined blended learning as a combination of online and in-person delivery. Additionally, in 2015 Meta-analysis, looking back historically at a comprehensive review of evidence-based research studies surrounding blended learning, found commonalities in defining blended learning as "the combination of physical [face-to-face] and online instructional methods. Learning methods, drawing on technology-mediated instruction, involve all participants in the learning process at times." separated by distance." All of these evidence-based studies also found that student achievement was higher in blended learning experiences when compared to fully online or fully face-to-face learning experiences.

Vocabulary

The terms blended learning, "blended learning," "technology-mediated instruction," "Internet-enhanced instruction," and "mixed-mode instruction" are often used interchangeably in the research literature. Although the concepts behind blended learning were first developed in the 1960s, the formal terminology describing it did not take its current form until the late 1990s. One of the earliest uses of the term appears in a 1999 press release in which Atlanta-based education business Interactive Learning Centers currently operates 220 online courses. The term blended learning was initially vague, covering a variety of technologies and teaching methods in various combinations (some using no technology at all). The term became more concrete with the publication of the first handbook of blended learning by Bank and Graham. Graham challenged the breadth and vagueness of the term's definition and defined "blended learning systems" as learning systems that "combine face-to-face instruction with computer-mediated instruction."

Samples

There is no consensus on the definition of blended learning. Some academic studies have suggested that this is a redundant term. However, there are unique blended learning models advocated by some researchers and academic think tanks. These models include:

- Face-to-face driver- Teacher directs instruction and augments with digital tools.
- Flex- Most courses are delivered via a digital platform and tutors are available for face-to-face advice and support.
- Laboratories- All courses are delivered via a digital platform, but in a fixed physical location. Students also typically take physical classes in this model.
- Self-mixing- Students choose to enhance their physical learning through online coursework.
- Online driver- Students complete the entire course through an online platform with possible teacher check-ins. All curriculum and teaching are delivered via a digital platform and face-to-face meetings are scheduled or made available as needed.
- Instructor-delivered content, e-learning, webinars, conference calls, live or online sessions with instructors, and other media and events, for example, Facebook, Including a blended learning model with multiple components such as e-mail. Chat rooms, blogs, podcasting, Twitter, YouTube, Skype, and web boards.

Benefits

- Blended instruction is more effective than purely face-to-face or purely online classes.
- Blended learning methods can also result in higher achievement levels for high-ability students than face-to-face learning.
- By using a combination of digital instruction and one-on-one face-to-face time, students can work on their own with new concepts freeing up teachers to disseminate and support individual students who need individual attention.
- "Instead of playing in a less common classroom—as they would in a physical classroom—teachers can now organize their instruction to help all students reach their full potential."
- Proponents of blended learning argue that incorporating "asynchronous Internet communication technology" into higher education courses helps to "facilitate a simultaneous independent and collaborative learning experience."
- Learning applications detected
- Curriculum through the merger, communication between lecturers and part-time students has improved, and students have been able to better assess their understanding of the course through "computer-based qualitative and quantitative assessment modules".
- Blended learning has the potential to reduce the cost of education. Blended learning reduces costs by placing classrooms online. And it replaces expensive textbooks with electronic devices. Digitally accessible e-textbooks can help reduce textbook budgets. Proponents of blended learning cite the opportunity for customization of data collection and instruction and assessment as two major advantages of this approach.
- Software that often automatically collects student data and measures academic progress in blended learning provides comprehensive student data to teachers, students, and parents. Often, tests are scored automatically, providing instant feedback.

- Student logins and work hours are also measured to ensure accountability. Schools with blended learning programs may also choose to reallocate resources to increase student achievement outcomes.
- Students with special talents or interests outside the available curriculum to improve their skills or exceed grade restrictions. Using educational technology.
- Blended learning allows for personalized education, replacing the model where one teacher stands in front of the classroom and everyone is expected to be at the same pace.
- Blended learning allows students to work at their own pace and ensures they fully understand new concepts.
- Some indicators of well-blended learning programs include "facilitating student learning, communicating ideas effectively, demonstrating interest in learning, organizing effectively, showing respect for students, and assessing progress fairly".

Evils

- If not successfully planned and implemented, blended learning can have disadvantages in technological aspects because it relies heavily on technological resources or tools that provide a blended learning experience. These tools must be reliable, easy to use, and up-to-date to have a meaningful impact on the learning experience.
- Blended learning has several drawbacks. While this type of learning gives students the ability to go online when needed or learn from anywhere, there is no guarantee that every student will have access to the tools they need to learn on the computer.
- Another problem that can arise is unreliable internet. Many times, the internet may be down.
- If the whole class doesn't have the same tools, the teacher can't keep the class on the same page. This creates a learning gap within classrooms.
- If the education system cannot provide reliable internet and computers to all students, it cannot be ensured that it is an effective substitute for mainstream education.
- From an educator's perspective, it has recently been noted that providing effective feedback when using electronic media is more time-consuming (and therefore more expensive) compared to traditional (e.g. paper-based) assessments.
- Using e-learning platforms may be more time-consuming than traditional methods and may come with new costs, as e-learning platforms and service providers may charge educators user fees.
- Finally, in academic disciplines where professional simulation and clinical-based placement are key components (ie, medicine, obstetrics, and gynaecology), in-person teaching is the cornerstone of clinical skills education, and teaching through online discourse alone is insufficient to fully replace and deliver.

21st Century Literacy

To describe the sociality of learning supported by the use of digital technologies in learning and collaboration. "Literacy for the 21st Century "By the National Council of Teachers of English was created. These 'new literacies' are described as "skills that students need for the society in which they work", including "strong communication and collaboration skills, expertise in technology, innovative and creative thinking skills and problem-solving skills".

- Manage, analyze, and integrate multiple streams simultaneously;
- create, critique, analyse, and evaluate multimedia texts;
- Attending to the ethical responsibilities these complex environments require.

Barriers to Implementing Blended Learning in Teacher Education (BIBLTE)

Barriers and solutions to blended learning in this section, we will discuss the barriers associated with the e-learning component of blended learning

- **Lack of infrastructure** - Due to lack of infrastructure, learning through technology demands reliable hardware, easy-to-use software, and high-bandwidth network connectivity, as well as skilled, trained staff to support and maintain the system.
- **Fear of technology** - Fear of the unknown and resistance to change is normal. But once a person becomes familiar with the new technology, if the enormous benefits are realized, this issue becomes insignificant.
- **E-learning apathy** - Initially there may be some reluctance to implement e-learning as a result of various reasons.

- **Assessment difficulties** - Through e-learning, a large number of students will be enrolled in many classes. Manual assessment with pen and paper for large number of students poses difficulties for teachers.
- **Difficult student counselling and curriculum planning** - In blended learning, a large number of students need advice on choosing the right courses to complete their degree requirements. These slots limit the time teachers are already occupied with lectures, teacher-marked assignments, and preparing for midterms and finals.
- **Inappropriate e-learning course material** - E-learning should be integrated into students' learning experience. A student must understand the material relevant to his experiences.
- **Poor language skills** - Most e-learning resources are in English and poor language skills and communication in English is a barrier to understanding and learning.
- **Difficulties in developing concepts and thinking skills** - Educational attainment is a significant part of any learning theory, is to develop conceptual understanding and higher-order thinking skills. Adequate Career Planning and Teacher Career Link Career planning is an important part of the learning process. It motivates students to pursue their goals. It can be challenging for a student to properly decide on a career path and what he/she wants to do from a professional standpoint.

Conclusion

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) provides opportunities to shift from instructor-centered to student-centered learning. These tools spread learning, resulting in a new society that is more developed, globally competitive, and capable of collaboration. Furthermore, we are in a global education world that believes in blended learning across multiple subjects and disciplines. A good example of blended learning is to provide a structured introductory course followed by sequential material.

Source Text

- https://enm.wikipedia.org.translate.google/wiki/Blended_learning?_x_tr_sl=en&_x_tr_tl=ta&_x_tr_hlc
- <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234635417.pdf>

ICT AND BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

We live in an period of Information conquered by Digital Technology. The whole world has disappeared into a Global village. Information is communicated within a element of a second. Everyone is obligated to equip oneself to suit the needs and demands of the society. In the recent times, technology has a great impact on the lifestyle of the people. People have accustomed to the rapid changes in the society. There is a dire need to restructure the curriculum to face the challenges in society. Earlier, persons used only the print material for searching information. With the onset of ICT, knowledge is only a click away. Blended learning solutions can be an appropriate approach to increasing access to higher education in India. The whole teaching – learning process have to be revamped, if ICT has to be introduced. ICT do not require any special setting or arrangement. The only requirement is computer systems and software. The student can use it even from home if made available on school website.

Keywords: *Blended learning, ICT, internet, technology, teacher, classroom, student*

Introduction

Education as confined to the literary terms, originated in the ancient times with the Guru Kula system. Down the ages, there has been a steady growth from the Guru Kula system to the present teaching pedagogy. New methods of teaching have to be introduced in apt with the growing trends. Teachers are on the constant vigil to improve their quality of teaching. They used teaching aids, like charts, models etc. In accordance with the digital technology, there is a need to accommodate ICT in their teaching module. This

paper discusses on the need to implement ICT and Blended learning to initiate effective learning among the students.

Information Technology

According to Smith & Campbell (1982), a mosaic of technologies, products and techniques have combined to provide new electronic dimensions to information management. This mosaic is known by the name of Information Technology. Information Technology is the technology involved with the transmission of stored information, the development and communication of information using computers. The development of Information Technology has led to the development of websites. Government, Corporate sector, educational institutions have started uploading the information on their websites. It facilitates information communication through Chat, e-mail, surfing and so on. Earlier, people used only the print material for searching information. With the onset of IT, knowledge is only a click away.

Blended Learning

Blended Learning is the learning process which combines various methods of teaching namely, face to face learning, distance learning, video – conferencing and elearning. There has been a fabulous influence of the electronic media on the lives of the adolescents in the modern society. Educational Institutions all over the world, are turning to blended learning to cater to the constructive learning of the students. New technologies formed by combining e-learning and distance learning are brought into the class room. It initiates learning opportunities outside the class room. It breaks the monotony in the class room and gives room for interaction. Researches prove that Blended Learning can produce effective learning and overcome the shortcomings of any single mode of teaching and learning.

ICT and Blended Learning

The growing use of ICT and Blended Learning has changed the face of teaching and learning process because of the onset of technological innovations. ICT provides rich material for the students and the teachers in the libraries and class rooms. This opens new opportunities for blended learning because they share experiences and technologies. Blended learning bridges the gap between Pedagogy and technology. It is a mix of the appropriate techniques and technology to enhance effective learning. Blended learning is the collaborative method and is the means to better understanding. Videoconferencing is an example. In spite of being in different time zones and linked at different local times, all participants are connected to the Video conferencing at the same time and communicate in real time. Internet chat and online instant message are other methods of ICT. Interactivity is another important feature of Communication technology. It is described as one-way or two-way communication.

One cannot ask a question or respond to an opinion in radio or TV broadcasting. They are examples of one-way technology, especially when they are pre-recorded. But by integrating telephone and email with live audio or TV broadcasting, two-way communication can be achieved. Videoconferencing is a two-way communication. Sometimes, a message is sent out at one time, a response is given later. Postal mail, e-mail and online discussion forums are all examples of asynchronous communication. Synchronous communication refers to the class room situation where the interaction takes place in real time along with the use of computers and recorded programmes. Blended Learning is multiple learning and guiding methods, where the face – to – face classes include on-line teaching modules also. ICT concentrates on real differentiation in content and learning methods. The Virtual class rooms and chat rooms provide a lot of room for interaction unlike the traditional class room. Earlier, the teacher used to take the teaching aids along with her to her class room.

With the onset of ICT, the teacher makes use of the Internet, online newspapers, web casts, etc. Students learn to listen, read, write, speak and react to a conversation using ICT as a result of Blended Learning. The students are open to novel ideas. No doubt, it promotes divergent and didactic thinking. Another form of digitalized lectures is Creating e – content. The competent teachers can develop e – content in their own areas of specialization. This has lots of potentiality to bring quality in teacher education. Instructional material and e-content are developed through ICT. Instructional materials in different subjects benefit the diverse users. The teachers who are well versed in their subjects digitalize the instructional material. Their lectures are digitalized and made available to all the users. It enhances the quality of instruction in the classrooms. The teacher uses them in the classrooms and organizes discussion among the students. The new points can be added both by the teacher as well as students. It will make the teaching

effective, participatory and enjoyable. The use of a variety of media, including print and electronic; two-way communication allows the students and teachers to interact in a tangible manner.

Need for ICT Learning

The present students live in a world, totally different from their parents. The electronic media emerged as a prominent influence on the modern society. The rise of science and technology has created a force whose educational functions challenge the traditional teaching and learning process. New technologies can stimulate the development of language skills, especially in Language learning. It spurs the spontaneous interest of the students when compared to the traditional modes of teaching. Students who use new technologies concentrate more than students in traditional settings. The impetus for constructivism is based on child – centered learning. The learner is given importance in relation to learning. Various methods are used to ensure that the student has understood that particular topic. The student is not considered as an empty vessel, rather learning is integrated with that of the prior knowledge. Experience enables individuals to build mental models, which in turn provide meaning and organization. Blended learning does not reduce costs but it improves the quality of education with innovative strategies.

Significant study of ICT and Blended Learning

No teacher can give up dates and complete information in his own subject. ICT and Blended Learning tries to fill this gap of imparting knowledge to the intrinsic detail. It develops understanding and application of concepts with varied illustrations and examples. Students and teachers can share their views and get clarification on any topic from experts. ICT provides variety in presentation content and initiates concentration and long retention of the knowledge. It also develops the power of expression and instills reasoning power. In comparison with the traditional teaching method, ICT emphasizes on improving the comprehension and the clarification of doubts are being done by the experts. In a virtual class room, the students interact with the students from different places under the guidance of the teacher. We live in an era of science and technology, where the technology is exploited to its best. The students can work on any project with the students or experts from other countries. Students who are familiar with ICT can master content faster and are better problem-solvers. They are self-directed, and are good decision makers. Knowledge is grasped beyond the class room. Teachers need to integrate their teaching along with the Internet or the online chat. They should know to challenge and respond to students. They should be prepared to facilitate Internet discussions. They should help the students, how to work the medium, how to communicate, and how to cooperate with their peers. Blended learning favours information transmission, and a reorientation in their knowledge construction. Outside the classroom, ICT literacy is essential for being productive citizens in a knowledge-driven society. Employers want their employees to have these skills. As a result, college and university administrators are beginning to require them as competencies for graduation. Blended learning is an integrated curriculum, which creates opportunities, for self- learning that is not found in a traditional, face to face classroom model within a specific discipline. It promotes cognitive and meta cognitive skills. It enhances the self – reliance of the students. It imparts scientific and technological knowledge to the learners. It saves time on the part of the teacher and students. The feedback is given immediately after the test is over, which gives an intrinsic reinforcement to the student. They do not need any special assistance from teacher. Unlike the paper-pencil test, it does not require paper setting and paper correction on the part of the teacher.

Conclusion

ICT is used only as an informational resource and facilitates its integration in a daily learning practice. The blended learning is a balance between the face to face and the online teaching. It provides multiple accessibility options to provide content delivery over TV, radio, Internet, and video conference-based communications. Blended learning access multiple methods for content development and presentation, teacher student interaction, and e-assessment. Blended learning is relatively cost effective, and can provide quality education to distant students. The pedagogy for ICT should be initiated to provide proficiency for teachers, so that they are empowered with the ICT skills.

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BLENDED LEARNING AND TEACHING OF THIRUKKURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract

Most of the students' learning approaches are inimitable based on their mental ability and understanding the subject concepts. Especially in terms of Thirukkural Education, there are different concepts among various scholars. Even though government insists to learn Thirukkural, students are not showing much interest in learning Thirukkural Education. Because of the blended learning methodology providing the easy and exceptional styles, which will attract the students from primary level to secondary level to learn Thirukkural and implement the concepts in their personal life, which cannot be learned through traditional class room teaching method. Because Thirukkural learning is not one time learning process like memorize the couplet of Kural and write it in the exam and reciting in the competition. It is the learning about life skills and personality development, which can be possible to learn through blended learning approach only. This article describes the approaches, benefits and problems in teaching Thirukkural through blended learning method.

Keywords: *Blended learning, Life skills, Personality Development, Thirukkural Education*

Introduction

Thirukkural is an Universal Veda as mentioned in Encyclopaedia. It is the only book accepted by all over world, since it covers all life skills. Government of Tamilnadu and Government of India are interested to teach Thirukkural to all the students in school education. Skill that develops individual's attitude and contribute to society's improvement is called Life skill. Thirukkural teaches various life skills through 1330 couplets of poem; all these life skills could not be taught in the formal class room method, which requires informal teaching tools to connect the everyday life aspects with improvement of knacks of perceptive, responsive, corporeal and societal. This article describes the need of blended learning and teaching method and challenges with suggestions to incorporate Thirukkural Education from primary level to secondary level school students.

Need of Blended learning on Thirukkural Education

Tamilnadu school education teaches Thirukkural. But the Life skills are not yet transformed individual and society as expected during last 50 years. Most of the adult over 50 years age expressed that Thirukkural life skills are important to their life, but they are not able to learn all the life skills from Thirukkural due the various reasons, mainly it is difficult to memorize the poem, the technique form Thirukkural is not convincing with day to day life and no time to learn Thirukkural with existing school work load for both students and teachers. Blended learning technique provides the platform to emergent user-friendliness of e-learning; it is a combination of learning methods that integrate innovative teaching models like. Students' Cooperative learning, Interactive discussion, Self-Thinking learning, User friendly Tool for teaching and learning, and Non-Academic Talk about life skills challenges.

Suggested Blended learning approach to teach Thirukkural Education

Most of the students' identified the problems in learning Thirukkural Education is to understand the meaning of words used in the couplets, translations and explanations are quite different from the original words used in the poem. The suggested blended learning to teach Thirukkural education is to teach all the words used in 1330 couplets with detailed explanation along with simple examples from primary level students itself. The words used in Thirukkural itself convey the concepts of life skills and personality development. And in the middle level students are asked to raise the questions about 133 topics in the Thirukkural. Later secondary level, Teacher has to address their questions with suitable couplets from Thirukkural. This WQE approach is suggested to teach Thirukkural Education.

Predicted benefits of Blended learning in Thirukkural Education

In general, students will not show more interest in continuing to learn Thirukkural Education. If the WQE approach of blended learning will be effectively implemented the following benefits can be achieved easily. 1. Whenever learning life skills from Thirukkural couplets, there will be chance to raise lot of doubts which can be addressed and cleared in the WQE approach because it facilitates instant communication between students and teacher. 2. Learning of life skills will achieve effectively with support from parents. 3. Getting the thinking skills about personal life decision making with the support of Thirukkural Education.

Barriers of Blended learning in Thirukkural Education

Even though technology helps to develop the blended learning models to teach life skills from Thirukkural Education, there will be some barriers yet to come across. Parents are expected the job oriented skills and recognised UGC degree from the reputed institutions. So far Tamil Nadu Government is not declared any formal degree course for Thirukkural Education. They declared that those who memorize 1330 couplets of Thirukkural will get scholarship for higher education and cash awards. But memorizing the 1330 couplets are not an easy task, due to that students and their parents are not showing much interest in Thirukkural Education. Since the existing school workload, teacher also not able to teach 1330 Thirukkural through blended learning approach.

Implementation of Thirukkural Education through Blended learning.

NEP 2020 focused to implement Life skills in Early Child Care Education (ECCE). Because of developing life skills like cooperation, resilience, communication, and creativity will be easy at ECCE stage. Thirukkural Education various life skills, we can select the suitable life skills and teach in early child level; it will help to develop the logical decision making, critical thinking and innovation. WQE approach of blended learning and teaching of Thirukkural Education will step to reach the experiential learning of students from primary level to secondary level. Educational institutions has to develop the WQE approach to attain the formal degree in Thirukkural Education with cooperation of parents

Quality of learning and Teaching Thirukkural Education through Blended Learning

Generally Education will be evaluated through written exams with descriptive answers, which is not assuring the required quality of Thirukkural Education. To improve the quality, the suggested WQE approach of blended learning can be evaluated through KAP model exams (Knowledge, Attitude, Practice). This KAP model exams will cover all the aspects of various life skills from Thirukkural Education, which can easily achievable through blended leaning system. Students can learn Thirukkural Education through training not merely memorizing the couplets. Training leads to improvement of words, examples, comparison, life skills, personality development and secrets of management. The training score should be added to degree exams then the quality of Thirukkural Education will be attained through expected quality of Thirukkural Education as per Madurai High Court order. KAP model exams will be like an objective type, descriptive type and group discussion etc.,

Conclusion

In recent years, Prime Minster mentions Thirukkural in his speech during various government functions. Even in the parliament also ministers mention Thirukkural, which creates the awareness about Thirukkural Education among Indians. But whoever interested to learn Thirukkural is forced to read the Thirukkural Translation as self-study method which will not help to complete the 1330 couplets mostly. In this situation, the WQE blended approach will guide the interested Thirukkural learners to get the proper

training and recognised degree to meet the job market. This article explains the need of life skills from Thirukkural and how it can be achieved through blended learning approach. Thirukkural Education should be trained through specific institutes like Institute of National Importance (INI), then it will be an easy approach to all the Indian language students to get their parallel degree along their regular degree course

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BLENDING LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION, SUGGESTED MODELS, APPROACHES

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Abstract

The world is changing constantly and the various domains are also influenced by the change. There is no exemption even in the education domain. The evolution of the digital learning platforms has a huge impact in educational institutions and has eventually put the traditional methods in the back seat. However, there are demands for both technology and traditional learning methods. As a result of this, the art of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching gave birth to the term "Blended Learning". This chapter deals about the educational transformations and the prerequisite for Blended Learning.

Keywords: *Safer learning environment, Traditional classroom, Flipped classrooms, Group work, innovative teaching*

Introduction

It is an instructional methodology, a teaching and learning approach that combines face-to-face classroom methods with computer mediated activities to deliver instruction. This pedagogical approach means a mixture of face-to-face and online activities and the integration of synchronous and asynchronous learning tools, thus providing an optimal possibility for the arrangement of effective learning processes. Blended learning is the term given to the educational practice of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching. In a true blended learning environment, both the student and the teacher should be physically located in the same space. Despite this, the digital tools used should be able to be utilised by the students in order to enforce some control over the speed or topics of their learning. The flipped classroom model is a similar program that aims to utilise technology in order to rearrange the learning experience and maximise the effectiveness of valuable face to face time in the classroom. In a flipped classroom programme, students would be encouraged to access digital learning materials via a cloud-based learning platform during their own time. Resources such as video lectures, podcasts, recordings and articles would be provided in order to transfer the main bulk of the necessary knowledge from teacher to student before each class. This then frees up time in class for teachers to support students in activities, lead discussions and facilitate engagement. Blended learning is a learning approach that combines instructor-led brick-and-mortar classroom training and online learning activities. Unlike full-fledged eLearning, the online

portion of the training doesn't replace face-to-face training with a teacher; teachers incorporate technology to enhance the learning experience and broaden understanding of certain topics. For example, they can share a link to a video and offer students to watch it at home, email their review to a teacher, and then discuss it in class.

Benefits of blended learning

If you're thinking about implementing blended learning, you'll probably want to know whether it's worth the trouble. So, take a look at some of the advantages of blended learning for learners and organizations:

- Safer learning environment
- Interactive learning process
- Learner autonomy
- Greater learner engagement
- Better comprehension
- Detailed analytics

What are the characteristics of blended learning models?

Blended learning models usually leverage a combination of in-person instruction techniques, teacher-led online modules, and self-paced learning. Students may participate in a combination of independent study, small group learning, and whole-class instruction, whether online or in person. Often, schools use elements of station rotation, a situation in which individual learners or small groups shift among the various learning configurations, on their own or according to a predetermined schedule. Regardless of which model is employed, ASCD recommends that educators incorporate the following attributes as they design blended learning experiences.

- Attention-grabbing content introductions that activate student engagement.
- Modelling and chunking strategies for helping students develop new skills.
- Checks for understanding and assessments that align with learning goals.
- Opportunities for interacting with other students to collaborate and process together.
- Scaffolding encourages learners to connect their understanding with meaningful scenarios.

Types of blended learning models

There are a variety of different models for facilitating blended learning. Some level of overlap exists among the various definitions, and the exact parameters of each model are subject to interpretation. Still, these categories describe the prevailing models for blended instruction. Each model differs somewhat in terms of teacher responsibilities, administrative requirements, and instructional emphasis. In addition, schools may choose to alter or adapt how and when students move between their homes and the school for various types of learning. All blended learning models allow for some flexibility in how they are implemented.

The flipped classroom model

Flipped classrooms give teachers the opportunity to facilitate the completion of educational projects and to support students as they practice using concepts learned independently. In a blended learning environment, teacher-led exercises can take place in person while individual study occurs at home using online modules or video lectures. A recent Ed Surge article noted that educators often use the face-to-face component of this model for:

- Class discussions
- Group work
- Delivering insights related to higher-order thinking
- Troubleshooting specific misunderstandings

The enriched virtual model

This method is similar to the flipped classroom. Students learn primarily online, though face-to-face sessions with the teacher are also required. While the flipped classroom can be thought of as reversing the original order of instruction compared to traditional learning environments, the enriched

virtual model starts with remote instruction as its origin. Online teaching is then supplemented with mandatory in-person educational experiences.

The individual rotation model

The individual rotation model can be employed in a variety of different educational settings, including in blended learning models. An educational resource from the Wisconsin Department of Public Instruction describes how students in this configuration will be sorted by their teacher or specialized software into unique educational pathways based on their needs. Learning opportunities include independent study, small groups, collaboration; lessons conducted by the teacher for the whole group, and individualized interventions. Fixed schedules may be used in place of customized learning journeys if needed, and various stations can be completed online or in person. For a fully in-person experience, students can participate in independent learning on a lab rotation schedule. Libraries and computer labs connect students directly to learning materials. Blended learning is an education program that combines online digital media with traditional classroom methods. It requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some element of student control over time, place, path, or pace. The word blending means combining.

In this study the blended learning is a combination of online self-learning by the students using the website as a distance education program, online real time interaction by the tutor and face-to-face classroom learning, which helps to enhance the communication skills of B. Ed. students. Blended Learning enhances flexibility in Teaching-learning process. In fact the technology assisted classrooms can provide better support for all the student groups basing on their abilities. Blended Teaching techniques are a boon for both highly intelligent students and less able students. Blended Learning inculcates the habit of independent and personalized learning. Students can come across diverse learning environments which can foster their ability to learn and acquire knowledge. These varied learning environments can provide interactive and collaborative learning platforms for all the regional, national and international level Teacher-Student communities. Blended Learning opens the door for face to face meetings, debates, forum discussions and brain storming sessions online, which can help the students improve their communication skills and even help them to share ideas and information.

In the recent times Blended learning in Classroom Teaching combines online digital media besides traditional methods. In the present context, classroom teaching depends on the Blended Learning Approach. The attitude and perception of this pedagogy is quite different from teacher to learner and teaching to understanding of the concept. Considering these facts in view, the researcher is trying to invent, “The Attitude and Perception towards Blended Learning Approach among English Language Teachers in Secondary Schools of North Coastal Districts of Andhra Pradesh”. Blended Learning using technology in traditional delivery comprises belief and practices of the pedagogy, which bring a greater level of effectiveness in teaching learning process. It is true that technology plays a pivotal role which influences the level of interest among the students more effectively. English teaching faculty possess the ability of learning and teaching inside and outside of the traditional classroom. The information and communication technology may help the Faculty in Teaching English to remove the barriers of geographical and situational learning, providing better opportunity of interaction between learners and English Teachers which lead to better quality of learning experiences.

Most of Faculty of Teaching English believes that the existing teaching strategies are a good practice for many years. But blended learning offers an effective process in practice teaching English and possesses more potential in performing face-to-face and online learning. Therefore, blended learning imbibes the values of traditional classroom teaching along with the use of technology, which helps to improve the effectiveness and efficiency in performance among English Teachers by deriving experiences. By adopting the blended learning procedures English language teachers transform from teacher to facilitator thereby they follow learning new technology adopted by the English Pedagogy, based on the implementation of innovative teaching strategies. 5 The adoption of Blended Learning process in Teaching English depends on the availability of resources in the respective institutions as well as awareness among the faculty. Teachers of English Language will get more advantage using their choice on the system of learning management, auto assessment tools and online technology to perform themselves more effectively. The researcher of the present study discussed the Attitude, perception of English Teachers towards Blended Learning in three phases as follows.

- The Attitude and Perception of English Teachers towards supportive e-learning

- The Attitude and Perception of English Teachers towards Blended Learning function.
- The Attitude and Perception of English Teachers towards Blended learning with technology.

Conclusion

The chapter provides detailed guidelines communicating minimum recommendations from UGC for implementation of BL. Universities and parent bodies need to ensure checking essential requirements to begin with and then should monitor processes to ensure successful implementation of BL. BL mode is to be used nation-wide to help learners develop 21st century skills along with the effective learning and skill development related to the subject-domains. BL should be carefully implemented and should not be replacing classroom time as a privilege. Every institute should strive to be a model institute to demonstrate a successful implementation of BL in the higher education of our country.

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BLENDING LEARNING IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS AT THE UPPER PRIMARY LEVEL

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Abstract

Math teachers have been using electronic resources more and more frequently in recent years. E-materials are a component of a new trend known as blended learning, or a new approach to teaching that combines real-world and online resources. Traditional classroom instruction and an online learning platform are combined in the blended learning concept (Zou, 2005). In this presentation, we'll go through some potential uses of "blended learning" in math instruction as well as some concrete instances of e-materials. We will also demonstrate how e-materials might encourage students in secondary schools to be more creative.

Keywords : *Blended learning, e-learning, constructivism*

Introduction

E-materials are a component of a new trend known as blended learning, or a new approach to teaching that combines real-world and online resources. Students have access to electronic materials such films, slideshows, electronic worksheets, e-tests, and educational software in addition to the traditional methods of material presentation. These resources can be accessed through online applications that can be used on tablets and smart phones in addition to computers. Also, practically every student has access to an

internet-connected smart phone, enabling and encouraging a personalised approach to learning with electronic resources. As a result, educators can take advantage of ICT's potential for teaching mathematics.

Concept and Significance of Blended Learning Approach

Recent technological developments have transformed and gradually replaced traditional didactic instruction and online learning with "Blended Learning." Recently, there has been a lot of interest in the idea of blended learning, which combines several teaching philosophies. According to Marsh and Drexler (2001) and Willett (2002), blended learning refers to all instructional approaches that incorporate technology, including e-mail, streaming media, and the Internet, and can be used in conjunction with conventional teaching strategies. Several lecturers have substituted one or two of the weekly curriculum's face-to-face lessons with online courses in the United States as an example of blended learning (Zou, 2005). According to published studies, when traditional instruction is mixed with computer-assisted teaching, significant academic advancement is made (Dalton & Hannafin, 1988). Consequently, traditional didactic teaching may be used in junior high school mathematics instruction when it complements computer assisted teaching approaches. Teachers could add specific components to enhance traditional didactic teaching, which prioritises teacher-centered lectures, rather than fully implementing computer-assisted teaching techniques in the classroom.

Mathematics Teaching and blended Approach

In the context of teaching mathematics in an ICT environment several approach generate rich dividend:

- Direct instruction (in person) - both teachers and students have access to and actively use ICT.
- E-learning is all-digital instruction and learning.
- Blended learning is the use of both face-to-face instruction and ICT tools while actively engaging in online learning.(Žilková, 2010)
- For self-study or as course material for students who need an individualised approach (physically, mentally, or socially disadvantaged groups of students or vice versa, gifted students), teachers can now use electronic materials, such as videos, presentations (created in MS PowerPoint, and interactive smart boards), concept maps, electronic texts, and mobile applications (constructivism in the digital environment, the Flipped Classroom method)
- Mathematical education tools like GeoGebra, electronic worksheets, and e-tests that are utilised to practise the curriculum.
- Computerized assessments for evaluation, such as Kahoot, mentimeter, quizizz, wooclap, plickers, Google forms, and other web-based assessment tools that can be customised by the teacher.

Electronic materials for blended learning accessible in Tamilnadu

There are many websites and recently even applications for smart phones which are used to teach mathematics in the form of blended learning. Tamil Nadu Government under the department of school education provides to all schools, students, teachers and parents all information and resources about teaching and learning related to school education. The site <https://tnschools.gov.in/scert/?lang=en> (Fig. 1) contains a number of professionally made material for mathematics like youtube videos, e-books, QR code, Taxonomy, Ennum Ezhuthum, Training Modules, electronic worksheet and tests which are grouped together according to the curriculum topics for students and teachers alike. This website's content includes some topics that go beyond the mathematics taught from primary to higher secondary school level.

fig. 1

<

Ennum Ezhuthum

Institutions

Training Modules

Kalvi TV

State Resource Center

>

About
 State Council of Educational Research and Training (SCERT) is the State apex academic body entrusted with the responsibility of conducting various educational activities such as development of curriculum, textbook writing, reviewing the textbooks, preparing Annual Work Plan Budget, designing, and conducting of training to teachers, conducting State Level Achievement Surveys, National Achievement Surveys, conduct State level workshops to prepare items and test materials. It designs professional development and capacity building programs with the objective of enhancing the efficiency of teachers. SCERT facilitates the integration of latest innovations in ICT in teaching learning to help students cope with technology advancement. It offers career guidance to help them meet challenges after schooling and to pursue their higher studies and select career options. It facilitates and enables teachers and teacher educators to undertake Action Research and empirical studies to address academic issues and enable policy makers to take informed decisions about the interventions to be adopted to enhance quality in learning outcomes among children all over the State.

Vision
 To create a school system which focuses on learning outcomes, holistic and joyful learning based on multiple pedagogy, alternate learning

What's New
 Feb 26 Naan Mudhalvan: College Exposure Visits for Government School Students to pursue Higher Education

The use of digital environment for developing better understanding of mathematical concepts

Students typically experience accelerated cognitive development as they mature. Their innate curiosity must be encouraged and nurtured in a suitable educational atmosphere with enough motivation. Additional traits that characterise students include curiosity, a love of learning, asking novel questions, and a strong capacity to persuade. Hence, using a constructivist teaching method will help students better understand the concepts and procedures of mathematics. The constructivist learning theory, which was created by Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget, is predicated on the idea that a student gradually creates an inner system of knowing while actively interacting with his surroundings. The entire learning process should take place in a stimulating learning environment that encourages pupils to explore. (2010) (Luká, S.a col). Vygotsky emphasises on cultural tools like technology which can create a vibrant zone for the student to learn mathematical concepts. By creating such dynamic environment using digital platforms, is quite possible in the present classrooms. At present more number of students have access to ICT, smart phones, computers, tablets, interactive whiteboards, software, etc. They bring such life to their learning environment and improve conceptualization by facilitating the visualisation of ideas using diagrams, charts, graphs, geometric figures, images of patterns, and other visual aids. The free programme GeoGebra is a fantastic stimulative digital learning environment for all constructivist methodologies. We introduce GeoGebra as a tool for a stimulating digital environment in this study. We can foster students' creativity in such a digital environment by employing a constructivist approach to teaching. Students have the opportunity to generate theories, test them, and resolve brand-new issues. Their natural inclination to enquire, capacity for autonomous thought, and capacity for observation can all be expanded. Their boldness and self-confidence also increase as they communicate their findings. All of that can aid in enhancing the students' creative abilities. We offer a few ideas for guided exploration in the GeoGebra environment in middle, high, and upper secondary schools. The ideas were developed as part of a national project called "Modernization of the educational process in high schools," where we proposed and tested a few constructivist learning ideas in the GeoGebra environment. The project was designed to prepare future teachers in the field of didactics of digital teaching of mathematics.

Few Scenarios for Teaching

Central angles

fig. 2

fig. 3

Task 1: On a circle, pick some circular arcs with various lengths and mark the following into a table: the length of the arc, the size of the central angle (at vertex S) and the size of the angle at the circumference (at vertex V). Find out in what relation are the central angle and the angle at the circumference. Is the length of the arc related to the angle at the circumference? Move vertex V to vertex X and deduce the relation between the central angle and the angle at the circumference. Possible solutions are on Fig. 2 and 3.

fig. 4

Task 2: Choose a few circular arcs on a circle that are different lengths. Vertex M lies outside the circle (choose different positions) and vertex N lies inside the circle. Mark the following into a table: the length of the arc, some related data about the angles BVC, BMC and BNC. Determine if there are any relations. Your conclusion should be supported by an argument. On Fig. 4, there are potential solutions.

Construction tasks solved using Euclidean plane isometric

Building activities in isometric instruction demand a greater level of abstraction and are generally challenging and time-consuming. Students can experiment and model all essential constructions with dynamic software like GeoGebra. We have used the constructivist method—controlled research—to the subject at hand.

Task 1: On the Internet, find an image of an interesting city with a river. Find a place on the river with a width d , where we will build a bridge orthogonal on the river flow so that the road from A to B will be shortest possible. Possible solutions are on Fig. 5.

fig. 5

Task 2: The flowerbeds in a children's park have the shape of a circle k and l and they lie on two sides of a river (on two separate half-planes divided by an axis p). The gardener wishes to mark a triangular-shaped walkway so that its endpoints are on flowerbeds and the river and that it is the same length on each side. That means to construct an equilateral triangle ABC so that vertex A lies on the circle k , vertex B on the circle l and the triangle's median on its side c lies on the axis p . Possible solutions are on Fig. 6.

Task 3: Find some intriguing flowerbeds on the Internet, then create a task for the gardener that is comparable to the one in the prior task 2. Use GeoGebra to solve and check. Describe the gardening process.

There are potential solutions in Fig. 7. These constructive approach makes learning meaningful for the learner.

fig. 6

fig. 7

The constructivist method of teaching enhances creativity, critical thinking, logical analysis, individuality and independent thinking. This process of teaching and learning mathematics is appropriate for developing the concept formation in mathematics among students. The use of digital technologies such as the open-source software GeoGebra allows the students to experiment and create and verify hypotheses and by that develop their unbiased comprehensions about various concepts. However, these blended methods do require trained and capable teachers. Only a teacher with appropriate attitude can experiment, and encourage students to explore. Blended learning technologies have changed a lot in teaching and learning of mathematics and after this pandemic, the inculcation of blended teaching, learning, assessment are well emphasised rightly in the NEP2020.

The effectiveness of blended teaching and learning in upper primary education

- Learning Efficiency - According to Piccoli, Ahmad, and Ives (2001), learning effectiveness includes changes in cognition, affect, and skills that occur as a result of education. Several variables, including learning achievement and learning attitude, are being used in relevant studies on digital learning to assess the efficacy of computer-mediated education (Chou & Liu, 2005). The learning efficiency gets strengthened on using blended learning methodology by the teacher while teaching mathematics at the upper primary level.
- Academic Performance - Academic achievement / performance is the term used to describe how students are evaluated during the learning process through tests and exams. Academic achievement of these student gets enhanced when blended approach is adopted in the mathematics class room. Studies show, blended learning enhances academic achievement, which is imperative of enhancing students learning effectiveness.
- Attitude towards Mathematics - According to Aiken's definition from 2000, attitude is "a acquired propensity to respond favourably or unfavourably to a certain object, situation, institution, or person" (p. 248). As a result, attitude influences behaviour because it reveals who a person is and how they feel about themselves. The assumption that attitude is important in mathematics learning has prompted research on attitude in the area of mathematics education. (Neale, 1969). When attempting to comprehend and explain variation in student math performance, attitudes are among the student variables that many researchers think are critical to consider (Mohamed & Waheed, 2011). Tan (1992) described mathematics attitude as an individual's views, viewpoints, and practises regarding mathematics, or as an individual's preference for mathematics. Few academicians were of the opinion that, pupils' attitudes towards mathematics are a term that combines their confidence and belief in mathematics (Tsaor & Chou, 1997).
- The influence in a blended learning setting - In a face-to-face teaching environment for beginners, we encounter mathematical problems that are difficult to solve. They may lack excitement, motivation, and a positive approach, while others may not want to specialise in it, thus they pay little to no attention to understanding fundamental mathematical concepts. (Abramovitz, Berezina Bereman, & Shvartsman, 2012). As a result, using a blended learning technique may increase learners' interest and attitude. Blended learning enables active learning and interaction between students and the learning environment's mediator. In addition to investigating the benefits of web-based technology in

mathematics education, the use of blended learning contributes to the diversification of instructional delivery in mathematics curriculum. (Awodeyi, Akpan, & Udo, 2014). According to Awodeyi, Akpan, and Udo's (2014) study, using a blended learning method increased students' achievement scores when compared to other strategies and had a good influence on their attitudes towards mathematics. (Iozzi, & Osimio, 2012).

Conclusion

The usage of blended learning is not only proving to be a successful way to teach mathematics, but it is also starting to become a reality in Tamil Nadu. Efforts like e-books, barcode ideas supported by pictures and animations, and web references have greatly aided students in developing their understanding of mathematical concepts and principles. The availability of portable technologies and students' motivation in a digital environment are just two factors contributing to the growing popularity of using a digital environment in education. If properly implemented and using a natural digital environment for the kids, the mix of traditional and online learning could help the teaching of mathematics in Tamil Nadu, especially at the upper elementary level.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning is an innovative concept that embraces the advantages of both traditional teaching in the classroom to support both offline and online teaching process. Even, hybrid learning needs rigorous efforts, right attitude, handsome budget and highly motivated teachers for its successful implementation. As it incorporates diverse modes so it is complex and organizing it is a difficult task. The present paper discusses the concept of blended learning, its main features and prerequisite of its implementation. Moreover, this paper also tries to explain that how blended learning (BL) is an approach that needs to be adopted. This chapter will first define blended learning, identify the challenges in teacher preparation programs and indicate how blended-learning approaches will assist teacher educators to meet long-standing and newly emerged challenges, and help future teachers to be reflective practitioners, better problem-solvers, and critical thinkers. This chapter also will discuss pedagogical values of blended learning and factors affecting blended learning course designs, and then showcase best practices using blended learning in order to show the effectiveness of blended learning approaches in teacher education. Lastly, this chapter will discuss considerations when blending teacher education courses.

Keywords: *Blended learning, webinars, COVID-19, ASCD recommends, learning management system*

Introduction

Blended learning term given to the educational practice of combining digital learning tools with more traditional class room face to face teaching. In a true blended leaning environment, both the student and the teacher should we physically located in the same space. But don't worry if traditional place-based classrooms are out of the question for the learners right now. By making in-person and online learning

complementary, Blended learning creates a truly integrated classroom where the needs of all type of learners can be met. Keeping students engaged, stimulated, and motivated teachers to be more effective and help them make greater gains with their students. Even more, blended learning is an educational strategy that lets students progress at their own pace. Additionally, students can refer to course concepts and material as needed and can advance when they feel ready. Therefore, Blended learning modes usually leverage a combination of in-person instruction techniques, teacher-led online modules, and self-paced learning. At the same time, BL shifts the teachers role from knowledge provider to coach and mentor. As well this shift does not mean that teachers play a passive or less important role in student education. Moreover, main aspect is that some control of learning is transfer from the teacher to student.

How can you introduce blended learning methods into the classroom creatively?

- Experiment with the flipped classroom model
- Switch to digital assessments for instant feedback
- Set digital revision tasks then use the results to inform class schedules
- Explore group projects that utilize multimedia tools.
- Choose the blended learning model that works for you.

Methods to improve blended learning in teacher education:

- The flipped classroom mode - Flipped classrooms give teachers the opportunity to facilitate the completion of educational projects and to support students as they practice using concepts learning environment, teacher-led exercise can take place in person while individual study occurs at home using online modules or video lectures.
- The Enriched Virtual Mode - This method is similar to the flipped classroom. Students learn primary online though face-to-face sessions with the teacher are also required. While the flipped classroom can be thought of as reversing the original order of instruction compared to traditional learning environments that enriched virtual model starts with remote instruction as its origin. Online teaching is then supplemented with mandatory in-person educational experiences.
- The individual Rotation model - The individual rotation model can be employed in a variety of different educational settings, including in blended learning models. An educational resource from the Wisconsin department of public instruction describes how students in this configuration will be sorted by their needs. Learning opportunities include independent study. Small groups, collaboration, lessons conducted by the teacher for the whole group, and individualized interventions. Fixed schedules may be used in place of customized learning journeys if needed, and various stations can be completed online or in person. For a fully in-person experience, students can participate in independent learning on a lab rotation schedule. Libraries and computer labs connect students directly to learning materials.
- The Flex Model - This is a self-paced , student-driven model. According to the book learning in the digital age, flex models were originally devised to assist returning student who had not completed their high school education. While educators construct learning opportunities for their students and support their progress as needed, individual earners proceed through modules on their own. This level of independence may be better suited to older students. in-person components of the model can be used for intervention opportunities, breakout rooms, lab exercises, and collaboration.

Discussion about the webinars in teacher education:

To reach your target group both live and afterwards a webinar gives you the opportunity to continue to reach your target group when the broadcast is over, since each webinar can also be watched on-demand. This enables you to increase both the reach and the impact of your message. Needless to say, it is important that your webinar can be found easily via Google, which is why a well-designed webinar is search-engine optimized. Interaction with your target group webinars enable you to utilize polls, chats and calls-to-action, or to show your viewers power point slides or videos. The more interactive your webinars is, the greater the impact of your message will be. Webinars save time and money long journeys involve travelling time and expenses, but a webinar eliminates the need to travel. Make it easier and cheaper for your target group to be engaged by your message. There is advantage for you as the ‘sender’ too: the costs area much lower than organizing a physical event and hiring and venue. However, webinars more important for teachers because the theory behind the webinar is to provide a person, face-to-face approach to teaching without the need for

the teacher to actually be present in the rooms, but instead be seen and heard with the help of the latest video conferencing technology.

Objectives of Educational institutes Leverage learning management system in education:

Implementing learning management system in education allows instructors to keep track of a learner's progress in terms of course completion, identification of knowledge gaps, participation and engagement level, and time taken to complete the course. Reporting is another exciting feature of LMS that education institutes can leverage. These detailed reports can help institutes in the evaluation of course suitability in terms of meeting the present requirements of the schools and colleges and whether they require any modification. Over the past few months, online learning has become a necessity, thanks to the pandemic. Teaching institutes struggled initially to make the shift from physical to digital classrooms. But one technology that made the shift much easier is the learning management system (LMS). Now LMS not only simplifies distance learning but also creates a better classroom experience. If you are unsure of its benefits or want to know what is LMS in education. LMS or learning management system is software designed to manage and support efficient learning. It is a complete teaching solution where instructors can upload course content, and learners can access it through their profiles. The system supports both face-to-face learning and virtual classes. Apart from that, it also facilitates communication, tracks progress, and keep records of all important data of students. While it helps the instructors work efficiently, it also caters to the needs of the learners. Overall, it is system that assists everyone involved in the teaching process. Here are some of the advantages of using an LMS for e-learning. So, if the student-teacher wants to upgrade their entire learning system by simply creating an online course, where a learning management system is the perfect solution to improve your standard to the right position.

About Blended learning view points during Covid-19

The COIVD-19 pandemic precipitated a profound change in the global educational system, transforming the way in which education was delivered. According to UNESCO 81.8% of students globally, at different academic levels, were affected by the total or partial closure of education centres. Initially, due to the lockdown, the education centers were forced to shut down, thereby shifting teaching to online platforms and resulting in an increase of up to 200% in the use of educational applications. As the health situation improved, students gradually moved back to face-to-face classrooms, giving rise, in many cases, to the teaching model known as blended learning (BL) which combines face-to-face and online learning strategies. BL allowed a partial return to the desired 'normality' respecting the current sanitary measures of social distancing and seating capacity. However, BL also posed a challenged to the actors involved in the learning process-teachers, student, and institutions-given the infrastructure and organization required to successfully carry it out. The Challenges and opportunities of BL implementation in teacher education during the COVID-19 period and post-Pandemic Nevertheless, COIVD-19 and the arrival of BL compelled universities to face a series of challenges for which they were not prepared.

Since the beginning of the health crisis, universities had to ensure continuity in teaching, necessitating training programs for teachers on the different online tools, as well as the new pedagogical ways of teaching simultaneously, universities had to invest in infrastructure and equipment to provide their centers, students, and teachers with the necessary resources to ensure that the learning process was effectively carried out in the new environment. The universities had to develop strategies to ensure that everyone could access ad attend their classes while safeguarding the students' safety from possible contagion Additionally they had to address the potential digital divide that could affect some of the students through the provision of computer aids and equipment, as well as by developing legal frameworks to regulate issues related to the introduction of technology, such as privacy concerns (due to the obligation to activate cameras) and student assessments. However, the implementation of BL has brought several opportunities for universities and educational institutions. The pandemic emphasized the development of contingency plans to be better prepared for future situations similar to this one and in enacting a rapid response. Blended learning highlighted the need to create continuous training plans for teachers and students using online tools.

Strategies that promote blended learning:

- Having compassion and empathy
- Creating a secure and dependable structure

- Ramping up the positive feedback
- Supporting academic risk
- Teaching active listening
- Embedding strategy instruction
- Building collaborative relationships

Conclusion

Concluding that blended learning brings exciting opportunities for new ways to teach and learn the concept on their own and then applies and reinforces what they learned during classroom time. Where BL is one of the teaching model, mixed traditional methods of teaching with an online courses for achieving specific learning goals. These models can be used as a teaching media and as an assessment. Although, by implementing hybrid learning in teacher education process, the teachers did not teach all the material in front of the class, but they guide the students to participate in the learning process and helped them share their knowledge and seeking of information they requires.

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CURRENT TRENDS OF BLENDED LEARNING IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended learning is a learning approach that combines instructor-led brick-and-mortar classroom training and online learning activities. Unlike full-fledged e-Learning, the online portion of the training doesn't replace face-to-face training with a teacher; teachers incorporate technology to enhance the learning experience and broaden understanding of certain topics. For example, they can share a link to a video and offer students to watch it at home, email their review to a teacher, and then discuss it in class.

Introduction

Along with blended learning, there is hybrid learning. These two learning approaches are often mistakenly considered synonymous. Although they both signify a type of mixture, there is a significant difference between them. In hybrid learning, a teacher or instructor delivers materials to learners, some of whom attend class in person, while others join the class virtually from home. In this case, the educator will teach remote and physically present students at the same time using tools like video conferencing hardware and software. Blended learning, on the other hand, combines in-person teaching with online learning methods. So, learners can listen to a lecture in a classroom and then take an online quiz right there or at home. Think of a hybrid car and a blender. A hybrid car combines two types of fuel, just as hybrid learning combines two types of learning environments. And a blender mixes whatever you put in it, and similarly, blended learning combines multiple types of learning content.

Benefits of Blended Learning

If you're thinking about implementing blended learning, you'll probably want to know whether it's worth the trouble. So, take a look at some of the advantages of blended learning for learners and organizations:

- **Safer learning environment** - If there's anything 2020 taught us, it's that being in one place with a bunch of other people can have its complications. And seeing those people only on the screen is unbearable. The blended approach makes learning safer by reducing the number of hours learners spend together offline but still provides them with live communication.

- **Interactive learning process** - Theoretical materials can be challenging (if not boring). It's one thing when learners sit and listen to a speaker for a few hours. And it's radically different when they learn that same information by clicking on buttons, participating in a dialogue simulation, taking a game-like course, and so on. Acquiring new knowledge can be fun, and blended learning provides lots of tools to make it so.
- **Learner autonomy** - Being able to control and schedule an individual learning path is essential for learners – and especially adults. Learning isn't the only (and hardly the most important) activity of students and employees. Work, family, hobbies, and friends – people's lives are made up of many facets, and learning shouldn't become an obstacle. In blended learning, learners can access courses 24/7 – whenever they want it and have the opportunity.
- **Greater learner engagement** - No business or institution wants to force its employees or students to learn, because it won't work. You need to engage learners in learning to make it effective. Blended learning leads to greater learner engagement by providing different opportunities and using digital tools.
- **Better comprehension** - One of the most popular blended learning models, called the flipped classroom results in better comprehension by having learners study all theoretical materials alone at their own pace and practice new knowledge and skills during in-person sessions.
- **Detailed analytics** - How much time did it take a learner to finish a quiz? How many attempts did they make? Do they have any expiring tasks? Can you answer these questions with classroom learning? Probably, yes. But how much time will you spend collecting all this information on each and every employee or student? With blended learning, you won't even spend a minute – a lms (learning management system) will do everything for you. Based on learner progress, you'll be able to see how competent a learner is at specific topics, whether they are ready to move forward or need to revise some materials, and much more.

Disadvantages of Blended Learning

Now that you know the 'why' of blended learning, let's also look at the 'why not.' Here are the cons of this learning approach:

- **New skill set for teachers/instructors** - Blended learning requires particular digital competence, as instructors need to create online courses, assign them to students, monitor their progress, and much more. Some eLearning tools have a steep learning curve, and not all teachers might be willing to invest the time and trouble needed to master a new technological tool. A new skill set also refers to the fact that digitally inexperienced teachers may give too much content to study just because they don't have classroom time limits and think: "Well, it's not that much. And learners are at home, so they have lots of spare time." And this could lead to cognitive overload on the part of the learners.
- **Plagiarism** - The more eLearning content you create, the greater the risk of plagiarism. Instructors might do this by accident, such as if they find an image that highlights their idea and add it to their online course, whereas the image is protected by copyright. If this occurs, it's the company or university that might get into trouble.
- **Higher cost** - If you use eLearning, you pay for eLearning software. If you have classroom learning, you pay for light, gas, equipment, etc. And if you have blended learning, you pay for everything.

Blended Learning Models

The most difficult thing about launching blended learning is that the technique is extremely flexible. The variety of strategies, tools, and the need to balance everything will likely make even experienced learning professionals feel overwhelmed and confused. We would like to highlight six principal blended learning models here:

- **Face-to-face driver model** - This model is the closest to traditional classroom training. This approach usually means that not everyone in the class will take additional online training, as it mainly targets the individual needs of those learners who are struggling or would like to go above and beyond.
- **Online driver model** - This model is the opposite of brick-and-mortar studying, as it relies entirely on a digital delivery of the training. It combines both synchronous training (live webinars, peer-to-peer training sessions, etc.) and a synchronous training (self-paced study of courses). With the online driver model, there's usually no need for live face-to-face meetings, but they can be arranged if necessary.
- **Rotation model** - This model involves breaking a group of learners into smaller units to perform different types of tasks at different stages in turns. Some activities are online and some are realized in

person. This allows learners with different types of learning styles to get the maximum benefit from the training.

- **Flipped classroom** - The motto of this model is “online learning, offline application.” With a flipped classroom, lectures and practical homework elements are reversed. Learners study new content at home before the class, and in-class time is devoted to active learning and applying the newly learned skills. This can be accomplished in the form of discussions, case studies, or project work. The instructor’s task is to guide the learners by answering questions and supporting them in the application of course concepts.

- **Flex model** - The Flex model allows learners to have control over their learning. Students or employees can move from one activity to another according to their needs. Activities can be both online and offline. Teachers or instructors are always on-site to instruct and help learners if necessary.

- **Individual rotation model** - Here, learners also move from one station to another, but it is the teacher (or instructor) or a special algorithm that sets an individual path. Students or employees don’t need to visit all the stations – only the ones that are on their schedule.

Conclusion

Blended learning method is another milestone in the field of education. In the period of Covid-19 entire teaching learning and evaluation process have been done in the online platform. Blended learning method is gives a new path in the teaching learning process through the online platform. So in future blended learning method is mandatory for all higher education institutions.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN INDIA IN CONTEXTS OF NEP2020

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Abstract

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) of India has proposed the implementation of blended learning as a way to improve the quality of education and increase access to it. However, there are several barriers to the successful implementation of blended learning in India in terms of infrastructure, teacher training, and teacher availability. This paper examines the challenges that must be addressed in order to ensure the successful implementation of blended learning in India in the context of NEP 2020. It identifies the need for increased access to digital technology, adequate teacher training and development, and increased availability of teachers as the key barriers to successful implementation. The paper also provides potential solutions to these challenges, such as government-supported initiatives to provide access to digital technology, the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning to automate teacher development and training, and the use of online platforms to recruit and employ teachers. The paper concludes by suggesting that NEP 2020 should be implemented in a way that takes into consideration these challenges and provides adequate support for teachers and schools to successfully implement blended learning into their curriculums.

Introduction

In India, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has laid the groundwork for the utilization of blended learning models in schools and higher education institutions across the country. Blended learning combines online and face-to-face instruction to create a more personalized learning environment, allowing students to receive instruction from both their teachers and from online resources. Although this approach holds numerous potential benefits for students, there are also some barriers to its successful implementation in India. The most prominent barrier to implementing blended learning in India is the lack of access to technology and digital infrastructure. Despite the government’s effort to bridge the digital divide, many rural and semi-urban students still lack access to the necessary technology and internet connectivity to effectively engage in online learning.

Blended learning

Blended learning involves a combination of online instruction, face-to-face instruction, and other forms of learning activities (Hannafin & Land, 2004). It is an approach that combines traditional classroom instruction with online instruction and activities. The goal of blended learning is to create an optimal learning experience for students by combining the advantages of both face-to-face and online instruction. Blended learning is an instructional strategy that combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning. It is an educational approach that combines online digital media with traditional classroom methods and is designed to facilitate student learning, engagement, and collaboration (Suhr, 2016). This approach utilizes a variety of learning styles, including online discussion forums, video conferencing, webinars, and other interactive learning tools. Blended learning can be used in a variety of educational settings, such as primary and secondary schools, universities, and professional training. It can also be used to supplement traditional teaching methods. Blended learning can be used to increase student engagement and motivation, as well as to create a more personalized learning experience. It can also be used to create a more efficient learning environment by reducing the need for physical infrastructure and reducing the amount of time needed for instruction. Additionally, blended learning can help to reduce the cost of instruction, as it eliminates the need for expensive materials and technology. Furthermore, blended learning is beneficial for teachers, as it can help them to better manage their workload and to provide more effective instruction.

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020)

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) is an overarching policy framework for the future of education in India. It is the first comprehensive education policy of India since the National Policy on Education (NPE) of 1986. NEP 2020 envisions a comprehensive transformation in the education system in India, with special emphasis on online and blended learning. The policy recommends that all educational institutions, from primary to higher education, should use online and blended learning tools to deliver quality education efficiently. It also calls for the establishment of a National Education Technology Mission to ensure that all institutions have access to the necessary technology and infrastructure for online and blended learning.

Models of Blended Learning

Blended learning is a combination of online and face-to-face learning. By using a blended learning approach, instructors can leverage the advantages of both online and traditional learning formats to create a more engaging learning experience. There are various models of blended learning, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. The Station Rotation Model is a popular model that involves rotating students through a number of learning activities or stations. Each station is designed to engage students in different types of learning activities such as online activities, small-group activities, and independent tasks. The Flex Model is a less structured approach that allows students to move freely between online and in-person learning activities. This model gives students more control over their learning and allows instructors to provide personalized learning experiences. The Flipped Classroom Model is an approach that flips the traditional classroom experience by having students watch instructional videos or read materials outside of class and then use class time for activities such as discussions, group work, and projects. The Individual Rotation Model involves each student spending part of the class period working independently on online activities and the rest of the period working with a teacher or in small groups. Finally, the Enriched Virtual Model is a completely online approach that uses technology to provide students with engaging learning experiences.

Benefits of Blended Learning according to NEP 2020

- **Increased Access** - Blended learning creates a bridge between physical classrooms and virtual classrooms, allowing students to access learning materials from anywhere, anytime. This makes education more accessible to students, especially those who lack resources or are geographically isolated.
- **Improved Learning Outcomes** - Blended learning helps students retain more information, leading to improved learning outcomes. It also encourages critical thinking, collaboration, and problem-solving skills.
- **Customized Learning** - Blended learning allows teachers to tailor their instruction to the individual needs of each student. This helps to maximize learning potential.
- **Flexibility** - Blended learning gives students the flexibility to learn at their own pace, allowing them to progress at their own speed.

- **Increased Engagement** - Blended learning encourages student engagement by using a variety of teaching methods, such as videos and interactive activities. This helps to keep students engaged and motivated.
- **Cost Savings** - Blended learning can save schools money by reducing costs associated with physical classrooms, such as textbooks and other resources.

Challenges in Implementation of Blended Learning in the contexts of NEP2020

Technology Accessibility

- **Inadequate Technology Infrastructure** - One of the main challenges in the implementation of blended learning in the context of NEP2020 is the lack of infrastructure. In India, there is a huge gap between the availability of technology and its actual usage in the educational domain. For example, in 2019, only 7% of the government schools in India had access to internet (Rao & Cheruvu, 2019). Moreover, even in schools with the infrastructure, there is a lack of technical support and knowledge of how to use the technology effectively (Khan & Prakash, 2020). This lack of infrastructure and technical support hinders the effective use of blended learning.
- **Accessibility of Technology** - There are also a number of accessibility issues associated with using technology for blended learning. For example, many students may not have access to the necessary hardware and software to access digital resources (Garg & Sharma, 2018). Additionally, if a student has a disability, they may not be able to access the digital resources or use the technology required for blended learning courses (Garg & Sharma, 2018).
- **Digital Literacy** - Furthermore, digital literacy is a critical factor for successful implementation of blended learning. Many students may not have the necessary skills to use the technology and digital resources required for blended learning courses (Garg & Sharma, 2018). Without the necessary skills and knowledge, students may struggle to benefit from a blended learning approach (Garg & Sharma, 2018).

Limited Resources

Financial resources are a significant challenge in implementing blended learning, as access to and utilization of technology and the internet often require a significant financial investment. For example, according to a report by the National Council of Educational Research and Training, “the cost of providing computers, tablets, and other digital devices to all students and teachers, as well as the cost of training the teachers and the cost of internet connections for the schools, is quite high” (Srivastava et al., 2020, p. 22). Additionally, the cost of maintaining and updating technology, as well as the cost of providing online content and other materials, can be prohibitively expensive. Additionally, in many regions of India, access to technology and the internet is limited, making it difficult to implement blended learning. For example, according to a report by the National Association of Software and Services Companies (NASSCOM), “only 15 percent of schools in India have access to the internet” (NASSCOM, 2020).

Furthermore, in many rural and remote areas, access to electricity and the internet is non-existent, making implementation of blended learning difficult. Moreover, there is often a lack of access to qualified instructors with knowledge and experience in blended learning techniques. According to a report by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, “there is a great shortage of trained teachers who can handle blended learning” (Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2018, p. 7). Furthermore, there is often a lack of teaching materials, such as textbooks, that are tailored to blended learning. Finally, the lack of knowledge and understanding of blended learning techniques is another significant challenge in implementing blended learning in the context of NEP 2020. According to a report by the Central Board of Secondary Education, “many teachers are not familiar with the concept of blended learning and its various methods, tools, and techniques” (Central Board of Secondary Education, 2020, p. 6).

Conclusion

While blended learning has the potential to provide numerous benefits to students and teachers, the implementation of blended learning in the context of NEP 2020 is challenged by numerous resource constraints, including, but not limited to, limited financial resources, lack of access to technology and the internet, limited access to qualified instructors and teaching materials, and limited knowledge and understanding of blended learning techniques.

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THREATS AND CHALLENGES TO BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract

Many tools and applications have exploded on the educational scene over the past 10 years, offering fresh approaches to delivering, enhancing, and evaluating knowledge. The most widely used products, nevertheless, straddle the line between assisting and supplanting educators. Finding a way to subtly integrate technology into classroom instruction in a way that actually improves the quality of students' educational experiences rather than just making it more convenient is the problem. A viable option is a blended learning strategy, where students learn using a combination of electronic and in-person education. The thought of altering the classroom's core structure and operation can be challenging for a teacher. A complete classroom overhaul is necessary. We were able to satisfy the various and special needs of each of our pupils thanks to a blended, self-paced, mastery-based instructional paradigm.

Keywords : *Blended learning, tools, applications, technology, education*

Introduction

As time goes on and conditions necessitate new modes of instruction, blended and hybrid learning become more and more common and useful. But, as the value of new educational technology for blended classrooms increases, obstacles also do. By providing focal areas for hybrid learning that span the so-called digital gap between students from various locations and circumstances, tools like interactive displays might help overcome obstacles. Blended learning combines various web-based tools, pedagogical approaches, and instructional technology with face-to-face instruction (Driscoll, 2002). The terms "blended learning", "hybrid education," and "technology-mediated/enhanced learning" have all been used interchangeably. The term "practices which drives attainment of high-quality learning outcomes and progressive students' learning experiences with increasing teachers' contentment" is used to describe the effectiveness of BL (Stacey & Gerbric, 2008). The two delivery methods for distance learning are synchronous and asynchronous. Synchronous methods demand that students interact face-to-face.

As opposed to asynchronous interactions, which do not require concurrent involvement, real-time interactions take place. Blended learning in the context of distant learning provides flexibility in terms of assessment methods, group-based work, assignment submission, marking, grading, feedback, and teacher-student communication. The Learning Management System, MOOCs, Moodle, Open Educational Resources, Twitter, blogs, discussion forums, e-portfolios, e-assessment, live internet streaming, video conferencing, and mobile applications are the most widely used blended learning platforms used by universities worldwide. With the use of information and communication technologies, each of these tools improves students' participation and the learning experience while also streamlining course management and administration. In general, the BL method has provided the internet generation with limitless learning options (Bo Tso, 2015). Let's discuss the most pressing issues affecting the adoption of blended learning and how modern educational technology might assist you address each.

Choosing the Best Technology for the Classroom

Without determining the tools your institution needs, you risk going over budget and experiencing a serious efficiency crisis. When using the incorrect tools, students and teachers must overcome an unrealistically high learning curve, which prevents them from truly learning. However, using a variety of tools and devices instead of a single integrated solution not only adds to the expense but also creates a real mess. connectors, cables, guides, and adapters. You don't want that, I understand. Interactive flat panels, often known as interactive displays, are platforms that neatly combine a variety of functions. A sizable, crisp display, cloud connectivity to support blended learning collaboration, and the majority of the required apps come pre-installed are all included. That covers video conferencing, video players, browsers, and even games with an instructional focus. And since the display is more than just a screen and functions as a whole computer, it is simple to add more right there. Imagine it as a very sophisticated, very large tablet.

Blended learning is frequently viewed as ineffective

Administrators and educators frequently get queries concerning the effectiveness of blended and hybrid learning. In reality, a lot of educators favour face-to-face instruction, which makes sense given that it has been the standard since the beginning of school. The online or digital components of classes frequently go unnoticed or are viewed as a small distraction, resulting in the loss of beneficial possibilities and resources as well as a subpar return on investment when purchasing new educational technology. Teachers may ignore digital training while students frequently neglect to complete digital tasks because online learning and teaching don't always receive the same degree of attention as traditional instruction. Technology can assist with this complex problem, but it cannot solve it entirely on its own. We can assist by offering powerful, straightforward tools. Yet, it is up to you to persuade educators, learners, and parents that hybrid learning is just as serious and significant as conventional learning. It is lot simpler with good technology and tools because, once you have them, you can demonstrate the advantages of blended learning to stakeholders in a way that is very evident to them. And everyone can relate to benefits on an instinctual level. A curriculum that very clearly explains both what you will teach and how you will teach it becomes easier to plan with appropriate educational technology.

Upholding Academic and Student Growth

Here, two key elements play significant roles. First, for rather clear historical reasons, the majority of teachers still choose paper-based exams and reports. Second, because hybrid learning depends on digital resources, tech-savvy students have an immediate advantage over less tech-savvy students, giving them a scholastic advantage as well. That is the digital gap that is frequently mentioned. When these factors are taken together, you get a situation where teachers employ paper examinations that aren't appropriate for contemporary blended learning instead of digital progress tracking systems. However, there are kids who fall behind not because they are less capable but rather because they are less exposed to modern technology, including cellphones, personal computers, and cloud-based apps. This necessitates returning to the original motivation for establishing blended learning. Addressing urgent situations, such as public health crises, is the rationale for this. Blended learning is all about flexibility and bridging gaps. While we don't advocate lowering academic standards, we do recommend making milestones more flexible and giving students greater freedom to work at their own speed. Although you can't guarantee that everyone has access to the same level of technological exposure, you can level the playing field by giving students more time to finish assignments and providing more individualised support. In addition to providing access to online

information from virtually anywhere, good ed tech solutions enable you to record classes so that students can watch them several times as needed.

Participation and Attendance

This cannot be disputed. Working from home is quite similar to remote learning, which makes up half of blended learning. It demands a lot of self-control and is continually "attacked" by different distractions. With only a few taps, students using personal devices like laptops, tablets, and cellphones can lose themselves in a game, YouTube, TikTok, Instagram, and other sites. The temptation may even reach teachers. The distraction element is increased by incoming Skype calls, background noises, scurrying pets, and family members moving around. The secret is to make hybrid learning attractive enough to block out any outside distractions. That's what effective solutions like unified interactive flat panels do by assisting you in gamifying your lessons. Although the term "gamification" is presumably well-known to you, its exact definition is still unclear. It does not merely entail playing games during class to make it more enjoyable. It entails incorporating gaming mechanics that have been shown to be advantageous for learning. Experience points, accomplishments, specific mission objectives, direction cues, and teamwork are some of them. Also, teachers should keep their pupils on their toes by posing questions, discussing thought-provoking subjects, and administering exams. One outstanding tool that springs to mind is Kahoot, which is adored by both students and teachers.

The Digital Divide

We briefly touched on this above, but now let's take a closer look at the digital divide. It is inevitable that not all students and even teachers will have the same amount of access to technology due to economic, social, and personal factors. Families with multiple children may only have one laptop, which makes managing remote learning challenging. Many students don't own personal smart devices, thus BYOD isn't an option for them when they choose in-person instruction. In terms of speeds and dependability, internet connection is, of course, far from being available in every household worldwide. Due to the inability of educators to directly address the core causes, these availability gaps provide enormous difficulties when attempting hybrid learning that depends on individual digital devices and ongoing high-speed internet access. An entire classroom can access an interactive flat panel or interactive display, which provides a centralised, focal platform. Students who have adequate access to technology can participate in hybrid learning through remote attendance, while those who have less access can attend in person. The mix of interactive screens and built-in apps makes it simple to record sessions if such in-person attendance is a problem. As long as teachers make sure to allow students extra time to complete chores, this provides students the freedom to watch classes when they can. Such flexibility is made possible by effective educational technology. Cloud collaboration solutions, such as Digital Whiteboarding software, which allow students to contribute to course content in real time and assist each other's development by sharing and co-editing files online, are also extremely beneficial for both in-person and online learning. This is a characteristic of a modern classroom that is appearing more and more frequently, especially on interactive screens.

Keeping the Authenticity of the Teacher

It's simple enough to put pupils in front of pre-made educational movies with an endless stream of pre-written questions when using technology in the classroom. But does it work? Teachers need adaptable instructional delivery methods created to maintain the instructors' authenticity, as they are the most significant change agent in the classroom. Teachers naturally take a backseat while using external content, and students could wonder if their teacher is actually committed to their study. Furthermore, the routine use of technology undermines a teacher's capacity to forge deep connections with students. As math educators, we found it quite difficult to find pre-made internet content that would interest our kids because it was either too difficult or too simple. We decided to make our own instructional films instead. To make our content interesting, we first conducted research on the best practises for producing instructional videos and created slide decks that were video-ready. We purchased iPads with Apple Pencils to create the movies, recorded our screens using Explain Everything, and then included built-in quizzes using Edpuzzle. We took some time to perfect this method, but it was worth it because our students enjoyed watching movies that their own professors had made, in addition to being geared specifically for the students we knew best. Now, we could

use videos to offer direct education without sacrificing authenticity or personality. It had a significant impact.

Creating a Successful Environment for Self-Paced Learning

By putting direct instruction into videos, we gave students the power to manage their own learning and progress at their own rates. Yet there were particular difficulties with this. The idea that some students need more time than others to learn skills is the foundation of self-pacing, a fundamental tenet of many blended learning programmes. Self-direction is a challenging academic talent, though, and kids need scaffolding in order to learn it. Without it, pupils who are excellent at managing their time thrive while those who aren't only lag behind. As a result, successful students learn rapidly and independently via an online portal, but failing students quickly fall through the cracks and experience loneliness and a sense of being lost in the classroom. Chunking is the secret to encouraging motivation and teamwork in a self-paced setting. We allow students to pace themselves within each unit of study rather than simply letting them run amok with their time. We established strict end-of-unit deadlines that kept students from getting too far behind and gave them the opportunity to start over at the conclusion of each unit. Because students are allowed to assist one another or ask for assistance at any time during the course, this self-pacing structure also naturally fosters teamwork. The classroom transformed into the controlled-chaos atmosphere of true learning that we sought when combined with activities that included group work, periodic small group and big group conversations to address themes in the material, and group-based activities.

Developing student authenticity

It's one thing to get children working independently on computers, but how could we make sure they were actually learning? Several computer-based programmes enable students to quickly complete criteria without actually understanding the knowledge or abilities required for success. We were aware that these methods would widen pupils' achievement gaps and subject them to excessive screen time. We had to properly "mix" learning in order to assure mastery, so we took kids away from their screens. The only option for pupils to move on to more complex material was to demonstrate mastery by submitting written or oral "mastery checks" to us at the end of each course. Students may respond to test questions that are connected to standards or explain something to us in person, or pass a test that we created online. It was important that every student had a thorough understanding of the subject. If a student didn't successfully demonstrate mastery the first time, we urged them to review with more practise problems or videos and revisit when they were ready with a fresh mastery check. After gaining mastery, we asked students to consider their accomplishments in order to assist them develop as learners. Our kids accepted the challenge when we placed an emphasis on mastery rather than completion.

Conclusion

The difficulty of blended learning is derived from the combination of in-person and online teaching strategies into a single integrated instructional strategy, as stated in its most basic and popular formulations. Based on its potential to avoid specific setting strengths and successful aspects, blended learning has been found to have a number of difficulties. Numerous works specifically list the advantages of blended learning, including: easily achievable class objectives, redesigned courses with easily quantifiable educational outcomes, student collaboration on their own time, improved computer literacy of both students and lecturers; student temporal independence; improved communication; and lower rates of dropout, failure, and withdrawal. The success of blending face-to-face and computer-mediated instruction, or how well the unique characteristics of the real environment in which blended learning is developed are taken into account, will determine the benefits of the blended learning model that are attained and its impact on the improvement of learning effectiveness. Educational institutions face difficulties with isolation and presence during the period following the epidemic as they prepare to reopen following the lockdown policy. This essay intends to educate educators and teachers so they can undertake more study on how students perceive social contact and presence in order to feel a sense of community.

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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF BLENDED LEARNING MODE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Blended learning is a mode of education delivery that combines online learning with face-to-face classroom teaching. This comparative study explores the Advantages and Disadvantages of blended learning compared to traditional classroom teaching. The study is based on a review of the literature, including academic journals and reports from educational institutions. The findings indicate that blended learning offers several advantages, such as increased flexibility, personalized learning, and improved student engagement. However, the study also identifies some challenges, such as the need for adequate technology infrastructure and teacher training, as well as potential issues with student motivation and participation.

Introduction

Blended learning is a hybrid approach to education that combines online learning with face-to-face classroom teaching (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). This mode of delivery has become increasingly popular in recent years, as advances in technology have made it more feasible and accessible. The aim of this comparative study is to explore the pros and cons of blended learning compared to traditional classroom teaching.

Methodology

The methodology of this study will be a comparative analysis of the literature review. The literature review will be organized thematically, and the positive and negative aspects of blended learning will be compared and contrasted. The analysis will be conducted using a qualitative approach, and the findings will be presented thematically.

Advantages of Blended Learning

- Access to Resources: Blended learning provides students with access to a wide range of resources, including online textbooks, videos, and interactive simulations. This can enhance the learning experience by providing students with multiple ways to engage with course material (Bonk & Graham, 2012).
- Career and Life Skills: Blended learning can help students develop important career and life skills, such as digital literacy, collaboration, and self-directed learning. These skills are increasingly important in the modern workforce and can benefit students beyond the classroom (Brame, 2013).
- Cost Savings: Blended learning can be a cost-effective solution for educational institutions. With fewer physical resources needed, such as classroom space and textbooks, institutions can save on costs while still providing quality education to students (Hrastinski, 2019).

- **Enhanced Accessibility:** Blended learning can make education more accessible to students who might not otherwise have access to traditional classroom-based instruction. For example, students who live in remote areas or who have disabilities that make it difficult to attend in-person classes can benefit from blended learning (Basham et al., 2019).
- **Flexibility for Instructors:** Blended learning can offer more flexibility for instructors in terms of scheduling and workload. By allowing for a mix of online and in-person components, instructors can adjust their teaching approaches to better meet the needs of their students (Basham et al., 2019).
- **Global Connections:** Blended learning can help students connect with peers and experts from around the world. Online communication tools, such as video conferencing and social media, can be used to facilitate global collaboration and learning (Hrastinski, 2019).
- **Improved Assessment:** Blended learning can provide a variety of assessment options that go beyond traditional tests and quizzes. For example, online discussions, group projects, and multimedia assignments can provide more authentic and meaningful assessments of student learning (Vaughan et al., 2013).
- **Improved Engagement:** Blended learning can be more engaging than traditional classroom-based instruction. Online learning activities can be interactive and engaging, and can be used to reinforce concepts covered in face-to-face sessions (Dziuban et al., 2015). This can lead to improved learning outcomes and greater student satisfaction.
- **Improved Time Management:** Blended learning can help students develop better time management skills. By offering a mix of online and in-person activities, students can learn to prioritize their time and plan their schedules more effectively (Vaughan et al., 2013).
- **Increased Collaboration:** Blended learning can facilitate collaboration among students and between students and instructors. Online discussion forums and collaborative projects can be used to promote communication and teamwork (Picciano, 2014).
- **Increased Flexibility:** Blended learning offers greater flexibility than traditional classroom-based instruction. Students have the opportunity to learn at their own pace and on their own schedule. This can be particularly beneficial for adult learners, who may have work or family responsibilities that make it difficult to attend traditional classroom sessions (Khan, 2017).
- **Increased Retention:** Blended learning can enhance student retention rates by providing multiple opportunities for students to review and engage with course material. For example, students can review online resources after a face-to-face session to reinforce their understanding of the material (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004).
- **Individualized Learning:** Blended learning can provide students with a more individualized learning experience. By allowing students to work at their own pace and offering personalized feedback and support, blended learning can help students achieve their learning goals (Brame, 2013).
- **Personalized Learning:** Blended learning allows instructors to tailor instruction to the needs and preferences of individual students. Online learning activities can be used to assess students' knowledge and understanding, and instructors can use this information to adjust instruction to meet the needs of each student (Means et al., 2013).
- **Scalability:** Blended learning can be a scalable solution for educational institutions that need to serve large numbers of students. With online components, instructors can reach more students while minimizing the need for additional physical space and resources (Basham et al., 2019).
- Overall, blended learning offers many potential benefits to students and instructors, including increased scalability, improved assessment, increased engagement, development of important career and life skills, cost savings, and flexibility for instructors. However, it is important to also consider the challenges and limitations of blended learning, such as the need for effective pedagogical strategies, technology requirements, and potential student resistance to online learning.

Disadvantages of blended learning

- **Access and Equity:** Blended learning may not be accessible or equitable for all students, particularly those who do not have reliable access to technology or who come from disadvantaged backgrounds. This can exacerbate existing disparities in educational access and outcomes (Brame, 2013).
- **Assessment and Feedback:** Blended learning can create challenges for assessment and feedback. Instructors must consider how to effectively assess student learning across different types of learning activities, and how to provide timely and meaningful feedback to students (Vaughan et al., 2013).

- **Cost of Technology:** Blended learning requires investment in technology infrastructure and equipment, which can be costly for educational institutions. The ongoing maintenance and updates to technology can also be expensive (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004).
- **Inadequate Faculty Training:** Instructors may not receive adequate training on how to effectively teach in a blended learning environment. This can lead to poor course design, inadequate use of technology, and ineffective teaching practices (Vaughan et al., 2013).
- **Inconsistent Quality:** Blended learning courses may vary in quality depending on the instructor's experience, course design, and use of technology. This can create inconsistency in the learning experience and outcomes for students (Hrastinski, 2019).
- **Increased Workload:** Blended learning may require students to complete additional online assignments or activities, which can increase the workload compared to traditional in-person instruction. This can be challenging for students who are balancing multiple courses or work commitments (Brame, 2013).
- **Lack of Student Self-Regulation:** Blended learning requires a high degree of student self-regulation, as students must manage their own learning in both online and in-person settings. Some students may struggle with self-regulation, leading to poor engagement and outcomes in blended learning environments (Basham et al., 2019).
- **Lack of Student Support:** Blended learning may not provide adequate student support, particularly for online learning components. Students may struggle with online content or technical issues, and may not receive the support they need to succeed (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004).
- **Limited Access to Resources:** In blended learning, students may not have access to the same resources they would in a traditional classroom setting. This could include physical textbooks, library resources, or specialized equipment, which may limit the scope of the course (Hrastinski, 2019).
- **Limited Social Interaction:** While blended learning can provide some social interaction through online discussion boards and other tools, it may not fully replicate the social experience of traditional in-person learning in terms of personality development, emotional development, social development etc. This may be a disadvantage for students who thrive in a more social learning environment (Brame, 2013).
- **Loss of Flexibility:** Blended learning requires students to attend both in-person and online classes, which may not be feasible for all students. This can lead to a loss of flexibility, which may be important for students who have work or family commitments (Hrastinski, 2019).
- **Pedagogical Challenges:** Blended learning requires effective pedagogical strategies that balance online and in-person learning activities. Instructors must consider how to design effective online content and ensure that it aligns with in-person instruction to create a cohesive learning experience (Vaughan et al., 2013).
- **Potential for Cheating:** Blended learning may create opportunities for cheating, particularly in online assessments. Instructors must consider how to design assessments that discourage cheating, and how to detect and address instances of cheating (Vaughan et al., 2013).
- **Reduced Interaction:** Blended learning can reduce the amount of interaction between students and instructors compared to traditional in-person instruction. This can lead to a loss of the social and emotional benefits of face-to-face interactions, which can be important for student learning and wellbeing (Hrastinski, 2019).
- **Reduced Motivation:** Blended learning may reduce motivation for some students who prefer traditional in-person instruction. This can lead to lower engagement and effort in the online components of the course, which may impact learning outcomes (Basham et al., 2019).
- **Resistance to Online Learning:** Some students may resist online learning and prefer in-person instruction. This can lead to lower engagement and motivation in the online components of blended learning, which can ultimately impact learning outcomes (Basham et al., 2019).
- **Technical Difficulties:** Blended learning requires a reliable internet connection and up-to-date technology, which can be a challenge for some students. Technical difficulties can impact learning outcomes and create frustration for students (Vaughan et al., 2013).
- **Time-Consuming:** Blended learning can be time-consuming for instructors who need to design and develop online content in addition to teaching in-person. The workload can become overwhelming if instructors do not have adequate support and training (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004).
- It is important for instructors and institutions to consider these potential challenges and work to address them in order to maximize the benefits of blended learning while minimizing its limitations.

Discussion

Blended learning, a combination of online and face-to-face instruction, has gained popularity in recent years. While the approach has many potential benefits, there are also drawbacks to consider. In this article, we have explored the advantages and disadvantages of blended learning. One of the most significant advantages of blended learning is its flexibility. Students can access course materials and complete assignments at their own pace and on their own schedule. This can be particularly beneficial for students who have work or family commitments, or who need to balance multiple courses (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). Additionally, the online component of blended learning allows students to engage with course materials in a variety of ways, including through multimedia, interactive exercises, and online discussions. This can increase student engagement and motivation, leading to improved learning outcomes (Picciano, 2009). Another key benefit of blended learning is its potential to increase access to education. By offering online components, blended learning courses can be accessed from anywhere with an internet connection. This can be particularly important for students in remote or rural areas, as well as for those who have mobility or accessibility issues (Bonk & Graham, 2012).

Blended learning can also provide a more personalized learning experience. Instructors can use data and analytics from online components to tailor instruction to individual student needs, providing additional support or challenge as necessary (Picciano, 2009). Additionally, blended learning can provide opportunities for peer-to-peer learning and collaboration, both online and in-person. This can enhance social learning and help students develop important teamwork and communication skills (Bonk & Graham, 2012). However, there are also drawbacks to consider. One major concern is the potential for reduced face-to-face interaction. Blended learning can result in less time spent in the classroom, which may limit opportunities for students to ask questions, participate in discussions, and receive immediate feedback from instructors (Basham et al., 2019). Additionally, the online component of blended learning can lead to feelings of isolation and detachment, particularly for students who struggle with self-directed learning (Vaughan et al., 2013). Blended learning also requires significant technical infrastructure and support. This can be a challenge for some institutions, particularly those with limited resources.

Additionally, the online component of blended learning can be prone to technical difficulties, which can impede learning and create frustration for students (Vaughan et al., 2013). Another concern is the potential for increased workload. Blended learning may require students to complete additional online assignments or activities, which can increase the workload compared to traditional in-person instruction. This can be challenging for students who are balancing multiple courses or work commitments (Brame, 2013). Additionally, blended learning may require additional technology or software, which can increase the overall cost of the course. This may be a barrier for students who cannot afford the additional expenses (Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). Finally, blended learning courses may vary in quality depending on the instructor's experience, course design, and use of technology. This can create inconsistency in the learning experience and outcomes for students (Hrastinski, 2019). Additionally, instructors may struggle to provide timely and detailed feedback in blended learning environments, particularly in online components. This can impact student motivation and engagement, and may limit the effectiveness of the course (Basham et al., 2019).

Conclusion

Blended learning has both advantages and disadvantages to consider. While the approach can provide flexibility, access to education, personalized learning, and opportunities for collaboration, it also has the potential for reduced face-to-face interaction, technical difficulties, increased workload, and inconsistent quality. It is important for instructors and institutions to carefully consider these factors when designing and implementing blended learning courses.

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LIFE SKILLS AMONG PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

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Abstract

What does it mean to have life skills? It means having the ability to navigate your life, make decisions and problem-solve in times of crisis. It's having the emotional intelligence to understand yourself and build healthy relationships. It's also having the grit and resilience to stay focused and maintain a consistent effort even in the face of stressful situations. These are all necessary qualities for prospective teachers after all, they're going to be responsible for molding young minds and teaching them how to act in challenging situations. In order for them to properly impart this knowledge, they must possess these skills themselves. The prospective teachers should possess the most important life skills are Critical Thinking, Problem-Solving, Interpersonal Communication, and Emotional Intelligence.

Keywords: *Life skills, Prospective, Teachers*

Introduction

Teaching is more than just a job; it's a calling. To be successful, a teacher needs to have more than just academic knowledge - they must also possess the necessary life skills to help them in their role. Whether it's managing difficult emotions, problem-solving, or communication and collaboration, the list of life skills that teachers should have is extensive and ever-evolving. The modern classroom is one where students are encouraged to be actively involved in their education, so teachers must learn how to balance the two sides of education: instruction and guidance. What does this look like? It means providing students with direct instruction while also helping them to acquire the tools necessary to take ownership of their learning. In this article, we're going to explore life skills among prospective teachers and how they can use those skills to create an atmosphere of success in the classroom. We'll look at different strategies prospective teachers can use to build these skills and offer advice for how current educators can sharpen those qualities too.

What are Life Skills?

When it comes to setting yourself up for success in your teaching career, one of the most important things you can do is develop a set of life skills. Life skills are abilities that help you stay composed, organized and ready to take on whatever the day throws your way. So what kinds of life skills should prospective teachers have? First and foremost, learning how to manage your time efficiently is key—knowing when to prioritize tasks and when to delegate them is vital in maintaining productivity. Good organizational skills will also come in handy—understanding the best way to store resources and organize your classroom are essential for teaching effectively. Additionally, communication is key—being able to maintain strong student relationships or working with colleagues on a project requires not only patience but also an ability to effectively express yourself verbally or in writing. Developing these communication skills can be just as important as teaching content knowledge. So, let's take a look at some of the most important life skills that prospective teachers should possess:

- **Critical Thinking:** The ability to think clearly and rationally about what to do or believe in any given situation is essential for teachers. By teaching their students how to think critically about a particular topic or situation, they will develop questioning mindsets that can lead to more independent learning.
- **Problem-Solving:** Prospective teachers should also have strong problem-solving skills so they can help their students analyze problems and come up with creative solutions when faced with difficult tasks or issues.
- **Interpersonal Communication:** Good communication is key when dealing with students who have different backgrounds, personalities and beliefs. Prospective teachers must possess strong verbal and non-verbal communication skills in order to effectively reach out and connect with their students on an interpersonal level.
- **Emotional Intelligence:** The ability to understand your own emotions as well as those of others is essential for establishing trust within relationships with students and colleagues alike. This is further compounded by the fact that

Finally, having effective problem-solving and decision-making abilities will go a long way as you progress through your career. Not all situations have easy answers, so being able to think critically will be beneficial in any setting—from managing classroom disruptions to developing a new lesson plan.

Benefits of Life Skill Acquisitions

For prospective teachers and educators, the acquisition of life skills can be extremely beneficial. With the help of these skills and competencies, teachers can better serve their students, create a more harmonious classroom environment, and foster healthy relationships with their students. Life skills also allow prospective teachers to gain an increased awareness of the cultural backgrounds of their students. This deeper understanding allows them to create an inclusive learning environment and better cater to their students' cultural needs. Additionally, life skill-building helps improve student engagement and learning outcomes in the classroom by opening the path for open dialog and critical thinking within the class setting. Finally, having a comprehensive understanding of life skills gives prospective teachers greater insight into how social factors such as gender roles, power dynamics, and cultural context shape student behavior. With greater insight into how these factors come into play both inside and outside of the classroom setting will help teachers become better mentors for their students by understanding them holistically.

Strategies to Teach Life Skills

When it comes to teaching prospective teachers life skills, there are a few strategies you can use to ensure success. Let's take a look at three of the most effective ones.

Developing Self-Awareness

Self-awareness is an essential life skill, and one that many of us don't even think about. It's important for prospective teachers to understand their emotional reactions and motivations so that they can make informed decisions and manage their emotions more effectively. Encourage your students to practice reflection exercises, such as journaling or meditation, which will help them understand their emotions better and make better decisions.

Communication Skills

Good communication skills are key for any professional in today's world, especially for teachers. When teaching prospective teachers how to communicate effectively, emphasize the importance of active listening skills, showing empathy and understanding different perspectives. Role playing is also a great way to help teach communication skills — have students practice having conversations with each other in a safe environment where mistakes are allowed and encouraged.

Decision-Making Skills

Decision-making skills are essential for any teacher who needs to navigate complex situations and manage difficult conversations. Teach your prospective teachers how to break down complex problems into easier components, weigh options based on facts rather than feelings, assess risks and look at the big picture when making decisions. Teaching them these life skills will lay the foundation for future success as educators.

How to Incorporate Life Skills Into the Classroom

Life skills are becoming increasingly important for prospective teachers to learn and understand. Being able to properly teach life skills can help the overall development of students, both in and out of the classroom. So, how can you incorporate life skills into the classroom? Here are some tips:

Involve Classroom Activities

One way to integrate life skills into the classroom is by having your students participate in activities such as debates or presentations. These types of activities have the potential to encourage critical thinking and collaboration among students, two valuable life skills.

Model Life Skills

It's also important for prospective teachers to model life skills to their students. This means demonstrating self-awareness, problem solving, self-management, positive communication and healthy relationships. Teaching these specific habits through demonstrations allow your students to learn how they can best apply them in their own lives.

Incorporate Technology

Technology has made it easier than ever before to teach life skills in the classroom. There are plenty of software programs available that can help you teach topics such as budgeting, health awareness and workplace ethics that are needed for success outside of school walls. Incorporating technology into your lessons helps make them more engaging for students and allows them to access valuable information from anywhere. By following these tips, prospective teachers can ensure their students learn valuable life skills that will last a lifetime.

Strategies for Student Engagement in Life Skills Development

One thing that all aspiring teachers should possess is the knowledge and skills to engage students in their individual liveskills development. Teaching life skills is a tough job, but there are certain strategies that can be employed to create a motivating and engaging learning environment.

Active engagement

Active engagement requires teachers to be creative in their instruction and provide students with meaningful activities in which they can actively participate. Activities might include role playing, simulations, breaking tasks into smaller steps, or other activities that require students to reflect and think critically about their own behavior and the behavior of others.

Variety of methods

Life skills should not be taught using traditional lecturing methods alone; teachers should use a variety of methods such as interactive discussions, self-directed learning activities, problem solving tasks, project-based activities and more. This variety of teaching strategies helps to keep the class engaged and interested, which will result in more effective learning outcomes.

Collaborative learning environment

Collaborative learning environments provide opportunities for students to interact with each other while learning life skills. Through collaboration, students are able to share ideas, practice social interaction skills, work together to develop meaningful solutions to complex problems, and more. This type of environment helps to nurture interpersonal relationships among students while also providing them with an effective way to learn life skills.

Resources for Acquiring Life Skills Among Prospective Teachers

As a prospective teacher, you may be looking for ways to acquire life skills in order to be a better educator. There are plenty of resources out there to help you with this. Here are a few:

Professional Development Opportunities

There are many professional development opportunities available that can help you acquire necessary life skills. These include seminars, workshops, and conferences that focus on teaching and

learning strategies and other important topics like classroom management. In addition, many universities offer courses on how to become a successful educator.

On-the-Job Training

Often times, new teachers will get the opportunity for hands-on experience through on-the-job training under the guidance of experienced educators. This type of training is invaluable and allows new teachers to practice their life skills in real classroom settings.

Mentorship Programs

Many school districts have formal or informal mentorship programs that pair experienced educators with new teachers so they have someone to guide them through the teaching process and learn from their experience. Finding the right resources for acquiring the necessary life skills as a prospective teacher can be daunting but it doesn't have to be! By taking advantage of professional development opportunities, on-the-job training, and mentorship programs, you can gain the confidence and knowledge you need to become an effective teacher in no time.

Conclusion

Life skills can play a major role in the development of future teachers. By having these skills, prospective teachers can model behavior for their students and provide them with the necessary tools to become successful in the working world. Life skill learning should be seen as critical to the development of future teachers, as it will provide them with the skills and abilities to pass on to their students. It is important to keep in mind, however, that while life skills are important, they should never replace the traditional academic knowledge and skills teachers must possess in order to effectively teach. Life skills provide additional tools that can be used to supplement academic knowledge and can be used to teach other skills such as problem-solving, communication, and decision-making. Prospective teachers should never neglect the importance of life skills and should strive to cultivate these skills to the best of their ability.

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DEVELOPING ENGLISH LANGUAGE FOR ARTS & SCIENCE STUDENTS THROUGH LIFE SKILLS

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Abstract

As an arts and science student, learning life skills in English is essential for achieving success. Developing problem-solving and analytical skills can help you to recognize challenges and effectively develop plans of action. Learning effective communication strategies helps you to increase your confidence in discussing topics with peers, professors, and other professionals. Understanding the principles of grammar enables you to effectively review your own work and improve the clarity of your written documents. Additionally, mastering the nuances of conversation helps you to better interact with others in social settings.

Keywords: *English, Language, Life skills*

Introduction

For students in the arts and sciences, it is essential to develop both life skills and English proficiency. A strong command of the English language ensures that students are able to express themselves clearly, accurately, and confidently. Life skills, meanwhile, encompass a variety of abilities such as problem-solving, critical thinking, communication and time management. All of these are necessary for achieving success in academia and later on in the workplace. But how can you begin to develop these important skills? In this article, I discuss the various ways that students can improve their life skills and English proficiency in order to achieve success in their studies. I'll also touch upon some of the advantages that come with being bilingual or trilingual. By reading this article, you'll gain insight into how bettering your life skills and language abilities can help you become successful as an arts or science student.

Keys to Achieving Success: Personal and Career Development

As an Arts & Science student, it is important to recognize that developing certain life skills and honing your English ability can lead to success in both your personal and academic pursuits. Success means different things for different people, but by developing strong communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and leadership skills, you can be better prepared for a successful future. In addition to cultivating these essential life skills, improving your English language proficiency can also open many doors. After all, in today's global society, the ability to express yourself fluently in written and spoken English is more important than ever. Being able to effectively communicate across cultures can open new doors of opportunity and create powerful networking connections that can be invaluable to your future success. By taking the time to develop these life skills and understand the power of effective communication you will be able to confidently engage with the world around you and take advantage of every opportunity that comes your way.

How English Proficiency Impacts Student Success

As an Arts & Science student, developing English proficiency is important for my academic success. The ability to communicate clearly and accurately shapes a student's capacity for critical thought and self-expression. Knowing how to effectively communicate in this way allows me to not only better understand course materials, but also engage actively in academic conversations. When I have the confidence to express my ideas with good English, I can gain a greater sense of achievement and satisfaction from my studies. Additionally, strong English language skills can help bolster one's resumé—whether that means applying for a job, internship or even grad school. Building a solid foundation of communication skills not only impacts how I approach my academic life today, but it helps open doors for the future. With proper guidance, I can develop the necessary Life Skills and English proficiency to set me up for success in any field I choose later on.

What’s Holding Arts and Science Students Back?

Having developed life skills and a mastery of the English language can be invaluable assets for any student, yet in many cases, arts and science students find themselves at a disadvantage. Low marks in English can be attributed to two main problems:

Lack of Exposure

When it comes to English, arts and science students don't always have the opportunity to practice their skills as often as other students. Arts and science classes rarely demand written assignments, meaning there is less opportunity for a student to practice their writing and develop the necessary skills to excel on exams.

Struggling with Terminology

Arts and science require their own specific vocabularies, varying from topics within mathematics, history or physics. This can often lead to a low comprehension level when it comes to grammatical rules that might not have been covered in class as extensively as they should have been. This often leads to fewer points on tests due to incorrect grammar usage or lack of understanding or an inability to express ideas in an acceptable manner.

Approaches to Improving English Abilities

As a science student, I’ve identified several approaches to improving my English abilities. The most effective approach I’ve used is by getting involved in extra-curricular activities that require English proficiency. For example, participating in debates was especially helpful for me since it required me to prepare and present my points eloquently. Additionally, I also volunteered for reading programs at libraries, which helped me to improve my comprehension skills. Furthermore, I made it a priority to practice writing regularly, which enabled me to utilize more precise language and strengthened my ability to express myself clearly. I also found mentors who could provide guidance and support while I was on the journey towards mastering the English language. My mentor was a great source of encouragement and motivation which pushed me to keep working towards my goals and ultimately achieve success in using English effectively. All of these approaches have enabled me to develop confidence in speaking and expressing myself in English.

Utilizing Life Skills Education to Help Reach Goals

As an Arts and Science student, I understand the importance of developing life skills. Good study habits, communication, critical thinking, and the ability to solve problems are all essential for success. As a student, I have found that learning and practicing these skills can help me to reach my goals more easily and quickly. One way I have personally utilized life skills education is in problem-solving. Knowing how to identify the problem, break it down into manageable chunks, assess the situation, weigh options in terms of effectiveness and feasibility, plan an approach to solving the problem and finally evaluate the results of my actions has been invaluable in helping me make decisions and solve issues. Additionally, effective communication is imperative for Arts & Science students. Cultivating my communication skills allows me to present complex concepts clearly and concisely so that others may understand them easier. Developing proficiency with language also helps me express thoughts precisely when writing research papers or lab reports as well as when conversing with peers or professors about academic issues. My experience further reveals that learning how to manage my time is another essential skill that I believe assists Arts & Science students in their educational pursuits. By understanding how long assignments take me to complete and how best I can maximize both study sessions and free time allows me to set daily goals that are achievable while still providing a sense of accomplishment at the end of each day.

Supporting Student Growth through Learner-Focused Programs

I strongly believe that with the appropriate support, students of all disciplines and backgrounds can excel in their academic and life pursuits. I have found that creating a learner-focused program tailored to individual student needs is the key to helping Arts & Science students reach their goals. By creating a program that centers around the students’ growth, incorporating both life skills and English language development, students are able to find success in all areas of their lives. The focus on learner-focused programs encourages our students to become self-advocates for their educational needs, empowering them

to take ownership over their learning and development. This autonomy in turn leads to an increased sense of agency over their academic and life paths. In my experience, a good learner-focused program begins by assessing each student's individual strengths and weaknesses. By understanding how best each student learns, we are better equipped to offer targeted strategies for improvement. Once we identify these strategies, our educators can then present opportunities for each student to practice these skills in class, as well as through extra-curricular activities such as field trips or guest speakers. By providing a safe space where Arts & Science students can learn both English language proficiency and life skills, they are more likely to find success both in their academic pursuits and life goals overall.

Conclusion

By developing and mastering life skills, Arts and Science students can enjoy greater success both academically and professionally. While fluency in English is a valuable asset for these students, acquiring strong life skills is just as important for achieving academic and career-oriented goals. By cultivating an understanding of communication, personal development, problem-solving, and leadership, students can learn to navigate the challenges that accompany transitioning from school to the workplace. With the right skills and knowledge, Arts and Science students can set themselves up for a successful and rewarding future. Learning these skills is necessary if I'm going to succeed in my studies and future career: it's only by honing my life skills that I can become the best version of myself, both academically and professionally. As such, I strive to continue improving my ability in these areas so that I can build a successful future.

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FOSTERING RESILIENCE IN CHILDREN

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Introduction

Life is full of ups and downs, and it's easy to feel overwhelmed when things don't go as planned. However, the ability to bounce back from setbacks is what sets successful people apart from those who crumble under pressure. Resilience is the key to not only surviving but thriving in the face of adversity. It's the ability to adapt to change, overcome obstacles, and come out stronger on the other side. In this post, we'll explore the power of resilience and how it can change your life for the better. You'll learn how to build resilience, how to develop a growth mindset, and how to bounce back stronger than ever before. So, buckle up and get ready to embrace the power of resilience.

Resilience

Resilience is the ability to navigate through challenges, adversity, and stress and come out stronger on the other side. It is a skill that everyone can develop and can be applied to various aspects of life, whether it's personal or professional by developing resilience, you can improve your ability to handle stress, build stronger relationships, and enhance your overall mental and emotional health. In this blog series, we will explore the power of resilience and provide you with practical tips and strategies to help you bounce back stronger than before

Tips and Techniques to Cultivate Resilience

- **Build strong relationships** Having a support network can help you manage stress and cope with adversity. Spend time with friends and family, and don't be afraid to ask for help when you need it.
- **Practice self-care** - Taking care of your physical and emotional needs can help you cope with stress and build resilience. Make sure you're getting enough sleep, eating a healthy diet, and engaging in regular exercise.
- **Stay positive** - A positive attitude can help you stay motivated and focused, even in difficult times. Try to focus on the things that are going well in your life, and practice gratitude for the good things.
- **Learn from failure** - Failure is a natural part of life, and it's an opportunity to learn and grow. Instead of dwelling on your mistakes, try to learn from them and use them as a stepping stone to future success.
- **Set goals** - Setting goals can help you stay focused and motivated, even in difficult times. Make sure your goals are realistic and achievable, and break them down into smaller, manageable steps.

Strategies to Overcome Setbacks and Obstacles

Setbacks and obstacles are inevitable in life, but it's how we respond to them that defines our level of resilience. Here are some strategies to help you overcome setbacks and obstacles and bounce back stronger than before:

- **Practice self-care** - Take care of yourself physically, emotionally, and mentally. This means getting enough sleep, eating a balanced diet, exercising regularly, and taking time to relax and recharge.
- **Reframe your mindset** - Instead of seeing setbacks and obstacles as failures, see them as opportunities to learn and grow. Reframe your mindset to focus on the positive and look for ways to turn challenges into opportunities.
- **Seek support** - Don't be afraid to reach out for help when you need it. This could be in the form of a friend, family member, mentor, or therapist. Having a support system can help you feel less alone and give you the strength and encouragement you need to keep going.
- **Take action** - It's important to take action to overcome setbacks and obstacles. Break down your goals into smaller, manageable steps and take action every day. This will help you build momentum and make progress towards your goals.
- **Stay resilient** - Resilience is not a one-time event, it's a lifelong process. Keep practicing resilience strategies every day and remember that setbacks and obstacles are just temporary roadblocks on the path to success. With resilience, you can overcome anything that comes your way and bounce back stronger than before.

The role of mindfulness and self-compassion in building resilience

Mindfulness and self-compassion are key components in building resilience. When we experience adversity or setbacks in life, it's easy to become overwhelmed with negative thoughts and emotions. Mindfulness helps us to stay present and focused on the present moment, rather than dwelling on the past or worrying about the future. It allows us to observe our thoughts and emotions without judgment, which can help to reduce stress and anxiety. Self-compassion is also important in building resilience because it helps us to be kind and supportive to ourselves, even when we make mistakes or face challenges. Self-compassion involves treating ourselves with the same kindness, concern, and support that we would offer to a good friend.

This can help us to feel more confident and less self-critical, which can in turn increase our ability to bounce back from adversity. One way to practice self-compassion is to use positive self-talk. When we face a setback or make a mistake, it's important to talk to ourselves in a compassionate and understanding way. Instead of berating ourselves for our shortcomings, we can remind ourselves that everyone makes mistakes and that we are doing the best we can. Incorporating mindfulness and self-compassion into our daily lives can help us to build resilience and bounce back stronger than before. By staying present, focusing on the positive, and treating ourselves with kindness and compassion, we can weather any storm that comes our way.

The importance of fostering resilience in children

Fostering resilience in children is incredibly important for their development and future success. Resilience is the ability to adapt and bounce back from adversity, stress, and setbacks. Children who develop resilience are better equipped to handle life's challenges and navigate difficult situations with confidence and ease. There are many ways to foster resilience in children. One of the most effective ways is to provide them with a safe and supportive environment where they can learn and grow without fear of failure or rejection.

Encouraging them to take risks and try new things, while providing guidance and support, can help build confidence and resilience.

Another key factor in fostering resilience is teaching children problem-solving skills. Helping them learn how to identify problems, brainstorm solutions, and implement them can give them a sense of control and autonomy, which can help build resilience. Additionally, it's important to help children develop a positive mindset. Encouraging them to focus on their strengths and successes, rather than their failures, can help build resilience and a positive outlook on life. Overall, fostering resilience in children is crucial for their personal and professional growth. By providing them with the tools and support they need to bounce back from adversity, we can help them develop into confident, successful adults.

Conclusion

Resilience is an essential life skill that can help you to overcome obstacles, bounce back from setbacks and emerge stronger and more determined than ever before. The power of Resilience lies in its ability to help us to adapt to changing circumstances, learn from our failures and setbacks, and build the mental and emotional strength we need to face the challenges of life head-on.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Blended Learning is an innovative methods in classroom teaching. It has scope for collaborative learning, constructive learning and computer assisted learning. The present paper discuss the concept of blended learning models, implementation and quality. The present paper also tries to explain that how blended learning is an approach that needs to be adopted.

Keywords: *Blended Learning, ICT supported Teaching, Models, Teaching Learning Process and Quality.*

Introduction

Education field has gone through significant changes in recent years. As teachers strive to help students engage with their learning in deep and meaningful ways, new strategies help them reach these goals. Blended learning models represent an innovative way to promote student success.

Blended Learning Model

Blended learning models are methods for encouraging hybrid learning. Schools and teachers create experiences and opportunities that combine face-to-face learning with distance learning.

Importance

Blended learning models usually leverage a combination of in-person instruction techniques, teacher-led online modules, and self-paced learning. Students may participate in a combination of independent study, small group learning, and whole-class instruction, whether online or in person.

Types of Blended Learning Models

There are a variety of different models for facilitating blended learning. Each model differs somewhat in terms of teacher responsibilities, administrative requirements, and instructional emphasis. All blended learning models allow for some flexibility in how they are implemented.

- **The Flipped Classroom Model** - Flipped classrooms give teachers the opportunity to facilitate the completion of educational projects and to support students as they practice using concepts learned independently.
- **The Enriched Virtual Model** - This method is similar to the flipped classroom. Students learn primarily online, though face-to-face sessions with the teacher are also required. Online teaching is then supplemented with mandatory in-person educational experiences.
- **The Individual Rotation Model** - The individual rotation model can be employed in a variety of different educational settings, including in blended learning models. Learning opportunities include independent study, small groups, collaboration, lessons conducted by the teacher for the whole group, and individualized interventions. Fixed schedules may be used in place of customized learning journeys if needed, and various stations can be completed online or in person.
- **The Flex Model** - This is a self-paced, student-driven model. According to the book Learning in the Digital Age, flex models were originally devised to assist returning students who had not completed their high school education. This level of independence may be better suited to older students.

Barriers Encountered in implementation of Blending

- Technical issues
- Learners may not access to the resources they need to lay in complete remote learning.
- Disabilities and Special needs.
- Lack of Interaction online distractions.
- Poor Digital Literacy

Quality Maintenance

Quality Blended Learning promotes the development of a comprehensive training material delivered through an interactive cross platform on-line resource that promotes the knowledge required for the design and the implementation of blended learning courses.

Conclusion

Blended Learning is to some extent is the solution to problems prevailing in our educational system. If implemented in a well planned organized way with right type of attitude it can become the future of our educational system. It is our own benefit that steps for adapting blended learning are soon initiated.

USING BLENDED LEARNING TO IMPROVE THE MATHEMATICAL ABILITIES OF DYSCALCULIC STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article enables us to understand the problem faced by the dyscalculic students and the ways how they come across to the subject of mathematics and the capacities to learn or pick up the mathematical

abilities in their daily life. Mathematical Abilities are easy computation, numerical processing of any problems, Identification of the word problems etc. Blended Learning is known as technology mediated learning instruction, web based or web enhanced instruction or mixed mode instruction is an approach which is best for mathematical learning and teaching which combines online educational materials and with traditional approaches for interaction and its classroom materials. The dyscalculic students find this method is to be more of practical to handle the mathematical difficulties to improve their Mathematical Abilities.

Keywords: *blended learning, mathematical abilities, dyscalculic students*

Introduction

Blended learning is a process where one can combine more of traditional methods and web based instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of educational environments to the students. Mathematical abilities refer to the ability to understand the basic number concept and principles of mathematics among school students. Blended Learning is a technique which combines the online and the normal traditional classrooms or face to face learning. As much as effective involvement of blended learning can enhance the dyscalculic students. Mathematical Ability is a human construct that may be defined cognitively or pragmatically, depending on the purpose of definitions. From this perspective, it can be defined as the ability to perform mathematical tasks and to effectively solve the given mathematical problems.

Mathematics and Mathematical Abilities

Mathematics is the science of measurement, quality, and magnitude. It is an area of knowledge which deals with quality, space, structure, and change. Mathematics plays a vital role among primary school students of different characteristics and perspectives. The mathematical skill helps the students to develop their basic arithmetical operations and develops the talent to solve the daily problems related to life and the academic activities in the school. They are numerical skills, observation skills, thinking skills, analytical skills, problem solving skills, decision making skills, life skills, understanding logics, skills of comparing, skills of interpretation, skill of special analysis and interpretation, skills of games. These skills could easily be developed by using indigenous materials like paper, sticks, pins etc. Learning Disability affecting math computation and numerical processing. Struggle to understand and memorizing processes, generalize for multiple math areas.

Dyscalculia

Literal meaning of the word ‘Dyscalculia’ is ‘disorder in calculation’ (Hannell, 2005:2). Dyscalculia is mainly used to describe the specific difficulties in learning mathematics. It is a condition that affects the ability to acquire the mathematical skills, especially difficulty with mathematical computation, mathematical reasoning and problem solving. Dyscalculia involves disturbances of quantitative thinking stemming from dysfunction of the central nervous system. Studies of traumatically brain-damaged adults indicate these specific arithmetical disabilities.

Different symptoms of dyscalculia

- Difficulty in memorizing table.
- Difficulty in understanding word problems.
- Have confusion in before-after concepts.
- Have difficulty in reading multi-digit number.
- Have difficulty in telling time.
- Difficulty in aligning numbers to do calculation.
- Inability to grasp the concept of place value.
- Inability to understand mathematical symbols.
- Poor computational skills like addition, subtraction, and multiplication
- Wrong placement of decimals.
- Not able to complete the assigned work in the given time.

The Definition of Blended Learning

According to Oxford Dictionary Definition of Blended Learning: a style of education in which students learn via electronic and online media as well as traditional face-to-face teaching. Blended Learning is known as technology mediated learning instruction, web based or web enhanced instruction or mixed mode instruction is an good approach for mathematical learning and teaching which combines online educational materials and with traditional approaches for interaction and its classroom materials.

Types of Blended Learning

The Flipped Classroom, Hybrid Learning You can read more about the most common types of blended learning, Using of Math app for the dyscalculia students is one of the best way to learn easily the numbers concept, easy to memorize the formulae etc. The classroom offers an opportunity for role-playing with immediate face-to-face feedback. Online learning offers personalized, self-paced learning with eLearning components that lend the students themselves to interactive media such as games, videos, tutorials, quizzes and social media components, all accessible from the learner's home page in the Learning Management System (LMS)—and accessible from the learner's Smartphone or tablet.

Teaching strategies for dyscalculic students

- **Thinking Hypothetical Strategy** - It represents a group of complex and interrelated processes and activities. It is performed by the brain that causes a person to interact with himself or with those around him when Exposed to a stimulus that is received by one or more senses, resulting in a response Or a group of different responses, depending on the circumstances. Virtual thinking is one of the types of thinking through which an individual can employ His abilities to put forward the hypotheses supported by evidence and unleash his thinking, and careful And scrutiny of sentencing.
- **Application Systems Symbol strategy** - This strategy depends on applying visual or numerical systems in communication between individuals instead of words and words or vice versa, such as the transition from the verbal system to the numerical system, and learners work when applying this strategy to graphically draw, draw relationships or write equations that link Show different variables using planning organizations, drawings or pictures and others.
- **Analysis of Point View strategy** - This method depends on looking at the reasons why a person is believed in a belief through meditation, analysis and reflection on these beliefs and then Judge it. Al-Baali (2013) notes that this type of thinking helps the individual To systematically face problems, gather and organize the most amount of information, Careful planning before making the decision, and clarifying the particles to reach conclusions rationality.
- **Web Analysis Strategy** - This strategy relies on interconnecting concepts and variables. Retina, since events and phenomena are usually associated in complex ways; except that the brain Man tends to simplify these relationships and explore the connections between them, because the brain is interested A lot to analyze, organize, and categorize objects in patterns and models besides discover Similarities, differences and comparisons.

Conclusion

Thus blended learning can be much assistive to the students who struggle with mathematical operations. While following the strategies and simplified steps for them which will reduce the pain of learning difficulties. It is the much encouraging ways and approaches which will enhance the mathematical abilities of the dyscalculic students. By following the blended learning techniques and technologies are also great sources of inspiration for their good out coming of learning process.

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BLENDED LEARNING AS A PART OF VIRTUAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Technology-based training emerged as an alternative to instructor-led training in the 1960s on mainframes and mini-computers. The major advantage that blended learning offers is scale, whereas one instructor can only teach so many people. One example is PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automatic Teaching Operations), a system developed by the University of Illinois and Control Data. PLATO in particular had a long history of innovations and offered coursework from elementary to the college level. Mainframe-based training had a number of interface limitations that gave way to satellite-based live video in the 1970s. The advantage here was serving people who were not as computer literate. The major challenge was the expense required to make this work. In the early 1990s, CD-ROMs emerged as a dominant form of providing technology-based learning as bandwidth through 56k modems weren't able to support very high quality sound and video. The limitation to CD-ROMs was tracking completion of coursework, so learning management systems emerged as a way to facilitate progress tracking. The aviation industry used this heavily to track how well one did on courses, how much time was spent, and where someone left off. AICC, Aviation Industry Computer-Based Training Committee, was formed in 1988 and companies such as Boeing used CD-ROMs to provide training for personnel. Modern blended learning is delivered online, although CD-ROMs could feasibly still be used if a learning management system meets an institution's standards. Some examples of channels through which online blending learning can be delivered include webcasting (synchronous and asynchronous) and online video (live and recorded).

Keywords: *Plato, Technology-Based Learning*

Introduction

A virtual learning environment (VLE) is a Web-based platform for the digital aspects of courses of study, usually within educational institutions. VLEs typically: allow participants to be organized into cohorts, groups and roles; present resources, activities and interactions within a course structure; provide for the different stages of assessment; report on participation; and have some level of integration with other institutional systems.

Components of Virtual Learning Environment

- A notice board for current information about the ongoing course
- The basic content of some or all of the course; the complete course for distance learning applications, or some part of it, when used as a portion of a conventional course. This normally includes material such as copies of lecture in the form of text, audio, or video presentations, and the supporting visual presentations
- Additional resources, either integrated or as links to outside resources. This typically consists of supplementary reading or innovative equivalents for it.
- Self-assessment quizzes or analogous devices, normally scored automatically
- Formal assessment functions, such as examinations, essay submission, or presentation of projects. this now frequently includes components to support peer assessment
- Support for communications, including e-mail, threaded discussions, chat rooms, Twitter and other media, sometimes with the instructor or an assistant acting as moderator. Additional elements include wikis, blogs, RSS and 3D virtual learning spaces.

- Links to outside sources – pathways to all other online learning spaces are linked via the VLE (Virtual Learning Environment).
- Management of access rights for instructors, their assistants, course support staff, and students
- Documentation and statistics as required for institutional administration and quality control
- Authoring tools for creating the necessary documents by the instructor, and, usually, submissions by the students
- Provision for the necessary hyperlinks to create a unified presentation to the students.
- A VLE is normally not designed for a specific course or subject, but is capable of supporting multiple courses over the full range of the academic program, giving a consistent interface within the institution and-to some degree-with other institutions using the system. The virtual learning environment supports an exchange of information between a user and the learning institute he or she is currently enrolled in through digital mediums like e-mail, chat rooms, web 2.0 sites or a forum thereby helping convey information to any part of the world with just a single click.

Other Names of Virtual Learning Environment (VRL)

Computerized learning systems have been referred to as electronic educational technology, e-learning, learning platform or learning management system. The major difference is that VLE and LMS are applications, whereas the Learning Platform shares characteristics with an Operating System (or Course Park Platform) where different educational web based applications can be run on the platform. The terms virtual learning environment (VLE) and learning platform are generically used to describe a range of integrated web based applications that provide teachers, learners, parents and others involved in education with information, tools and resources to support and enhance educational delivery and management. These terms are broadly synonymous with 'managed learning environments' (MLEs). The applications that form part of these online services can include web pages, email, message boards and discussion forums, text and video conferencing, shared diaries, online social areas, as well as assessment, management and tracking tools. The specific functionality associated with any implementation of a learning platform will vary depending upon the needs of the users and can be achieved by bringing together a range of features from different software solutions either commercially available, open source, self-built or available as free to use web services. These tools are delivered together via a cohesive user environment with a single entry point, through integration achieved by technical standards.

Blended Learning as a Part of Virtual Learning Environment

Some online institutions connect students with instructors via web conference technology to form a digital classroom. These institutions borrow many of the technologies that have popularized online courses at the university level. Some advantages of blended learning, particularly at a Kindergarten to grade 12 level of education, can be found under the general concept of educational technology. It is also one of the most effective ways for personalized learning at scale. Blended learning supports the Common Core State Standards, which encourage integration of technology into a variety of subjects. A learning management system helps develop a better feel for an online community where discussions can be held to better aid students. This virtual learning environment helps connect professors with students without physically being present, thus making this a 'virtual cafe'. Many schools use this online tool for online classes, class work, question & answer forums, and other school related work. Blended learning yielded positive results from the online community. The advantages of blended learning are dependent on the quality of the programs being implemented. Some indicators of excellent blended learning programs are "facilitating student learning, communicating ideas effectively, demonstrating an interest in learning, organizing effectively, showing respect for students, and assessing progress fairly."

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BLENDED LEARNING AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE : A PROMISING APPROACH FOR TEACHER TRAINEES

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Abstract

Blended learning is a type of education that combines traditional classroom instruction with online learning activities. Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to identify and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others. Emotional intelligence is a crucial skill for teachers, as it allows them to build positive relationships with their students, manage stress effectively, resolve conflicts, improve communication, and enhance teaching effectiveness. Blended learning has been found to be an effective approach to teacher education, offering flexibility, personalization, engagement, collaboration, and cost-effectiveness. However, it is important to ensure that blended learning programs are designed and delivered effectively, with appropriate support and resources for teacher trainees. Blended learning and emotional intelligence development can be effectively incorporated into teacher education programs. Online emotional intelligence assessments and training, blended learning activities that promote emotional intelligence, peer feedback and support, and reflective practice are all effective strategies for promoting emotional intelligence development in teacher trainees. The researchers found that the blended practices had a positive impact on participants' emotional intelligence, particularly in the areas of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation and social skills.

Keywords : *Blended Learning , Emotional Intelligence , Teacher Education, Blended practices*

Introduction

Blended learning is an approach to education that combines traditional face-to-face classroom teaching with online learning. This hybrid model of learning allows teacher trainees to access educational resources, participate in discussions, and complete assignments online, while also providing them with opportunities for in-person interaction and instruction. Blended learning has become increasingly popular in recent years, as advances in technology have made it easier to deliver educational content online. This approach offers a number of benefits, including increased flexibility for students, greater access to educational resources, and the ability to personalize learning to meet the needs of individual students. However, it also requires careful planning and management to ensure that students are getting the most out of both the online and in-person components of their education. Emotional intelligence (EI) refers to the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions, as well as the emotions of others. It involves a set of skills that allow individuals to recognize, understand, and regulate their own emotions, while also being able to empathize with others and respond appropriately to their emotions. Research has shown that individuals with high EI are more likely to be successful in their personal and professional lives. In education, teachers with high EI are better equipped to manage their classrooms, build positive relationships with their students, and support student success. EI can be developed and improved through training and practice, and can have a positive impact on both individuals and organizations.

Models in Blended Learning

Blended learning can take many different forms, depending on the needs of the students and the resources available to the teacher. Some common examples include:

- Flipped classroom: In this model, students watch pre-recorded video lectures or complete online readings before coming to class, and then spend class time engaged in discussions and activities.
- Rotation model: Students rotate between different learning stations, spending some time in traditional classrooms and some time working independently online.

- Flex model: Students have a great deal of flexibility in how they complete their coursework, with some work done online and some done in person.
- A la carte model: Students can choose which courses they take online and which they take in person, allowing them to customize their education to fit their needs.
- Blended learning has become increasingly popular in recent years, as advances in technology have made it easier to deliver educational content online. This approach offers a number of benefits, including increased flexibility for students, greater access to educational resources, and the ability to personalize learning to meet the needs of individual students. However, it also requires careful planning and management to ensure that students are getting the most out of both the online and in-person components of their education.

Effectiveness of Blended learning in teacher education

Blended learning has become increasingly popular in teacher education programs as it offers a combination of face-to-face instruction and online learning activities. Here are some ways in which blended learning has been found to be effective in teacher education:

- Flexibility: Blended learning offers teachers the flexibility to access course materials and resources at their own pace and schedule. This allows teachers to balance their work and personal responsibilities, while still advancing their education and professional development.
- Personalization: Blended learning can be personalized to meet the needs of individual teachers. Teachers can choose to focus on specific areas of interest, work at their own pace, and receive individualized feedback and support from instructors.
- Engagement: Blended learning can increase engagement and motivation among teachers. The combination of face-to-face instruction and online learning activities can provide a variety of learning experiences, which can keep teachers engaged and motivated throughout the program.
- Collaboration: Blended learning can facilitate collaboration among teachers. Online discussion forums, group projects, and other collaborative activities can help teachers connect with one another, share ideas, and build a supportive community.
- Cost-effective: Blended learning can be more cost-effective than traditional face-to-face instruction, as it reduces the need for physical classroom space and travel expenses.
- Blended learning has been found to be an effective approach to teacher education, offering flexibility, personalization, engagement, collaboration, and cost-effectiveness. However, it is important to ensure that blended learning programs are designed and delivered effectively, with appropriate support and resources for teachers.

Components of Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman EI is composed of several components, including:

- Self-awareness: the ability to recognize and understand one's own emotions.
- Self-regulation: the ability to manage and control one's own emotions and behaviours.
- Motivation: the ability to use emotions to drive behaviour and achieve goals.
- Empathy: the ability to understand and recognize the emotions of others.
- Social skills: the ability to communicate effectively, build relationships, and work collaboratively with others.

Importance of Emotional Intelligence to teachers

Emotional intelligence is an essential skill for teachers because it allows them to understand and manage their own emotions, as well as the emotions of their students. Here are some reasons why emotional intelligence is important for teachers:

- Building positive relationships: Teachers with high emotional intelligence are better equipped to build positive relationships with their students. They can empathize with their students, understand their feelings, and respond appropriately to their emotional needs. This helps to create a positive and supportive classroom environment.
- Managing stress: Teaching can be a stressful job, and emotional intelligence can help teachers manage stress effectively. Teachers with high emotional intelligence are better able to regulate their own emotions and avoid getting overwhelmed by stress. This, in turn, helps them to perform better and provide better support for their students.

- Resolving conflicts: Conflicts can arise in any classroom, and emotional intelligence can help teachers resolve conflicts effectively. Teachers with high emotional intelligence are better able to communicate clearly, listen actively, and find mutually beneficial solutions to conflicts.
- Improving communication: Emotional intelligence can also improve communication between teachers and students. Teachers with high emotional intelligence are able to communicate more effectively, using clear and concise language, active listening, and nonverbal cues to convey their message.
- Enhancing teaching effectiveness: Finally, emotional intelligence can enhance teaching effectiveness. Teachers with high emotional intelligence are better able to understand the needs of their students and adjust their teaching methods accordingly. They can also provide better feedback and support for their students, which can lead to improved academic performance.

Incorporation of Blended Learning and Emotional Intelligence Development

Blended learning and emotional intelligence development can be effectively incorporated into teacher education programs. Here are some ways in which these two approaches can be combined:

- Online emotional intelligence assessments: Teacher education programs can use online emotional intelligence assessments to help teachers identify their strengths and weaknesses in this area. This can help teachers to develop targeted strategies for improving their emotional intelligence.
- Online emotional intelligence training: Teacher education programs can incorporate online emotional intelligence training modules into their curriculum. These modules can provide teachers with information and strategies for improving their emotional self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and social skills.
- Blended learning activities that promote emotional intelligence: Blended learning activities can be designed to promote emotional intelligence development. For example, online discussion forums can be used to encourage students to share their emotional experiences and perspectives, while face-to-face instruction can be used to facilitate group activities that promote empathy and social skills.
- Peer feedback and support: Blended learning can facilitate peer feedback and support, which can be an effective way to promote emotional intelligence development. For example, online peer review can be used to provide constructive feedback on emotional intelligence development strategies, while face-to-face group activities can be used to provide emotional support and encouragement.
- Reflective practice: Teacher education programs can incorporate reflective practice activities into their blended learning curriculum. These activities can help teachers to reflect on their emotional experiences and develop strategies for improving their emotional intelligence.
- Several studies have explored the relationship between blended learning and emotional intelligence. Here are a few examples:
- In a study published in the *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, researchers found that blended learning had a positive impact on the emotional intelligence of students. The study involved 96 undergraduate students who completed a blended learning course. The researchers found that the course improved students' emotional self-awareness, emotional self-regulation, and social skills.
- Another study, published in the *Journal of Educational Psychology*, examined the effects of blended learning on emotional intelligence in a sample of 159 high school students. The researchers found that blended learning had a positive effect on students' emotional intelligence, particularly in the areas of emotional self-awareness, emotional self-regulation, and empathy.
- A study published in the *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education* explored the impact of blended learning on the emotional intelligence of adult learners. The study involved 52 participants who completed a blended learning course. The researchers found that the course had a positive impact on participants' emotional intelligence, particularly in the areas of emotional self-awareness, emotional self-regulation, and motivation.
- Overall, these studies suggest that blended learning can have a positive impact on emotional intelligence of teacher trainees, particularly in the areas of emotional self-awareness, emotional self-regulation, and social skills. However, more research is needed to fully understand the relationship between these two constructs.

Blended practices for improving emotional intelligence of teacher trainees

Improving emotional intelligence (EI) among teacher trainees is important because it can positively impact their ability to manage their own emotions, empathize with others, build strong relationships with students, and create a positive classroom climate. Blended practices, which combine both online and offline components, can be an effective way to improve the emotional intelligence of teacher trainees. Here are some blended practices that can be used:

- Online EI assessments: Use online assessments to help teacher trainees understand their own emotional intelligence. These assessments can provide a baseline understanding of their emotional intelligence levels and areas for improvement.
- Online EI training modules: Provide teacher trainees with online EI training modules that cover topics such as self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, and relationship management. These modules can be completed at their own pace and can be reinforced through in-person discussions and activities.
- In-person group discussions: Facilitate group discussions among teacher trainees to encourage them to reflect on their emotions and their impact on others. These discussions can be guided by a trained facilitator who can help trainees develop strategies for improving their emotional intelligence.
- Role-playing exercises: Use role-playing exercises to help teacher trainees practice empathy and relationship management skills. This can be done in-person or through virtual simulations.
- Feedback and coaching: Provide trainees with ongoing feedback and coaching to help them improve their emotional intelligence skills. This can be done through one-on-one coaching sessions, group feedback sessions, or through online platforms.
- By using these blended practices, teacher trainees can develop their emotional intelligence skills and become more effective educators. The combination of online and in-person components provides a flexible and comprehensive approach to improving emotional intelligence.

Conclusion

In conclusion, blended learning and emotional intelligence development can be effectively incorporated into teacher education programs. Online emotional intelligence assessments and training, blended learning activities that promote emotional intelligence, peer feedback and support, and reflective practice are all effective strategies for promoting emotional intelligence development in teachers.

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BLENDING LEARNING SUGGESTED MODELS AND APPROCHES IN MATHEMATICS

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Abstract

Blended Literacy (face- to- face plus online literacy) is now part of the literacy geography in Higher Education, not just for lot- grounded courses but also for courses designed for scholars studying at a distance (Distance Education). This paper focuses on exploring blended literacy as an approach to the tutoring and literacy of mathematics in Advanced Education. Its give knowledge and understanding of current and future trends regarding how conventional face- to- face instruction in mathematics is told by web- grounded/ computer- supported literacy. Practical pedagogical issues related to mathematics and blended literacy in Higher Education are also disputed. The experimenter recommends that advanced institutions could use

blended literacy situation similar as WebCT in the tutoring and literacy of mathematics in Advanced Education.

Keywords : *Blended literacy , Higher education, Mathematics, WebCT.*

Introduction

The rapid-fire development of information and communication technology(ICT) and the move toward a robust knowledge- ferocious and globalized society have created new challenges and openings in educational design model and pedagogical approaches in the tertiary institutions(UNESCO, 2003; Tella, 2014). The use of ICT in the academic geography has removed time and place constraints in the tutoring and literacy of mathematics. These studies of ICT in the tutoring and literacy of mathematics is eased through the use of web- grounded and computer- supported technologies in both schedule and non schedule dimensions, generally known as virtual literacy terrain(VLE). VLE can be defined as a self - paced computer- grounded(web) situation enabling communication between demonstrators and scholars where colorful tools are handed for the scholars to present their literacy experience(Chin, 2003). Some VLEs bear specific software to be installed on the learners ' computer, but utmost VLEs operate across the World Wide Web, so learners frequently need Internet connectivity to access a VLE.

Access to online courses is granted with a word available only to scholars enrolled in the sanctioned institutional courses by the demonstrators (Torrieco & Scancarello, 2009). Downes (2010) noted that the web is shifting from being a medium in which information is transmitted and consumed to a platform, in which content is created, participated, repurposed, and passed along as connective knowledge in networks. Study materials are produced and altered by scholars, occasionally in collaboration, with speakers, who takes the part of intercessors in the process of tutoring of the subject matter using web- grounded approaches (Komlenov, Budimac, Putnik & Ivanovic, 2013). Therefore, knowledge only resides not only in the mind of an educator or individualities, but also in a distributed manner across a network, and literacy is the act of recognizing patterns shaped by these complex networks (Siemens, 2003). The main point of distributed knowledge is that the literacy situation is designed to accommodate the fact that scholars have different literacy styles, requirements and preferences. Meta- analyses have shown that the growing number of scholars in Advanced Education have problems understanding the course content in mathematics, because of their poor knowledge of the subject matter attributed to educational approaches and learners ' comprehensions of the literacy situation (Lizzio, Wilson & Simons, 2002). Its well- known that mathematics examinations are a major obstacle for scholars taking fine wisdom- related course in advanced institution. They've the maximum failure rate, numerous dropouts and lead to considerable detainments in completing university degrees. Some may lack of interest, provocation, and positive thinking, and some aren't interested in specializing in mathematics (Abramovitz, Berezina, Bereman, Shvartsman, 2012). Therefore, they pay little or no attention to understanding introductory fine generalities. Thus, supplementing conventional face- to- face literacy in the classroom with technological- grounded tools could stimulate learners ' interest and gives learners control of their literacy task and may also increase the number of scholars taking mathematics courses. This blended literacy approach could impact scholars' comprehensions of the literacy situation, their literacy approaches, and learning issues in the subject matter. This article provides view into current and future trends regarding how conventional face- to- face instruction is eased and influence by web- grounded/ computer- supported literacy and other arising technologies. Practical pedagogical issues related to mathematics blended learning in advanced institutions are also discussed.

Perspective of Blended Literacy in Advanced Education

There's no agreed description of blended literacy, but there has been a common theme presented in numerous conversations in the literature; the recognition of some combination of virtual literacy and the physical situation. Blended literacy is a collaboration of conventional face- to- face literacy and online literacy(virtual literacy), adapted to foster active literacy, interactivity, and cooperative literacy experience as learners ' strive to understand, develop knowledge, and creativity in the literacy process. According to Singh (2003) blended comprises colorful event- grounded conditioning including face- to- face literacy in the classroom, live e-learning (online) and self - pace literacy. This pedagogical model encourages scholars to learn in an interactive and cooperative situation at their own pace and in their own time. Oliver and Trigwell (2005).

Summarize the concept of blended learning as follows:

- Combining or mixing web- grounded technology to negotiate an educational goal.
- Combining literacy propositions (e.g., constructivism, behaviorism, cognitivism, and connectivism) to produce an optimal literacy outcome with or without educational technology with face- to- face instruction- led training and
- Incorporating educational technology with the design model of an educational program of study.

Blended Literacy Tools in Mathematics Education

The mathematics/ computer laboratory is considered to be suitable situation for the relinquishment and perpetration of a blended literacy approach. The mathematics/ computer laboratory could also deliver the growth of blended literacy, if the needed software, hardware and Internet installations are created to optimize its functionality. Principally, blended literacy tools that deliver mathematics instruction are computer- supported instructions similar as MATLAB/ SIMULINK software, Modular computation Software(scar), Home Work System(HWS), Microsoft MathType Software(MMS), and SPSS. Technology- enhanced tools similar as; e- forum/e-mail platforms, videotape on Demand, Animated videotape Delivery System, and power point donation provide blended literacy in mathematics instruction when moderated by tutors on colorful courses in advanced institutions. Nonetheless, sophisticated web-grounded or VLEs have emerged similar as; The Modular Object acquainted Dynamic literacy situation (MOODLE) platform, Blackboard Learning Management System, e-converge pedagogical model, WebCT, MUMIE online resources, WebALT, web2.0, and other open courseware(Albano, 2012; Albano & Maresca, 2010). VLEs can condense traditional face- to- face tutoring styles, but there are a number of challenges in Advanced Education where; for illustration, increased scholars ' number, automated assessment, increased participation, and bettered access to limited resources. These tools are designed with features that blend with the conventional face- to- face classroom and the aim of the courses, as well as, easing ferocious literacy openings for the learners. Chin (2003) suggested that the basic tools offered by any VLEs to additional conventional face- to- face classroom should including the following:

Communication tools

The introductory point of any VLE that can condense conventional face- to- face classroom literacy is any form of schedule or non schedule communication tools. It should allow forwarding of matters to regular Internet e-mail addresses. Scholars are encouraged to use the e-mail feature and communicate with tutors and with fellow scholars. It provides a more accessible system of filing correspondence relative to the course. Another basic communication tool is the discussion board; an electronic board works in important the same way as a physical notice board, by allowing scholars to post dispatches for others to read and post replies. This tool helps to collect comprehensive class conditioning and quiz schedules for the online study sessions, and other applicable information pertaining to the course. A live converse or discussion forum is another schedule communication tools blended into VLEs. One benefit of this tool is that it can enable pupil-pupil, and pupil- tutor / demonstrator communication at different locations. Interactive whiteboard are used in VLEs to help scholars and tutors to compose material interactively in a basic way so that everyone can see the work of another and contribute.

Content delivery tools

A core function of a VLE is the ability to deliver content in a variety of formats. This tool allows the instructor/course designer to submit/upload files (e-book, e-journal), deliver lecture support notes, and image, audio, or video presentation files, as well as interactive animations.

Assessment tools

This tool enables students to view their quiz grades and examination results. Its enables instant marking, quick data analysis and quick feedback for students. The results can be used with other features within the system by the lecturers.

Content exchange and group work tools

These tools allow staff and students to provide and share files with one another. This means that students can share work in an online environment rather having to meet face-to-face. Students can use this tool to make group presentations.

Benefit of Blended Literacy in Advanced Education

Studies have shown that courses using blended literacy delivery system contribute to better literacy issues for the scholars (Boyle, Brandley, Chalk, Jones & Picard, 2003; Groen and Carmody, 2005; Iozzi & Osimio, 2012). Twisg (2003) reported that courses redesigned to include blended literacy redounded in scholars achieving advanced grades, lesser knowledge, and understanding of course generalities. This could lead to a reduction in the pupil dropout rate in advanced. Another benefit of blended literacy is the increased inflexibility of access to literacy which facilitates review and learners' control of the literacy situation. The Internet provides flexibility and effectiveness in tutoring and literacy conditioning. Tutoring sessions can be conducted via videotape or teleconference links so that learners can attend classes online. Study materials are readily available over the Web. Operations handed over the Internet similar as e-libraries, e-books, e-resources give openings for learners and preceptors. The blended literacy approaches allow learners who lives some distance down from the institution to enroll in a program, and the online element allows them to work whenever and wherever they prefer because they can pierce the Internet without making the trip to campus (Tam, 2000).

Garrison and Kanuka (2004) explored how blended literacy can offer transformational capabilities to advanced institutions. Advanced institutions could harness innovative technologies in tutoring and literacy program by redesigning the class to enhance a community of enquiry, supporting active and meaningful Blended literacy also foster professional learning community, improves institutional character, and allows the development of social cohesion due to the addition of the face- to- face element(Owston, Wideman, Murphy & Lupshenyuk, 2008). Blended literacy is cost and resource effective. Institutional costs are reduce because the materials can be placed online and re-used at convenience (Vaughan, 2007; Holland, 2012). The size of the pupil cohort can increase and the number of classrooms decreases. The use of blended literacy can help to reduce number of staff and pupil classroom contact time, and accordingly save staffing costs. Blended literacy also promotes pupil interest, comprehensions and satisfaction in the literacy terrain. It enables scholars to be more motivated and more involved in the literacy process, thereby enhancing their commitment and perseverance. Dziuban, Hartman, Juge, Moskal, Sorg (2006) reported that scholars satisfaction is advanced with blended literacy courses compared with purely face- to- face courses. In addition, Azizan (2010) envisaged that blended learning in Higher Educational Institution

- Offer an efficient and effective approach
- Provide more choice of learning to learners
- Increase learning resources
- Encourage independence and conviviality.

Challenges of Blended Learning in Higher Education

- Despite the opportunities delivered by blended literacy, the scholars, preceptors and institutions face some challenges with its perpetration. These include the following:
- Studies have shown that scholars enrolled in blended courses can occasionally have unrealistic expectations. The scholars in blended literacy programmes assumed that smaller classes meant minimum work, sufficient time, management skills were sufficient , and they endured problems with accepting responsibility for particular literacy(Vaughan, 2007)
- Scholars in similar courses have also reported feeling insulated due to the reduced openings for social commerce in a face- to- face classroom situation.
- Having difficulty with further sophisticated technologies is another challenge when enforcing blended literacy. For illustration, scholars may have to calculate on slow (e.g., dialup) Internet connections. Poor Internet connectivity has been reported to inhibit scholars' capability to engage in online conversations, which could lead to considerable frustration and have a negative impact on literacy.
- The challenge for perpetration of blended literacy in advanced institutions is time commitment. Johnson (2002) estimates that planning and developing a blended literacy course for maximum numbers generally takes two to three times the quantum of time needed to develop a analogous course in a traditional format.
- Finances are inadequate for the development of a **Learning Management System** (LMS), which is needed to enhance blended literacy in advanced.
- Specialized support for course design may be lacking. This results from inadequate interrelation between the ICT experts and faculty members offering blended literacy courses. In order to ensure a successful blended literacy experience for scholars; there should be university support for course

redesign, which may involve deciding what course objects can best be achieved through online literacy conditioning, what parts of the course can best be fulfilled in the classroom, and how to integrate these two learning surroundings.

Proposed Blended Learning Model for Higher Education

Khan, as cited in Singh (2003), proposed a blended literacy model. The frame has eight confines institutional, pedagogical, technological, interface design, evaluation, management, resource support, and ethical. Each dimension in the frame represents a order of issues that need to be addressed. These issues help to organize thinking, and ensure that the performing literacy program creates a meaningful literacy experience.

- **Pedagogical** - This dimension is concerned with the combination and selection of the literacy contents to be delivered online and to be delivered offline (face- to- face). It also analyzes the learners' learning style, ideal of the contents, and evaluates scholars learning.
- **Technological** - This dimension examines the availability and usability of the LMS to enable the synchronicity of blended literacy. The technological element also requires the services of specialized experts to support the operation.
- **Management** - This element deals with issues related to quality control, availability of specialized experts, elevation of architectures for multiple deliveries and enhancement.
- **Interface design** - This addresses issues related to the learner interface of each element in the blended literacy.
- **Evaluation** - This assesses the capability and effectiveness of the blended literacy situation and examines the functionality and advancements of a specific LMS.
- **Resource support** - This deals with making different type of interactive materials (online and offline) available for learners.
- **Ethical** - The ethical dimension identifies the ethical issues that need to be addressed when developing a blended literacy program, for illustration, equal occasion, artistic, diversity, and nation.

Conclusion

The emergence of computer and technologies has made tutoring and literacy of mathematics a dynamic process. Blended literacy courses are being offered at different advanced institutions through the use of LMS. This study has outlined the conception of the blended literacy approach from the perspective of mathematics in Advanced Education. Also, the different blended literacy tools that can enhance tutoring and literacy in mathematics education are discussed. The benefits of blended literacy as well as challenges during perpetration are also discussed. This study proposes a blended literacy model that can foster stylish practices in blended literacy (i.e., Khan's octagonal model). The study can be considered as a visionary prospect for advanced institutions aiming to borrow a blended literacy approach, in order to harness the different literacy openings that technology can give. It may also enable faculty members to elect a suitable blended literacy situation for tutoring and literacy program in Mathematics.

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SUGGESTED MODELS APPROACHES IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The current educational climate is essentially driven by an overriding interest in preparing students to become effective teachers. Therefore, some teacher education programmes have been developed in order to enhance this process. These programmes explore the possible approaches which could encourage student-teachers or teachers-in-service towards learning-focused teaching activities. Although teacher education programmes have been in existence for a long time, ESL teacher education is a relatively recent development. Numerous educational theorists and practitioners have handed down different opinions on the possible models for teacher education from their personal point of views. However, most of the researchers shared three common views. Subsequently these three concepts attained worldwide critical acclamation as teaching models. The latest models of teacher education have been put forward by, Michael J. Wallace in 1991. Wallace moulded his models after the existing concepts of his precursors, but in a more convenient or transparent way.

Introduction

Initial teacher education programs across the world bear many resemblances to one another in respect to their overall design features. Students generally follow courses that teach them foundational knowledge pertaining to education, like psychology or sociology, disciplinary knowledge in particular subject areas, and general and specific pedagogical knowledge. In addition, students are exposed to varying degrees of school placements. Despite these similarities in overall structure, the curriculum content and activities of teacher preparation may vary considerably, dependent on the underpinning conceptions of the goals and purposes of the program. Historical and geographical contexts also influence the choice of particular goals for teacher education.

The Applied Science Model

The Applied Science Model is the traditional and perhaps still the most prevalent model underlying most ESL teacher education programmes. It was put forward by Michael J. Wallace in 1991 based on the Technical Rationality of Donald A. Schön. The model derives its authority from the achievements of empirical science, particularly in the 19th and the 20th centuries. The Applied Science Model emerges on the following assumptions:

- Teaching is a science and as such can be examined rationally and objectively.
- Teachers learn to be teachers by being taught research-based theories.

These theories are being conveyed to the students only by those who are considered to be the experts in the particular field. Teachers are said to be educated when they become proficient enough to apply these theories in practice.

The Craft Model

The Craft Model is the oldest form of professional education and is still used today in ESL teacher education, albeit rather limitedly. Its conceptual basis, however, is widely utilized in practicum courses in which students work with classroom teachers, often called cooperating teachers. Its use in one course in a programme of ESL teacher education cannot be regarded as a model for an entire programme. The basic assumptions underlying this model are as follows:

- In its most basic form, Craft Model consists of the trainee or beginner working closely with the expert teacher.
- The practitioner is supposed to learn by imitating all the teaching techniques used by the experienced teacher.
- Knowledge is acquired as a result of observation, instruction, and practice.

The Reflective Model

The reflective practice has become a dominant paradigm in language teacher education research and programmes worldwide. But it is not an innovation in teaching. It has its roots in the work of a number of educational theorists and practitioners. Most definitions on reflective thinking found in the literature of teacher education are based on Dewey's inquiry oriented concepts. In the 1980s, Dewey's foundational aspects on reflection were further extended by the American sociologist Donald A. Schön. Later on, in 1991 Michael J. Wallace described Schön's critique in a more explicit way. The Reflective Model is based on the assumption that teachers develop professional competence through reflecting on their own practice. In other words, a teaching experience is recalled and considered to reach an evaluation and to provide input into future planning and action. For Wallace a teacher education course should include two kinds of knowledge for it to be professionally structured:

- **Received knowledge** - It is related to all the theories, concepts and skills that are studied during the student-teacher's ELT methodology lessons. **Experiential knowledge:** It is that knowledge which is developed by the trainees throughout their teaching practice. Wallace's Reflective Model is applicable to both pre-service and in-service education. The model is separated it into three stages:
- **The pre-training** - It is believed that the person who has decided to embark on professional education does not enter the programme with blank mind. He has, at least, some pre-training knowledge about teaching.
- **The professional development** - It is the stage of professional education or development through theory and practice.
- **The professional competence** - The ultimate goal of this model is to increase professional competence. Wallace presents the Reflective Model as a cyclical process in which the trainees are involved throughout their teaching experience. Such a cycle aims for continuous improvement and the development of personal theories of action. There is an assumption that the student-teachers already have some knowledge that they acquired as students and during the development of their English programme. Once the student-teachers have the opportunity to enter the classroom environment, they discover the actual framework of teaching and become aware of the different classroom situations. Thus, they start recalling about their performance during the teaching practice, how some experienced teachers deal with those situations, and also, how they themselves could manage them. So, they make some decisions and think about possible actions they could apply to their context. Or sometimes they simply reflect upon their classroom activities to evaluate their professional performance. Such a study helps them to figure out both the positive as well as the negative side of their teaching strategy. That means reflection helps them to avoid various future professional dilemmas by recalling and evaluating past experiences. The following illustration is a graphical representation of Wallace's Reflective Model of professional education or development.

Conclusion

Reflective teaching is very much beneficial for teacher development. It offers more advantages than disadvantages. Reflective practice helps the novice teachers become more aware of decision-making processes to help them determine the effect their decisions have in the context in which they are implemented. Reflective Model is broad in scope since it enables teachers to investigate, and clarify their own classroom processes, and their individual theories of teaching and learning, instead of relying on some specific method of teaching. The Reflective Model is a process oriented teaching approach since it provides an opportunity for the teacher to reveal his creative sides. Reflective practice provides an opportunity for the teacher to find a self-defined solution for a particular classroom problem. With a sharp contrast to the other models of teacher education, the Reflective Model does not treat the student-teacher as a passive participant. Here he works with his educator as a co-participant. This is the only model that fulfills almost all the requirements for teacher development.

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QUALITY MAINTENANCE IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Learning, the Treasure Within, the report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty- first Century, is the result of a three year worldwide process of consultation and analysis carried out by a distinguished panel of specialists under the chairmanship of Mr. Jacques Delors, former President of the European Commission. It is a thought provoking one that proposes ideas that go far beyond mere educational reform. It examines the place and functions of education in relation to individual achievement and social development in a changing world. Education is one of the principal means available to foster a deeper and more harmonious form of human development and thereby to reduce poverty, exclusion, ignorance, oppression and war. The coming century, dominated by globalization, also means that education will have to adapt itself to considerable economic, social and cultural changes resulting in inevitable tensions between tradition and modernity, competition and equality of opportunity, spiritual aspirations and material reality, local interests and global considerations, the unlimited expansion of knowledge and the limited capacity of human beings to assimilate it. In this context, learning throughout life will a key role in meeting the challenges of the next century.

Introduction

The central role of teachers and the need to improve their training, status and conditions of work is particularly stressed. In a world increasingly dominated by technology, emphasis is placed on the use of technology in the service of education and adequate training for later use at work and in daily life. Innovative guidelines are set out for educational renewal, based on strategies of education reforms which take into account a broad-based dialogue, and by increasing responsibility and involvement of stakeholders at every level. The report closes with a strong plea for more resources to be devoted to education, both nationally and internationally, and for strengthening international co-operation in education, with UNESCO as a key player. The pointers identified and recommendations made in the "Learning The Treasure Within" by the International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first century are explained here under

From the Local Community to a World Society

Worldwide interdependence and globalization are major forces in contemporary life. They are already at work and will leave a deep imprint on the twenty-first century. They require that overall consideration, extending well beyond the fields of education and culture, be given, as of now, to the roles and structures of international organizations. The major danger is that of a gulf opening up between a minority of people who are capable of finding their way successfully about this new world that is coming into being and the majority who feel that they are at the mercy of events and have no say in the future of society, with the dangers that entails of a setback to democracy and widespread revolt.

From Social Cohesion to Democratic Participation

Education policy must be sufficiently diversified and must be so designed as not to become another contributory cause of social exclusion. The socialization of individuals must not conflict with personal development. It is therefore necessary to work towards a system that strives to combine the virtues integration with respect for individual rights. Education cannot, on its own, solve the problem raised by the

severance (when this happens) of social ties. It can, however, be expected to help to foster the desire to live together, which is a basic component of social cohesion and national identity. Schools cannot succeed in this task unless they make their own contribution to the advancement and integration of minority groups by mobilizing those concerned while showing due regard for their personality. Democracy appears to be progressing, taking forms and passing through stages that fit the situation in each country. Its vitality is nevertheless constantly threatened. Education for conscious and active citizenship must begin at school.

From Economic Growth to Human Development

Further reflection on the theme of a new model of development, showing more respect for nature and the structuring of people's time. A future oriented study of the place of work in society, taking into account the effects of technical progress and change on both private and community life. A fuller assessment of development, taking all its aspects into account, along the lines of the work done by UNDP. The establishment of new links between educational policy and development policy, with a view to strengthening the bases of knowledge and skills in the countries concerned. Encouragement of initiative, teamwork, realistic synergies taking local resources into account. Self - employment and the spirit of enterprise.

The Four Pillars of Education

Education throughout life is based on four pillars: learning to know, learning to do, learning to live together and learning to be. Learning to Know, by combining a sufficiently broad general knowledge with the opportunity to work in depth on a small number of subjects. This also means learning to learn, so as to benefit from the opportunities education provides throughout life. Learning to do, in order to acquire not only an occupational skill but also, more broadly, the competence to deal with many situations and work in teams. It also means learning to do in the context of young people's various social and work experiences which may be informal, as a result of the local or national context or formal, involving courses, alternating study and work. Learning to live together, by developing an understanding of other people and an appreciation of interdependence - carrying out joint projects and learning to manage conflicts in a spirit of respect for the values of pluralism, mutual understanding and peace. Learning to be, so as better to develop one's personality and be able to act with every greater autonomy, judgement and personal responsibility. In that connection, education must not disregard any aspect of a person's potential: memory, reasoning, aesthetic sense, physical capacities and communication skills. Formal education systems tend to emphasize the acquisition of knowledge to the detriment of other types of learning but it is vital now to conceive education in a more encompassing fashion. Such a vision should inform and guide future educational reforms and policy, in relation both to contents and to methods.

Learning through Life

The concept of learning through life is the key that gives access to the twenty-first century. It goes beyond the traditional distinction between initial and continuing education. It links up with another concept often put forward, that of the learning society, in which everything affords an opportunity of learning and fulfilling one's potential. In its new guise, continuing education is seen as going far beyond what is already practised, particularly in the developed countries, i.e. upgrading, with refresher training, retraining and conversion or promotion courses for adults. It should open up opportunities for learning for all, for many different purposes offering them a second or third chance, satisfying their desire for knowledge and beauty or their desire to surpass themselves, or making it possible to broaden and deepen strictly vocational forms of training, including practical training.

From Basic Education to University

A requirement valid for all countries, albeit in various forms and with different types of content: the strengthening of basic education: hence the emphasis on primary education and its traditional basic programmes: reading, writing, arithmetic but also on the ability to express oneself in a language that lends itself to dialogue and understanding. The need, which will be still greater tomorrow, for receptivity to science and the world of science, which opens the door to the twenty-first century and its scientific and technological upheavals. The adaptation of basic education to specific contexts, the most deprived countries as well as the most deprived section of the population, starting out with the facts of everyday life, which affords opportunities for understanding natural phenomena and for different forms of socialization. The

pressing needs of literacy work and basic education for adults are to be kept in mind. In all cases, emphasis is to be placed on pupil-teacher relations, since the most advanced technologies can be no more than a back up to the relationship (transmission, dialogue and confrontation) between teacher and pupil. Secondary education must be rethought in this general context of learning throughout life. The key principle is to arrange for a variety of individual paths through schooling, without ever closing the door on the possibility of a subsequent return to the education system. Debates on selection and guidance would be greatly clarified if this principle were fully applied. Everyone would then feel that whatever the choices made or the courses followed in adolescence, no doors would ever be closed in the future, including the doors of the school itself. Equality of opportunity would then mean what it says.

Conclusion

While the psychological and material situation of teachers differs greatly from country to country, an upgrading of their status is essential if 'learning throughout life' is to fulfil the central function assigned to it by the Commission in the advancement of our societies and the strengthening of mutual understanding among peoples. Their position as master or mistress in the classroom should be recognized by society and they should be given the necessary authority and suitable resources.

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IMPORTANCE OF QUALITY IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education is a powerful weapon for changing lives and shaping the future. Good quality education is an essential tool for gaining the best knowledge and develop modernization in society. The outcomes of learning for individuals may vary based on different contexts but at the completion of the elementary education cycle, every person should imbibe basic life skills, scientific knowledge, and beginning levels of numeracy and literacy. These two words, “quality” and “education” are commonly and carelessly used in every day discussion – especially among leaders and business men and women. Every leader promises to provide the populace with quality education. Many of such promises have come and gone without any remarkable impact on the quality of education provided to the populace. It is on records that many leaders, institutions, organizations and individuals have in various ways spent large amount of their resources to ensure that the objective of providing quality education is achieved. In most cases, the situation remains the same if not worsened.

The big question one may ask here is, do such leaders or institutions or bodies understand what constitutes quality education? This is because a woman who doesn't know the ingredients that make soup tasty may be given a huge amount of money – yet the husband may be tempted to sack her because of the nature of the soup she prepared. It is therefore necessary that the two key words, “quality” and “education” be defined. Quality as contained in Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (2010), means the standard of something when it is compared to other things like it; how good or bad something is. Quality is used on every commodity e.g quality shoes, shirts, cars, etc. When a woman selling banana in the market sees a potential customer approaching her shed, she will not waste time to make use of “quality” to draw the man nearer for the purchase of her banana. Thus she will say “buy high quality banana”. This means that any commodity can either be of a high quality or low quality. Equally we have low quality and high quality education.

Introduction

Having seen what quality stands for, let us now briefly define education before marrying the two words – for a better understanding of the concept —Quality education Today, education has become one of

the greatest enterprises and has been defined in different ways by different people in different parts of the world and occupations. A renowned scholar, R.S. Peter's defined education as the transmission of what is worthwhile to those who are committed to it – be they children or adults. Another educator and philosopher, Brameld saw education as —the greatest power man has not yet subdued. Okpala in his lecture stressed that education is a process of tendering, nurturing and nursing the individual so as to make him a full fledged member of the society to which he belongs. Generally, education can be regarded as an activity which goes on in a society and its aims and methods depend on the nature of the society in which it operates; so, education is sensitive to time, place and circumstances. This is because it is constantly changing, adapting itself to new demands.

Understanding Quality Education

Education International (EI), a Belgium-based organization, defines quality education as one that focuses on the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development of each student regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, or geographic location. It prepares the child for life and not just for testing. In 2012, the United Nations for the first time included Quality Education in their Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). Further, education in modern times is highly influenced and dependent on Information and Communication Technology which has paved the way for students to attain school or higher level education. Quality education not only prepares a student for a job but also develops the overall personality of an individual. In the case of children, it aims at their complete upbringing where morals and ethics are taught as part of the curriculum to help them live a healthy lifestyle.

Teacher quality

The framework for this study includes five broad categories of measurable and policy relevant indicators to organize the teacher characteristics assumed to reflect teacher quality. It is notable that findings for these characteristics frequently differ for teachers at the elementary school level and teachers at the high school level and that the body of research on the subject of teacher quality suggests that the context of teaching matters (e.g., differences in grade levels, subject areas, and student populations). A refined understanding of how teacher attributes affect their performance across these different teaching contexts can be helpful in determining the range of potentially effective policy options.

The highlights of the empirical evidence include

- **Teacher experience** - Several studies have found a positive of experience on teacher effectiveness; specifically, the —learning by doing effect is most obvious in the early years of teaching.
- **Teacher preparation programs and degrees** - Research suggests that the selectivity/prestige of the institution a teacher attended has a positive effect on student achievement, particularly at the secondary level. This may partially be a reflection of the cognitive ability of the teacher. Evidence suggests that teachers who have earned advanced degrees have a positive impact on high school mathematics and science achievement when the degrees earned were in these subjects. Evidence regarding the impact of advanced degrees at the elementary level is mixed.
- **Teacher certification** - Research has demonstrated a positive effect of certified teachers on high school mathematics.

Achievement when the certification is in mathematics

Studies show little clear impact of emergency or alternative-route certification on student performance in either mathematics or science, as compared to teachers who acquire standard certification.

Teacher coursework

Teacher coursework in both the subject area taught and pedagogy contributes to positive education outcomes. Pedagogical coursework seems to contribute to teacher effectiveness at all grade levels, particularly when coupled with content knowledge. The importance of content coursework is most pronounced at the high school level. While the studies on the field experience component of teacher education are not designed to reveal causal relationships, they suggest positive effects in terms of opportunity to learn the profession and reduced anxiety among new teachers.

Teachers' own test scores

Tests that assess the literacy levels or verbal abilities of teachers have been shown to be associated with higher levels of student achievement. Studies show the National Teachers Examination and other state-mandated tests of basic skills and/or teaching abilities are less consistent predictors of teacher performance. Given that many dimensions of teacher characteristics matter—preparation in both pedagogic and subject content, credentials, experience, and test scores—the findings from the literature imply that there is no merit in large-scale elimination of all credentialing requirements. Nor are improvements in teacher quality likely to be realized through the status quo. Rather, teacher policies need to reflect the reality that teaching is a complex activity that is influenced by the many elements of teacher quality. Most of the research does not seek to capture interactions among the multiple dimensions of teacher quality, and as a result, there are major gaps in the research that still need to be explored. Nor does the research fully address evidence about teacher quality at the elementary and middle school levels, in subjects other than mathematics, or among different populations of students (such as high poverty, English language learners, or special education).

Quality Teachers

In opposition to those who propose to eliminate all requirements for entering the teaching profession, this analysis supports a judicious use of the research evidence on teacher characteristics and teacher effectiveness. The evidence indicates that neither an extreme centralized bureaucratization nor a complete deregulation of teacher requirements is a wise approach for improving teacher quality. What holds a great deal more promise is refining the policies and practices employed to build a qualified body of teachers in elementary schools, middle schools, and high schools; for disadvantaged, special needs, and advantaged students; and for math, science, languages, English, social studies, and the arts.

Conclusion

Education policy makers and administrators would be well served by recognizing the complexity of the issue and adopting multiple measures along many dimensions to support existing teachers and to attract and hire new, highly qualified teachers. The research suggests that investing in teachers can make a difference in student achievement. In order to implement needed policies associated with staffing every classroom—even the most challenging ones—with high-quality teachers, substantial and targeted investments must first be made in both teacher quality and education research.

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A STUDY ON AWARENESS OF BLENDED LEARNING AMONG B.ED STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract

The education system at present transferred from traditional method to digital method gradually. Education is the process of facilitating learning or acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and beliefs. Education is a deliberate, conscious and dynamic process that enables individuals to develop, adapt and adapt to the accelerating change. Information and Communication Technology is one of those factors that influence students to learn effectively. Blended learning is seen as an integration between face-to-face learning and online learning, with an emphasis on the use of internet-based technologies, such as an emphasis on the role of online activities to expand and develop face-to-face learning. If the student teachers are clearly understood the concepts, they can perform better in their teaching. Therefore, traditional learning is no longer used by the student teachers. The student teachers active participation in the teaching and learning process is the main goal of blended learning that provides the most efficient and effective

learning. The development of teaching competencies in this context requires exposure to face-to-face activities. To the one-on-one approach to online education. Acquire information processing skills. Collaboration is more important than ever. However, despite widespread interest in the technology, little Attention has been given to developing new methods to improve participation in student teachers education programs for Teachers and teachers of the future. The researcher used a normative survey method. The sample consisted of 100 B.Ed Student teachers. The sample was stratified based on gender, subject, and Location and internet users. Therefore, researchers try to study the awareness of blended learning among B.Ed student teachers. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be statistically significant in their awareness of blended learning.

Keywords: *Blended learning, information and communication technology (ICT)*

Introduction

Education is a powerful weapon to change the world. Education is the process of facilitating learning or acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and beliefs. Education is a deliberate, conscious and dynamic process that enables individuals to develop, adapt and adapt to the accelerating change. Information and Communication Technology is one of those factors that influence students to learn effectively. The National Education Policy (1986) focused particularly on the use of computers, which are part of "educational technology", to improve the quality of education. The rapid development of information and communication technology (ICT) gives different perspectives on the learning process. The application of ICT in learning may change the teacher model of learning from teacher-centered to student-centered learning. The use of technology in education has an important role and should be applied in the learning system. Technology integration with teaching plays a major role in transforming the educational system from teacher centered to a rich, interactive environment centered on the student. Incorporating technology into the traditional classroom improves students' active participation in the teaching and learning environment. Blended learning is any instruction that combines classroom learning with online learning (Friesen, 2012; Tucker, 2013). Graham (2006) describes blended learning as a model "that combines realistic and interface instruction with computer-based instructions." Blended learning is seen as integration between face-to-face learning and online learning, with an emphasis on the use of internet-based technologies, such as an emphasis on the role of online activities to expand and develop face-to-face learning. Blended learning describes learning activities that involve a systematic combination of interaction in a shared present and technology-mediated interaction between students, teachers, and learning resources. Blended learning was seen as an important alternative approach to overcome the different limitations of both face-to-face and online learning, because the blended learning approach embraces the advantages of both types of learning. In addition, blended learning is more effective than face-to-face or online learning in terms of student satisfaction and faculty responses, flexibility of time and space, ease of use of resources, increased interactions, and effectiveness of peer-teacher interaction. . In this era of technological advancements, blended learning is an essential component of education. Awareness of blended learning is an important factor for upper secondary teachers. It represents a lot of innovation and educational flow in the classroom. Therefore, the researcher made an attempt to study awareness about blended learning for upper secondary teachers.

Need for the Study

The traditional or traditional learning is no longer used by the teacher. Educators are asked to use a variety of methods that provide more opportunities for learning through the use of different resources. Blended learning plays an important role in enhancing the teaching and learning process and making the learning sessions interactive, stimulating and engaging. Blended learning is important because it breaks down the traditional walls of teaching and also provides flexible timeframes that can be customized for each person, giving them the ability to learn at their own pace. Thus, integrating traditional learning with blended learning is an urgent requirement to realize the learning process returns. The student's teachers active participation in the teaching and learning process is the main goal of blended learning that provides the most efficient and effective learning. So the investigator decided to undergo the current investigation in a necessary manner. Therefore, the proposed study was considered a required one.

Objective of the study

- To find out the significant difference between Male and female B.Ed student teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.
- To find out the significant difference between Rural and urban area of B.Ed student teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.
- To find out the significant difference between Arts and Science subject B.Ed student teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.
- To find out the significant difference between Internet users and non users B.Ed student Teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.

Hypotheses of the study

- There is no significant difference between Male and female B.Ed student teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.
- There is no significant difference between Rural and urban area of B.Ed student Teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.
- There is no significant difference between Arts and Science subject teaching B.Ed student teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.
- There is no significant difference between Internet users and non users of B.Ed student teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning.

Methods of the Study

The investigator has administered normative survey methods used in this study.

Tools Used

Blended learning Awareness Questionnaire was constructed and standardized by investigator. This Questionnaire consists of 20 items.

Sample of the Study

In this study, a sample of 100 B.Ed student teachers working in different pedagogy subjects was taken. A simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample. Samples were collected from Government College of Education, Komarapalayam, Namakkal district.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques have been used in the present study for the analysis of collected data.

- Descriptive Analysis
- Differential Analysis

Table 1 - Significant difference between Male and female B.Ed Student Teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' test	Level of Significance
Male	40	16.52	4.32	0.62	NS
Female	60	18.25	4.28		

The mean score of male teachers 16.52 and mean scores of female student teachers 18.25. The calculated t value 0.42 is less than the table value at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between the male and female teachers, The mean value is high for female than male student teachers.

Table 2 - Significant difference between Rural and urban area B.Ed Student Teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning

Locality	N	Mean	SD	't' test	Level of Significance
Rural	70	22.02	4.17	0.84	NS
Urban	30	17.12	3.20		

The mean score of rural area teachers 22.02 and mean scores of urban area teachers 17.12. The calculated t value 0.84 is less than the table value at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between the rural and urban area student teachers, The mean value is high for rural than urban student teachers.

Table 3 - Significant difference between Arts and Science subject teaching B.Ed Student Teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning

Subject	N	Mean	SD	't' test	Level of Significance
Arts	20	16.12	2.56	2.86	S
Science	80	25.44	4.21		

The mean score of Arts subject student teachers 16.52 and mean scores of Science subject student teachers 25.44. The calculated t value 2.86 is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that there is significant difference between the arts and science subject student teachers, The mean value is high for science subject teachers than Arts subject student teachers.

Table 4 - There is no significant difference between Internet users and non users B.Ed Student Teachers in respect of their awareness of Blended learning

Internet	N	Mean	SD	't' test	Level of Significance
Internet uses	80	20.15	3.22	2.10	S
Non users	20	15.23	2.21		

The mean score of Internet uses teachers 20.15 and mean scores of non user's teachers 15.23. The calculated t value 2.10 is less than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level. Hence the hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that there is significant difference between the internet uses and non uses teachers, The mean value is high for internet using student teachers than non internet using student teachers.

Findings of the Study

- There is no significant difference between the male and female student teachers, The mean value is high for female (18.25) than male (16.52) student teachers .
- There is no significant difference between the rural and urban area of student teachers, The mean value is high for rural (22.02) than urban (17.12) student teachers
- There is significant difference between the arts and science subject of student teachers, The mean value is high for science subject (25.44) student teachers than Arts subject (16.12) student teachers
- There is significant difference between the internet uses and non uses student teachers, The mean value is high for internet uses(20.15) student teachers than non uses (15.23) student teachers .

Conclusion

The conclusion of this investigation revealed that the student teachers understanding ability and level of teaching have been enhanced by applying the specially designed blended learning techniques. The present day traditional method of teaching has failed to achieve the required outcomes. Hence, conclude that the blended learning strategies would help to learn the concept effectively and would their academic achievement and meaningful learning. Finally the researchers conclude that there was no significant difference between gender and location in respect of their awareness of Blended learning, but Internet users and subject of teaching showed a significant difference in the awareness of blended learning. Thus, the present study shows how blended learning strategies in the classroom redefine established teaching learning styles. Thus blended learning strategies among student teachers play a pivotal role in the acquisition of knowledge and competency.

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IMPACT OF TECHNO PEDAGOGY IN 21ST CENTURY – OVERVIEW OF TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Pedagogy is the art as well as science of teaching methods. Techno-Pedagogy is the art of incorporating technology in designing teaching learning experiences. Real knowledge of teaching has achieved by practice and experience in the classroom. It deals with beliefs, values and attitudes with people not statistics. The emergence of new technology has influenced every aspect of human life. Today a classroom without technology is inconceivable. Teachers play a vital role in realizing the educational goals of a dynamic society. Teachers make use of the ICT integrated Education in classrooms. Teachers of Higher education have to equip themselves with information and communication technology skills. Many of the teachers were not using Information and Communication Technology in classroom teaching. The main reason is unavailability of ICT resources in their institutions. Educational technology emphasizes the maximum use of available resources in the learning situations, which may benefit all the pupils of the nation from those limited resources which are available for teaching work pertaining to this. Techno-Pedagogy brings desired improvement in teaching-learning process by making it effective. It develops to the maximum the cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects of the pupil. For Higher education the teachers are personally using the Internet in their homes and they prepared theses information for teaching. This paper tries to explore the status in impact of Techno-Pedagogy in 21st century from Teacher Education.

Keywords : *Techno-Pedagogy, ICT, 21st Century, Teacher Education, Higher Education*

Introduction

The Education is mainly considered as a process of human development. All the educational institutions or schools and colleges have to focus to impart the knowledge to the students for their development. Education is a process by which a child makes his internal at external. The term education is also used for preparing teachers in teacher education. All the teachers training Institutions are known as college of Education or department of education. In these college of Education, theory and methodology of teaching are taught to the pupil teaching and teaching practice is organized to prepare effective teachers. Teaching is oriented for the desirable changes among learners. The use of ICT can improve the quality of the student learning experiences and make education and training opportunities available to a broader spectrum of the population in developing countries. At present educators are executed by the success of information technologies and want to implant them into instruction.

Techno Pedagogy

Technology's impact on the teaching and learning environment has changed not only the way our students process new concepts and achieve learning objectives, but it has also modified the way in which instruction is delivered. Students' needs are diverse, and the forms of technology that they encounter in their learning environment may not fit those needs of every student or subject (Halverson, 2003). The educational

technologies that a teacher may use in the teaching and learning environment may not adapt to every diverse need; rather, it is the job of the teacher to creatively apply these tools to meet the needs of the student.

Technological Knowledge

Technology is the use of scientific knowledge to meet the needs of daily life or the practical form of scientific technology. All the teachers are in need of technology knowledge. Technology knowledge means the knowledge about all the standard technologies from textbooks to recent technologies such as interactive white board, digital Video etc. Technological Knowledge (TK) is the Knowledge about certain methods for considering, and working with technological instruments and different resources of innovation.

Pedagogical Knowledge

Pedagogical knowledge is teacher's profound information that incorporates the systems, procedures, practices and standards of teaching learning, classroom administration and association in Education (Shulman, 1987). Pedagogical knowledge is a knowing aspect mainly related to cognitive domain. Pedagogical knowledge refers to the teachers repertoire of generic teaching techniques , like cooperative learning, role playing, or group work techniques that are equally relevant to all academic content domains. An educator with profound Pedagogical Knowledge sees how learners build learning and secure aptitudes in separated routes, and additionally how they create propensities for brain and demeanors toward learning.

Need and Importance of Techno Pedagogy

Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) is an understanding of how teaching and learning change when specific innovations are utilized. This incorporates knowing the instructive affordances and limitations of a scope of technological devices and assets. Technological Pedagogical Knowledge requires building an understanding of the potential advantages and confinements of specific advancements as they can be connected inside specific sort of learning exercises, and additionally in the teaching-learning settings inside which these technological bolstered exercises works best. An imperative part of Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK) is the creative adaptability with accessible instruments important in planning to utilize them for particular pedagogical purposes. This is the hybrid method of teaching in which ICT is being used for teaching learning situation. Literally Pedagogy refers to the art, science of teaching and techno refers to the art-skill in handcrafting. Here “techno” is a qualifier; it intersects or crosses the meaning of pedagogy with its own. Techno pedagogy refers to weaving the techniques of the craft of teaching into the learning environment itself.

Role of Techno- Pedagogy in Higher Education (TPK)

TPK is an understanding of how teaching and learning can change when particular technologies are used in particular ways. This includes knowing the pedagogical affordances and constraints of a range of technological tools as they relate to disciplinarily and developmentally appropriate pedagogical designs and strategies. To build TPK, a deeper understanding of the constraints and affordances of technologies and the disciplinary contexts within which they function is needed.

- Develop Teaching learning process
- Enhance linguistic abilities
- Improve to develop study materials
- Support Distance Education
- Stimulate self learning
- Development of life skills

Challenges of Using Techno – Pedagogy in Higher Education

Today we need the knowledge and use of advanced technology to assimilate this knowledge repository like security. We need to learn not only to acquire knowledge but also to learn the way of acquiring knowledge. Innovative way of Techno- Pedagogical skills among the Trainees can solve the problem of Higher Education. We will discuss the challenges required for Techno-Pedagogy. In teacher education programme Teacher Educators need to move from Pedagogies to Techno-Pedagogies. There

should be adequate integration of mini-teaching skills, media and techno pedagogic skills. Therefore there must be programmes to develop Information and communication technology literacy and techno-pedagogy competences of teacher educator and teachers. Software programs such as Microsoft office suite such as Ms-word, Ms-Excel, Ms-PowerPoint and Msn-Messenger are usually designed for business surroundings'. Web based technologies such as blogs or Pod case are created for the purpose of entertainment, Social network and Communication. Learning materials in different media forms such as Compact Disk, Video films should be available in all the libraries of educational institutions.

Conclusion

With the progression of technology it is very hard to teach learners according to their standards. The expert teacher brings diverse experiences and frames to the classroom. In this 21st century the teacher who uses technology in teaching learning process plays a vital role. Technology enhances the learning and makes the teaching process as more effective. So the techno pedagogical skill of the teachers has to be increased and also should bring positive posture towards techno pedagogy.

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION

P.YUGASINI

Introduction

Blended learning, also known as technology-mediated instruction, web-enhanced instruction, or mixed-mode instruction, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. The world is changing constantly and the various domains are also influenced by the change. There is no exemption even in the education domain. The evolution of the digital learning platforms has a huge impact in educational institutions and has eventually put the traditional methods in the back seat. However, there are demands for both technology and traditional learning methods. As a result of this, the art of combining digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face to face teaching gave birth to the term “Blended Learning”. This chapter deals about the educational transformations and the prerequisite for Blended Learning. BL is not a mere mix of online and face-to-face mode, but it refers to a well-planned combination of meaningful activities in both the modes. The blend demands consideration of several factors, mainly focussing on learning outcomes and the learnercentred instructional environment. Given the emergence of digital technologies and the emerging importance of leveraging technology for teaching-learning at all levels from school to higher education, the NEP 2020 recommends for use of blended models of learning. The NEP-2020 states that while promoting digital learning and education, the importance of face-to-face in-person learning is fully recognized. Accordingly, different effective models of blended learning will be identified for appropriate replication for different subjects.

The important features of Blended Learning environment are:

- Increased student engagement in learning.
- Enhanced teacher and student interaction.
- Responsibility for learning.
- Time management and flexibility
- Improved student learning outcomes
- Enhanced institutional reputation.
- More flexible teaching and learning environment
- More amenable for self and continuous learning
- Better opportunities for experiential learning

Characteristics of Blended Learning

People with experience in the educational industry sometimes have to choose between online and traditional education. Somehow, blended learning links these two and offered a mixed type of education. As an education provider, you may create your website and use it to share your knowledge. This is a great idea also for implementing blended learning. Let's discuss some of its most important characteristic features of it.

The blended learning program is

- **Partly Online** - As we have already understood, some blended learning is done online. Students don't have to visit schools or educational centers daily (depending on the learning model). As a teacher, you may send some courses and tasks through your platform, and they complete them online.
- **Partly Away** - Students sometimes visit different places such as libraries, special educational centers, schools, and even camps to complete some stages of the learning process.
- **Through Learning Path** - The personalized learning path helps students to learn through different interactive activities, discussions, courses, games, etc.

Advantages of Blended Learning

- **Flexibility** - The teachers can choose any task to assign, whether synchronous or asynchronous teaching, etc. On the other hand, the learners are free to choose the time and the way they prefer to learn. Such an approach motivates the students and evokes their interest in learning more.
- **Effectiveness** - According to research, blended learning examples provide better effectiveness and productivity. Having the freedom to choose and follow their preferences, students learn more and give better results. Additionally, the online platforms increase student engagement through live chats, emails, and similar discussions. In this way, students get used to collaborative learning.
- **Personalization** - In blended learning, instructors better understand the student's progress, thanks to online learning tools. Accordingly, it becomes easier and faster to shape an opinion about the student and provide methods that better meet their needs and interests.
- **Increasing Reach** - Traditional face-to-face classes follow some limitations related to time, distance, etc. Blended learning, on the other hand, doesn't face such distinctions. The audience is increased thanks to the technologies and the possibility of remote knowledge. This allows the instructors to increase their Reach and work with more potential students.
- **Cost-effectiveness** - One of the most significant advantages of blended learning is that most of the costs faced by educational institutions are reduced. Transportation fees up to an event ticket or printed material require a significant amount of money that is missing in the case of blended learning.

Disadvantages of Blended Learning

- **Infrastructure** - There are at least two angles to this problem. The first is building the essential infrastructure within an educational institution or particular class. Does the facility have the required IT workforce? Can it allocate the right budget, or does it, in fact, reveal any willingness to shell out on an experimental case? Acquiring software technology and hardware for your blended learning program can be costly. Even more so if you are dealing with a large campus or multiple branches. However, there is a long-term silver lining to it. By investing into the right tech set today, you are probably saving loads of cash that would otherwise be spent on supporting an obsolete brick-and-mortar framework.
- **Mentality** - The tech resources employed in blended learning need to be reliable, easy to use, and unanimously accepted by all stakeholders of the learning process. Otherwise, the initiative will most

likely be gathering dust until some remote milestone is reached. The other issue is IT literacy, which may be a significant barrier for teachers rather than students. The availability of solid tech support and trainers is an absolute must. It's also important to nurture a blended learning community to evangelize the value of training technology. Any hiccups and lack of organization may bring along the looming danger of failure. Old school supporters always have an ace up their sleeve: a long track record and verified methodology. Innovators really have to go the extra mile to convince the hesitant and reveal the benefits rather than disadvantages of blended learning models.

- **Pace of advancement** - What primarily looks like an upside turns into a downside when you come to review specific learning scenarios.
- **Overwork** - It's hard to disagree that there's a significant amount of extra teacher's work involved in the primary stages. Managing a blended learning experience can certainly be time-consuming. The paradigm shift is not exactly a trifle. A teacher adopting blended learning has to pick the right syllabus, the right ratio between face-to-face learning and online learning, and to the best of my knowledge, there's no universal recipe to it. The Web Quest model might be worth checking out, as a sample of successful 'hybridization'. Also, technical training is key. The broader your horizons, the easier to find a best-fitting solution to make a blended learning program work.
- **Cognitive load** - The first thing that comes to mind when you think of the disadvantages of blended learning is the cognitive load. **New to the blended learning model, some teachers may start over delivering content and educational activities.** The new blended learning program may become a friend if tailored to individual student needs, and a foe if applied in bulk, as is usually the case with traditional classroom.

Blended Learning Structures in Education

Many factors must be considered when choosing how to blend in-person and online teaching and learning activities. In some cases, most interactions between students and the teacher, as well as the direct delivery of instruction, take place in person in the classroom, while materials and possibly some additional activities are delivered online. In other cases, most of the class activities occur online, with infrequent meetings in person to solve problems and support community building. In some blended arrangements, students may choose which activities to complete online and which to complete in a classroom. Ideally, blends are personalised so individual students have the blend that best fits their age, life circumstances and learning needs. These are called à la carte models. Students choose what to take fully online, what to take fully in person and, when the design is available, blended courses where they choose when to go to inperson classes and when to watch videos, download readings and complete assignments online. This kind of personalisation is not always available. Most important is ensuring that students are able to function well as learners with any delivery method, single-mode or blended, even if it is not their preference or the best situation for them. Teachers are valuable coaches for helping students manage in any learning situation; it is up to teachers and learning designers to offer blended activities that best suit the subject, the learners' needs and the curriculum requirements. Not all unique and interesting BL designs are one-size-fits-all model. Below are seven sample configurations of BL activities to consider for BL teaching situation. These examples of BL are drawn from higher education but can be shaped to fit any teaching and learning situation.

- **Blended face-to-face class** - Also sometimes called the "face-to-face driver model," the blended face-to-face class model is based in the classroom, although a significant amount of classroom time has been replaced by online activities. Seat time is required for this model, while online activities are used to supplement the in-person classes; readings, quizzes or other assessments are done online at home. This model allows students and faculty to share more high-value instructional time because class time is used for higher-order learning activities such as discussions and group projects.
- **Blended online class** - Sometimes referred to as the "online driver model," this class is the inverse of the blended face-to-face class. The class is mostly conducted online, but there are some required in-person activities such as lectures or labs.
- **The flipped classroom** - The flipped classroom reverses the traditional class structure of listening to a lecture in class and completing homework activities at home. Students in flipped classes watch a short lecture video online and come into the classroom to complete activities such as group work, projects or other exercises. The flipped classroom model can be seen as a sub-model of the blended face-to-face or blended online class.

- **The rotation model** - In this model, students in a course rotate between various modalities, one of which is online learning. There are various sub-models: station rotation, lab rotation and individual rotation. Some of these sub-models are better suited to K–12 education; station rotation, for example, requires students to rotate between stations in the classroom at an instructor’s discretion. Others work well on a college campus; the lab rotation model, for example, requires students in a course to rotate among locations on campus. In the individual rotation model, a student rotates through learning modalities on a customized schedule.
- **The self-blend model** - While many of the BL models on this list are at the course level, self-blending is a programme-level model and is familiar to many college students. Learners using this model are enrolled in a school but take online courses in addition to their traditional face-to-face courses. They are not directed by a faculty member and choose which courses they will take online and which they will take in person.
- **The blended MOOC** - The blended MOOC is a form of flipped classroom using in-person class meetings to supplement a massive open online course. Students access MOOC materials - perhaps from another institution or instructor if the course is openly accessible - outside of class and then come to a class meeting for discussions or in-class activities. In 2012, San Jose State University piloted a blended MOOC using MIT’s Circuits and Electronics course, with students taking the MOOC out of class while face-to-face time was used for additional problem solving.
- **Flexible-mode courses** - Flexible-mode courses offer all instruction in multiple modes - in person and online and students choose how to take their course. An example of this is San Francisco State University’s hybrid flexible (HyFlex) model, which offers classroom-based and online options for all or most learning activities, allowing students the ability to choose how they will attend classes: online or in person.

Conclusion

Blended learning is a learning process that combines face-to-face learning with online learning to produce valid, effective and efficient learning. Blended learning, one of the teaching model, mixed traditional methods of teaching with an online courses for achieving specific learning goals.

PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY AND META COGNITIVE AWARENESS

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Abstract

Academic self-efficacy is receiving increasing recognition as a predictor of educational performances. Academic self-efficacy describes "a person's confidence in their abilities to organize, execute and regulate performance to attain designated types of performances". It functions at a multilevel and multifaceted set of beliefs that influence how people feel, think, motivate themselves, and behave during various educational tasks. Self-Efficacy view point can be built up on four bases of knowledge, vicarious experiences, enactive mastery as well as physical and emotional states. Self-efficacy development is closely intertwined with a person's experiences, competencies and developmental tasks in different domains at different stages in life. Self-efficacy beliefs should be relevant for understanding educational outcomes because self- efficacy leads to specific behaviours and motivations that can encourage or discourage effective performance.

Keywords : *Academic Self-Efficacy, Educational Performances*

Introduction

This paper proposes, on the basis of a reflection made in relation to the new educational demands of

the current era, a number of strategies with the aim of enhancing the quality of the learning situation and ultimately the level of educational performances of the learners. Researchers in personality and social psychology have long been interested in the role of self related perceptions. Individuals who are otherwise similar feel differently about themselves and choose different courses of action, depending on how they interpret themselves- what attributes they think, they possess, what roles they presume they are expected to play, what they believe they are capable of, how they view they fare in comparison with others and how they judge they are viewed by others without doubt, these are beliefs and perceptions about self that are heavily rooted in one's past achievement and reinforcement theory. It is only reasonable that these self-perceptions have received a great deal of attention in educational research (Byrne, 1984). Children with different self-beliefs demonstrate different levels of cognitive, social and emotional engagement in schools. Because school related experience makes up a major portion of children's lives and shapes the early path to important life outcomes, educational researches try to grasp the meaning of self in student's minds. During the past couple of decades, numerous studies in educational research have resorted to academic self-efficacy to explain the function of self in school contexts. Various definitions are given about academic self-efficacy and its dimensions but all of them included a general academic goal oriented attitude. Before discussing the concept of academic self-efficacy, let us know about self-efficacy.

Significance of Self-Efficacy

The term self-efficacy was coined around 40 years ago by Albert Bandura (1977a). Since then, research in this area has been growing steadily and focuses mainly on the concept of self-efficacy which is considered as “one of the most theoretically, heuristically and practically useful concepts formulated in modern psychology” (Betz et al., 1996, p. 47). Self-efficacy is not the same as ability or motivation, but they are strongly related (Kozlowski & Salas, 2010). Indeed, self-efficacy is the personal determination of one's own ability to deal with a certain task. Bandura's theory identifies four core features of human agency: intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness, and self-reflectiveness (Bandura, 2004). Social cognitive theory is rooted in a view that individuals are agents proactively engaged in their own development and can make things happen by their actions. In the social cognitive view people are neither driven by inner forces nor automatically shaped and controlled by external stimuli.

Rather, human functioning is explained in terms of a model of triadic reciprocity in which behavior, cognitive and other personal factors, and environmental events all operate as interacting determinants of each other. The construct of self-efficacy helps explain the finding that the behavior of individuals is not always accurately predicted from their capability to accomplish a specific task. How a person believes they will perform is often more important. One construct gaining increased credence as a determinant of student's goal orientation is academic self-efficacy (Skaalvik, 1997). It refers to student's judgments of how well he or she can do class-related works (Bandura, 1986). During the past two decades, self-efficacy has emerged as a highly effective predictor of students' motivation and learning. As a performance-based measure of perceived capability, self-efficacy differs conceptually and psychometrically from related motivational constructs, such as outcome expectations, self-concept, or locus of control. Self-efficacy beliefs have been found to be sensitive to subtle changes in students' performance context, to interact with self-regulated learning processes, and to mediate students' academic achievement. *“Academic self-efficacy refers to a person's conviction that they can successfully achieve a designated level in a specific academic subject area”.*

Need for Academic Self-Efficacy

In Education, self-efficacy is a key contributing factor to learners' success, because self-efficacy influences the choices learners make and the courses of action they pursue (Pajares, 2002). Academic self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief (conviction) that they can successfully achieve a designated level on an academic task or attain a specific academic goal. Academic self-efficacy is grounded in self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1977). According to self-efficacy theory, self-efficacy is an “individual's confidence in their ability to organize and execute a given course of action to solve a problem or accomplish a task” (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002, p. 110). Self-efficacy theory suggests that academic self-efficacy may vary in strength as a function of task difficulty—some individuals may believe they are most efficacious on difficult tasks, while others only on easier tasks.. Self-efficacy is different from self-esteem or self-concept as it is a task-specific evaluation whereas self-esteem and self-concept reflect more general affective evaluations of self.

Academic self-efficacy refers to individuals' convictions that they can successfully perform given academic tasks at designated levels. A similar definition also expressed by Midgley et al. (2000) as "academic self-efficacy refers to students' perceptions of their competence to do their classwork". Students make reliable differentiations between their self-efficacy judgments across different academic domains which, collectively, form a loose hierarchical multidimensional structure. Self-efficacy beliefs should be relevant for understanding academic outcomes because self-efficacy leads to specific behaviors and motivations that can encourage or discourage effective performance. As outlined by Bandura (1993), students with high academic self-efficacy increase their efforts in cases of failure to achieve the goals they have set. This highlights the reciprocal or cyclical relationships among the environment, self, and behaviors posited by Bandura's (1977) social cognitive theory. Environmental interventions may improve self-efficacy, which can lead the student to select more challenging tasks, which in turn creates more opportunity for useful feedback and can lead to increased self-efficacy and better outcomes.

Statement of the Study

This study is intended to find out the Academic self-regulation, Academic self-efficacy and Meta cognitive awareness and Academic performance of the perceptiveteachers as applicable to certain sub sample such as Gender, Residence, Qualification, Medium of instruction, Type of institution, Location of institution, Family type, Marital status, Father's qualification, Mother's qualification, Father's occupation, Mother's occupation, Family income and birth order. The statement of the problem for the study is "**Prospective Teachers In Relation To Academic Self-Efficacy And Meta Cognitive Awareness**".

Sources of Self-Efficacy

In Education, self-efficacy is a key contributing factor to learners' success, because self-efficacy "influences the choices learners make and the courses of action they pursue" (Pajares, 2002, p.116). Generally, self-efficacy is influenced by four main sources: enactive mastery experience—that is, hands-on experience; vicarious experiences—that is, other people's experience; verbal persuasion—that is, appraisal or feedback from others; and physiological and affective states—that is, stress, emotion, mood, pain, and fatigue (Hodges, 2008). Mastery experiences are considered to be the most significant source of efficacy (Bandura, 1977a). Once self-efficacy is established, it can be applied to similar learning situations. The closer these situations are to those in which self-efficacy has been improved, the stronger the effect (Bandura & Adams, 1977). These sources are selected, interpreted and integrated into a total estimate of self-efficacy that in turn influences subsequent, cognitive, motivational, emotional and selective processes.

Variables adopted for the present study

- **Dependent variable:** Academic Performance
- **Independent variables:** Academic self-regulation, Academic self-efficacy, Metacognitive awareness
- **Demographic variables:** Gender, Place of Residence, Qualification, Type of institution, Location of institution, Family type, Marital status, Father's qualification, Mother's qualification, Father's occupation, Mother's occupation, Family income and Birth order.

Methodology

Population of the study

All the items under consideration in any field of inquiry constitute the 'universe' or 'population' of the study. It is the aggregate or totality of objects or individuals, learning to influence in a study. It is the group on whom the investigator dying in intends to apply the results. The population of the present study is the prospective teachers studying in college of education in and around Kanchipuram district.

Sample of the present study

Random sampling technique will be used in the selection of the sample. 750 prospectiveteachersinandaroundKanchipuramdistrictwillbeselected.

Tools used in the present study

- Academic self-regulation scale constructed by Brown, Miller and Lawendowski (1999).
- Academic self-efficacy scale developed by Abdul Gafoor. Kand Mohammed Asharaf. P (2006).
- Meta cognitive awareness scale constructed by Schraw and Dennison (1994).

- Academic performance scale constructed and validated by the investigator.

Method for the present study

Normative survey method will be employed in the present study. The survey methods gather data from a relatively large number of cases at a particular time. It is interested in knowing something about the whole population. The present investigation aims to bring the status of above said aspects (variables) in the colleges of education.

Statistical techniques used in the present study

- Descriptive Analysis
- Differential Analysis
- Relation Analysis and
- Regression Analysis

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STUDY INVOLVEMENT AND ONLINE LEARNING STYLE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE

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Abstract

‘Education is the manifestation of the perfection that is already in man’ The aim of education is to develop harmonious personality of the learner. Education should make pupils fit to live with. One of the main objectives or major objectives in the field of education is to achieve knowledge, skill and the ability to adjust with the environment successfully. All aspire for better living conditions irrespective of their capacities and strive to achieve something great. For school children most probably parents and teachers set contain goals and standards to be achieved in order to enable their easy transition from one role to another. Success or failure in one’s attempt to secure good grades reflects the others. Hence the student community places much importance in their studies. This is especially true for adolescent pupils who have to be the future architect of a better society. ‘Education means that there is a self in man which is self-contained and

is a part of the universal reality .The purpose of education is to make man aware of this cosmic power in him and enable him to draw this out to lead a complete life.

Keywords : *Study Involvement ,Online Learning Style, and Academic Achievement*

Introduction

The aim of education is to develop harmonious personality of the learner. Education should make pupils fit to live with. One of the main objectives or major objectives in the field of education is to a achieve knowledge, skill and the ability to adjust with the environment successfully. All aspire for better living conditions irrespective of their capacities and strive to achieve something great. For school children most probably parents and teachers set contain goals and standards to be achieved in order to enable their easy transition from one role to another. Success or failure in one’s attempt to secure good grades reflects the others. Hence the student community places much importance in their studies. This is especially true for adolescent pupils who have to be the future architect of a better society. ‘Education is the manifestation of the perfection that is already in man’ It means that there is a self in man which is self-contained and is a part of the universal reality .The purpose of education is to make man aware of this cosmic power in him and enable him to draw this out to lead a complete life. According to **Raymont**, “Education is that process of development which consists of the passage of human beings from infancy to maturity, the process, whereby he adopts himself gradually in various ways to physical, social and spiritual environment”. **Tagore** says, “Education makes man’s life in harmony with all existence”.

Significance of the study

Many methods of teaching and learning are being tried out and applied in schools, to augment the academic performance of the students, in these present days. The younger generation of children is learning more when compared with their previous generations. The emerging challenges and faster growth of industrialization, urbanization, and globalization have enforced the students to learn and shine in their scholastic achievements, regardless of their strength and weakness. The responsibility of the student community is much more along with their parental responsibility. The degree of study involvement of children affects the learning output of the students. It could surge up with greater level of motivation. Online Learning style is an important factor in the academic achievement of the students. Some students have good learning styles, some students may have poor learning styles which may be due to several factors. Individual differences also play a vital role in learning styles of children. Learning styles may be different from student to student and they also differ in case of high, average and low achievers. And the learning styles also vary among the students from gender, type of management, locality, etc. All school entrants, from beginning to end, require some styles and practice them to successfully pursue knowledge. The achieved test score determines their future career. The ambitions and aspirations of our students are largely governed by their learning skills adopted by the students. By this consideration, the investigator takes up the present study as “**study involvement and online Learning Styles of higher secondary schoolstudents in relation to their Academic Achievement in science**”.

Statement of the study

This study is intended to find out Emotional intelligence, study involvement, online learning style and academic achievement in science of the higher secondary students as applicable to certain variables such as gender, locality of school, type of management, religion, community, father’s education, mother’s education, father’s occupation, mother’s occupation and type of family. The statement of the problem for the study is “**study involvement and online Learning Styles of higher secondary school students in relation to their Academic Achievement in science**”.

Operational Definitions

Study Involvement

Study involvement refers to the degree of feeling of being actively involved in one's own learning process affecting the performance in studies.

Online Learning styles

Online Learning style refers to a person's natural, habitual and preferred ways of learning. Keefe defines it as "characteristic cognitive, affective and physiological behaviors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how learners perceive, interact with and respond to the learning environment".

Academic Achievement

Dictionary of Education (Good, 2009) had defined Academic achievement as "The knowledge attained and skill developed in the school subjects which are usually determined by test scores or marks assigned by the teacher or both".

Higher secondary students

Higher secondary Students refers to the students who have passed their tenth standard examination and studying eleventh and twelfth standard.

Objectives of the study

- To develop and validate the Study Involvement Scale of higher secondary students.
- To find out the level of study involvement of higher secondary students.
- To find out the level of online learning style of higher secondary students.
- To find out the level of academic achievement of higher secondary students.
- To find out whether there is any significant difference in the, study involvement, online learning style and academic achievement with respect to following sub-samples:
 - Gender (Boys / Girls)
 - Locality of School (Rural / Urban)
 - Type of management (Government / Aided / Self-finance)
 - Religion (Hindu / Christian / Muslim)
 - Community (Scheduled Caste / Backward Community / Most Backward Community / Other Community)
 - Father's education (Illiterate / School education / College education)
 - Mother's education (Illiterate / School education / College education)
 - Father's Occupation (Coolie / Business / Private Employee / Government Employee)
 - Mother's Occupation (Coolie / Business/ Private Employee / Government Employee)
 - Type of family (Joint / Nuclear)
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between and study involvement of higher secondary students and its sub- samples.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between and online learning style of higher secondary students and its sub- samples.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between and academic achievement of higher secondary students and its sub- samples.
- To find out whether there is any significant contribution of, study involvement (Independent variables) on online learning style, academic achievement (Dependent variable) of higher secondary students.
- To find out whether there is any significant contribution of sub-samples on online learning style, academic achievement (Dependent variable) of higher secondary students.

Hypotheses of the present study

- The level of study involvement of higher secondary students is low.
- The level of online learning style of higher secondary students is low.
- The level of academic achievement of higher secondary students is low.
- There is no significant of difference in the study involvement, online learning style and academic achievement with respect to the following sub-samples:
 - Gender (Boys / Girls)
 - Locality of school (Rural / Urban)
 - Type of management (Government / Aided / Self-finance)
 - Religion (Hindu / Christian / Muslim)
 - Community (Scheduled Caste / Backward Community/Most Backward Community/Other Community)
 - Father's education (Illiterate / School education / College education)
 - Mother's education (Illiterate / School education / College education)

- Father's occupation (Coolie / Business / Private Employee / Government Employee)
- Mother's occupation (Coolie / Business / Private Employee / Government Employee)
- Type of family (Joint / Nuclear)
- There is no significant contribution of, study involvement (Independent variables) on the online learning style, academic achievement (Dependent variable) of higher secondary students.
- There is no significant contribution of sub-samples on online learning style, academic achievement (Dependent variable) of higher secondary students

Methodology

Population of the study

All the items under consideration in any field of inquiry constitute the 'universe' or 'population' of the study. It is the aggregate or totality of objects or individuals, leading to inferences in a study. It is the group on whom the investigator intends to apply the results. The population of the present study is the higher secondary students studying in higher secondary schools in Kanchipuram educational district.

Sample of the present study

Random sampling technique was used in the selecting the sample of 750 higher secondary students in Kanchipuram Educational District for the study.

Tools used in the present study

The investigator has used the following tools:

- Emotional intelligence Scale constructed by **Anukool Hyde and SanjyotPethe's. Mayer, Salovey& Caruso** Emotional Intelligence Test (MSCEIT)
- Study Involvement Scale constructed and validated Study involvement constructed and validated by **Asha Bhagrinath (1985)**
- Online learning style Scale constructed and validated by the investigator
- Academic achievement Scale by Academic achievement questionnaire developed and standardized by the **Leon Mann.(1982)**

Method for the present study

Normative survey method has been employed in the present study. The present investigation was undertaken by using normative survey method. The survey methods gather data from a relatively large number of cases at a particular time. It is interested in knowing something about the whole population. The present investigation aims to bring the secondary schools

Statistical techniques used in the present study

- Descriptive Analysis
- Differential Analysis
- Correlation Analysis and
- Regression analysis
- Percentage analysis
- 't' test
- Chi-square
- Correlation
- ANOVA

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BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION: SUGGESTED MODELS AND APPROACHES

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Abstract

Blended learning, also known as technology-mediated instruction, web-enhanced instruction, or mixed-mode instruction, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with physical place-based classroom methods. Blended learning requires the physical presence of both teacher and student, with some elements of student control over time, place, path, or pace. While students still attend brick-and-mortar schools with a teacher present, face-to-face classroom practices are combined with computer-mediated activities regarding content and delivery. It is also used in professional development and training settings. Since blended learning is highly context-dependent, a universal conception of it is difficult. Some reports have claimed that a lack of consensus on a hard definition of blended learning has led to difficulties in research on its effectiveness. A well-cited 2013 study broadly defined blended learning as a mixture of online and in-person delivery where the online portion effectively replaces some of the face-to-face contact time rather than supplementing it.

Introduction

Additionally, a 2015 meta-analysis that historically looked back at a comprehensive review of evidence-based research studies around blended learning, found commonalities in defining that blended

learning was "considered a combination of physical f2f [face to face] modes of instruction with online modes of learning, drawing on technology-mediated instruction, where all participants in the learning process are separated by distance some of the time." This report also found that all of these evidence-based studies concluded that student achievement was higher in blended learning experiences when compared to either fully online or fully face-to-face learning experiences. "Blended learning" is sometimes used in the same breath as "personalized learning" and differentiated instruction. The terms "blended learning", "hybrid learning", "technology-mediated instruction", "web-enhanced instruction", and "mixed-mode instruction" are often used interchangeably in research literature.

History of Blended Learning

Although the concepts behind blended learning first developed in the 1960s, the formal terminology to describe it did not take its current form until the late 1990s. One of the earliest uses of the term appears in a 1999 press release, in which the Interactive Learning Centers, an Atlanta-based education business, announced a change of name to EPIC Learning. The release mentions that "The Company currently operates 220 on-line courses, but will begin offering its Internet courseware using the company's Blended Learning methodology." The term "blended learning" was initially vague, encompassing a wide variety of technologies and pedagogical methods in varying combinations (some making no use of technology whatsoever). In 2006, the term became more concrete with the publication of the first *Handbook of Blended Learning* by Bonk and Graham. Graham challenged the breadth and ambiguity of the term's definition, and defined "blended learning systems" as learning systems that "combine face-to-face instruction with computer mediated instruction". In a report titled "Defining Blended Learning", researcher Norm Friesen suggests that, in its current form, blended learning "designates the range of possibilities presented by combining Internet and digital media with established classroom forms that require the physical co-presence of teacher and students". Technology-based training emerged as an alternative to instructor-led training in the 1960s on mainframes and mini-computers. The major advantage that blended learning offers is scale, whereas one instructor can only teach so many people. One example is PLATO (Programmed Logic for Automatic Teaching Operations), a system developed by the University of Illinois and Control Data. PLATO in particular had a long history of innovations and offered coursework from elementary to the college level. Mainframe-based training had a number of interface limitations that gave way to satellite-based live video in the 1970s. The advantage here was serving people who were not as computer literate. The major challenge was the expense required to make this work. In the early 1990s, CD-ROMs emerged as a dominant form of providing technology-based learning as bandwidth through 56k modems wasn't able to support very high quality sound and video. The limitation to CD-ROMs was tracking completion of coursework, so learning management systems emerged as a way to facilitate progress tracking. The aviation industry used this heavily to track how well one did on courses, how much time was spent, and where someone left off. AICC, Aviation Industry Computer-Based Training Committee, was formed in 1988 and companies such as Boeing used CD-ROMs to provide training for personnel. Modern blended learning is delivered online, although CD-ROMs could feasibly still be used if a learning management system meets an institution's standards. Some examples of channels through which online blending learning can be delivered include webcasting (synchronous and asynchronous) and online video (live and recorded)..

Models of Blended Learning

There is little consensus on the definition of blended learning. Some academic studies have suggested it is a redundant term. However, there are distinct blended learning models suggested by some researchers and educational think-tanks. These models include:

- Face-to-face driver – where the teacher drives the instruction and augments with digital
- Rotation – students cycle through a schedule of independent online study and face-to-face classroom time.
- Flex – Most of the curriculum is delivered via a digital platform and teachers are available for face-to-face consultation and support.
- Labs – All of the curriculum is delivered via a digital platform but in a consistent physical location. Students usually take physical classes in this model as well.
- Self-blend – Students choose to augment their physical learning with online course work.

- Online driver – Students complete an entire course through an online platform with possible teacher check-ins. All curriculum and teaching is delivered via a digital platform and face-to-face meetings are scheduled or made available if necessary.

It is important to note that even blended learning models can be blended together and many implementations use some, many, or even all of these as dimensions of larger blended learning strategy. These models, for the most part, are not mutually exclusive.

There are many components that can comprise a blended learning model, including "instructor-delivered content, e-learning, webinars, conference calls, live or online sessions with instructors, and other media and events, for example, Facebook, e-mail, chat rooms, blogs, podcasting, Twitter, YouTube, Skype and web boards".

Advantages of Blended Learning

- Blended instruction is reportedly more effective than purely face-to-face or purely online classes. Blended learning methods can also result in high levels of student achievement more effective than face-to-face learning.
 - By using a combination of digital instruction and one-on-one face time, students can work on their own with new concepts which frees teachers up to circulate and support individual students who may need individualized attention. "Rather than playing to the lowest common denominator – as they would in a physical classroom – teachers can now streamline their instruction to help all students reach their full potential."
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- Proponents of blended learning argue that incorporating the "asynchronous Internet communication technology" into higher education courses serves to "facilitate a simultaneous independent and collaborative learning experience".
 - This incorporation is a major contributor to student satisfaction and success in such courses. The use of information and communication technologies have been found to improve student attitudes towards learning.
 - By incorporating information technology into class projects, communication between lecturers and part-time students has improved, and students were able to better evaluate their understanding of course material via the use of "computer-based qualitative and quantitative assessment modules".
 - Blended learning also has the potential to reduce educational expenses, although some dispute that blended learning is inherently less expensive than physical classroom learning.
 - Blended learning can lower costs by putting classrooms in the online space and it essentially replaces pricey textbooks with electronic devices that students often bring themselves to class. E-textbooks, which can be accessed digitally, may also help to drive down textbook budgets. Proponents of blended learning cite the opportunity for data collection and customization of instruction and assessment as two major benefits of this approach.
 - Blended learning often includes software that automatically collects student data and measures academic progress, providing teachers, students and parents detailed student's data. Often, tests are automatically scored, providing instantaneous feedback. Student logins and work times are also measured to ensure accountability. Schools with blended learning programs may also choose to reallocate resources to boost student achievement outcomes.
 - Students with special talents or interests outside of the available curricula use educational technology to advance their skills or exceed grade restrictions. Blended learning allows for personalized education, replacing the model where a teacher stands in front of the classroom and everyone is expected to stay at the same pace. "Blended learning allows students to work at their own pace, making sure they fully understand new concepts before moving on."
 - A classroom environment that incorporates blended learning naturally requires learners to demonstrate more autonomy, self-regulation, and independence in order to succeed. If teachers offer a form of initial program orientation before introducing blended learning strategies, it can better prepare students to feel confident navigating the different components and developing a stronger sense of independence.
 - Blended learning plays an important role to prime students' learning and to then maximise in-person opportunities and resources.
 - Some online institutions connect students with instructors via web conference technology to form a digital classroom. These institutions borrow many of the technologies that have popularized online

courses at the university level. Some advantages of blended learning, particularly at a Kindergarten to grade 12 level of education, can be found under the general concept of educational technology. It is also one of the most effective ways for personalized learning at scale.

- Blended learning supports the use of standards as a way to manage quality and ease of use. This includes multiple kinds of standards: interoperability standards like the SIF specification from A4L or the Learning Tools Interoperability specification from IMS Global Consortium or academic standards like state standards and Common Core State Standards, which encourage integration of technology into a variety of subjects.
- A learning management system, or federation of systems, helps develop a better feel for an online community where discussions can be held to better aid students.
- This virtual learning environment helps connect professors with students without physically being present, thus making this a 'virtual cafe'. Many schools use this online tool for online classes, classwork, question & answer forums, and other school related work. Blended learning yielded positive results from the online community. Such results were compared and showed similar results from that of Alcoholics Anonymous and Weight Watchers.
- The advantages of blended learning are dependent on the quality of the programs being implemented. Some indicators of excellent blended learning programs are "facilitating student learning, communicating ideas effectively, demonstrating an interest in learning, organizing effectively, showing respect for students, and assessing progress fairly".

Disadvantages of Blended Learning

- Unless successfully planned and executed, blended learning could have disadvantages in technical aspects since it has a strong dependence on the technical resources or tools with which the blended learning experience is delivered. These tools need to be reliable, easy to use, and up to date, for them to have a meaningful impact on the learning experience.
- There are several disadvantages to blended learning. While this type of learning does offer students the ability to go online when necessary, or learn from anywhere, there is no guarantee that each student will have access to the tools that they need to learn on the computer. Another problem that may arise is unreliable internet. Many times, the internet may be down. If the whole class does not have access to the same tools, then the teacher will not be able to keep the class on the same page. This creates a learning gap within classrooms. Unless the education system can offer reliable internet and computers to all students, it is not possible to ensure that this is an effective alternative to mainstream education.
- IT literacy can serve as a significant barrier for students attempting to get access to the course materials, making the availability of high-quality technical support paramount.
- Other aspects of blended learning that can be challenging is group work because of difficulties with management in an online setting.
- Reportedly the use of lecture recording technologies can result in students falling behind on the materials. In a study performed across four different universities, it was found that only half of the students watched the lecture videos on a regular basis, and nearly 40% of students watched several weeks' worth of videos in one sitting. This has further implications for the educator and in how much online resources need to be revealed to the student but also ensure it is at the right level for the intended student.
- From an educator's perspective, most recently, it has been noted that providing effective feedback is more time-consuming (and therefore more expensive) when electronic media are used, in comparison to traditional (e.g. paper-based) assessments. Using e-learning platforms can be more time-consuming than traditional methods and can also come with new costs as e-learning platforms and service providers may charge user fees to educators.
- Another critical issue is access to network infrastructure. Although the digital divide is narrowing as the Internet becomes more pervasive, many students do not have pervasive and ubiquitous access to the Internet – even in their classrooms. Any attempt to incorporate blended learning strategies into an organization's pedagogical strategy needs to account for this. This is why learning centers are built with good wi-fi connections to make sure this issue is addressed.
- Finally, in educational fields where interprofessional simulation and clinical based placement are key components (i.e. medicine, obstetrics & gynaecology), in-person teaching remains a cornerstone of

clinical skills education, and teaching via online discourse alone is not sufficient to completely replace and provide comparable learning outcomes.

Conclusion

The term "21st century literacies" was coined by The National Council of Teachers of English to describe the social nature of learning that is supported by the ability to collaborate using digital technologies in learning. These 'new literacies' are described as "skills students will need for the society in which they will work", including "strong communication and collaboration skills, expertise in technology, innovative and creative thinking skills, and an ability to solve problems". This set of skills and understandings will "prepare the workforce or citizenry for a changing, interconnected world". These literacies are dynamic due to the ability to be linked to one another. According to NCTE, active, successful participants in this 21st century global society must be able to:

- develop proficiency and fluency with the tools of technology;
- build intentional cross-cultural connections and relationships with others so to pose and solve problems collaboratively and strengthen independent thought;
- design and share information for global communities to meet a variety of purposes;
- manage, analyze and synthesize multiple streams of simultaneous information;
- create, critique, analyze and evaluate multimedia texts;
- attend to the ethical responsibilities required by these complex environments;

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BLENDING LEARNING IN TEACHER EDUCATION: QUALITY MAINTENANCE (BLTEQM)

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ABSTRACT

Quality Blended Learning promotes the development of comprehensive training material delivered through an interactive cross-platform online resource that promotes the knowledge required for the design and implementation of blended-learning courses. This material includes a blend-it-well handbook and a training activity specially designed for educators involved in adult education aiming in identifying the gaps in their knowledge, providing them with the skills required for developing high-quality blended learning activities.

Blended Learning

Blended learning, also known as hybrid learning, is an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction online with traditional place-based classroom methods.

Quality Blended Learning

Quality Blended Learning promotes the development of comprehensive training material delivered through an interactive cross-platform on-line resource that promotes the knowledge required for the design and implementation of blended-learning courses.

Define objectives

As with any type of training model, you need to start with an objective; What's the purpose of the training and what's the end goal? Not only will this create clarity for your learners, but it enables you to build a more focused program that gives learners the skills and knowledge they need.

Make it interactive

Blended learning courses can be as interactive as you want. It's up to you to decide the amount of learning that will be through online training and how much will take place through self-paced learning. For example, you could set a task for learners to complete before a live webinar training session. During the webinar, you discuss the task and share solutions.

Assessments

You'll need to monitor and assess your learners progress at the end of the program. This will give you insight into how successful the training was, and if there are any knowledge gaps that need to be addressed. With an LMS, you can easily set exams or assessments to be completed at the end of the training.

Blended Learning in Covid-19

It is justified to deduce that the integration of information technology in education has been accelerated by the pandemic. This crisis opened gates for opportunities in the education sector for the incorporation of digital methods. Covid-19 has also proven that integrated learning is very convenient and flexible for both learners and tutors, which makes it safe to assume that online education will eventually become an integral component of the education system. According to a Financial Advisor, "Majority Indians prefer a mix of online and in person training or course. 81% of people in India believe that students can have a good university experience combining in-person and online, hence giving way to blended learning." It further adds, "Whereas, 88% of learners globally say online learning will be a permanent part of primary, secondary, and higher education moving forward. 87% of Indian students think online learning will be a part of the education experience moving forward. Thus, the blended learning approach will be the norm in the new normal adopted by educators."

Advantages of Blended Learning

Blended learning consolidates the best of both traditional and digital methods of education. While classroom learning is important to incorporate overall discipline, online learning helps students to customize their education.

Some of the advantages of blended learning are as follows:

- Blended learning methods enable students to explore information or guidance online, which can be accessed any time they need and classroom learning helps to build better relations between the learner and the teacher.
- Education is not just about academics but also learning time management, discipline, and blending learning helps both students and teachers to learn according to their own pace and schedule.
- Extra-curricular and various other hands-on activities help students to build their social persona effectively and online learning offers a wider selection of content and information they need for the overall physical and psychological development of their personality.
- Blended learning makes it easy for learners to communicate about their assignments, announcements, test results, or anything else they might need to know from their teachers and makes assessment and evaluation more personalized and effective.
- Education becomes less expensive and more accessible to a wide range of learners.
- Blending learning helps students to explore technology and use different tools or techniques for learning, for example, PowerPoint, Virtual classrooms, Video lectures, etc.
- Blended learning improves the quality of education and information assimilation while making teaching more efficient and productive.

How to Maintain Quality in Blended Learning (QM)

Quality assurance testing is not just about content and visuals but includes many more elements (i.e., text, context, visuals, audio, navigation, quizzes, interaction, compliance, user access, and system compatibility). Each of these categories has at least 5 assessments. By ensuring you have quality tested all the element categories, you will raise the standard and ensure the delivery of a quality online course. With so many checks at every stage of the process, quality assurance testing might look cumbersome and complicated. So let's look at how you can improve the eLearning quality assurance testing process

Optimize Courses Using an e-Learning QA Checklist

Creating Testing Scenarios

Before you even start quality testing the online course, you should create testing scenarios. Testing scenarios are any functionality that can be tested. This set of actions assists in the actual execution process of verifying a particular online course element. Once you have created a testing scenario, you will have a high-level idea of what items will be tested and how to execute the QA testing process. For example, let's say your online course will have a test at the end of every module with *X no. of attempts* and an *X time limit*, and the score will be calculated for evaluation. An example test scenario for eLearning courses in the scenario mentioned above could be:

Test Scenario 1

Check whether the learner can go back to the course material once they start the test (ideally, they should not be able to).

Test Scenario 2

Check whether the user can open the quiz in a new window while still browsing through the course in another browser window.

Test Scenario 3

If the user fails to attempt the answer right and get the minimum required score, are they able to retake the test? And, if so, how many times?

Make it Easy to Report Bugs

You must already be aware that every bug is different. But do the details of the issues need to be spread across all platforms that your team uses for communication? No, right? Instead of putting effort up front to talk about a bug in chats, emails, and messages, take the time to report it in full detail, mark all its attributes, and provide its characteristics—all in one place. Sharing all feedback in one system helps everyone who will review the bug know all aspects of the reported issues. And this is why it becomes crucial that you make it easy for your team members and external stakeholders to be able to effectively report bugs. So how do you do it specifically in regard to improving the e-Learning QA process?

- Break down the bug reporting process based on the online course elements.
- Do report multiple or duplicate bugs for a single issue.
- Ask team members to first review existing bugs before adding a new one, chances are someone from the team has already reported it.
- Monitor and track bugs to make sure they are worked on and dealt with on time.

Use a Centralized System To Report Bugs

We already discussed making the bug reporting process easy and how you can do it. But where do you report the issues and defects? Do you make notes and write docs about it, have an email thread, or a chain of chat messages? No, you don't need any of this. All you need is a visual review and bug-tracking tool to create and manage issues and defects. Using a centralized bug reporting tool allows project teams to collaborate to help during development and testing. Because team members can report, review, and work on the same bug after it has been found during the QA process, it helps speed up and improve the e-Learning QA testing process and assist in fixing those issues and defects.

Stick to The Initial Project Plan/Finalized Storyboard

Throughout the content development process, there are going to be iterations requested. But if you keep incorporating all the iterations as and when they come, you will create something that the client didn't ask for and wasn't visualized during the story boarding process. It is imperative to stick as much as possible to the original and finalized storyboard. Sticking to the initial and approved project plan makes the QA testing process easier and quicker, as there are either zero or very few modifications to the content; therefore, the tester can stick with the finalized storyboard and testing scenario while running through the QA testing checklist.

Use a Checklist to Guide You Throughout The QA Testing Process

Last but not least, a tip for improving the eLearning quality assurance testing process is using an eLearning quality assurance and testing checklist. Numerous elements, features, and functionality need to be tested before delivering an excellent and engaging experience to the learners. A checklist acts as a guide in assessing an eLearning course. The QA checklist does not need to be a complex and exhaustive list, but it should include all the elements that should be checked. Also, having testing scenarios when running through a checklist is helpful.

Quality in Blended Learning (QBL)

The rapid advancement of technologies and their ubiquitous use in our daily lives have dramatically changed the way knowledge is created and disseminated. As a technology enhanced pedagogical approach, blended learning – the deliberate combination of online learning with face-to-face classroom-based learning – provides higher education institutions (HEIs) with the opportunities to enhance the quality of teaching and learning. While many of these opportunities have been well-documented in the literature, implementing and scaling up blended learning courses pose enormous challenges for HEIs in the Asia-Pacific region. To address these challenges, UNESCO Bangkok in partnership with The Education University of Hong Kong (EdUHK) launched a two-year project to build the capacity of HEIs for blended learning. One of the outcomes of the project was , a team of blended learning experts and leaders in the region. Blended Learning for Quality Higher Education presents a framework and self-assessment tool developed from a holistic view of building institutional capacity to drive, sustain, and scale up blended learning. It incorporates case studies from experienced HEIs in the region to demonstrate how the framework and its dimensions could be operationalized, and how the gaps identified in the self-assessment exercise could be addressed.

Optimize Courses using an e-Learning QA Checklist

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Tips to Maintain the Quality of Blended Learning

It is one thing to decide you would like to have a blended classroom, and another to ensure that the blended classroom is successful enough to be maintained in the long run. The following are some tips to help you maintain a great blended learning environment;

Find the Right Mix

Most blended learning projects will fail because of a lack of efficiency when coming up with the course structure. The course structure needs to be designed in a way that balances both independent learning and in-person classes, and this balance needs to incorporate all parties involved. For example, it may not be possible for a teacher to give a class of 30 one-one attention.

Keep it Personal

When coming up with the course structure for blended learning, it is very important to take into consideration the personal learning styles of the learners. Face to face learning allows the teacher to customize learning to the individual needs of the student, and this where blended learning can be absolutely magical. But even this needs to be planned correctly, since the content of the course needs to be relevant to the learner and the time needs to be convenient for the teacher. It is also vital to make it possible for the course work to be available both online and in the classroom. This is because not all learners are, therefore may not respond to the same learning styles.

Flexibility is Key

Holding physical classes may not be sufficient since it may limit the students to only learn on specified days of the week at specified time. For students who may have other commitments such as work or families, this is a rigid form of learning that may not be very useful to them. In contrast, online learning allows all students regardless of their commitments to fully engage with the course work since they can do it in their own time and at their own pace. Social learning management systems can further streamline the learning process, allowing students and lecturers to use the chat to explain course work that students may find challenging.

Involve the Right People with Online Courses

It is very important to ensure that you involve the right people with the online courses, particularly in the beginning. It would be very difficult for a student to complete all the online courses alone without the guidance of teachers who can point them in the right direction in terms of where to start. Successful onboarding of a new student into the system can only be accomplished with other people helping. For students and teachers looking for the ultimate interactive learning environment that is both flexible and adaptive, blended learning is one of the best solutions. But for it to be successful, a flexible and balanced course structure needs to be at the core of the strategy. The right tools will also make or break your blended learning project. When it comes to tools, however, you may find it beneficial to choose a tool that is a complete learning management system, allowing your students to access the course materials and participate in group discussions via chat. Video recording software will also prove very useful to you in the quest to create the perfect blended classroom.

Conclusion

The first thing you need to do when optimizing or setting up a blended classroom is to determine how much of the course will be interactive. Blended classrooms are designed to incorporate the e-learning experience to the course and use the internet to reach students wherever they are. But it is not designed to be completely online. Therefore, the first thing you must determine is how much of the course will be accomplished in the classroom and how much of it will be done online. For instance, you might want to decide which part of the course will be done exclusively in the classroom and which part of the course will be done exclusively online. Knowing this will help you effectively plan for the course, including lesson planning as well as with scheduling. Your students will know when they are supposed to be in the classroom physically and when they can learn online.

Resources

- <https://ascnet.ie/projects/quality-blended-learning/>
- <https://www.learnupon.com/blog/what-is-blended-learning/>
- <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/importance-of-blended-learning-in-the-era-of-digital-education-1783488-2021-03-25>
- <https://elearningindustry.com/tips-improve-elearning-quality-assurance-and-testing-process>
- <https://bangkok.unesco.org/content/blended-learning-quality-higher-education-introducing-new-self-assessment-tool-asia-pacific>
- <https://democreator.wondershare.com/elearning-tips/how-to-improve-blended-learning.html>